

**AN INVESTIGATION OF SOCIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL
DISCLOSURE IN THE NIGERIAN OIL INDUSTRY**

A THESIS PRESENTED

BY

CHARLES THOMPSON ATANG

TO

THE SCHOOL OF BUSINESS & CREATIVE INDUSTRIES

UNIVERSITY OF THE WEST OF SCOTLAND

IN PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF THE REQUIREMENT OF

DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY

AUGUST 2021

ABSTRACT

The thesis examines social and environmental disclosures in the Nigerian oil industry. This thesis identifies companies' motivations for SED in the Nigerian oil industry, investigates the perceptions and associations between the oil companies and the host communities where they operate and discusses the challenges faced in developing and promoting the social and environmental disclosures reporting among the host communities and the Nigeria oil industries. In addition, the thesis also explores the scope of social and environmental disclosure (SED) reporting practices among oil industries that operate in the Nigeria oil sector and examines the differences between Nigeria's domestic and international oil industries concerning the disclosure of social and environmental information to several stakeholders. A mixed research design approach using primary and secondary research methodology was applied to answer the related research questions.

For the primary research design based on the qualitative approach, the researcher collected data from the interview responses of twenty-four participants drawn from the four Nigerian states: - Akwa Ibom State, Bayelsa State, Delta State, and Rivers State. Thematic analysis using NVivo software generates broad themes to answer the research objectives/questions on the host communities' motivation, perception, and association with SED and the challenges the Nigerian oil industry faced with SED reporting. The thematic analysis findings indicate that host communities are motivated to assess social welfare contribution, environmental conservation, and waste management practices adopted by the oil industries; also, the regulations and accountability are some of the motivations for developing and promoting the SED in Nigeria oil industries. However, when oil prices have declined, inconsistent SED policies and financial restrictions remain a crucial challenge in the Nigerian oil industries' regular provision of SED reports. Challenges emanate from the lack of solid laws to compel the companies to embrace SED in their operations. Most of the interviewed individuals

expressed positive perceptions of their association with the oil companies in their communities, while the others expressed dissatisfaction.

For the secondary research design based on the quantitative approach, the researcher collected data from the Nigeria Stock Exchange and SED annual reports of eighteen Nigerian oil industries (Domestic and International oil companies). The researcher applied qualitative content analysis to examine SED reporting practices' leading causes in the Nigerian oil industry and the differences between domestic and international oil industries. Data analysis involved using SPSS and ANOVA statistical tools to establish significant differences between the concepts investigated. The outcome based on the qualitative content analysis reveals that community welfare disclosure, employee-related SEDs, and environmental SEDs are the most critical factors of social and environmental disclosure among the Nigerian oil industries.

Furthermore, the findings from the content analysis indicate that due to their strong corporate governance structures and financial capability, most of the international oil industries that operate in Nigeria have better SED reporting practices than the Nigeria domestic oil industries. The thesis concludes and recommends promoting a culture of SED reporting practices. There is a need for a solid regulatory framework to guide SED reporting coupled with a sensitisation on community involvement. These findings have a significant implication for the social and environmental policies that need to be adopted by Nigeria's stock market and industry regulatory agencies. Moreover, the thesis also concluded that SED development in Nigeria's oil industry was gaining significant growth and importance, but the domestic oil industries needed to do more.

Keywords: *Social and Environmental Disclosure (SED), Disclosure Themes, Stakeholder Theory, Thematic Analysis, Content Analysis, Community Welfare and Waste Management.*

CERTIFICATION OF THESIS

I certify that the work presented in this thesis is my project, except where otherwise recognised. This thesis is my original work and has not formerly been tendered for a degree in any other university.

Charles Thompson Atang

Authorisation Date

Dr Xin Michael Guo

Authorisation Date

Dr David Leung

Authorisation Date

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I am thankful to Almighty God for giving me life and strength for doing this thesis and seeing me through to completion. To my parents, Mr., and late Mrs Atang Thompson Obong, I will say your prayers, and numerous words of encouragement helped me forge ahead when I was in despair; I will say thank you so much. I want to use this medium to appreciate my wife, Mrs Ndifreke Charles Atang, for her countless love, inspiration, and financial support during my course of study. To my beloved Mrs Viktoria Nagy, I will thank you for your enormous physical help and economic contribution through my research journey and to my good friends- Funke Ladipo and Emmanuel Eze, Valentine Onyeka and Deborah Chiagozie Onukwube, Babatunde Ishowo and Zaliya Musah who supported me morally and financially during my research, I say thank you.

However, I will personally thank my Director of Studies, Dr Michael Xin Guo, for his remarkable contribution to the success of this thesis. Sir, I am highly grateful for all the advice, remarks, criticism, and continuous support, which made my thesis much easier; I am excitedly thankful to you for the valuable advice and suggestions you provided during my study, which I deeply appreciated. I will also thank my associate supervisor Dr David Leung; I would not have completed this thesis without your valuable guidance and expertise. My sincere gratitude goes to my assessor, Dr Christian Harrison, who supported and encouraged me with prudent advice and guidance during the early stage of my study; it was the tools I needed; thank you, sir.

Moreover, I wish to recognise my good friend Dr Kingsley Omeihe and Mr Ai-Quang Tonthat for their significant academic contributions and assistance; I am indebted to you both. I will also use this medium to especially thank Mr Lawrence Akpan(AKA-Enang), who accompanies me throughout collecting my research data within the south-south states of the

Niger Delta in Nigeria. Thank you so much for your commitment and time to actualising this project. I would not be able to list entirely individuals who supported me in the success of my thesis reality; I will say thank you all.

Moreover, I will thank my family members and relative of mine, who played a big part in my journey from the start of my study till the end; they include Grace, David, Joseph, Godwin, Gabriel, Elliana, Mary, Charity, Christina and Solomon, Koko, Etebong, Nsikak-abasi, Mmedaraobong and her children. Sister Imeh, Mmayen, with her family, I will say a big thank you to all of you for the prayers, support, and encouragement during my study.

Finally, I would like to thank Elder and Mrs Usen Udofia, sir/ma; I am greatly indebted to you for your everyday prayers and words of encouragement. Thanks to Mr Tamas Tibor Nagy and Mrs Tiborne Nagy Tamas for their support and reassurance during my studies. Additionally, I will also thank my fellow postgraduate colleagues Ayodele and Olamide, the Postgraduate School and the Student Help Desk (Hub), the UWS IT Department and to, the VIVA team Dr Alan Murray who chaired the Viva examination, Dr Magda Abou-Seada- External Examiner-Essex University, and Dr Mary Fletcher- Internal Examiner-UWS for their support in realising my studies. Thank you all. This acknowledgement would not be complete without thanking God Almighty, who made this thesis achievable and reliable. May his name be praised. Amen.

DEDICATION

This thesis is dedicated to the Almighty God who made the start and completion of my study successful and to the memory of my beloved late mother, Mrs Mary Atang Thompson Obong, who died before my research journey

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ABSTRACT	i
CERTIFICATION OF THESIS	iii
ACKNOWLEDGEMENT	iv
DEDICATION	vi
GLOSSARY	xx
CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION	1
1.1 Background	1
1.2 Problem statement	5
1.3 Research Aims and Objectives	6
1.4 Research Questions.....	7
1.5 Need for the Research.....	7
1.6 Justification for the study.....	8
1.7 Limitation of prior studies	8
1.8 Methodological Approach.....	10
1.9 Thesis Structure	13
CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW (1)	14
2.1 Introduction	14
2.2 Concepts of CSR and SED.....	17
2.2.1 Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)	17
2.2.2 The primary characteristics of Corporate Social Responsibility	21
2.2.3 Voluntary.....	22
2.2.4 Internalisation and Management of Externalities	23
2.2.5 Orientation towards multiple stakeholders.....	23

2.2.6	Aligning Social and Economic Responsibilities.....	24
2.2.7	Values and Practice.....	24
2.2.8	Beyond Philanthropy	25
2.2.9	Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure (CSR D).....	25
2.2.10	Types of Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosures (SED).....	26
2.2.11	Components of Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosures	27
2.2.12	SED Concepts.....	29
2.2.13	The Difference Between CSR and SED.....	30
2.3	Nigeria as a research study context	30
2.3.1	Historical background of the Nigerian Oil Industry.....	33
2.3.2	Background Region of the Niger Delta region and Its Crisis.....	38
2.3.3	Brief origins of the South-South Catchword in Nigeria	42
2.4	Conclusion	43
CHAPTER TWO: (2) SOCIAL ENVIRONMENTAL DISCLOSURE (1)....		45
2.5	Introduction.....	45
2.5.1	Nature of Social Environmental Disclosure	47
2.5.2	Social Environmental Disclosure theory.....	49
2.5.3	Social Environmental Disclosure Information	50
2.5.4	Motivation for Social Environmental Disclosure	51
2.5.5	Perception and Challenges of SED.....	55
2.5.6	The Scope of SED	56
2.5.7	Differences in SED between Domestic and International Oil Industries in Nigeria.....	57
2.6	Evidence of Social Environmental Disclosure	58
2.6.1	Introduction	58

2.6.2	Examining Social Environmental Disclosure Quality	59
2.6.3	SED practices on Developed Country studies.....	64
2.6.4	SED practices on Developing Country studies	70
CHAPTER TWO: (2) SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW.....		78
2.7	Introduction.....	78
2.7.1	Description of the SLR protocols	79
2.7.2	Justification (motive) for the SLR.....	81
2.7.3	SLR question	82
2.7.4	SLR based on study	83
2.7.5	Discussions for the SLR table	93
2.7.6	Finalisation of the systematic literature review	115
2.7.7	Systematic Review of the Existing Research Gaps in the Study.....	116
2.8	Conclusion	117
CHAPTER THREE: THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK.....		119
3.1	Introduction.....	119
3.2	Evaluation of how the Theoretical Framework evolves from the Literature Review	121
3.3	Adapted Theories for this study	122
3.4	Legitimacy Theory	123
3.5	Stakeholder Theory.....	125
3.6	The justification for the Stakeholder Theory	131
3.7	Conclusion	132
CHAPTER FOUR: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY.....		133
4.1	Introduction.....	133
4.2	Research Design.....	136

4.2.1	Pragmatism Stance.....	137
4.2.2	Research Philosophy	139
4.2.3	Different Types of Philosophical Positions	140
4.2.4	Justification for the use of the Pragmatic Research Philosophy	142
4.3	Study Zone of Thesis (South-South Region of Nigeria).....	142
4.4	Thesis Population and Sample	144
4.5	Judgmental Sampling.....	145
4.5.1	Characteristics of Judgmental Sampling.....	147
SECTION 1- INTERVIEWS		150
4.6	Primary Research Design.....	150
4.6.1	Introduction	150
4.6.2	Primary Data Collection Design.....	151
4.6.3	Interview Sample Selection.....	153
4.6.4	Descriptive: Interviewees Sample Structure	158
4.6.5	Qualitative Data Analysis.....	163
4.6.6	Data Coding for Qualitative Analysis.....	165
4.6.7	Unit of Analysis of Qualitative Data.....	166
4.6.8	Quality of Primary Data (Interview).....	167
4.6.9	The Reliability and Validity of Interview Data.....	167
SECTION 2- CONTENT ANALYSIS		169
4.7	Secondary Research Design.....	169
4.7.1	Data Collection Design.....	169
4.7.2	Sampling Design	170
4.7.3	Content Analysis.....	176
4.7.4	Data Analysis	178

4.7.5	Data Coding for Quantitative Analysis and Analytical Tools.....	182
4.7.6	Component Analysis for SED Quantity.....	183
4.7.7	Quantity of Annual SED Reports.....	184
4.7.8	The Quality of SED and Annual Reports.....	185
4.7.9	Social and Environmental Disclosure Categories.....	187
4.8	Validity and Reliability of Content Analysis.....	192
4.9	Scope of SEDs in the Nigerian Oil Industry.....	192
4.10	Differences in SED Reporting between Domestic and International Oil Industries.....	194
4.10.1	Differences in SED Reporting Practices and Relative Analysis.....	195
4.11	Data Analysis Approach and Analytical Tools.....	196
4.11.1	Social and Environmental Disclosure (SED) Index.....	197
4.12	Ethical Considerations.....	198
4.12.1	Ethical Issues and Principles.....	200
4.13	Conclusions.....	204
	CHAPTER FIVE: RESULT FINDINGS 1: INTERVIEWS.....	206
5.1	Introduction.....	206
5.1.1	Data Coding and Analysis.....	207
5.1.2	Overview of the Thematic Analysis Results.....	208
5.2	Thematic Codes on SED Motivations.....	219
5.2.1	Alignment to Community Development.....	220
5.2.2	Community Welfare.....	225
5.2.3	SED Benefits or Damages.....	227
5.3	Thematic Codes on SED Perceptions.....	230
5.3.1	Responsible Corporate Citizens.....	231

5.3.2	Community Involvement	234
5.3.3	Social and Environmental Issues.....	237
5.3.4	Communication on SED Policy.....	240
5.4	Thematic Codes on Social Environmental Challenges.....	243
5.4.1	SED Policies.....	244
5.4.2	Interaction with Communities.....	246
5.4.3	Community Support	248
5.4.4	Funding	250
5.5.	Summary of Findings.....	252
	CHAPTER SIX: RESULT FINDINGS 2: CONTENT ANALYSIS	254
6.1	Introduction.....	254
	CONTENT ANALYSIS 1.....	254
6.2	Descriptive Analysis Results: The Extent of SED in the Nigerian Oil Industry.....	254
6.3	Content Analysis Findings	261
6.3.1	The Scope of SED in the Nigerian Oil Industry	261
6.3.2	The Extent and Variation in SED among Nigerian Oil Industries.....	266
6.3.3	The Extent and Variation in SED by Types of Disclosure.....	279
6.4	Normality Test and Kruskal-Wallis Test for Extent of SED.....	284
6.4.1	Normality Tests	284
6.4.2	Non-Parametric Kruskal-Wallis Test.....	286
6.5	The Effect of Firm Size and Age on Social and Environmental Disclosures (SED).....	287
6.6	Social and Environmental Disclosure Index (SEDI)	289
	CONTENT ANALYSIS 2.....	291

6.7 The Extent and Variation in SED between Nigeria Domestic International Oil Industries.....	291
6.8 Relationship in Extent of SED among Domestic and International Oil Industries.....	304
6.9 Validity and Reliability of Content Analysis	305
6.10 Chapter Summary.....	306
CHAPTER SEVEN: DISCUSSION	308
7.1 Introduction.....	308
7.2 Motivations for SED in the Nigerian Oil Industry	309
7.3 Perception of Disclosure of SED among Host Communities.....	312
7.4 SED Reporting Challenges in the Nigerian Oil Industry	317
7.5 The Scope and Determinants of SED in the Nigerian Oil Industry.....	321
7.6 Difference in SED among the Domestic and International Oil Firms	323
7.7 Implications for Policy and Practice.....	326
CHAPTER EIGHT: CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS .	330
8.1 Introduction.....	330
8.2 Key Findings	330
8.3 The Key Findings that Extend to Existing Literature	333
8.4 Policy Recommendations.....	335
8.5 Original Contribution to Knowledge	336
8.6 Implications for Future Research	338
8.7 Executive Summary.....	341
REFERENCES.....	344
APPENDICES	367
Exhibit 1: Research Schedule Gantt Chart	367

Exhibit 2: Nigeria Registered Oil Companies.....	368
Exhibit 3: Reflection on Data Collection Trip to Nigeria.....	375
Exhibit 4: Interview Question Guide.....	384
Exhibit 5: Participants Information Sheet.....	388
Exhibit 6: Research Consent Form.....	392
Exhibit 7: Ethics Approval	393
Exhibit 8: Word Frequency Results: Minimum Length =4	394
Exhibit 9: Word Frequency Results: Minimum Length =8	396
Exhibit 10: Research Themes	398
Exhibit 11: Summary of the Social and Environmental Disclosure (SED) per Firm	400
Exhibit 12: Mean Number of Disclosure by Firm Size and SED Component.....	401
Exhibit 13: Mean SED by Size and Component (International Oil Firms)	407
Exhibit 14: Sampled Companies in the Nigerian Oil Industry	410
Exhibit 15: Thirteen companies listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange	411
Exhibit 16: ANOVA and Paired-Sample T-Test Results: Nigerian Domestic Oil Firms.....	412
Exhibit 17: ANOVA and Paired-Sample T-Test Results: Domestic and International Oil Firms	412

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 2.1	The dimension of defining CSR in different periods.....	20
Figure 2.2	The primary characteristics of CSR.....	21
Figure 2.3	The components of CSR Disclosure	28
Figure 2.4	Context of Research study map.....	31
Figure 2.5	Key historical developments in the Nigerian oil industry	37
Figure 2.6	Map of the Niger-Delta region	39
Figure 2.7	Motivation for SED	52
Figure 2.8	Methods of Social Environmental Disclosure (SED)	63
Figure 2.9	The published SED research country of origin.....	66
Figure 2.10	Systematic literature review PRISMA flow diagram.....	84
Figure 4.1	Diagrams Showing the Breakdown of Primary and Secondary Research Method Approaches.....	134
Figure 4.2	South-South Region in The Nigeria Map.....	144
Figure 4.3	Sample Structure Based on Interviewee’s Marital Status	159
Figure 4.4	Sample Structure Based on Interviewees Age.....	161
Figure 4.5	Sample Structure Based on Participant’s Educational Level	162
Figure 5.1	Thematic Codes on SED Motivation	220
Figure 5.2	Word Frequency Cloud from the Interview Transcripts.....	221
Figure 5.3	Thematic Codes on SED Perception.....	231
Figure 5.4.	Thematic Codes on Social and Environmental Issues	244
Figure 6.1.	Composition of SEDs per Firm: Top Five Nigerian Oil Industries ...	257
Figure 6.2	Composition of SEDs per Firm: Other 13 Nigerian Oil Industries ...	258

Figure 6.3 Mean Number of SED by Firm Size and Component.....266

Figure 6.4 Mean SEDs by Types of Disclosure284

Figure 6.5 SED Indicators (Frequency Scores) in Domestic and
International Oil Industries303

Figure 6.6 Mean SED by Firm Size and Components: Domestic and
International Oil Industries303

LIST OF TABLES

Table 2.1	Summary of studies conducted in Developed Nations.....	67
Table 2.2	Items of SED in Annual Reports	72
Table 2.3	Summary of studies conducted in Developing Nations	75
Table 2.4	Systematic Review Table	86
Table 4.1	Evidence of interview's conducted.....	156
Table 4.2	Sample Structure Based on Interviewees' Gender Profile and Marital Status	159
Table 4.3	Sample Structure Based on Interviewees Age.....	160
Table 4.4	Sample Composition Based on Participant's Educational Status	162
Table 4.5	Sampled Companies in the Nigerian Oil Industry	171
Table 4.5.1	Thirteen Companies Listed in the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE).....	175
Table 4.6	SED Categories.....	188
Table 5.1	Summary of Thematic Coding	208
Table 6.1	Top Five and the Other Thirteen Nigeria Oil Industries	255
Table 6.2	Mean Number of SED per Firm	256
Table 6.3	Mean Number of Disclosure by Firm Size and SED Component.....	264
Table 6.4	Summary of ANOVA Results	267
Table 6.5	One-way ANOVA Test Results: Variation in SED Among Domestic Oil Industries.....	268
Table 6.6	Mean SEDs by Types of Disclosure	282
Table 6.7	Normality Tests for Extent of SED in Nigerian Domestic	

Oil Industries.....	285
Table 6.8 Normality Tests for Extent of SED in International Oil Industries.....	285
Table 6.9 Kruskal-Wallis Test: Differences in SED by Components for Nigerian Domestic Oil Industries.....	286
Table 6.10 Kruskal-Wallis Test: Differences in SED by Components for International Oil Firms	287
Table 6.11 Multiple Regression: Effect of Firm Size and Age on SED: Nigerian Domestic Firms.....	288
Table 6.12 Multiple Regression: Effect of Firm Size and Age on SED: International Oil Firms	289
Table 6.13 SED Index for Disclosure of Nigerian Oil and Gas Firms’ Annual Reports.....	290
Table 6.14 Descriptive Statistics: Extent of SEDs in Domestic and International Oil Industries	292
Table 6.15 Descriptive Statistics: Extent of SED Category in Domestic and International Oil Industries.....	293
Table 6.16 Comparison of the Type of SED in Domestic and International Oil Industries	294
Table 6.17 Descriptive Statistics: Type of SED by Domestic and International Oil Industries	295
Table 6.18 Summary of the ANOVA Results: SED in Domestic and International Oil Industries	296
Table 6.19 One-Way ANOVA Test Results: Variation in SED among International Oil Industries.....	297

Table 6.20 Mean SED by Firm Size and Component: Domestic and International Oil Industries	300
Table 6.21 SED Indicators (Frequency Scores) in Domestic and International Oil Industries.....	302
Table 6.22 Correlation Analyses: Extent of SED in International Oil Industries	304
Table 6.23 Correlation Analysis: Extent of SED in Nigerian Domestic Oil Industries.....	305
Table 8.1 Summary of Key Thesis Findings (Interview).....	331
Table 8.2 Summary of Key Thesis Findings (Content Analysis).....	332

GLOSSARY

API	- American Petroleum Institute
APPEA	- Australian Petroleum Production and Exploration Association
AR	- Annual Report
CA	- Companies Act
CCG	- Code of Corporate Governance
CDC	- Community Improvement Cost
CEO	- Chief Executive Officer
CER	- Corporate Environmental Reporting
CSR	- Corporate Social Responsibility
CSED	- Corporate Social and Environmental Disclosures
EC	- European Commission
EDQI	- Environmental Disclosure Quality Index
EHSC	- Employee Health and Safety Cost
EMC	- Environmental Maintenance Cost
EPNL	- Elf Petroleum Nigeria Limited
FCMT	- Federal College of Marine Technology
GDP	- Gross Domestic product
GRI	- Global Reporting Initiative
HCS	- Host Communities
IDSL	- Integrated Data Services Ltd
IEPE	- International Environmental Performance Evaluation
IOCs	- International Oil Corporations
IPIECA	- International Petroleum Industry Environmental Conservation Association
ISO	- International Organisation for Standardisation
JSE	- Johannesburg Stock Exchange (South Africa's)
JVCs	- Joint Venture Contracts
KRPC	- Kaduna Refinery & Petrochemical Co
LC	- Local Content
MNCs	- Multi-national Companies
MPNU	- Mobil Producing Nigeria Unlimited
NAOC	- Nigerian AGIP Oil Company Ltd

NAPIMS	- National Petroleum Investment Management Service
NCDMB	- Nigerian Content Development and Monitoring Board
NETCO	- National Engineering & Technical Co.
NGC	- Nigerian Gas Co
NGOs	- Non-Governmental Organisation
NIW	- Nigerian Institute of Welders
NNOC	- Nigerian National Oil Corporation
NNPC	- Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation
NPDC	- Nigerian Petroleum Development Co.
NSEC	- Nigerian Securities and Exchange Commission
OECD	- Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development
OPEC	- Organisation of Petroleum Exporting Countries
PAT	- Profit After Tax
PBC	- Personnel Benefit Cost
PHRC	- Port Harcourt Refinery Co
PSCs	- Production Sharing Contracts
SEB	- Securities Exchange Board (India's)
SEC	- Securities Exchange Commission
SED	- Social and Environmental Disclosure
SEDI	- Social and Environmental Disclosure Index
SEG	- Social and Environmental Governance
SMEs	- Small- and Medium-Scale Enterprises
SPDC	- Shell Petroleum Development Company of Nigeria
TOPCON	-Texaco Overseas Petroleum Company Nigeria
UNGC	-United Nations Global Compact
UNO	- United Nations Organisation
UV	- Ultraviolet
VMS	- Vendor Management System
WMC	- Waste Management Cost
WRPCO	- Warri Refinery & Petrochemical Co.

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

The ever-changing state of the global environment and the numerous impacts that human activities have on the ecological systems have raised public concern and profound inquiry into the company's business activities (Zeng et al., 2010). In the current business world, corporations must demonstrate a high awareness of their activities and address their daily operations' impacts on the environment and general society (Russo and Perrini. 2010). Therefore, based on this concern, the retention and improvement of the quality of society and the environment where the organisations operate have thus become one of the most significant issues modern businesses face. The growing industrial impacts on the environment through pollution and environmental degradation have contributed to corporate social and environmental responsibility growth among modern businesses (Gamerschlag et al. 2011). Since environmental and social issues, if ignored, have significant adverse economic, social, and political effects primarily on the growing economies, business organisations are thus subjected to a conditional responsibility of reporting and accounting for their social and environmental activities (Jenkins and Yakovleva 2006).

Corporate social and environmental disclosures have increased significantly over the last twenty years, despite variations in how it is carried out among nations. For instance, studies in the United States, the U.K., and Australia show that social and environmental disclosures have increased significantly over the years (De Villiers and Van Staden 2010). Most developed nations, such as the U.S., have initiated mandatory disclosures in reporting requirements, making it an obligation for organisations to disclose and report their activities in their annual reports (Zeng et al. 2010). However, the situation is not similar in most developing countries, such as Nigeria.

Organisations in most developing nations largely depend on reporting firms' voluntary disclosure initiatives, making the process highly unregulated in countries such as Nigeria (Lyon and Maxwell 2011). Nonetheless, there has been mounting pressure and interest from various stakeholders in developing countries to have a voluntary society and environmental engagement to enhance sustainability.

However, there is limited empirical evidence dedicated to Nigerian oil companies' corporate social and environmental disclosures (SED). Although sustainability disclosures are voluntary in the country, there is no recommended standard for SED reporting for Nigeria's oil Industries. Besides, in the recent past, most companies' reputation in the country has been deteriorating due to destructive policies regarding sustainable development practices (Jenkins and Yakovleva 2006). Thus, the lack of substantive research on SED by Nigeria oil Industries makes a compelling case for the present study.

The industrial revolution saw more vibrant industrial activities that led to economic empowerment for the countries involved. The activities saw heavy use of natural resources to produce better, quality products that meet clients' demands and the general population. Energy requirements grew that saw the use of coal fields overexploited and the subsequent innovations of other energy resources such as electricity innovations and the use of oil. During these activities, most companies are not concerned about their operations' effects on the environment. According to Qureshi et al. (2015), industrial activities and urbanisation activities contribute immensely to environmental degradation. The intensified industrial activity directly links to the harmful environmental disasters that are being witnessed across the world. For instance, the current generation's environmental concern arises from the rise in global temperatures that have led to global warming (Trenberth et al., 2014). Industries release their wastes into the environment in large quantities ranging from toxic chemicals

laden with carcinogenic materials that have seen cancer incidences increase worldwide. The wastes have also resulted in poor air quality and the ozone layer damage, leading to negative impacts of the planet's ultraviolet (U.V.) rays (Ball et al., 2018).

The activities highlighted translate in all the industrial activities like the oil sector — operations ranging from the exploration of the resource and all the activities involved in the refinery process. The study by Elum et al. (2016) reflected on what the oil industry has caused to Nigeria's environment and the general population. The findings indicate the pollution effect the sector has caused and the implications resulting from the same. Such activities and their negative impacts on the environment led to an up-rise by the consumers to hold companies accountable for their actions and the environment's consequences. The demand for environmental concern, safeguard, and conservation made companies worldwide willingly adopt Social and Environmental Disclosure (SED). KPMG (2011) Postulate that the act has gained popularity globally, and consumers hold companies accountable for the disclosures. Thus, it has become part of the corporate social responsibility to give annual SED reports. The reports detail the companies' attempts to meet the demands of their clients regarding social and environmental accountability. The release of yearly SED reports depends on the willingness of the companies to do so.

In Nigeria, the most vibrant industrial activity results from the oil Industries, contributing to over 87 per cent of the country's exports (Africa Check, 2018). The numbers put Nigeria as the leading exporter in Africa, with over 280 companies in the industry. The magnitude of the industry potentially causes various environmental issues that can harm the environment. As such, the industry must be cross-examined to examine how the companies have embraced the act of SED disclosure to the public. Various regulations have been developed that have made disclosures compulsory in many parts of the world (KPMG 2017). The increase in reporting levels instigated this research to examine companies' willingness to report their SED annually

in the oil industry. The research attempts to unearth the motivations surrounding reporting social and environmental disclosures in the Nigerian oil industry.

The regulations and the standards that form the basis and guidance for the reporting process have pushed companies to the edge, making them report their SED even when they do not want to report their SED activities (Odera et al., 2016). Some challenges exist that make it difficult or create barriers that the companies need to break to prepare, document, and release these reports. The research looks at such challenges between the companies and their efforts to make their disclosures. The challenges would provide vital information on what the companies in the sector must endure to meet the regulations set for the disclosures. Further, the research set to determine the perceptions the community members hold regarding the disclosures made by the companies in the oil industry. The companies do not work in isolation, but their operations directly influence the activities and general well-being of the community members. The research then documented how the population perceived the disclosures by the companies operating in their communities. Communities have different associations with the companies working within their area, and the researchers investigated the associations that the communities have with the companies.

The research investigated social and environmental disclosures in the oil industry. The companies engage in various activities that have negative implications for the environment. But to what extent do the companies make their disclosures? The research delved into determining the companies' practices regarding corporate social responsibility in SED reporting. Corporate social responsibility incorporates environmental pollution due to the economic implications they pose, social issues, and the same political implications. Investigating the SED in Nigeria's oil industry attempted to determine its concern for the environment and conservation efforts. Corporate goals require that the company take

initiatives to be accountable for the environment and conserve the materials they create wealth (Wirth et al., 2016).

Another aspect that defined the research is the comparative analysis of Nigeria's domestic and international oil Industries regarding disclosures. Regulations worldwide bind SED disclosures and look at how well the companies adhere to these rules in their SED disclosure process. Comparing these companies` disclosure to their different stakeholders informed the level with which other companies perceive the need to release the information. The release of the information would help the companies conform to the Nigerian Securities and Exchange Commission (NSEC) regulations. In the code, the companies must observe social and environmental disclosures that help mitigate the problems arising from environmental degradation. Comparing the Nigerian domestic and international oil Industries regarding the SED could give essential details regarding companies conforming to the regulations of the NSEC. Finally, the research incorporated an aspect of looking at the SED scope in Nigeria's oil industry. Looking at the extent and the information in the report delved into the information that forms the essential parts involved in the reporting. Therefore, the present study examines social and environmental disclosure in the Nigerian oil industry.

1.2 Problem Statement

The Nigerian oil industries' social and environmental disclosure has not been adequately investigated. One study by Asaolu et al. (2011) assessing the Nigerian oil industry's SED level was done using a content analysis approach to identify the extent to which the disclosures have adhered to global best practices. Since then, no evidence exists that shows the SED status in the Nigeria oil Industries or the scope with which it is done. The researcher formulated to bring these issues into context and establish what the sector companies are doing regarding the SED by conducting face-to-face interviews with the oil companies and

their host communities using a thematic analysis approach to answer the qualitative questions. Moreover, it is not in the public domain what the companies face when preparing the disclosures. Perceptions and the associations of the members of the communities under which the firms operate are unknown. The study is vital in finding the answers to the issues highlighted. Attempts are rife to conserve and keep the environment sustainable for the next generations. Plans are also made to mitigate the effects of climate change due to global industrial pollution. SED is the one way a country can measure the steps being made to reduce pollution and protect the country's environment. With this spirit, the researcher forged to investigate and establish Nigeria's oil industry regarding SED status and scope.

1.3 Research Aims and Objectives

The study aims to examine social and environmental disclosures in the Nigerian oil industry and to address the following objectives:

1. Identify the motivations behind social and environmental disclosure in the Nigerian oil industry.
2. To investigate the perceptions of host communities on the SED reporting practices of the Nigerian oil industries.
3. To discuss the challenges faced by the Nigerian oil industry in developing and promoting SED.
4. To examine the scope of Social Environmental Disclosure (SED) among Nigerian oil industries.
5. To examine the differences in SED reporting practices between the Nigerian domestic and international oil industries.

1.4 Research Questions

The thesis set to answer the following questions that were aligned according to the objectives of the study:

1. What motivational aspects influence stakeholders' view of Nigerian oil industries' social and environmental disclosure (SED) practices?
2. What are the perceptions of the host community concerning the Nigerian oil Industries' social and environmental disclosures (SED) practices?
3. What are the stakeholders' perceptions of Nigerian oil Industries' challenges in developing and promoting social and environmental disclosures?
4. What is the scope of social and environmental disclosures (SED) among the oil Industries that operate in Nigeria?
5. Are there considerable differences in the social and environmental disclosures (SEDs) among Nigeria's domestic and international oil industries?

1.5 Need for The Research

The research was timely and informed since the Nigerian government put the NSEC code in place in 2011. No evidence exists of documented information to show significant strides made since then regarding SED. Companies in the oil industry, like companies in other sectors, endeavour to meet the standards, but their challenges are not yet known. Thus, the research was essential to document the companies' challenges in attempts to report their SED annually. The investigation was vital to increase the knowledge and inform the public on the Nigerian oil sector's state regarding social and environmental disclosures. The findings could tell the people about the SED information and how the oil Industries endeavour to disclose this information. Notably, the public needed to know about the organisations in the oil industry's attempts regarding conservation measures made to sustain the environment.

1.6 Justification for The Study

Social and environmental disclosures are essential when a country is conscious of industrial activities' influence on the environment. The recent increases in global temperatures and the consequent devastating climatic changes emanate from industries' pollution activities. The oil sector in Nigeria is very vibrant and directly influences the environmental implications across the country. Therefore, the researcher must investigate the oil sector's SED status to ascertain the strides the oil Industries have made in achieving this course. Also, various countries have implemented strategies, making it mandatory for firms to document their SED annually. The attempts are gaining momentum, and Nigeria should not be left behind in making environmental accountability plans and implementing them. Looking at the challenges of making the SED disclosures is vital in helping put a mitigation framework in place. Lastly, the research is essential in informing the public and the regulatory agencies about what the companies are doing to conserve sustainability.

1.7 The Limitations of Prior Studies

This study reviewed variables that depict the SED quantity and quality. Aburaya (2012) indicates that in the last forty years, there has been discussion on SED in the literature (p.5). Social and environmental disclosure have allowed research on how firms can gain from societal interactions (Gray, 2010, p. 49). As a result, companies are establishing strategies that adhere to SED requirements. A wide range of literature has indicated that SED is a vital phenomenon undertaken by firms and influenced by multiple factors.

Regardless, there are multiple limitations in studies conducted in the past, among them being that they are focused on quantity rather than the quality of reporting. According to Brammer et al. (2006), quality disclosure is not associated with the report's quantity (p. 1028). Further, dependency on quantitative data may also be misleading. As Smith et al. (2005) indicated,

considering the word count of a report does not translate to disclosure comprehension (p.127). On the other hand, focusing on quantity does not translate to quality that reflects the actual state of a company. Therefore, a high volume of disclosures does not translate to more excellent quality (Aburaya, 2012, p. 10). A perception is held that the disclosure quality impacts stakeholders and society compared to the quantity.

However, quality reflects the company's provision of information on its actual activities or provides general information (Aburaya, 2012, p. 11). Moreover, quality is a daunting and subjective task, hence considering the quality and quantity of SED reporting. Analysing the various dimensions of quality provides an in-depth comprehension and insight into the quality of disclosures. Most existing research has focused on the environmental impact of business activities and environmental disclosure while setting aside the social implications and disclosures. The motivation inherent in these studies is the growth of global environmental concerns and the greater attention paid. Compression from the public about the impact of corporations' actions on the environment, with other studies emphasising that environmental evidence is not the central social disclosure area in the annual report (A.R.). For Rizk et al. (2008), information tied to employees is vital within the Egyptian context (p.308), and Sobhani et al. (2009) stated that information on human resources was prevalent in the context of Bangladesh.

Environmental factors have focused on specific economic sectors sensitive to the environment, ignoring other economic sectors (p.179). The rationale is that the other sectors do not affect the environment, which runs the risk of providing misleading disclosures. Nigerian studies rarely focus on the oil industry, with only a single study by Asaolu et al. (2011) assessing the Nigerian oil industry's SED level. The study employed a content analysis approach in identifying the extent to which the disclosures have adhered to global best practices. The study established that they were arbitrary and incompatible SED

disclosures of the sample firms hence recommended introducing a framework for SED. Other studies conducted in the past identified two primary limitations. These were SED-related, and the focus on environmental disclosure with minimal attention given to the impact of the perceptions held by Host Communities (H.C.s) regarding SED in the country's oil industry.

This study (An Investigation of social and environmental disclosures in the Nigeria oil industry) examines experienced the limitations like the lack of a good measure for the quality of the SED. The 2-point scale and whether the documented information satisfied the stakeholders were not conclusive. The other limitation is the number of companies that served as the study population, which are eighteen (18) oil companies. The companies could be fewer, considering 281 oil companies operating in Nigeria. However, the population was arrived at since the companies are listed in the Nigeria stock market, and their information could be obtained easily, unlike those listed. The limitation is the measure of perception and satisfaction as a scale for this does not reflect the totality of the topic. However, the limitations could not deter the investigation from presenting an accurate picture of the SED in the Nigerian Oil Industry.

1.8 Methodological Approach

The study will adopt a mixed research design, which entails both qualitative and quantitative approaches. To Creswell and Creswell (2017), this method involves collecting, analysing, and integrating qualitative and quantitative data in a single study to provbetter understand research problem under investigation. According to Merriam & Associates, 2002, the qualitative method employs language and narratives, which seeks to understand social experiences surrounded by the point of view of the participant's perceptions and experiences. The researcher will gather qualitative data from primary data sources from the field, including raw data collected using interviews. Interviews will be preferred for collecting

preliminary data from the area since they provide a platform for the researcher to elicit more information about the subject matter as well as offer the ability to observe both the subject and the situation to which the interviewees respond to the question (Creswell and Creswell 2017).

The researcher will conduct a face-to-face interview using semi-structured topic guide questions on two target groups which include (1): Company Management and their Employees. (2). Community Leader, Youth Leader, Community Clergy (Pastors), Community Residents and Academician within the target company area. The researcher will select four companies from the sample eighteen oil firms for the interviews. Two oil companies will be international oil industries, and the other two will be domestic (Local) oil industries. The four companies were chosen based on their different geographical locations in various states, enabling the researcher to gather information from varied social and environmental settings. The interview will be carried out mainly for the heads of departments of the sampled oil companies to ensure the accuracy of the information. Besides, an interview of the people responsible for the different departments in the organisation would provide a rich blend of views on the company's responsibility to both social and environmental aspects of their existence and operation.

On the other hand, the quantitative data will be gathered from secondary data sources such as the annual reports, Nigeria Stock Exchange, Media and Articles/Reports instigated by Nigeria oil companies will also be considered. Binh (2012) describes secondary data as those previously gathered by other scholars while conducting their primary studies. The study will also incorporate the yearly reports of the targeted eighteen oil Nigerian industries. Company annual reports are chosen because they are readily available on company websites and can easily be accessed. The research will use yearly company reports from 2011 to 2018 due to the recent rise of awareness and interest in CSR.

The research objectives /questions will be answered as follow:-

- What motivational aspects influence stakeholders' view of the Nigerian oil industries' social and environmental disclosure (SED) practices? Face-to-face interviews using a semi-structured questionnaire will be used to establish data. Thematic analysis using NVivo will analyse the responses.
- What are the host community's perceptions concerning the social and environmental disclosures (SED) practices by the Nigerian oil Industries? Face-to-face interviews using a semi-structured questionnaire will be used to establish data. Thematic analysis using NVivo will analyse the responses.
- What are the stakeholders' perceptions of the Nigerian oil Industries' challenges in developing and promoting social and environmental disclosures? This will also be determined through face-to-face interviews using a semi-structured questionnaire to establish data. Thematic analysis using NVivo will analyse the responses.
- What is the scope of social and environmental disclosures (SED) among the oil Industries that operate in Nigeria? The researcher will also consider assessing Annual Reports, Nigeria Stock Exchange, Media and articles/reports instigated by Nigerian oil companies. Content analysis and descriptive statistics using SPSS will analyse the responses.
- Are any social and environmental disclosures (SEDs) differences between Nigeria's domestic and international oil industries? Assessment of Annual Reports, Nigeria Stock Exchange, Media and articles/reports instigated by Nigeria oil companies will also be considered. Content analysis and descriptive statistics using SPSS will analyse the responses.

1.9 Thesis Structure

Chapter 2 discusses the literature review in two. Literature Review 1. Examining the concepts of CSR and SED, Nigeria as a Research Study Context. Literature Review 2- Described Social Environmental Disclosure (SED), Evidence of Social Environmental Disclosure, Examining the quality of SED, SED theory and Systematic Review literature. Chapter 3 emphasises the theoretical framework, which deliberates two theories, the Stakeholder's theory and the Legitimacy theory, used to determine the research objectives. Chapter 4 describes the research methodology employed and how the data was obtained, collected, and analysed using the accepted research software tools. Chapters 5, 6 and 7 will summarise and discuss the thesis results. Chapter 8 concludes with the outcome of the thesis findings and outlines the originality contributions to knowledge. Policies recommend showing the study's limitations and then offering the Implication direction for further research.

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW 1

2.1 Introduction

Today, the environment is of significant concern within the existing ecological, social, and economic setup. Retaining and improving the environment has become vital within the context of business globally (Uwuigbe & Uadiale, 2011, p. 258). Firms are responsible for ensuring that they engage in their activities in an environmentally sustainable manner, and their actions often place a significant amount of pressure on the environment's structure (Uwuigbe & Uadiale, 2011, p. 258). In the last twenty years, environmental accounting has emerged. The emergence has been a response to the public demand for companies to be socially responsible; hence firms have embarked on making voluntary social and environmental disclosure (SED) tied to their activities as a means of being accountable to their consumers and meeting their demands (Sani, 2018, p. 56).

Further, there has also been increased concern about the environmental impact of industrial activity. The problems tied to global warming and greenhouse gas emissions have also increased the interest among stakeholders in incorporating environmental activities and their overall effect on the environment (Uwuigbe & Uadiale, 2011, p. 258). Climatic concerns have led to a rise in SED among firms.

The increased response varies in different companies and countries wherein most developed nations, such reporting was developed voluntarily, for instance, through standards such as global reporting initiatives (GRI). The increased reporting is evidenced by the rise in the Social, Environmental, and Governance (SEG) reporting globally in 2017, according to surveys by N100 and G2601, as mandatory requirements by governments and stock markets in these nations (KPMG, 2017, p. 26). Similarly, regulation may be deemed the primary and sole driver of increased reporting practices' stability. Therefore, despite corporate SED being

acknowledged as being a voluntary undertaking, a mandatory requirement has made such reporting reach its present levels and is also a key to improving future reporting practices (Roca & Searcy, 2012, p. 106; Alonso-Almeida et al., 2014, p. 320; KPMG, 2017, p. 30). Despite the advancements made in SED reporting practices in developed countries, the regulations are still available to ensure proper reporting. For example, in Australia, the Financial Service Reforms Act (FSRA) was enacted in 2010 that mandates social disclosures (Sani, 2018, p. 56). Similarly, in France, the Grenelle Act was passed in 2009, making it mandatory to engage in SED in the country. Likewise, the companies Act revised in 2006 in the United Kingdom (UK) obligated the companies to make SEDs.

In Denmark, large corporations must disclose climate and human rights information as part of their annual reports and accounts (Sani, 2018, p. 57). Consequently, governments and stock markets in developed nations are placing regulations to promote social and environmental accountability. For example, in developing countries like Indonesia, listed and publicly owned firms must provide their Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) reports. Further, India's Securities Exchange Board (SEB) and Companies Act (CA) demand CSR reporting. Also, South Africa's Johannesburg Stock Exchange (JSE) has made it mandatory for companies to discuss their operational environments (Sani, 2018, p. 57). Therefore, developed and developing nations have mandatory requirements for corporate social disclosure for practice enhancement.

Corporate social and environmental responsibility has developed and presently includes environmental elements. These comprise issues, for example, environmental pollution and degradation, which have become significant global economic, social, and political problems. These have forced corporations to establish measures for environmental accountability and reporting. According to Margolis and Walsh (2003), from a societal perspective, creating

wealth and contributing to material wellbeing, the measures for environmental accountability and reporting are vital corporate goals. The measurements are also essential for the restoration and equipment, including protecting and repairing the natural environment (p. 862). They argue that since firms may be designed to advance these objectives but operate in a setting infected by a host of recalcitrant problems hampering these objectives.

Nigeria is a developing nation. Recently, the Nigerian Securities and Exchange Commission (NSEC) mandated that firms adhere to specific social and environmental disclosures in its 2011 Code of Corporate Governance (CCG). There is significant potential for causing considerable and avoidable damages through unchecked activities involved in Oil and Gas exploration, in addition to the health hazards linked with exploration activities due to pollution (Uwaoma & Ordu, 2016, p. 2). Similarly, the Nigerian culture and the local and Indigenous communities' socioeconomic structure are also affected as the existing environmental laws are deemed ineffective, compounding the already existing problems as they are inadequate/inadequately enforced (Uwaoma & Ordu, 2016, p. 2). Therefore, according to a 2005 report by the Klynveld Peat Marwick Goerdeler (KPMG), it has led to a push by academics and other stakeholders in the field, especially environmentalists, for oil companies to voluntarily improve their performance concerning reporting as the environmental laws in these nations are inadequate (KPMG, 2005, p. 19).

The improved practices will promote sustainability reporting and accounting, which can be described as a set of conditioned rules that are socially accepted, have multiple significant effects on societal operations, and assist in the demonstration of accountability and integrity in businesses' actions attained through SED. Oil firms and industry groups increasingly recognise that global oil companies have operations in developing nations, for example, Nigeria. Such a country has inadequate environmental laws and should adopt the best practices. For instance, the American Petroleum Institute (API) is obligated to adhere to all

rules and best practices related to oil exploration (Uwaoma & Ordu, 2016, p. 2). The adherence is part of their pledge to ongoing health, safety, and environmental improvement. Further, the Environmental Policy of the Australian Petroleum Production and Exploration Association (APPEA), established in 1997, requires member companies to adhere to the applicable laws, regulations, standards, and guidelines protecting the environment (Uwaoma & Ordu, 2016, p. 2).

These laws, regulations, standards, and guidelines are absent, and they are expected to adopt the best practical means for preventing/minimising the adverse environmental effects of the activities (Uwaoma & Ordu, 2016, p. 2). Within the industry, it is also recognised that sustainability reporting, including providing reports on other non-financial indicators, is vital for management and measuring the firms' progress. Such reporting is also crucial as a means of stakeholder engagement that fosters a better understanding of the stakeholders' concerns. In developing countries like Nigeria, firms are rarely obligated to engage in accountability measures due to inadequate laws and enforcement. The impact of the oil industry on the environment demands rigorous SED reporting. Therefore, this study investigates social and environmental disclosure in the Nigerian oil industry, and the understanding of the disclosure is the focus of the literature review.

2.2 Concepts of CSR and SED

2.2.1 Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) as a notion has gained prominence in the business field in the recent past. However, it is not a new concept within the management field that contributes to societal progress through collaboration with firms. In the 1770s, Adam Smith introduced the analogy of "the invisible hand" to illustrate capitalists' domestic economic significance despite their primary intention being their interest. According to Smith, the

'hand', which is metaphorical, is beneficial to society, even if the benefits were unplanned. The invisible hand produces unexpected outcomes. Therefore, according to Smith, social welfare results from capitalists' activities. Consequently, the effect's CSR activities on society have been debated since then to date.

Despite numerous arguments and discussions on companies' social responsibility, an important question remains about CSR. At one point, CSR may refer to the engagement with Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs), while in another instance refers to charitable donations and later ethically treating employees. CSR refers to the obligations people in business have in pursuing policies, making decisions, and following desirable courses of action that benefit society (Hamidu et al., 2015, p. 84).

The other definitions available during the '50s recognised managers need to be responsible for the societal good. Therefore, CSR must factor in whether actions of the public's interest advance foundational societal beliefs and promote stability, strength, and harmony in the community (Hamidu et al., 2015, p. 84). The definitions here are linked based on the need to align CSR activities with management's consideration of the existing socio-political factors within the context of their operations. Presently, firms are under immense pressure to comply with established regulations related to environmental protection and transparency. Combined with the competitive saturation in the market, CSR is considered a strategy by firms to survive and increase their operational efficiency. Recent research is focused on CSR's impact on financial performance. The focus has drifted from an ethical perspective to performance orientation with the analysis, shifting from a macro-social perspective to an organisational level. There has also been increased institutional pressure to increase CSR activities that have demanded the introduction of CSR initiatives that cover more than maximising the shareholder's wealth. Firms are expected to engage in sustainable developmental activities, ensure accountability and transparency in operations, maintain good relationships with

stakeholders, comply with the set global CSR standards, engage in ethical business practices, and engage in advocacy related to elements of human rights and principles of democracy.

A review of CSR's multiple definitions highlights that firms should contribute to society's development as they improve their corporate reputation and embrace corporate citizenry. Therefore, the legal, ethical, and economic initiatives are the main focus of meeting stakeholders' expectations. CSR definition by authors is divergent and heterogeneous. For instance, some researchers view CSR as the corporate status and activities concerning their perceived societal and stakeholder obligations. On the other hand, as a corporate concept, Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) has recently acquired traction in the business world. The focus of CSR definition by multiple authors is divergent and heterogeneous. For instance, Herrera & Heras-Rosas (2020, pg. 841) define CSR as the corporate status and activities derived from or perceived through societal and stakeholder obligations. According to Agudelo et al. (2019, pg.4-6), CSR definitions emphasise sustainability and societal duties such as economic, legal, ethical, and discretionary responsibilities. However, today CSR is commonly described as a firm's voluntary contribution toward sustainable development beyond legal obligations.

Figure 2.1: The Dimensions of Defining CSR In Different Periods

Period & Focus Area	Summary of Dimensions
1950's – 1960's <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Religious & Humane philosophies • Community development • Unregulated philanthropy • Poverty alleviation • Obligation to the society 	Philanthropy
1970's – 1980's <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extension of CSR commitments • CSR as symbol of Corporate citizenship • Stakeholder relationship management • Corporate reputation • Socio-economic priorities • Bridging governance gap • Stakeholders rights • Legal & Ethical responsibilities 	Regulated CSR
1990's – 21st Century <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Competitive strategy • Environmental protection • Sustainability • Internationalisation of CSR standards • Transparency & accountability 	Instrumental/Strategic CSR

Source: (Hamidu, et al., 2015, p. 85).

At this stage, the whole notion of CSR revolves around philanthropy, which can be regarded as transcending charity with just a few actions. CSR has evolved from generosity to approved practices and instrumentality or planned CSR since the 50s era (Aminu, 2015). Firms are constantly being pushed to observe environmental rules, openness, and the industry is flooded with rivals in the new century, forcing the use of CSR as a method to thrive and be more effective (Aminu, 2015). Researchers are currently focusing on CSR's impact on economic success. The focus of CSR conceptual examination and empirical studies has switched from ethics to performance in this era, and the type of expertise has transitioned from macro-social to corporate (Aminu, 2015). Institutional pressure to improve CSR has increased, necessitating the establishment of CSR initiatives beyond maximising shareholder profits.

2.2.2 The Primary Characteristics of Corporate Social Responsibility

Regardless of the multiple dimensions in defining CSR, certain core features of the concept can be seen in CSR practice. Most definitions, if not all, consider these features as the focus around which CSR practice manifests itself. The core attributes are discussed and summarised in Figure 2.2 below.

Figure 2.2: The Primary Characteristics of CSR

Source: (Hamidu, et al., 2015, p. 87).

CSR is a broad term encompassing a range of optional corporate practices beyond what the law demands. Many businesses are now more aware of and willing to assume responsibilities above the regulatory minimum (Aminu, 2015). CSR strives to limit or prevent unnecessary regulation by conforming to societal moral norms. Voluntarism is frequently cited by critics of CSR as a major problem regardless of it being a characteristic of CSR (Aminu, 2015).

According to them, the fundamental organisational aim should be to maximise shareholder revenue.

2.2.3 Voluntary

Voluntary disclosure displays a social obligation in the absence of statutory restrictions. Voluntary SED informs the public about the company's actions and how they affect the community and the environment. On the other hand, the corporation selects what to disclose, how to report, and how much detail to note (Odera, Scott and Gow, 2016). As a result, more prominent organisations typically have more stakeholders interested in SED. Many prior studies have demonstrated that the size of a firm is a good motivator for SED.

Furthermore, because SED is a method of coping with public pressure, the longer a firm has been publicly listed on the Exchange, the more probable it is to release more Information (Odera, Scott and Gow, 2016). According to several pieces of research, one of the most crucial characteristics that might impact SED is the firm's age (Odera, Scott and Gow, 2016). Profitable enterprises also report SED to demonstrate their impact on society's well-being, which helps to legitimise their existence. Finally, the private costs of a firm, like capital structure and profitability, are important motivators of its SED (Odera, Scott and Gow, 2016). Thus, voluntary SED informs the public about the company's actions and how they affect the community and the environment.

According to scholars, corporate social responsibility is any discretionary business effort beyond legal requirements. This emphasises governments and stakeholders, mostly in developing nations (Crane et al., 2008, p. 12). Firms are today familiar with and willing to consider such responsibilities beyond the law. The development of self-regulatory measures is perceived as a means of circumventing additional legal regulations through compliance with social and moral requirements.

2.2.4 Internalisation and Management of Externalities

Externalities in CSR are all the factors that impact the rights of the stakeholders and are often inadequately addressed in the firm's decision-making process. The examples here include environmental degradation as society is affected by the production process. Regulations may require companies to cater to the costs of such externalities; however, CSR is a viable discretionary method for dealing with such externalities, such as increasing safety measures. Most CSR activities deal with externalities related to the employees' human rights, minimising the impact of rationalisation, positive stakeholder relationships, and eliminating production processes and products that are unneeded, harmful, or dangerous. For instance, Unilever partnered with Oxfam to study the impact of businesses on Indonesians' lives to deal with the externalities associated with MNCs in Asia. Such externalities may have unexpected effects; hence CSR initiatives provide humane means of assisting as part of the corporate response.

2.2.5 Orientation Towards Multiple Stakeholders

The key theme in stakeholder management is identifying the stakeholders' orientation based on power, legitimacy of their claim, and urgency. Therefore, the definition of stakeholder orientation is vital in identifying and prioritising stakeholders by adopting a stepwise approach that begins with internal preparations, the appointment of a team of internal stakeholder leadership for marketing, communication, units of operation, human resources, investor relationships, and internal affairs to mention a few (Ahmad et al., 2014, p. 2). Corporate social responsibility involves factoring in multiple interests and impacts on different stakeholders. The assumption is that firms have an obligation toward their shareholders, but since it depends on their stakeholders to survive and thrive, their responsibility goes beyond the shareholders (Hamidu et al., 2015, p. 86). There is debate on

how shareholders and stakeholders should be incorporated into CSR activities. It is expanding the activities in CSR to include all the groups that evoke the practice's character.

2.2.6 Aligning Social and Economic Responsibilities

The practice (CSR) takes a broader perspective that includes societal interests, but it should not conflict with the primary purpose of engaging – profit-making. A wide range of CSR definitions highlights that social and economic responsibilities are aligned (Hamidu et al., 2015, p. 86). The feature has given significant attention to CSR's business elements, precisely its benefits from economic and social responsibility.

Another important aspect is the balancing of various stakeholder values. While CSR may include going past a tight focus on stakeholders and income, many individuals believe it should not be incompatible with it (Aminu, 2015). Although this is a divisive subject, many corporate and political descriptions of CSR highlight that it is about progressive self-concern in which economic and social responsibilities are intertwined.

2.2.7 Values and Practices

CSR is evidently about a set of corporate tactics and processes that focus on issues. Still, it is about something more for many individuals: a worldview guiding these efforts. One of the causes for the subject's division is the values component of CSR (Aminu, 2015). If it were just about what companies do in the social realm, there would be less debate than there is now about why they do it.

Corporate social responsibility involves specific practices and strategies that handle social issues, including a philosophy/set of values underpinning methods. The perspective is seen in communitarian/communicative societies' CSR initiatives that value traditions and cultural practices within their local communities (Lei, 2011, p. 14). The value dimension raises the

contention that CSR would not be contested if it focused on the social arena. According to Duarte (2010), in his study of the managers' perceptions and influence of personal values toward work, CSR practices are affected by the managers' value systems as the formulated CSR policies are based on their values and attitudes (p. 358).

2.2.8 Beyond Philanthropy

In other parts of the world, CSR involves public Philanthropy and corporate discretionary responsibility/voluntarism. Presently, CSR is mandatory as regulations protect it, and international standards are going towards a more instrumental/strategic approach from an altruistic approach (Hamidu et al., 2015, p. 87). Therefore, as a practice, CSR goes beyond Philanthropy due to its ability to meet the stakeholder demands and potential to achieve organisational objectives (Hamidu et al., 2015, p. 87). The argument assumes that CSR should be regulated and institutionalised as a standard business practice, not a discretionary undertaking.

2.2.9 Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure (CSR D)

As aforementioned, CSR is the voluntary contribution by a company to the sustainable development of a society beyond the requirements of the law. There has been a rise in CSR campaigns and related disclosure activities (Gamerschlag et al., 2011, p. 234). Large companies have put much effort and channelled finances into disclosing their social and environmental performance information.

CSR's importance is rising globally, and companies are increasingly providing CSR disclosures to meet the stakeholders' demands and expectations. CSR disclosure refers to the revelation or reporting of a company's CSR undertaking as part of its accountability to its stakeholders (Ernfjord & Voigt, 2018, p. 1). It communicates the social and environmental

impacts that are because of the economic actions of an organisation of specific interest groups and the larger society (Tran, 2018, p. 70). Therefore, executives must promote proper counselling and functions of providing resources of the independent directorate system by disseminating information in a timely and appropriate manner to interested parties (Tran, 2018, p. 70).

2.2.10 Types of Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure (CSR)

There are multiple forms of CSR disclosure of reporting that are mandatory and voluntary reporting. Mandatory reporting involves disclosing a company's CSR activities as required by law, while voluntary reporting involves voluntarily disclosing its activity (Alawiye-Adams & Busola, 2017, p. 5). The corporation's culture can attribute the motive for voluntary disclosure, the size of the company, the industry of operation, the legitimisation of current activities, forestalling disclosure by other parties, politics, and competitive advantage, to mention a few (Alawiye-Adams & Busola, 2017, p. 5). There is also an increase in responsible investors and investment funds that makes CSR disclosure vital in providing information on the market competitiveness and companies' future performance (Nofsinger et al., 2019, p. 712). Investors and other stakeholders demand transparency in the economic context and other aspects of the business. Consequently, voluntary disclosures are becoming mandatory disclosure requirements.

As highlighted by Crowther & Aras (2008), the European Commission (EC) indicates that CSR is an enterprise's responsibility to impact society (p. 35). Firms can develop social responsibility by adhering to the law, including consumer, environmental, social, ethical, and human rights concerns with their strategies and operations (Crowther & Aras, 2008, p. 52). The enterprises inform the interested parties on the CSR achievements of the social and environmental performance within their annual, integrated, and social reports, including their

website (Crowther & Aras, 2008, p. 52). The 2008 global financial crisis increased CSR accountability and reporting due to the need to restore investor and consumer trust in the market. Improved information, including its availability, restored stakeholder confidence (Crowther & Aras, 2008, p. 58). Therefore, disclosure helps build, maintain, and restore consumer confidence, promoting competitiveness and innovation in business.

2.2.11 Components of Corporate Social Reporting Disclosure

The components of CSR disclosure may include a myriad of factors depending on its originators. The features of CSR are demanded by various organisations such as the Securities Exchange Commission (SEC), the United Nations Global Compact (UNGC), the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), and the International Organisation for Standardisation (ISO). The Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) vary (Wuttichindanon, 2017, p. 157). These variations are presented in Figure 2.3 below.

Figure 2.3: The Components of CSR Disclosure

CSR component	UNGC	OECD	ISO	GRI	SEC
1. Good practice		✓	✓	✓	✓
2. Environment	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
3. Science and Technology		✓			
4. Consumer Protections		✓	✓	✓	✓
5. Fair business Practices	✓	✓	✓		✓
6. Human Rights	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
7. Labor Standards	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
8. Community and Society			✓	✓	✓
9. Innovation					✓
10. Anti-corruption	✓	✓	✓		✓

Source: (Wuttichindanon, 2017, p. 158).

The Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) is a commonly recognised institution that helps organisations, businesses, governments, and industries to understand and communicate their effects on environmental issues such as human rights, corruption, and climatic changes. It is an international organisation that is responsible for providing a global platform standard for reporting all problems relating to the environment. The Initiative spells make it mandatory for stakeholder groups to be transparent about their social, economic, and environmental impacts by publishing a sustainability report. Therefore, its framework for sustainability reporting assists companies in identifying, gathering, and reporting information regarding the social environment more clearly and comparably. The Conference of the Parties (COP) is an annual two-week meeting addressing countries' commitment to advance their actions regarding environmental sustainability. COP26 was the intended COP in 2020 but failed due to COVID

19 pandemics. During the conference, stakeholders from around the world discuss climatical changes and crises; for example, COP26 was meant to address the rising global temperature. Issues of wildfires, floods, drought, and rising sea levels were to be addressed, and each stakeholder declared commitment to addressing these issues and action plans for achieving a sustainable environment.

Research conducted today includes anti-corruption as part of its components. Nine CSR disclosure components are relevant to most listed companies; however, the features may depend more on the country of origin and regulatory body. In the oil industry, the components majorly focus on environmental issues and may include other parts.

2.2.12 SED concepts

Social and environmental disclosure comprises information about a firm's aspirations, public image, and activities concerning the environmental employee, community, and consumer-related issues. SED further involves the factors of equal opportunities, fair trade, corporate governance, and energy usage. Different media display social and environmental disclosure such as annual reports, advertising, employee councils, school education, and booklets. The concept of corporate social responsibility and social and environmental disclosure has, in the recent past, attracted many researchers. Different points of view have been deduced by researchers, especially on the production of environmental and social reports. Studies concerned with the decision-usefulness of reporting have, in most cases, reported social and environmental disclosures as significant decision points significance. Agency theory views voluntary disclosure as a way of reducing agency costs or as a method of forestalling future agency costs caused by legislation and regulation. Theorists who employ legitimacy theory view disclosures as essential to maintaining a corporation's freedom, reputation, and status,

having stakeholders and influential personalities. Disclosures are critical when employed by corporations, although it is suggested that one should expect that higher and larger profile companies exhibit a greater predisposition towards the use of SED.

2.2.13 The differences between CSR and SED

Social and environmental disclosure (SED) is considered generalised information that relates to a firm's activities and public image concerning the environmental community, consumer issues, and employees. On the other hand, corporate social responsibility is a self-regulation model that helps firms become mindful of the effects they cause on society, including environmental, economic, and social impacts. Furthermore, SED is a compulsory requirement that compels corporations to comply with the set of rules and regulations at the national and international levels. At the same time, CSR is a voluntary commitment by corporations to become socially responsible and accountable to themselves, the public, and their stakeholders.

Corporate social responsibility is characterized by voluntary activities, stakeholder management, alignment of social and economic obligations, externalities management, and values and practices. Profitability margins, corporation size, and industrial affiliation illustrate social and environmental disclosure.

2.3 Nigeria as a Research Study Context

Nigeria is a West African country with an estimated population of 210 million people and is the world's sixth most populous (World Bank 2021). According to the research, Nigeria is Africa's most significant oil and gas exporter due to its natural resource endowment, notably in gas reserves (Craggs & Neate 2019). Oil and gas exports are projected to account for more

than 90% of its exports. In a research study context, Nigeria is the largest exporter of oil and gas in Africa due to its natural resource endowment, especially in the gas reserves (Craggs & Neate 2019). It is estimated that oil and gas exports account for more than 90% of its exports. Poverty and environmental pollution remain a significant challenge despite her natural resource endowment. The annual carbon emission is estimated at more than 82.6 million tons (World Bank, 2021). The researcher continues to explain Nigeria as an economic, geographical, political, and social environment below.

Figure 2.4: Context of Research Study Map

Map of Nigeria shows the 36 states and federal capital territory (FCT), Abuja.

Sources: Charles T Atang

- **Economics:**

Nigeria has the largest economy in Africa, with an annual 2019 GDP estimated at \$448.1 billion and a GDP per capita of \$2,230 as of 2019 (World Bank 2021). In terms of nominal GDP, the country is considered the 26th largest economy globally. Nigeria is a lower-middle-

income economy, mainly dependent on natural resources endowment, especially crude oil and gas. The oil and gas sector contributes an estimated 10% of the country's GDP. According to World Bank (2021), the crude oil and natural gas sector contribute the most significantly to Nigeria's GDP. However, despite its strong economy, the country's economic development has been affected by corruption, resource mismanagement, and military rule (Craggs & Neate 2019). That has contributed to rising inflation in the economy, estimated at 11.4% as of 2019 (World Bank 2021).

- **Political:**

Nigeria's political system has historically alternated between democratic and military governance (Yagboyaju & Akinola 2019). At present, the federal government of Nigeria consists of the executive, under President Muhammadu Buhari, the legislature and the judiciary. The west African country, which attained independence on 1 October 1960, is known for its pre-modern Kingdoms and extensive traditional states (Yagboyaju & Akinola 2019). Despite its prominence as one of the largest states in the continent, there has been a recurrent perception that Nigeria is still underperforming as a lower middle-income country due to inadequate political governance systems (Yagboyaju & Akinola 2019).

- **Geography:**

Nigeria is a West African country with neighbours Benin in the west, Niger in the North of the country, and Cameroon in the east (Craggs & Neate 2019). As a federal republic, Nigeria comprises 36 states, including the target chosen states- Akwa Ibom State, Bayelsa State, Delta State, and Rivers State, Delta, which focus on this study. The country is the most populous nation in Africa and the seventh most populous country globally, with an estimated 210 million people; it is the most populous nation in Africa and the sixth most populated

country in the world (World Bank 2021). Regarding its geographical profile, the government is mostly a patchwork of distinctive regions, including deserts, swamps, mountains, and plains (Craggs & Neate, 2019).

- **Social and Environment:**

Nigeria is an English-speaking nation and the most culturally and ethnically diverse country, with more than 250 ethnic groups. The three dominant ethnic groups in the country are the Igbo, Yoruba, and Hausa-Fulani (Craggs & Neate 2019). Regarding religious affiliation, 50% of the population is Christian, while the remaining half is Muslim. Nigeria's environmental conservation performance is considered less desirable given that in 2019, its total GHG emission was estimated at 100.2 million tonnes, representing a 2.61% increase from its 2018 level. According to Omofwonmwan and Osa-Edoh (2017), the Niger Delta region, known for its large oil industries, has been reported to experience large oil spills and other environmental challenges. Some of Nigeria's common environmental issues are waste management problems, deforestation, and soil degradation (Omofwonmwan & Osa-Edoh 2017). Therefore, the contextual study setting chosen is Nigeria due to the country's poor environmental conservation with numerous oil spills, deforestation, and soil degradation.

2.3.1 Historical Background of the Nigerian Oil Industry

The exploration of oil and gas in Nigeria commenced in 1908 after the British Colonialists gave a royal charter to the German entity – the Nigerian Bitumen Corporation – and a company chartered by the colonial rules – British Colonial Petroleum. These companies began exploring oil and gas in Western Nigeria, specifically the Araromi area (Dickie, R.K 1966). However, World War I in 1914 disrupted these exploration activities. Exploration resumed later in 1937, but it was done with a different company - Shell DD'Arcy– a

consortium of Shell and Royal Dutch and presently known as the Shell Petroleum Development Company of Nigeria. The company was a sole proprietor in oil exploration and prospecting in the whole of Nigeria (H.L Schatzl 1969, p.1). However, its efforts were interrupted by World War II in 1945 but resumed in 1947. Oil was discovered at commercial levels in 1956 at Oloibiri in Bayelsa state after drilling 28 oil wells and 25 core dry holes, with actual production beginning two years after the discovery where 5,100 bbl./d. Was recorded (J. Oke 2006, P.26).

The country got its independence in 1960, and the Nigerian government, now run by locals, opened the industry and allowed onshore and offshore oil and gas exploration in other areas of the Niger Delta. These rights were given to Mobil, Agip, Elf (previously Safrap), Texaco (previously Tenneco), and Chevron (previously Amoseas). They destroyed the monopoly held by Shell in oil exploration in the country, but it remained the most significant oil corporation. The opening of the industry allowed more firms to join oil exploration, and by 1970 its production had peaked at 2.4 million bbl./d, making it the country's 7th largest oil-producing company in the world (Decree No 51 of 1969(Now Cap P10 Law of the Federation of Nigeria (2004).

In the early stages, the government had a minimum interest in the industry and only collected royalties, rent, and taxes. However, this shifted after following the United Nations Resolution on Permanent Sovereignty over Natural Resources (Taju Audu & Co, 2015). The resolution evoked significant interest from the government in controlling the industry, and it has begun to take steps towards gaining control by enacting the 1969 Petroleum Act. The Act bequeathed control and ownership of all petroleum-related resources to the Federal government, and in 1971 the country joined the Organisation of Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPEC). As part of its policy, the organisation required its member countries to acquire the concessionary interests held by foreign firms and, through a 1971 decree by the

country's military government, established the Nigerian National Oil Corporation (NNOC). The decree granted the NNOC controlling interests of firms in the industry and was renamed the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC) in 1977. The corporation has Joint Venture Contracts (JVCs) with six International Oil Corporations (IOCs) and one indigenous company (NNPC Act No 33 of 1977(Now NNPC Act Cap N10 LFN 2004). These areas are listed below.

- The SPDC – The Company accounts for 40% of oil production. The JVCs comprise NNPC, Shell, Elf, and Agip with 55%, 30%, 10%, and 5%, respectively.
- Chevron with a JVC of 60% for NNPC and 40% for Chevron.
- The Mobil Producing Nigeria Unlimited (MPNU) comprises NNPC (60%) and Mobil (40%).
- The Nigerian AGIP Oil Company Ltd. (NAOC) contains NNPC (60%), Agip (20%), and Philips Petroleum (20%).
- The Elf Petroleum Nigeria Limited (EPNL) comprises NNPC (60%) and Elf (40%).
- The Texaco Overseas Petroleum Company Nigeria (TOPCON) includes NNPC (60%) and Chevron (40%).

The Nigerian corporation has Production Sharing Contracts (PSCs) with Addex, Snepco, Statoil, Esso, Oranto, Ocean Energy, Philips, Conoco, ChevronTexaco, Elf, NAE, and Petrobrass. In contrast, it has a single service contract with Agip. The National Corporation established refineries in Kaduna, Port Harcourt, and Warri between 1978 and 1985 that have a cumulative capacity of 445,000 BPD connected by pipelines and depots.

The primary function of the NNPC, as created in 1977, was overseeing the industry's regulation, including making upstream and downstream developments. However, over time the mandate has changed to rule and Business Corporation. The entity was restructured in

1988, and the restructuring involved its division into six directorates. These directorates included Exploration and Production, Refineries and Petrochemicals, Finance and Accounts, Commercial and Investment, Corporate Services, and Gas and Power under a Group Managing Director. Further, another twelve subsidiaries were developed during the restructuring process. These subsidiaries included Duke Oil, Hyson (Carlson Bermuda), Integrated Data Services Ltd (IDSL), National Engineering & Technical Co. (NETCO), Nigerian Gas Co. (NGC), Nigerian Petroleum Development Co. (NPDC), National Petroleum Investment Management Service (NAPIMS), Warri Refinery & Petrochemical Co. (WRPCO), Kaduna Refinery & Petrochemical Co. (KRPC), and Port Harcourt Refinery Co. (PHRC) (Isochukwu 2018).

In the 80s, oil production significantly declined due to an economic recession in the country, but the industry rejuvenated in 2004 when production reached a record 2.5 million barrels daily. Development strategies were established to further increase the production volume with the target of a production level of 4 million barrels per day by 2010 (Giwara, 2011, p. 1). Today, exports in the industry are a significant revenue source for the company accounting for approximately 90% of Nigeria's gross earnings. A summary of the key historical developments is provided in Figure 2.5 below.

Figure 2.5: Key Historical Developments in The Nigerian Oil Industry

S/N	KEY DATES	NIGERIAN OIL INDUSTRY HISTORICAL DEVELOPMENT
1	1908	Oil is discovered in Nigeria.
2	1971	Nigeria decides to join OPEC; Nigerian National Oil Corp. (NNOC) is created.
3	1977	NNOC becomes Nigerian National Petroleum Corp. (NNPC).
4	1981	NNPC decentralizes into nine subsidiaries.
5	1999	Nigeria adopts a new constitution; democratically elected president Olusegun Obasanjo is inaugurated.
6	2003	The government begins to deregulate fuel prices and announces that its four major oil refineries will eventually be privatized.
7	2005	The company signs a \$1 billion contract with Chevron Texaco Nigeria to construct the Floating, Production, Storage, and Offloading Vessel (FPSO) for the Agbami deep offshore oil field.

Source: (Funding Universe, n.d.).

2.3.2 Background District of the Niger Delta Region and its Crisis.

The Niger Delta, one of the 36 states in Nigeria, is located along the Niger River and positioned directly along the Gulf of Guinea and the Atlantic Ocean (Craggs & Neate 2018). The Niger Delta region consists of nine (9) Nigerian coastal cities, as shown by the geographical map depicted in Figure 2.6 below. The nine (9) coastal towns in the south of Nigeria include Ondo State, Edo State, Delta State, Bayelsa State, Imo, State Akwa Ibom State, Abia State, Rivers State, and Cross River State (Udotong et al. 2017). The background zone for this study included the four states within the Niger Delta region (i.e., Akwa Ibom State, Bayelsa State, Delta State, and Rivers State). The researcher selected the participants for the investigation from the four states of the Nigerian south-south region. Udotong et al. (2017) state only the Cross-River state is considered a non-oil and gas-producing state.

Figure 2.6: Map of the Niger Delta Region, Nigeria

Map of the Niger Delta Region, Nigeria
Source: Charles T. Atang (2022)

The Niger Delta region, also known as the Oil Rivers region, is densely populated and has a considerable history as a critical producer of palm oil and petroleum oil. In the period between 1885 to 1893, the region was recognised as a British Oil Rivers Protectorate (Ugbebor & Yorkor 2018). The area, which extends over 70,000 (sq. m), has an estimated population of 31 million people with more than 40 ethnic groups.

Over the years, the Niger Delta region has been at the centre of environmental degradation concerns from international environmental organisations such as the UNEP (Udotong et al., 2017). Concerns have been raised over rising pollution in the region due to its strategic position as a significant oil-producing region. Numerous oil spills and air and soil pollution have been reported in the area due to the multinational oil corporations' unrestrained oil and gas exploration activities (Ugbebor & Yorkor 2018). The host communities in the region have experienced poor living standards and suffering due to the environmental damage

caused by the multinational oil-producing companies that operate in the area. According to Vidal (2010), the region recorded more than 7,000 oil spill cases over the 30 years from 1970 to 2000.

Its Crisis:- Nigeria is considered the largest oil producer nation in the African subcontinent ("Nigeria" 2015). The historical evidence of the oil industry in Nigeria points to the early 1900s, at the beginning of World War I. Since the early 20th century, Nigeria has been known to be one of the essential areas of the world where oil is extracted, refined, and produced. Its Crisis started when the Nigerian government embarked on the privatisation and nationalisation of a few Nigerian industries. Not only did this include the oil industry, but it also paved the way for loopholes in the infrastructure of the oil-based sector. The Nigerian central government nationalised the oil industry in the 1970s by issuing a verdict establishing the "Nigerian National Oil Corporation" ("Overview of Nigerian" 2016). Nigeria's desire to join OPEC has also hastened the nationalisation of the oil sector. Ethnic agitation and barbarism have erupted across Nigeria, particularly in the Niger Delta states, because of the overwhelming support based on inborn affinity. The stakes for controlling the massive oil assets are high.

At both state and central government levels, influence and, in this way, riches had ordinarily been hoarded by the chosen entryway groups who kept up a solid inclination to take care of their own by fiscally compensating their political supporters. This marks the beginning of the increasing political interest of foreign and domestic investors in the nation's oil segmentation (Oben-Torkornoo, 2018). The overwhelming support dependent on inborn alliance has energised ethnic agitation and savagery throughout Nigeria, especially in the Niger Delta states. The stakes for control of the enormous oil assets are high. Following the Nigerian National Oil Corporation (NNOC's) beginning, the Nigerian government earned authority

over oil incomes. Other externalities that bear the responsibility for weakening the oil industry depend upon the environmental legislation's social and environmental arguments.

- **Oil Spillage:** Oil spillages and related hazards are so common in Nigeria that it has been assessed that somewhere in the range of 9 and 13 million barrels have been spilt since oil boring began in the 1950s. One reason that consumption represents such a high level of all spills is that because of the small size of the oilfields in the Niger Delta; there is a comprehensive system of pipelines between them (Chete et al. 2011). Seasoned measures to build numerous offices and channels are inadequately kept up and have outlasted their assessed life span (Ifunanya, 2010). Oil spills majorly affect the biological system.

- **Gas Flaring:** It has been reasoned that Nigeria flares more flammable gas than all the other oil-producing nations in the world. Since it is expensive to isolate economically feasible gas from oil, gas is flared to build rough creation. Flaring has developed substantially with oil production in Nigeria since it has been confined in the west. While the international community, the Nigerian government, and oil companies tend to agree that gas flaring should be reduced, efforts have been limited and unsuccessful (IPIECA, 2018). Flares that are more seasoned and wasteful are periodically relocated away from towns. They are known to coat the ground and networks in the region with residue and destroy the nearby plants.

- **Corruption and Oil Theft:** The biggest threat to Nigeria's oil industry has been their very own administration. The Nigerian government has been engrossed in misusing the power to acquire any property for oil organisations. The state and federal governments receive a large portion of every dollar that leaves the Nige-delta area

(Okotie et al., 2018). In July 2013, research examining the consequences of oil robbery in Nigeria found that Nigeria lost \$10.9 billion in potential oil revenues between 2009 and 2011 (Okotie et al., 2018).

Even with all these crises emanating from the formulation of militancy and other Crises within the Niger-Delta region, Nigeria's economy has established a firm stance that is important, both historically and economically (Dada, 2007). However, the Nigerian oil industries are currently encountering significant barriers and tussles that have started to affect the oil industry and other dependent sectors. Be that as it may, rivalry for oil benefits created an incredible fear and struggle for those living in the locale (KPMG Professional Services, 2014). Many Nigerians believe they haven't witnessed the financial benefits that oil companies have brought to the country. Furthermore, Nigerian government officials have remained significant investors in the benefits of producing Nigerian oil, resulting in the government capturing nearly all oil production. At the same time, locals perceive little financial benefits and demand that oil companies compensate citizens.

Therefore, the Niger Delta region is a vital study zone for this research due to the region's historical background as a significant oil producer in Nigeria. Because the host communities in Niger Delta have experienced considerable pain and suffering due to environmental pollution, the region is considered the best zone to investigate the Nigerian oil industries' social and environmental disclosure (SED) reporting practices. The four states selected in the Niger Delta region include Akwa Ibom, Bayelsa, Niger Delta, and the Rivers States.

2.3.3 Brief Origins of the South-South catchword in Nigeria

Farooq A. Kperogi (2014) reports that at the 1994-1995 National Constitution Conference, Nigeria's Second Republic Vice President Dr Alex Ekweme developed the phrase "South-

South" to refer to Nigeria's Deep South (Farooq, 2014). In addition, the Nigerian print media enthusiastically endorsed and pushed the project. South-east states like Imo and Abia are further south than "South-South" states, such as Edo state and northern Cross River; therefore, the phrase isn't a geographical category at all. South-South is nothing more than a poor attempt to build a geo-cultural and political terrestrial—and character—for ethnic minorities in the formerly Eastern Area. Edo and Delta states were never part of the Eastern Area and were initially in the Western Region before the Nigerian government created a Mid-Western region. A new term has been coined, "South-South," to describe all people throughout Nigeria's south who do not identify as Igbo or Yoruba.

2.4 Conclusion

In conclusion, the concepts of corporate social responsibility (CSR) and social and environmental disclosure (SED) are essential aspects of the discussion. They are deeply analysed by determining the values and practices upheld by oil-producing companies and organisations in Nigeria. The impacts created by SED and CSR practices and activities are later examined in this study to identify the existing gaps in the services offered. The study discusses techniques such as voluntary activities, determination of externalities in management, the role of stakeholders, philanthropy, and the alignment of social and economic responsibilities as significant components of corporate social responsibility and SED.

The differences between SED and CSR are also defined where SED is more of mandatory regulation. At the same time, CSR is viewed as a voluntary activity and practice obligation internally developed and delivered to the community. Nigeria, as the main scope of the study, has been defined in terms of its geographical, economic, political, social, and environmental position concerning the practices of SED and CSR. Further, to determine the current levels of

CRS and SED in Nigeria, the historical background of oil-producing companies has been critically analysed by considering the activities of companies such as Joint Venture Contracts like Shell and Mobil Producing Nigeria Unlimited and Nigerian AGIP Oil Co.Ltd.

2.5 Literature Review 2- (1) Social Environmental Disclosure (SED)

2.5.1 Introduction

Over the years, as stated above, there has been increasing public awareness of firms' social and environmental responsibilities by the public. The increased attention is the origin of SED. Social and environmental accounting and disclosure research have been in existence for years. The studies have emphasized the importance of such disclosures as an indicator of a business' transparency (Katsoulakos & Katsoulakos, 2006, p. 52). The arguments here are that if the known results of specific actions can be attributed to men, then a business's responsibilities should comprise known outcomes of the business' undertakings regardless of their recognition by law. The element of business and social welfare was introduced in the 1930s by Theodore Kreps. He often used the social audit when referring to companies need to report their social responsibilities. Later in 1942, Peter Drucker, in his book, "The Future of Industrial Man", stated that firms have social and economic goals.

Finally, the assertion made in 1962, Milton Friedman argued that the primary purpose of a company's existence is generating profits for its shareholders. This allegation can be discussed to have increased the attention on the social and environmental outcomes of business activities. Studies conducted during this period considered SED as a variable when conducting a company's social and financial performance analysis. Despite the early mentions of disclosure, disclosure tied to a business's social and environmental elements can be traced back to the 1970s, when there was much debate on the role of business in providing services not provided by the government. During this period, firms in America and Europe began undertaking SED practices that identified, measured, monitored and disclosed the socio-economic impact of firms on society (Kolk, 2006, p. 36; Barr, 2011, p. 6).

Further, in the 1960s and 70s, there was increased criticism of industrialization, and, as a result, firms, especially multinationals, developed policies and strategies that would ensure social and environmental responsibility (Barr, 2011, p. 23). Therefore, the origin of SED can be traced back to the sixties (60s), when there was increased concern and debate on the social responsibility of firms and their increased impact on the environment. This situation introduced SED in accounting research and business literature.

Corporate disclosure experienced a significant transformation in the mid-seventies (the 70s) from focusing on profits. It was broadened to include SED, with Ernst & Ernst being the first company to highlight the changes. According to Kolk (2006), Ernst & Ernst's survey revealed that more companies were engaging in SED reporting (p.26). Further, Trotman (1979), in his study conducted in Australia at the time, also revealed that more firms were increasingly engaging in reporting that had the nature of SED over a ten-year period (1967-1977) (p.27). However, the disclosure was minimal. Similar trends were seen in America among the Fortune 500 nations, where SED between 1971 and 1975 rose from 51.4% to 85.7% (Abbott & Mosen, 1979, p. 510). During the period, SED was most notable in Germany, Netherlands, and France Europe, focusing primarily on employees and majorly quantitative (Kolk, 2006, p. 28). However, due to the poor economic conditions in the early eighties (80s), SED undertakings plummeted.

The undertaking re-emerged in the late eighties (80s) and under NGOs' influence; its focus was on the dimensions of external accountability. Consequently, the research focus was on the quantity of SED in AR. An examination conducted by Cowen et al. (1987) revealed that the average disclosure by various American companies in 1978 AR ranged from 0.4 – 1.25 pages (p.119). Similar findings were established among UK-based companies for a study (Harte & Owen, 1991, p. 58). Since then, SED has been on the rise. Internationally, SED

increased concern as evident in need to establish global SED reporting standards as in triple bottom line reporting and GRI. Despite the increased attention on the fallacy of a firm's profitability in determining the organizational performance, given its ignorance of the externalities involved in business operations, SED, after its reemergence in the 80s, has slowed down piecemeal and lacks a solid theoretical foundation.

2.5.2 Nature of Social Environmental Disclosure

Social and Environmental Disclosure has no universally accepted definition, including the well-defined guidelines on what comprises SED data. However, according to Gray et al. (2010, pg. 53), SED refers to the process of providing information that is designed to promote social accountability. Therefore, it involves providing information regarding organizational performance based on the firm's interaction with the environment and, per concept, the social and physical environment. It is accountable for and provides reports on policies, procedures, and their impact on the social and the general environment. There is SED essentially in a CSR undertaking, including voluntary and involuntary disclosures that affect society and the environment, which is the focus of this study, including the number of disclosures in research.

The rationale for the establishment of SED is to determine the monetary impact with solid data that an enterprise's activities have socially and environmentally induced. Since CSR activities are at different development levels in developed and developing countries, SED activities also vary. Disclosure activities in developing countries are more focused on meeting society's social and cultural demands, improving their quality of life, promoting equity, ensuring justice, and dealing with issues tied to pollution rather than material needs, as this is the concern of most of the population. However, the opposite applies to developing

countries where much focus is on meeting the basic material needs. The purpose of such disclosure is to account for the company's activities (social and environmental) to the affected stakeholders. The perception of a firm's CSR activities as they conform to those expected by its consumers improves financial performance.

Further, it is considered a situation where firms set out to maximize the wealth of their shareholders in line with the established CSR goals. This undertaking would impact the firm's performance (Lou & Bhattacharya, 2006, p. 3). According to Yuen & Yip (2002, pg. 98), SED recognizes organizational performance. Jenkins & Yakovleva (2006) highlights SED's roles, which include measurement, reporting, and assessing the efficacy of firms' social and environmental programs. Despite its benefits, developing countries like Nigeria have poorly implemented such disclosure strategies. The nature of SED is also the fact that it corresponds to one of the core characteristics of CSR that goes beyond the law; therefore, SED is not regulated by legislation. This quality produces variations in disclosure requirements and information across different regions.

However, international agencies are attempting to create uniformity in the quality and consistency of voluntary SED undertakings through the establishment of global standards and guidelines, for example, the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI), with the core principle within these standards being the promotion of clarity within the organizational objectives, ensuring a systematic approach to reporting, and ensuring completeness, integrity, and independence in the reports. For example, the GRI's principles combine the organization's information and the stakeholder to ensure they have a mutual understanding. The guide ensures fairness and truthfulness in reporting, allows comparisons, and ensures credibility in addressing the stakeholders' concerns. Research on SED should comprise the rationale behind the disclosure, issues the firm faces, and the elements that differentiate SED reports from other reports.

Therefore, despite being faced with problems such as the poor understanding of SED by firms, their defensive nature, and a lack of independent auditing that reduces is the degree of comparability, SED allows the making of assessments on the degree of the fulfilment of the social contract by a company, but three critical problems face the process.

2.5.3 Social Environmental Disclosure Theory

Since the act's introduction in 2010, petroleum-producing firms in Nigeria have been obliged to boost their yearly local investment by 63 per cent, according to Ovidia (2013). Regulatory requirements for patronizing Nigerian-sourced products and services increased from \$8 billion in 2010 to \$13 billion in 2015. The overall management issue was that, despite significant investment in local content development by petroleum-producing businesses, there is little study on the consequences of the companies' performance. In Ayoola and Olakunle's (2017) opinion, the specific management challenge was determining how the perception of the act on employees' task performance and perceived business performance of the organization affected employees' perceptions of their task performance (Ayoola & Olakunle, 2017). As of 2011, IPIECA has given guidance for enhancing the creation and implementation of local content policies within the petroleum sector.

Global oil and gas industry group IPIECA (International Petroleum Sector Environmental Conservation Association) has created a local content task force to update rules on local content development in the petroleum industry. IPIECA was founded in 1974. Based on several local content case studies in Norway, Brazil, Yemen, Russia, Trinidad & Tobago, Angola, and Nigeria, IPIECA guided the efficiently creating and execution of local content policies in the organization's Local Content Strategy paper.

2.5.4 Social Environmental Disclosure Information

Despite the emphasized advantages, specific issues may jeopardize the act's accomplishment of its goals. One restriction that Idris and Salisu (2014) is corruption, a severe socio-economic problem in Nigeria. The act's provisions have features that make it vulnerable to corruption. This includes the possibility of a conflict of interest among the many parties engaged in enforcing the act's requirements and the high chance of political influence, either through discretionary authority or through the impact of multinational petroleum-producing businesses. Lack of transparency in the petroleum industry's procurement process and the possibility of enabling a proliferation of facilitation payments to the Nigerian Content Development and Monitoring Board are additional components of the legislation's corruption vulnerabilities (NCDMB).

Another problem that might impede the achievement of the act's aims, according to Sola, Obamuyi, Adekunjo, and Ogunleye (2013), is the overall lack of infrastructure development across Nigeria, particularly at the grassroots level of society. Nigeria's industrial industry, small and medium-sized companies, and banking sector have all been impacted by the country's poor social and economic infrastructure development. As a priority, the Nigerian government must address the country's ongoing lack of infrastructure development. The lack of a strong accountability culture and the inadequate implementation of regulatory standards, particularly in environmental protection and community development, might limit the act's advantages. Another aspect that might impact the act's aims is access to capital for establishing local companies. To meet the sector's expectations, the local petroleum industry needs the assistance of local firms that are financially strong, inventive, employ well-trained employees, and are technologically sophisticated.

2.5.5 Motivations for Social Environmental Disclosure

Recently, a study has been conducted to determine the drivers for Social and environmental disclosure based on quantity and quality assessments. Ali's recent survey et al. (2022, pg. 3474) showed a variety of internal and external factors that influence disclosure and its dimensions in developing countries.

Figure 2.7 Motivation for SED

Determinants of CSR/Environmental Disclosure	Sig +ve	Insignificant	Sig -ve	Grand Total
Firms Characteristics				
Firm size	33	1	7	41
Industry	18	0	1	19
Financial performance	11	2	2	15
Firm age	3	1	1	5
Firm value	4	0	0	4
Leverage	1	1	1	3
Transparent information	3	0	0	3
Audit firm size	1	0	1	2
Managers/accountants positive attitude	2	0	0	2
Asset management	1	0	0	1
Capital expenditure	1	0	0	1
Employees' information	1	0	0	1
Fear of liability	0	0	1	1
Investment capability	1	0	0	1
Lack of resources	0	0	1	1
Non availability of data	0	0	1	1
Non-existence of need to legitimize corporate actions	0	0	1	1
Corporate Environmental Policies and Concerns				
Environmental concerns	7	0	0	7
Environmental performance	2	0	0	2
Institutional environment	2	0	0	2
Sustainability orientation	2	0	0	2
Eco friendly practices	1	0	0	1
Environmental expenditure	1	0	0	1
Financing for environmental equipment	1	0	0	1
GRI adoption	1	0	0	1
Determinants of CSR/Environmental Disclosure				
	Sig +ve	Insignificant	Sig -ve	Grand Total
Governance Characteristics				
Board size	6	0	5	11
Board independence	5	1	4	10
Stakeholders' interest/concern	10	0	0	10
Board gender diversity	4	1	4	9
CEO duality	1	2	2	5
Board age diversity	0	2	1	3
Board education	1	0	1	2
Board meetings	1	0	1	2
CSR committee	2	0	0	2
Independent audit committee	1	0	1	2
Long term tenure of directors	2	0	0	2
Foreign directors on board	1	0	0	1
Vision and mission	1	0	0	1
Owners and Shareholders				
Managerial ownership	2	3	1	6
Disperse ownership	3	0	1	4
Foreign ownership	3	0	1	4
Government ownership	3	1	0	4
Institutional ownership	2	1	1	4
Shareholder contribution	3	1	0	4
Public ownership	1	0	0	1

Sig +ve: Significant positive relationship; Sig -ve: Significant negative relationship; Insig: Insignificant.

According to the above table, the internal factors that include corporate environmental policies, company characteristics, corporate governance, owners, and shareholders strongly affect the company's disclosure levels. Company characteristics include the firm's size (33),

financial performance (11), and industry (19) are the most significant influencers in driving SED in developing countries. Following the list are the company characteristics, including audit size, dependency on the government, and capital expenditure. The three internal factors stand at one each, illustrating some influence on disclosure. Furthermore, in developing countries, factors such as lack of resources, non-availability of SED-related data, liability fear, and a lack of the need for the legitimization of corporate actions lead to a lack of disclosure of SED practices in companies in developing nations.

Moreover, positive attitudes from managers, information transparency levels, investment capability of firms, and asset management were positive factors that contributed to disclosure. Corporate governance includes board size, audit committee independence, board diversity, and meetings, according to the study, showed mixed influence on the level of disclosure in a company. Shareholders' ownership and concerns also influence the SED of a company in developing countries.

Similarly, considering the external environmental factors of a company, the research indicated that the promotion of SED relies on them. The analysis depicted that despite the existing poor legislation and enforcement in developing countries, some regulatory pressures in place influence the SED disclosure. The study has it that in the absence of legal legislation and policing, low implementation levels and weak institutions negatively influence SED activities and practices. Both the media and government pressures have been proved to impact disclosure positively. The global supply chain and social-cultural factors affect a company's disclosure level. At the worldwide level, stakeholders such as international buyers and sellers, global supply chain, international NGOs, globalization, and international regulatory bodies, for example, the World Bank, have a positive impact on social-environmental disclosure in developing nations. Moreover, companies' collaboration with

other normative organizations such as NGOs, SED forums and networks, and SED setting institutions in developing countries were influential on the levels of SED disclosure. Lack of public concern over social environment issues negatively influences social and environmental disclosure levels.

Furthermore, the industrial factors that affect SED in developing countries like Nigeria include current levels of competition, customer concerns, stock market listing, and overseas listing. Financial markets usually promote SED disclosure, while supplier's problems negatively affect disclosure. However, according to Ali et al. (2022, pg. 3475), the main motivations of SED are gaining corporate reputation and enhancing financial performance as well as demonstrating corporate accountability, managing key stakeholders, and further attracting investment opportunities.

Therefore, analyzing SED is vital for any firm. The primary questions in such an analysis are whether firms adopt general or specific attitudes in accounting for SED disclosure. The rationale is the differences between the levels of disclosure among different companies, which forms the foundation for understanding the motivation behind SED (Hassan, 2010, p. 7). According to Zhang et al. (2019, pg. 575-576), the critical motivations for social-environmental disclosure in businesses and companies include branding, relation-building, organizational culture, market pressure, financial benefits, reputation, and image, and the strategic business direction laid by the organization.

Additionally, the motivation behind SED may be political, commercially related, innovation, and technology-driven, often the unchanged attitude towards SED (Henderson, 2006, p. 231). Other motivating factors for engaging in SED include credibility, reputation, business case, morality, and external pressure (Kolk, 2004, p. 60; Thien et al., 2010). Therefore, it is vital to understand that firms that disclose their SED information provide more than enough

information which is essential in promoting and improving accountability. Moreover, the combination of the stakeholders,' self-determination and institutional commitment are motivators of social-environmental disclosure.

2.5.6 Perception and Challenges of SED

Corporations have in the past been faced with the challenge of how and what to report on their activities that support social environment disclosure and corporate social responsibility activities. Due to the complex nature of SED, stakeholders in most corporations have seemed to lack a consensus on identifying activities of preference since the actions affect their economic status. Similarly, the decisions on demand and consumer purchase have also been affected by SED. According to Zamora (2021), a study done in 2018 by Nielsen indicated that several consumers reported that they changed their consumption habits to conserve and reduce environmental impact. Similarly, employees in the same study stated that they were willing to contribute specific percentages of their earnings to boost the activities carried out by their organization in social and environmental conservation. Individuals and organizations across the globe value SED activities. Therefore, different social classes are somehow affected by SED activities and have varying perceptions of the subject matter.

However, implementing social environment disclosure faces challenges while collecting data about people and companies, especially when data mining feels so private or personal. Juhmani (2014) observes that customers and the public are most interested in whether the Nigerian oil industries have set aside sufficient funds to support the CSR and community welfare projects and the extent to which their oil exploration activities have affected the environment. However, factors such as the ill-defined SED policies, lack of senior management commitment, and ineffective corporate governance structures are considered

key challenges that have adversely affected the SED reporting practices of the Nigerian oil industries. Privacy disclosure is risky since information relating to people's daily lives is incorporated while dealing with corporate social responsibility. For example, data involving pregnancy in women requires the sensitive mining of private data. According to Zhang (2020, pg. 472-475), information such as personal social networking and life chores makes people feel monitored and sometimes viewed as unethical when inquiries are performed.

2.5.7 The Scope of SED

The theoretical and empirical literature review insight indicates that Nigerian oil companies have begun to appreciate the importance of issuing non-financial disclosure reports, which target other stakeholders besides the companies' shareholders (Oyadonghan & Gbalam 2013). The implication is that the focus of the Nigerian oil firms has shifted from the sole production of financial reports targeted at the stockholders to the provision of SED annual reports alongside the financial statements to disclose their social and environmental sustainability performance (Yusuf, Samuel & Ekundayo 2016). The literature review indicated that the main factors of the SED reporting practice among the Nigerian oil and gas firms focus on community welfare disclosure (Oti & Geraldine 2018; Sani 2018). For instance, according to Oti and Geraldine (2018), Nigerian oil firms have invested in innovative waste management practices to limit the adverse effects of oil spills on the community's social welfare and health. Adopting environmental conservation initiatives, including waste management, has also been noted to positively affect the company's financial performance and economic development (Oti & Geraldine 2018).

This study aims to find out the levels of SED in Nigerian oil companies. To achieve the stated objective, content analysis and deep analysis of debates regarding SED previous studies have

been used to select companies such as Shell. The preference of the companies used has been motivated by the existing nature of operational activities by the companies and their impact on the environment. The companies were selected based on the nature of environmental pollution, disposal of wastages, and types of raw material used. For instance, the study by Ironkwe and Promise (2016) found that unrestrained oil explorations tend to adversely affect the financial and social structures of the host communities. Furthermore, these companies had easy access to their mandatory disclosure reports as specified by Nigeria's stock listing authorities. In this respect, Sani (2018) argues that Nigeria's stock listing authorities need to review the authenticity of the issued SED reports to ensure that the oil companies accurately report their social and environmental performance.

2.5.8 Differences in SED between Domestic and International Oil Industries in Nigeria

The international oil industries have better social and environmental disclosure (SED) reporting performance than their local counterparts. Specifically, the global oil companies compare favourably to their local partners regarding their community, social, environmental, and employee disclosures (Ekundayo et al., 2016). According to Sani et al. (2018), Nigerian foreign oil companies tend to have relatively better financial resource capacity and robust corporate governance frameworks, allowing them to issue the annual SED reports consistently. There is evidence that, compared to their local counterparts, the international oil firms have been known to invest in multi-billion community development projects in the host communities where they operate (Ekundayo et al., 2016; Sani et al., 2018). The differences between the local and international oil firms in their SED reporting is accounted for by the

fact that the foreign oil firms tend to have strong organizational and benevolent culture (Ekundayo et al., 2016).

2.6 Evidence of Social Environmental Disclosure

2.6.1 Introduction

Various researchers and their studies on organizational growth and development have addressed SED extensively. Nigeria's positive social transformation was researched by Ayers (2015), who focused on policy formulation, execution, and societal growth. By suggesting improved local content policy design and execution techniques to enhance indigenous involvement and wealth redistribution in Nigerian society, the study's findings have the potential to lead to beneficial social change. According to the study's findings, the legislation significantly influenced the respondents' internal competence component, which included problem-solving abilities, decision-making skills, flexibility, honesty, adaptability, and collaboration with contractors/stakeholders.

In the future, the Nigerian government's policymakers should concentrate on improving the policy's design and execution techniques to increase the internal competency of employees and other players in the petroleum sector, particularly in contractor collaboration, which is critical to the act's success. Creating an environment that encourages local engagement in the oil sector requires cooperation between management and employees of petroleum-producing businesses and local firms wishing to do business with petroleum-producing companies.

Another study by Agwu and Emeti (2014) looked at SED results in Nigeria's petroleum industry. However, even though oil firms have spent a lot of money on local content development, there has been little study on the consequences of the businesses' performance

on the local economy. Petroleum businesses faced a particular management challenge: determining the act's impact on workers' task performances and perceptions of the company's business success. For this quantitative correlational study, the five prominent Nigerian oil firms were asked to evaluate the link between workers' reported level of execution of the act and their perception of task performance and company performance.

2.6.2 Examining Social Environmental Disclosure Quality

The measurement of the quality of SED involves significant controversy and is deemed to be a daunting task. The challenges can be attributed to the prevailing debates regarding the meaning and components of quality that pose a challenge in determining a clear, concise, and acceptable quality of disclosure measurement (Aburaya, 2012, p.11). Therefore, measuring quality relies on the subjective understanding of quality based on the quality of information or traits, for instance, comparability, comprehension, relevance, and reliability. Efforts have been established to differentiate the multiple forms of disclosures to make the unique attributes of disclosed information. Like CSR, two forms of SED are mandatory and voluntary, but SED may originate from a third party, which may be deemed involuntary SED. On the other hand, involuntary SED involves disclosing a company's information without its consent, while voluntary means disclosing the information after the company's consent. The disclosure is often due to external pressure, as discussed in the motivation sections, from stakeholders with a vested interest in the organizational performance or by law.

There are multiple methods for examining the quality of SED developed over time. For instance, the environmental disclosure quality index (EDQI) based on the GRI framework was developed by Clarkson, Li, Richardson, and Vasvari in 2008. The index contains specific reporting principles, including transparency, materiality, relevance, and reliability. It follows

GRI standards and has categories that focus on soft rather than complex disclosures. Also, Siddique et al. (2011) developed a quality determination approach for SED based on the report's relevance and the content included in the report. For them, a SED is deemed relevant when it contains information regarding the impact of a firm's activities on the environment and outcomes of the community's perceptions of its financial and operational activities. The measurement is based on the guidelines of GRI G3. The disclosures should include the strategy, including the challenges and impact and target setting and impact and performance regarding pollution, emission and waste, product and service, transport, and compliance to regulations. Therefore, environmental information is crucial because it addresses the firm's impact.

Besides, a method that employs the International Environmental Performance Evaluation (IEPE) criteria was developed by Liu et al. (2011). In the model, evaluation is through an index with the total score being 100. All indexes are weighted equally; the initial part is 75 in 25. Each index has a maximum score of 3 and is valued as 0,1,2, or 3, where 0 indicates the absence of SED information, 1 is an indicator of minimal description, and 3 shows a detailed description. The second part has a score of 25, and the disclosure forms comprise SED reports and information on the environment. If a company discloses its environmental report, it may earn 10 points; when it does not, it gets a 0. Inherent in the paragraph description regulations, the presence of an independent description is awarded a score of 3, with the best explanation in each paragraph earning 15 points. Further, Glaum et al. (2013) determined the SED quality based on AR data.

Their method comprises a checklist with over 300 criteria used to establish whether reporting has been done and the quality of the report. The factors shown in the interviews and surveys are used to weigh individual items, and as a supplement to AR data, the SED should have

future-oriented information (Glaum et al., 2013, p. 85). The quantity of information determines the SED quality, the availability of general verbal and comparative data, precise point estimates, and quantitative value ranges. The ranking is founded on subjective judgments and weighting; however, according to (Glaum et al. (2013), the method has two key advantages. These advantages include the direct measurement of quality and consistency in scientists' independent data collection over time.

Furthermore, Magness & Bewley (2011) employed the tool developed by Clarkson et al. (2008) - the disclosure-rating device. The total is based on GRI and has 45 rating items within the tool's seven categories. Each category has four sections with hard disclosure items and comprises governance, credibility, environmental, and expenditure items (Magness & Bewley, 2011, p. 555). The rationale is that SED information signals quality as they cannot be copied with considerable costs. The tools' final sections comprise the environmental vision, profile, and initiatives and are categorized as soft information due to the massive scope of claims that have not been substantiated (Magness & Bewley, 2011, p. 555).

Moreover, Eugster & Wagner (2011) employed a direct measure of the voluntary disclosure quality of a company that uses a scorecard with over 100 questions continued within 35 items that have been grouped into nine (9) categories that are vital to investor decision making (Eugster & Wagner, 2011, p. 10). Ranking involves summing up the scores of items in the checklist that are ranked between 1 (no information) and 6 (high-quality information) based on content and quality (Eugster & Wagner, 2011, p. 15).

The ratio between attained and attainable points was used to establish voluntary disclosure quality. Finally, Delmas & Blass (2010) used seven indicators to show SED content quality from AR and websites. These indicators include whether the company publishes SED, whether the SED is based on GRI guidelines, whether the SED is signed by the Chief

Executive Officer (CEO), the degree of transparency and ease of acquisition of information, the presence of specific and clear goals and improvement targets, verification of quantitative data by a third party, and the actuality of performance numbers (Delmas & Blass, 2010, p. 258). These elements are hence the indicators of the quality of the SED. The Pacific Social Index has also been used, whose score is dependent on the scope and quality of coverage.

Figure 2.8 Methods of SED

Source: *Employed from Deloitte Touche Tohmatsu International (1993)*

The two basic types of SEDs are mandatory and voluntary (Deloitte Touches Tohmatsu International, 1993). Voluntary SED is the voluntary sharing of information, whereas involuntary SED is the revelation of a firm's operations without its permission and against its will; nevertheless, SED from a third party might be considered involuntary. The disclosure of information mandated by law is known as mandatory SED. On the other hand, Clarkson et al. (2008) developed a GRI-based environmental disclosure quality index. The guidelines are founded on essential reporting criteria for analysts and stakeholders, including transparency,

materiality, pertinence, and dependability. The GRI standards are followed in the content and structure of the quality index, which includes topics such as corporate concepts and environmental policy, governance structure, and organisational processes. The categories represent hard and soft disclosures, with complex disclosures having a more significant weighting than quiet disclosures.

Siddique et al. (2011) define disclosure quality as relevance or reportability. Relevant SED includes (1) data on the impact of organisational actions on the anticipated environment; and (2) the importance of community knowledge of the impact on the organisation's financial and practical activities. This definition, the Global Climate Disclosure Framework, and the Climate Disclosure Standard Board Framework are guided by the GRI G3 guidelines. The following is a list of notable SEDs: (1) Procedure disclosure (recognising problems and business impact; creating performance goals); and (2) Effect and Performance Disclosure (material, water, and energy utilise; pollution: emanation and waste; product and service; transport; environmental regulation compliance). According to the list, environmental data is significant when it provides information about the organisation's impact on the natural environment, such as asset utilisation, pollution, and the organisation's method for recognising threats and opportunities.

2.6.3 SED Practices in Developed Countries Studies

According to Zhang et al. (2015), petroleum-producing organisations should create a long-lasting relationship with the host countries to enhance investment security even in the long term. The effectiveness of local content development guidelines and policies is dependent on the environment (Zhang et al., 2015). Elements like the degree of infrastructure development and the provision of quality education that results in skilled labour are critical to local content

development. Further, these factors create an immense impact on the economic growth and development of a country. It is also essential to maintain political stability and the effectiveness of legal policies and regulations to maintain the benefits of local content development projects. In most developed countries, high-quality education, availability of skilled labour, and promising infrastructural developments have helped them reach high economic and social development levels. Studies conducted within developed nations were reviewed to analyse the existing literature.

Further, SED's nature varies over time and between different countries, where factors deemed essential in one nation, or a time may be less important in another country or another. However, with economic growth and increased globalisation, SED practices are likely to converge. Further, according to Tan et al. (2021, pg. 429), developed countries in the past continued to champion SED goals by implementing economic policies that promote economic efficiency while stimulating technological innovations and advancements in their activities. By following the developed nations as the lead, the developing countries are increasingly focusing their energy and resources on developing projects in manufacturing and tourism to promote SED.

Figure 2.9 The Published SED Research Country of Origin

Table 2.1: Summary of Studies Conducted in Developed Nations

Table 2.1: Summary of Studies Conducted in Developed Nations

STUDY	AIMS	COUNTRY	FINDINGS
Marna De Klerk, Charl de Villiers, Chris van Staden	The influence of corporate social responsibility disclosure on share prices: Evidence from the United Kingdom, 2015	UK	Companies close to the market, or are brand-names, are likely to adopt SED
Tong, N	Corporate governance and corporate social responsibility disclosure: Evidence from China 2015	China	SED quantity is low. There is an association between SED and most governance mechanisms.
Chau GK, Gray SJ	Ownership structure and corporate voluntary disclosure in Hong Kong and Singapore. 2002	Hong Kong & Singapore	Companies increased only negative and negative disclosures when prosecuted
Garcia-Ayuso & Larrinaga (2008)	Analyse SED practices.	Spain	SED increase due to rise in social concerns for environmental issues.
Aburaya (2012)	Examines the relationship between corporate governance and SED quantity and quality.	UK	SED quantity is low, but quality is comparatively high. An association exists between SED and most governance mechanisms.
Haddock-Fraser & Fraser (2008)	Examine whether market proximity affects SED extent and form.	UK	Companies close to the market, or are brand-names, are highly likely to adopt SED.
Chen S, Bouvain P	Is corporate responsibility converging? A comparison of corporate responsibility reporting in the USA, UK, Australia, and Germany 2009	USA, UK, Australia, and Germany	SED practices improved
H. Cho, C., Michelon, G., M. Patten, D. and W. Roberts, R.	CSR report assurance in the USA: an empirical investigation of determinants and effects, 2014	USA	It was established that ownership, risk, and firm size determine the levels of SED
Thorne, L., Mahoney, L. S., Gregory, K., & Convery, S.	A comparison of Canadian and U.S. CSR strategic alliances, CSR reporting, and CSR performance: Insights into implicit–explicit CSR. 2014	Canada	In both countries, SED is focused on employees and the environment

Moussa, T., Kotb, A., & Helfaya, A.	An empirical investigation of U.K. Environmental targets disclosure: The role of environmental governance and performance. 2019	United Kingdom	SED practices are affected by shareholder structure and the relationship with the stakeholders
Cecil (2010)	Explore SED practices.	USA	There is a growing trend in issuing SED. There are very few SEDs audited or assured.
Holder-Webb et al (2009)	Evaluate SED.	USA	SED disclosed by most companies.
De Barros & Monteiro (2012)	Analyse SED level.	Portugal	Most (77%) do not provide SED.
Branco & Rodrigues (2008)	Examine SED.	Portugal	The perspective adopted explains SED by banks.
Monteiro & Aibar-Guzmán (2010)	Examine SED practices.	Portugal	Even though SED level is low, the extent has increased.
Gallego-Alvarez (2008)	Verify presentation of SED.	Portugal	Companies make known their ethical behaviours and seek to improve the quality of life of their workers, as well as their social conditions.
Llena et al (2007)	Explore and explain SED content.	Spain	Significant SED increase. The amount of narrative data exceeded that of quantitative data.
Sweeney & Coughlan (2008)	Examine how to orient SED towards different stakeholders.	UK	Difference exists on how organisations report SED.
Brammer & Pavelin (2008)	Examine patterns in SED quality.	UK	High quality SED disclose associated with larger firms.
Khan & Charaf (2010)	Explore SED patterns.	France	SED focus on employees and environment.
Damak-Ayadi (2010)	Analyses changes in SED practices.	France	Most SED were qualitative reflecting human resources and community involvement.
Bouten et al (2021)	Examine SED determinants.	Belgium & USA	Different determinants influence SED and the disclosure level.

Evaraert et al (2007)	Examine SED practices.	Belgium	SED extent is different between industries. Utilities and banks are providing more elaborate SED than other categories.
Orens et al (2005)	Extent to which managers have changed their behaviour towards SED over time.	Belgium	Improvement in SED practices.
Gamerschlag et al (2011)	Extend SED motivations.	Germany	SED issues are affected by their visibility, shareholder structure, and relationship with their stakeholders.
Quick (2008)	Evaluates SED quality.	Germany	A weak positive correlation found between the financial strength and SED quality.
Cormier et al (2005)	Identify SED determinants.	Germany	Risk, ownership, and firm size determine SED level.
Giannarakis et al (2011)	Illustrate what SED provide to readers.	Greece	SED are almost similar in all dimensions.
Papaspyropoulos et al (2010)	Examine differences among company sectors in terms of SED.	Greece	Few companies reported SED.
Kotonen (2009)	Analyses SED.	Finland	Companies understand SED as a response to stakeholders' expectations and demands.
Belal & Lubinin (2009)	Examine SED extent.	Russia	90% of companies provided SED with employee related disclosures being the dominant category.
Uyar & Kiliç (2012)	Examine SED practices.	Turkey	SED is value relevant.
Ahulu et al (2010)	Investigate SED changes.	Australia	Significant increases in SED.
Guthrie (2007)	Develop an industry-specific SED framework.	Australia	Companies reported more on industry-specific issues than CSR issues.
Gadenne & Ladewig (2007)	Examine SED practices.	Australia	Companies increased only negative and neutral disclosures if prosecuted.
Mitchell et al (2006)	Examine SED practices.	Australia	Violating companies' AR are limited to amounts of positive SED.
Deloitte & Van Staden (2011)	Investigate SED motivations.	New Zealand	New Zealand companies are recent reporters of SED with under-developed and under-utilised systems.

Table 2.1 above summarises the multiple studies conducted in developed nations. The studies were done across the globe. Each of the studies was based on a specific parameter to determine the SED levels under factors such as corporate governance, assurance, share prices in the market, and voluntary disclosure while using the content analysis approach. The findings from studies done in the USA, UK, Australia, and Germany revealed a growth in SED. At the same time, in the UK, a study indicated that the shareholder structure and another one reported SED affected SED practices to be primarily employee-related, including one having different SED determinants. SED study in such countries has a broad scope and is subject to government regulation. Therefore, they are extensive as the nations are in higher social and economic status hence under immense pressure from stakeholders to report.

Research previously carried out in most developed countries indicates that SED determinants have continued to increase based on various circumstances that include pressure from activists, risk, legislation, ethical investors, awards, economic activities, social media interest, politics, and specific events. According to Garcia et al. (2020, pg. 445-448), SED determinants can be investigated along the line of voluntary corporate disclosure based on how firms and organisations satisfy the implicit claims of non-stakeholders and shareholders' great interest in the organisation's performance. The researcher argues that voluntary disclosure theory encompasses the reduction of information asymmetry at its core and interlinks the efficiency of information disclosure, the incentives involved, and the impact caused. The research categorised the theory into three taxonomic descriptions that explain numerous studies. The categories include discretionary-based disclosure, efficiency-based disclosure, and association-based disclosure. Furthermore, the theory explains that two lines of argument can be used to demonstrate the strengths of social-environmental disclosure determinants using agency theory, legitimacy theory and stakeholder theory.

The legitimacy theory states that companies seek legitimacy by appearing to be socially responsible while using voluntary corporate transparency to achieve this objective. The theory, therefore, is usually based on a general assumption that an entity's actions are desirable, appropriate, and desirable when integrated within social norms, beliefs, values, and definitions. Companies and firms adopt different strategies to achieve social disclosure to maintain a social contract for ensuring their survival and legitimising their future existence. Strategies such as constructing communication links between organisations and the social surroundings are used to help gain, maintain and recover legitimacy. The links are created to enhance the dissemination of crucial information to stakeholders in pursuit of their good intentions. From managers' point of view, disclosure is a public-relation tool that helps influence the way outsiders and stakeholders think or view an organisation.

The agency theory explains the emerging trends and motivations for the various levels of voluntary disclosure of information. Under this theory, companies previously managed by owners are forced to manage their relationships between the principal owners, stakeholders, and the administrators referred to as the agents. The management must avoid conflict of interest and agency problems, and the agent acts as the principal owner in a way that avoids any conflict of interest. When the owners and agents are not aligned, then informational asymmetry conflict can arise. The agency theory assumes that managers must make social information available only when the benefits of disclosure surpass the associated costs leading to an increase in their well-being.

Finally, the stakeholder theory explains social responsibility disclosure by measuring stakeholders' power, economic performance, and strategic posture. The three factors are related to social-environmental disclosure determinant levels. The theory elaborates the importance of stakeholder engagement and management, which goes beyond their significant role in profit maximisation. Under stakeholder theory, an organisation's leadership is tasked with recognising and minimising the legitimacy gap while implementing the social practices necessary to achieve full environmental disclosure. Management must disclose their actions and decisions to the stakeholders to enhance accountability. Information so disclosed may be viewed as a legitimate social contribution by an organisation. Therefore, under this theory, stakeholders view SED as a criterion for measuring the legitimacy and credibility of their organisation.

2.6.4 SED Practices on Developing Countries Studies

According to Tan et al. (2021, pg.432-433), most developing countries' economies are facing environmental difficulties arising from climatic effects and human beings' life concerns. Therefore, governments are forced to produce strategies to reduce industrial adverse

environmental impact and create job opportunities for local communities to improve people's economic status. Tan et al. (2021, pg. 429) argue that in the current era, developing countries primarily focus on economic developments to achieve the country's financial strength and security by creating jobs and employing the local community. For example, Shell's management stated that their workforce comprised 90% of Nigerians to cater to local communities by providing employment. Shell's executives used local contractors and service providers as a commercial tactic to achieve a competitive edge. In manufacturing operations, projects, and well engineering, the company's management encouraged the employment of locally made items and Nigerian service firms.

With technical and financial assistance, Shell's management supported indigenous asset ownership of marine vessels, rigs, and transport boats. Local equipment and pipe manufacturing firms were also assisted in building up facilities and obtaining globally recognised accreditation for the local fabrication of equipment and line pipes for use in the Nigerian petroleum sector. Research in most developing countries such as Tunisia, Nigeria, Egypt, and Libya, indicates that education and training, environmental management, and risk management are essential practices companies concentrate on.

According to Eljayash (2015), most countries, through their biggest companies, have paid a lot of attention to education and training, as illustrated by the table below. The table demonstrates the disclosure for several items and shows that many companies extensively focused on education and training. Environmental management and risk management followed the list accordingly. On the other hand, water effluent, litigation about environmental issues, awards, and environmental costing did not disclose in the annual reports covered in the study.

Table 2.2 Items of SED in annual reports

Items	2012	2013	2014	% Of	% Of	% Of
	2012	2013	2014	2012	2013	2014
Education and training	825	969	1212	14.24	14.58	13.73
Environmental management	768	813	901	13.26	12.24	10.21
Risk management	663	727	830	11.45	10.94	9.4
Environmental accidents	501	514	844	8.65	7.74	9.56
Wastes	486	558	754	8.39	8.4	8.54
Environmental policies	482	622	805	8.32	9.36	9.12
Litigation on environmental issues	412	476	599	7.11	7.16	6.79
Land rehabilitation and remediation	340	416	494	5.87	6.26	5.6
Sustainable development reporting	337	420	491	5.82	6.32	5.56
Air emission	295	369	480	5.09	5.55	5.44
Spill	245	273	847	4.23	4.11	9.6
Environmental auditing	180	206	208	3.11	3.1	2.36
Water effluent	157	173	216	2.71	2.6	2.45
Environmental spending and activities	101	108	145	1.74	1.63	1.64
Awards	0	0	0	0	0	0
Environmental cost accounting	0	0	0	0	0	0
Totals	5792	6644	8826			

According to Eljayash (2015), disclosure increased in national oil industries that provided environmental information when issuing their annual reports over the period studied. At first, the quantity of disclosure was below 101 words but rose over the years to over 1212 words

which meant an increase in disclosure levels. Education and training were disclosed at the highest levels over the three years. The level of interest in disclosing company information continues to grow in developing countries, as illustrated in the table above. A lot of focus is on the education and training sector.

Developing countries have adopted and invested in education and professional training to create a pool of skilled human resources. Ngoasong (2014) investigated Eni's management, which implemented a Vendor Management System (VMS) to provide support and training to local companies to achieve international certification in standards and performance levels, as well as improve their ability to execute new supply contracts. Vidat (2015) argued that establishing a collaborative strategy between the government and the petroleum-producing corporations will enhance the possibilities of local content projects' success. Based on a comprehensive assessment of present local capability and the potential of the host nation, the government and oil-producing corporations should work together to guarantee realistic local content development objectives are met within a specific timetable. According to the collaborative approach, the petroleum-producing companies will be better able to assess their capacities and needs.

Moreover, they can establish better links between oil companies and local firms to meet their needs by utilising local sources. Companies in developing nations have become more responsive to their social and environmental impact, and there is also increased public pressure for firms to become responsible. However, SED practices are still archaic in developing nations. According to Abdulkabir et al. (2015), the Nigerian government began creating a framework for a local content policy to be implemented in the Brazilian petroleum sector as part of an innovation system. The Nigerian government utilised the Norwegian local content policy to compare the Nigerian and Norwegian local content policies. The practical implementation of the local content development project relied on several players. The

national oil corporation, its subsidiaries, the legal sector, regulatory agencies, and the government are among the stakeholders. Local content development in Nigeria was ineffective because local companies were separated from the technological capabilities of the national oil corporation. The subcontracting method caused the separation, which prohibited any direct connection between local firms vying for contracts and the national oil corporation. As a result, the Nigerian local content development innovation system was hindered by the lack of a link between the primary stakeholder, the national oil corporation, suppliers, universities, and research institutions.

Table 2.3: Summary of Studies Conducted in Developing Nations

Table 2.3: Summary of Studies Conducted in Developing Nations

Study	Aims	Country	Findings
Setyorini & Ishak (2012)	Examine SED.	Indonesia	SED extent increased.
Sorour et al 2021	To explore the evolving motives underlying corporate social responsibility(CSR) disclosures in developing countries: the case of “political CSR” reporting	Egypt	Politics affect CSR activities through regulations and the legitimacy framework
Mahameed et al 2021	To determine social accounting in the context of profound political, social, and economic crisis: the case of Arab Spring	Egypt, Tunisia, Jordan, Morocco	The political, social and economic contexts are related to social accounting
Albu et al 2021	To examine the role of imprints in shaping social and environmental reporting in a post-communist context	Romania	Communism and the western ideologies impact the process of environmental reporting and disclosure
Mehjabeen et al 2021	To determine the effects of SED and CSR activities on political arena in developing countries	Bangladesh	Corporate activities have emerged in guise of SED and CSR
Gunawan (2010)	Investigates SED as perceived by the stakeholders.	Indonesia	There are gaps between SED perceived by stakeholders and those disclosed by the companies.
Siregar & Bachtiar (2010)	Investigate the effect of board size, foreign ownership, firm size and profitability on SED.	Indonesia	Board and firm size have a positive relationship with SED.
Suttipun & Stanton (2012)	Investigate SED practices.	Thailand	Companies providing the most SED were in the resources business while the smallest were in services industry.
Mahmood and Uddin 2021	To determine the effects of SED on institutional planning such as markets in sustainability reporting	Pakistan	SED themes have shifted from human resource to marketplace which has also been backed up by communities and businesses.

Adler et al 2021	To perform an analysis of the houbara bustard bird threatened extinction and the government’s accountability failure	Pakistan	There exists a dysfunctional political and judicial system that is not environmentally accountable
Sidhu and Gibbon, 2021	To investigate the institutionalization of sustainability in the United Nations Clean Development Mechanism by determining the empirical evidence from Malaysian organisations	Malaysia	Institutional regulations regarding SED and CSR are not properly affected and adhered to
Thoradeniya et al 2021	To determine the diffusion of sustainability key performance indicators in a developing country context	Sri Lanka	Investing in environmental education and training is the main focus to improve SED levels
Samkin and Wingard 2021	To understand the systematic change in the context of social and environmental disclosures of a conservation organization in a developing country	South Africa	Information on society about social and environmental disclosures is mostly addressed extensively regarding the extent of SED
Ratanajongkol et al (2006)	Examine SED extent and nature of practices.	Thailand	A trend of increasing SED on human resources.
Kuo et al (2012)	Evaluate SED quality.	China	Environmentally sensitive industries (ESIs) and state-owned enterprises (SOEs) are significantly more committed to SED.
Yao et al (2011)	Identify SED determinants.	China	Negative relationship between SED and firm age.
Azim et al (2011)	Identify SED practices.	Bangladesh	Companies in the banking sector secure the highest rank in terms of SED; more than one half of the disclosures are in the director’s report and the mean number of disclosures is less than half a page.
Kamal & Deegan (2013)	Investigate SED practices.	Bangladesh	The textile and garments companies disclose their governance policies and procedures to secure/maintain legitimacy and/or to meet community expectation.
Khan (2010)	Investigate SED level.	Bangladesh	Demonstrates that though voluntary, overall, SED are moderate, however, the varieties of CSR items are impressive.

Khan et al (2011)	Examine SED tendencies.	Bangladesh	Information on society is addressed most extensively regarding the extent of SED.
Yeshmin (2012)	Explore SED.	Bangladesh	Most of the SED is qualitative in nature.
Murthy (2008)	Examines SED practices.	India	Companies use dual strategies in reporting their human resource and social relations to legitimise their activities to stakeholders.
Amiolemen et.al 2018	To determine the levels of corporate social environmental reporting and stock prices by analyzing listed firms in Nigeria	Nigeria	Companies financial performance has direct relationship with SED.
Emmanuel et.al, 2018	To determine the levels of corporate diversity and social environmental disclosure of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria	Nigeria	The levels of SED have increased in the manufacturing sector.
Buniamin (2010)	Determines SED quantity and quality	Malaysia	Only 28% of the companies reported SED.
Esa & Ghazali (2012)	Investigate SED changes.	Malaysia	The paired-sample t-tests showed that there was an increase in SED extent.
Homayoun et al (2012)	Examine SED level.	Malaysia	Many companies are ignoring new requirements to enhance SED on their websites.
Mohammed et al (2010)	Investigate how Shari'ah compliant listed companies present SED.	Malaysia	SED on corporate governance index themes, followed by social/environmental index themes.
Rahman et al (2010)	Examine SED locations, extent, and trends.	Malaysia	Volume of SED improved.
Rahman et al (2011)	Assess SED level.	Malaysia	SED theme has shifted from human resource to marketplace. This is followed by community and finally, environment. Ironically, companies are not only disclosing good news, but also negative news.
Al Naimi et al (2012)	Explore the current status and extent of SED.	Qatar	Most companies disclosed information related to human resources and product development, followed by community development.
Zubairu et al (2011)	Examine SED practices.	Saudi Arabia	Islamic banks have much more in common with their conventional counterparts than they do with banks that are based on Shari'ah.

Ismail & Ibrahim (2008)	Investigate SED extent.	Jordan	85% of the companies report SED. Human resource is the most disclosed theme while the environmental issue had the lowest disclosure.
Menassa (2010)	Identifies SED quality and extent.	Lebanon	The banks attribute greater importance to human resource, product and customers' disclosures, whereas the extent and availability of SED is still weak.
Alawi & Rahman (2011)	Examine SED level.	Yemen	While SED level is low, companies have increased the disclosure in response to CSR award announcement.
Kabir & Akinmusi (2012)	Determine SED practices.	Swaziland	CSR is fairly new and very few companies provide SED.
Ponnu & Okoth (2009)	Investigate SED practices.	Kenya	SED received only modest attention and the theme most disclosed was community involvement.
Mahadeo et al (2011)	Examine SED.	Mauritius	Increase in SED volume and variety, although information in relation to social activities remains the most prominent form of disclosure.
Aldrugi & Abdo (2012)	Investigate relationship between SED level and company characteristics.	Libya	Identified several characteristics that are associated with SED, namely, company size, privatisation, age and nationality.
Ahmad & Mousa (2010)	Examine SED extent and practice.	Libya	SED quantity and quality has developed over the study period.
Bayoud et al (2012)	Explore whether company age, size and industry type influence SED levels.	Libya	Positive relationship between all factors influencing SED level.
Elmogla (2009)	Investigates SED.	Libya	Companies disclose some information related to social responsibility.
Pratten & Mashat (2009)	Examine SED.	Libya	Emphasis on SED is different from those found in the West.
Dawkins & Ngunjiri (2008)	Compare SED.	South Africa	SED frequency and level in South African companies was higher than that of the Fortune Global 100, which indicates willingness to convey social responsibility in their disclosure practices.

De Villiers & Alexander (2010)	Compare SED in South Africa and Australian mining companies.	South Africa	No significant differences between the two countries.
Uwalomwa & Jimoh (2012)	Examine SED level and practices.	Nigeria	Most companies disclose SED related to products, consumers, employees and community involvement.
Uwalomwa & Egbide (2012)	Investigate the relationship between companies' financial performance and SED level.	Nigeria	Companies' financial performance and size of audit firm have a positive relationship with SED level.
Uwalomwa (2011a)	Investigate the association between company characteristics and SED level.	Nigeria	Positive association between company's characteristics and SED level.
Uwalomwa (2011b)	Investigates relationship between management ownership and SED level.	Nigeria	Managerial ownership structure has a positive impact on SED level.
Assaolu et al (2011)	Assess SED level.	Nigeria	Arbitrary and incompatible SED indicators.

The summary of these findings is presented in Table 2.3 above, with fifty (50) of these being reviewed according to the aims, methods, country, and findings. Thirty were focused on Asian nations, while Nineteen (19) were based on African governments and one from Eastern Europe. Further, forty-one (41) studies considered SED practices, and seven (7) whether attributes such as politics, logistics, and economic crisis affected SED practices. Some studies illustrate those institutions such as educational and judicial systems like regulations affect the social-environmental disclosure practices in developing countries, and two studies made comparisons of SED practices in developing and developed nations. However, all of them employed a content analysis approach. This study has mixed results, and despite using companies as their case study, the sample size, the number of companies used, the size of the companies, and the type of theories used differed.

2.7 LITERATURE REVIEW 2- (2) SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW

2.7.1 Introduction

A systematic literature review is a distinct research methodology that identifies, selects, and critically appraises prior literature findings and insights to attain a concrete solution to specific research questions (Snyder 2019). The systematic literature review provides a structured approach to a comprehensive and transparent search of the previous literature related to the research study of interest. The systematic literature review entails using a structured examination of relevant articles from critical databases and grey literature, which other researchers can replicate (Xiao & Watson 2017). Researchers can develop testable hypotheses related to the research question based on the analysis, summary, and synthesis of prior literature (Xiao & Watson 2017). In social and scientific research, the outcome of the systematic literature is expected to be dependable, valid, and repeatable by other researchers using the same methodology.

An excellent systematic literature review entails applying a structured literature search and synthesis process. The systematic literature review requires considering four (4) essential aspects before producing the final articles for review. The first aspect involves the initial search of the literature articles using keywords and phrases (Snyder 2019). For instance, in this thesis, the researcher considered keywords/phrases such as 'social and environmental disclosures' and 'community welfare' during the initial search of the articles. The second criteria usually applied in systematic literature review involves restricting the study period for articles published within a specified period. For instance, in this Study, articles published between 2008 and 2020 were considered in the systematic literature review search. The country of publication is also an essential aspect of the systematic literature review. The government of publication search criteria limited the articles to those published in Nigeria and, to a certain extent, the U.K. and the U.S.

Finally, as part of an excellent systematic literature review articles search and selection process, the specification of only reputable journal articles and databases is an important consideration. The implication is that the journal articles' search and retrieval focused on reputable databases to enhance the systematic literature review process (Xiao & Watson 2017). There are several benefits of using a systematic literature review approach to analyse and synthesise findings from prior studies. Firstly, the systematic literature review approach reduces bias and subjectivity because relevant journal articles are selected using structured rules and protocols (Snyder 2019). Besides, the systematic literature approach is considered most appropriate in selecting and synthesising relevant journal articles consistent with the research topic.

Furthermore, the replicability of the systematic literature review tends to enhance the transparency of the stated research design approach (Xiao & Watson 2017). However, the systematic literature review is considered time-consuming despite its objectivity and replicability strength. That grey literature, including government/industry publications, is usually omitted, creating a bias (Snyder 2019).

2.7.2 Description of the SLR Protocols

The systematic literature review is guided by specific protocols that include rationales, hypotheses, and planned methods/procedures for identifying and selecting relevant research articles (Briggs 2007). The first systematic review protocol included a statement of rationale, which justified why the researcher conducted the systematic review. In this Study, the reliability, objectivity, transparency, and replicability of the systematic review are the primary rationale for applying the approach to facilitate the identification and selection of research articles.

The other essential protocols the researcher devised before using the systematic literature review approach consisted of the inclusion and exclusion criteria for research articles. Specifically, the inclusion/exclusion criteria guided using (i) Keywords/phrases, (ii) Databases, (iii) Country context, (iv) Publication date, and (v) Boolean logic. The list of keywords/phrases captured the following words or statements; "Social and Environmental Disclosure", "SED Reporting Practices in Nigeria", "SED Reporting in Nigerian Oil Sector", "Community welfare", "Corporate Social Responsibility", "SED Reporting". On the other hand, the systematic review protocol also specified a specific research profile from where the articles were supposed to be searched.

The implication is that the researcher selected the journal articles from only highly reputable databases, including the Africa-Wide, African Journal Online, African Research Online, and ResearchGate. The third systematic review inclusion criteria captured the country context, meaning that Nigeria's consideration guided the identification, selection, and retrieval of the articles in the study context. Therefore, as part of the review protocols, the researcher was required to focus on articles published in Nigeria or those that examine Nigeria as a study context. The country context inclusion/exclusion criterion was justified because the research focuses on reviewing the SED reporting practices in Nigeria, especially the Niger Delta region.

The publication date inclusion criterion was explicitly included as part of the review protocol to ensure that only recent articles were selected for synthesis. The publication date criterion stated that only SED-reported research articles published between 2009 and 2020 were included in the literature review. Finally, the Boolean logic, which included "AND", "OR", "FOR", "IN", and "OF", was also specified as part of the review protocol to aid in the retrieval of the relevant journal articles.

2.7.3 Justification (Motive) for the SLR

The researcher conducted the systematic literature review for several reasons related to its distinct attributes. First, the researcher conducted a systematic literature review to obtain quality and reliable articles for inclusion in the research's theoretical and empirical literature review section. According to Snyder (2019), the systematic literature review is considered the most ideal and structured approach for retrieving quality and reliable journal articles relevant to the research topic. The retrieved research articles' quality, reliability, and relevance are evidenced by the researcher selecting the reports from reputable databases (Africa-Wide, African Journal Online, ResearchGate, and Africa Research Online). Besides, the significance of the selected journal articles is guaranteed by considering recent articles (publication date of 2009-2020) that focused on the research topic of interest and were published in Nigeria or incorporated Nigeria as the study setting.

The second necessary justification for using a systematic literature review is because the approach provides an objective and unbiased selection of articles. Xiao & Watson (2017) contend that the systematic literature is dependable because of the structured and standard process of selecting a final list of articles for inclusion. The application of the systematic literature review implies that each of the initial articles that meet the inclusion criteria has an equal chance of being retrieved and included in the final list. Therefore, based on the systematic literature review, there is a greater possibility that the final list would consist of articles that represent the general insight from the population of all journal articles, which focus on the research topic of interest.

The final reason for using the systematic literature review in this Study is its replicability. According to Snyder (2019), one of the advantages of the systematic literature review is its ease of replication. The implication is that when applied consistently using all the search and

inclusion/exclusion protocols, two researchers can produce a similar set of studies for further synthesis (Xiao & Watson 2017). Specifically, the transparency feature of the systematic literature review is considered most important in facilitating replicability of the article identification and retrieval.

2.7.4 SLR Questions

An excellent systematic literature review is usually guided by a comprehensive list of study questions (Snyder 2019). Several review questions showed the entire article identification and selection process in the systematic literature review. The first review question focused on identifying journal articles that have researched the research topic of interest; What are the articles that focus on the social and environmental disclosure (SEDs) reporting practices? This review question formed the first of a series of inquiries that led to selecting the final list of fifty-five (55) articles. The researcher posed the first review question by including keywords and phrases in the Google Scholar search engine. As shown in the PRISMA flow diagram below, the first review question was answered by identifying 10,300 articles that address the issue of SED reporting practices.

The second review question, which guided the systematic literature review, sought to assess the articles focusing on SED reporting practices within the context of Nigeria. This review question stated: What articles focus on SED reporting practices in Nigeria? The stated review question meant restricting or limiting the retrieved articles to only those focusing on Nigeria as a research study context. The second review question was answered by identifying 1,650 articles published in Nigeria or including Nigeria as a study context.

The third question also sought to assess all the articles that focused on the SED reporting practices within the Nigerian oil and gas sector. Essentially, the third research question, which restricted the selected articles to those that explore the practice of SED reporting in the

Nigerian oil industry, was specified as follows; What are the journal articles that focus on SED reporting practices in the Nigerian oil industry? The solution to the third review question stated by identifying 837 articles that incorporated content most relevant to the Study. Finally, the other review questions sought to assess and facilitate the identification of articles from reputable journal articles (i.e., What are the most reliable and reputed research databases that include African-based studies on SEDs?) as well as articles that meet the specified publication date (i.e., What are the relevant journal articles that focus on SED and published between 2009 to 2020?).

2.7.5 SLR based on the Study

The PRISMA flow diagram for the systematic literature review applied in this research study is represented in Figure 2.10 below. As described in the PRISMA flow diagram, most of the final 116 articles included in the review were journal articles retrieved from highly reputable databases. The initial search process began with keywords/phrases (i.e., "Social and Environmental Disclosure") over the specified period, 2009-2020. Initially, the Google Scholar search engine generated 10,300 journal articles relevant to the Study.

Figure 2.10 Systematic Literature Review PRISMA Flow Diagram

However, after specifying journal articles published in Nigeria or focusing on the social and environmental disclosure (SED) practices in Nigeria, the researcher reduced the initial 10,300 articles to 1,650 pieces. The PRISMA flow systematic review diagram depicted in Figure 2.10 also indicates that only 837 articles met the inclusion criteria when the search specification was restricted to those journal articles that focus on SEDs practices in the Nigerian oil sector for studies published between 2009-2020. Subsequently, 218 journal articles were subjected to a review of title pages, abstracts, and introduction. However, based on the review of title pages, abstracts, and introduction, forty-five ($n = 45$) articles did not meet the inclusion criteria. They were considered non-relevant in facilitating the attainment of the research study. This means that 173 journal articles attained the inclusion criteria based on the quality of their contents. However, thirty-seven ($n = 37$) of these articles were considered inconclusive findings/outcomes, which affected their reliability. Therefore, as depicted in the PRISMA flow systematic review diagram, the researcher's final list of journal articles included in the systematic literature review was 136. . Due to large volume the journal articles or limited space of thesis words count, the researcher will only discuss 57 articles out of the 136 to maximise volume space to achieve the thesis maximum words count.

The systematic literature review also included several published articles from the European Parliament and the US Department of State. These published articles were considered relevant for the research study, which examined Nigerian oil industries' social and environmental disclosure reporting practices. The search for these articles started with identifying ten articles through references to the included journal articles. However, after screening for abstracts, title page and introduction, only four (4) published papers met the eligibility requirement. Finally, two articles published by the European Parliament and the US Department of State were included as part of the systematic literature review. Therefore,

several studies were subjected to a structured and systematic literature review that included peer-reviewed journal articles focusing on the SEDs reporting practices among Nigerian oil industries.

Table 2.4 Systematic Literature Review Table

Systematic Review Table

S/N	AUTHOR(S)	PUBLICATION YEAR	RESEARCH TITLE	RESEARCH GAP
1.	Odera, Scott, and Gow	2016	An examination of the quality of social and environmental disclosures by Nigerian oil companies	The study broadened SED investigation, explored the inspirations of SED suppliers and established connection between partner requests and exposure level.
2.	Yusuf, Samuel, and Ekundayo	2016	The extent of environmental disclosures in listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria	The researchers upgraded the comprehension of natural divulgence practices of oil and gas organizations in creating nations.
3.	Dibia and Onwuchekwa	2015	Determinants of environmental disclosures in Nigeria: A case study of oil and gas companies.	The scholars analysed the relationship between organization measure and corporate social responsibility confession.
4.	Sani	2018	Mandatory social and environmental disclosure: A performance evaluation of listed nigerian oil and gas companies pre- and post-mandatory disclosure requirements.	The researcher studied the impact of number of corporations on the volume of the acknowledgment and showed that corporate size positively affects the exposure.

5.	Oti and Geraldine	2018	Analysis of environmental and social disclosure and financial performance of selected quoted oil and gas companies in Nigeria (2012-2016).	The researchers studied the effect of natural and social revelation on financial progress and Showed that confession on waste administration had a positive and critical impact on company's economic development.
6.	Odera	2014	An examination of social and environmental disclosures in Nigerian oil companies	The scholar differentiated the Nigerian host networks' (HCs) view of SEDs with and analyzed the position of other oil companies concerning their SEDs.
7.	Sani	2016	Social and environmental disclosures: A comparative analysis of listed Nigerian and UK oil and gas companies	The researcher compared the spending on social and ecological exposures between Nigerian and UK organizations and recorded a low amount and nature of exposure.
8.	Haladu & Salim	2016	Sustainability reporting by firms in the Nigerian economy: Social versus environmental disclosure	The study examined the natural and social classes of environmental disclosure and showed that organizations performed better on social detailing than on ecological disclosure.
9.	Ironkwe & Promise	2016	Environmental reporting in the oil and gas industry in Nigeria.	The researchers studied the environmental impact caused by unrestrained oil and gas exploration drills and argued that financial and social structure of native networks are significantly influenced by such activities.

10.	Yusuf, Joseph, and Ekundayo	2016	The extent of environmental disclosures in listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria	The researchers studied the ecological acknowledgment in Nigerian oil and gas industry and identified the need to improve the technological progress to minimize environmental pollution.
11.	Oscar & Juliet	2015	The effect of corporate governance on the extent of environmental reporting in the Nigerian oil industry.	The study analyzed the impact of corporate administration on environmental reporting and revealed that board strength, structure, and administrative efficiency positively influence the environmental reporting.
12.	Otu, Okon, Okafor, and Nnanna	2018	Oil companies performance and environmental accounting reporting in Nigeria.	The researchers studied the importance of relationship between environmental accounting and oil organizations in Nigeria and identified the need to make ecological divulgence obligatory and enforce the infringement by Nigerian oil organizations.
13.	Odia & Imagbe	2015	Social and economic consequences of corporate social and environmental disclosures in Nigeria	The scholars analyzed the corporate social and ecological exposures in Nigeria and identified the need to expand the social revelations to enhance ecological exhibitions and enhance financial progress.

14.	Pantamee	2014	The effect of corporate governance on corporate social responsibility disclosure in the Nigerian petroleum marketing industry	The study bolstered the significance of hazard administration advisory with respect to corporate social obligation in the Nigerian petroleum marketing industry.
15.	Nwaiwu and Oluka	2018	Environmental cost disclosure and financial performance of oil and gas in Nigeria	The study analyzed the impact of ecological cost revelation and economic progress of Nigerian oil companies and identified the need to build up a well-articulated ecological costing framework to ensure a contention free corporate environment.
16.	Taiwo	2010	The influence of work environment on workers productivity: A case of selected oil and gas industry in Lagos, Nigeria	The study highlighted the issues of the workers in the oil and gas sectors of the Nigerian economy and analysed the effect of workplace on future specialist's efficiency.
17.	Adinehzadeh, Jaffar, Shukor and Rahman	2018	The mediating role of environmental performance on the relationship between corporate governance mechanisms and environmental disclosure	The scholars studied the relationship between corporate administration and environmental disclosure and showed that the former is significantly connected with natural execution and its divulgence.

18.	Haladu and Salim	2017	Board characteristics and sustainability reporting: environmental agencies' moderating effects	The researchers examined the efficiencies of government natural offices in the revelation of ecological data by specific Nigerian organizations and identified the need to instruct the nonexecutive members of Board of Directors on natural issues to balance their approach on the acknowledgment of ecological data.
19.	Yunusa, Mohamed, and Adam	2016	Executive and non-executive auditors and environmental disclosure among listed firms in Nigeria	The scholars studied the connection among official and non-official auditors and showed that non-official examiners significantly affect the environmental disclosure in Nigerian oil companies while official evaluators have no critical association with ecological divulgence.
20.	Haufler	2010	Disclosure as governance: The extractive industries transparency initiative and resource management in the developing world	The study showed that converging transnational systems with reciprocal worldwide standards encourage the organizational growth and promote economic development.
21.	Joseph	2016	Effect of sustainability reporting on firm's performance: A review of literature	The scholar analyzed the impact of sustainability reporting regarding firm's execution and identified the need to improve data collection and presentation techniques to enhance organisational performance.

22.	Oba and Fodio		Comparative analysis of environmental disclosures in oil and gas and construction industries in Nigeria	The study investigated the degree of environmental disclosures in selected Nigerian oil and gas companies and identified the need to have more exposure for rapid economic development.
23.	Esira, Ikechukwu, and Ikechukwu	2014	Environmental cost management and profitability of oil sector in Nigeria (2004-2013)	The scholar impacts of environmental cost management on the profitability of Nigerian oil companies and identified various norms that control environmental cost management.
24.	Ebiringa, Yadirichukwu, Chigbu, and Ogochukwa	2013	Effect of firm size and profitability on corporate social disclosures: The Nigerian oil and gas sector in focus	The scholar analyzed the impact of firm size on the degree of corporate social disclosures and revealed that an irrelevant negative relationship exists between CSR exposure and firm size.
25.	Nosakhare, Ahmad, and Adam	2016	Environmental disclosure in Nigerian quoted companies: The longitudinal study.	The study examined the ecological data of Nigerian organisations and offered a comprehensive examination of the amount of environmental disclosure uncovered by organisations in Nigeria
26.	Adaeze		Determinants of corporate sustainability reporting in selected companies in Nigeria	The scholar utilized longitudinal approach and overviewed outline to realize the destinations of corporate sustainability reporting.

27.	Evbota and Ohalehi	2017	Determinants of corporate social and environmental disclosure of Nigeria oil and gas companies	The researcher analysed different determinants of corporate social and natural disclosure in the oil and gas part and investigated the social and ecological revelation of oil and gas organisations in Nigeria.
28.	Tomlinson	2017	Oil and gas companies and the management of social and environmental impacts and issues	The study highlighted the advancement of global oil organisations' methodologies, audited social and ecological management, and featured a portion of the uncertain issues developing today.
29.	John	2011	Gas flaring and its implication for environmental accounting in Nigeria	The researcher analyzed the hypothetical system for gas flaring and its suggestion for environmental accounting and identified the need to improve the incorporated corporate natural approach to streamline ecological data revelations in yearly accounts.
30.	Moussa, Kotb, and Helfaya		Environmental governance and performance on SED and CSR in U.K	Found that companies with better performance environmentally set and disclose hard environmental targets. Similarly, companies with high environmental sensitivity disclose soft and semi-hard ETs. Need for better regulations that enhance usefulness of disclosures and encourage serious actions to be taken by companies.

31.	Olayinka and Oluwamayowa	2014	Corporate environmental disclosures and market value of quoted companies in Nigeria	The research showed that the mean and middle qualities are inside the base qualities and the standard deviation is low and identified the need to take alert in territories where ecological exercises impacts the organisational values.
32.	Onyinyechi & Ihendinibu	2016	Impact of environmental and corporate social responsibility accounting on organisational financial performance: Evidence from selected listed firms in Nigeria Stock Exchange	The scholar analysed the degree to which organisations' PAT influences the CSR, EMC, and the PBC, and identified the need to upgrade CSR and ecological record for effective management.
33.	Cui	2018	Corporate social responsibility of oil multinationals in Nigeria.	The study featured the inconsistencies that encourages mismanagement in multinational organisations and highlighted Corporate Social Responsibility to accomplish the manageability in the advancement of such a dubious vitality asset.
34.	Egbon	2014	An exploration of accountability : evidence from the Nigerian oil and gas industry	The researchers investigated the idea of responsibility in a creative nation setting and reviewed various methods to execute that idea in Nigerian oil industry.

35.	Ebimobwei	2011	A study of social accounting disclosures in the annual reports of Nigerian companies.	The scholar studied social accounting disclosures in Nigerian oil companies and identified various methods of accepting social accounting disclosures as ethical obligation.
36.	Thorne, Mahoney, Gregory, and Convery	2017	A comparison of Canadian and U.S. CSR strategic Alliances, CSR Reporting, and CSR performance: Insights into Implicit - Explicit CSR	The researchers compared the Canadian and the U.S. CSR strategic Alliances and CSR reporting and CSR performance. They found out that the U.S firms mostly engage in signaling activities that are more explicit and strategic than Canadian counterparts.
37.	Eze	2015	Analysis of oil export and corruption in Nigeria economy	The scholar analysed the income produced from oil trade to explore Nigeria's oil fare and its commitment to the development of economy.
38.	Musa, Yusuf, Mcardle, and Banjoko	2013	Corporate social responsibility in Nigeria's oil and gas industry: The perspective of the industry	Current investigation of CSR in the oil and gas industry in Nigeria exclusively focused on multinational organisations and their exercises.
39.	Omoredede	2014	Assessment of the impact of oil and gas resource exploration on the environment of selected communities in Delta State, Nigeria	The scholar evaluated the issues related to oil exploration and its purification in Nigeria and identified the need to apply greatest endeavors to ensure strict consistence of its lawful instruments by the oil partaking ventures for a practical improvement.

40.	Lebura	2013	Stakeholder relationships in the Nigerian oil industry	The study explored the social contract hypothesis that draws out the place of understanding in the support of these connections between partners, with the assets being vital in the assurance of the power balance.
41.	Gbalam, James, and Peter		Social and environmental accounting: The challenges of implementation in oil prospecting companies in the Niger Delta States of Nigeria	The scholar studied various variables influencing the act of social disclosure in Nigeria and revealed that the tested organisations did not report reality gauge of the externalities created by their executives, instead; brought only the little intercession cost under the administrator's report.
42.	Adedeji, Sidique, Rahman, and Law	2016	The role of local content policy in local value creation in Nigeria's oil industry: A structural equation modeling (SEM) approach	The scholar evaluated the effect of LC strategy in impacting esteem creation with specific reference to indigenous oil firms' investment, in reverse linkages and employment creation.
43.	Jike	2010	Oil companies and host community: A probable scenario for reciprocal empowerment	The scholar embraced basic functionalism and comprehensive quality as a hypothetical model for comprehension and making a limit for peace in the Niger Delta.

44.	Cho, Michelin, Patten, and Roberts	2014	SED and CSR report assurance in the USA: imperial investigation of effects and determinants	The authors discovered that membership and the levels of disclosure influence the choice of attaining party assurance on CSR reports.
45.	Vita, Lagoke, and Adesola	2015	Nigerian oil and gas industry local content development: A stakeholder analysis	The study showed that a minor role is played by advanced education establishments inside the system, but it is multinational oil companies display global centrality inside the business management.
46.	Oisamoje and Aigboduwa	2013	Promoting small and medium enterprises in the Nigerian oil and gas industry	The researchers analysed the authentic pattern in the advancement of SMEs in Nigeria and recognized the few chances and upper hands presently only held for Nigerian organizations.
47.	Okafor	2018	Environmental costs accounting and reporting on firm financial performance: A survey of quoted Nigerian Oil Companies	The study showed that better environmental management emphatically affects the business estimation of an association or an established company and gives it a chance to decrease ecological and social expenses and enhance their execution.

48.	Asuquo	2012	Environmental friendly policies and their financial effects on corporate performance of selected oil and gas companies in Niger delta region of Nigeria	The investigation revealed that organisations should define and actualize ecological and satisfying strategies to upgrade their aggressiveness and steadiness.
49.	Effiong	2010	Oil and gas industry in Nigeria: The paradox of the black Gold	The scholar identified the need to develop a new method for building up a powerful oil strategy system that will incorporate every one of the partners in the management of oil assets.
50.	Omenikolo and Amadi	2010	Challenges facing Nigerian local content in oil and gas industry	The researcher differentiated the difficulties for insufficient usage of the Nigeria content approach and proposed a system to address the variables expected to advance dynamic interest of Nigerians in oil and gas drills.
51.	De Klerk, De Villiers, and Van Staden	2015	The main aim of the paper was to determine the association between market share prices and levels of SED	The research indicated that higher levels of disclosure are related to higher share prices. However, there is need for further study to identify the methods of overcoming the identified limitations of this literature.

52.	Uzonwanne, Yekini, Yekini, and Otobo	2014	An evaluation of management perspectives of sustainability reporting in the Nigerian Oil Industry	The scholars explored the points of view of directors associated with sustainability and management affairs, who believed that oil organisations working inside the district have social obligations to carry out while operating in the sector.
53.	Otomposoba & Dosunmu	2016	Local content policy and its implications on marginal oil fields operations and the Nigerian Economy	The scholars examined the current state of negligible oil fields in the Nigerian economy and identified the need to utilize the neighborhood content arrangement to incur lower expenses of oil production.
54.	Gabriel, Kareem, Kari, Alam, and Matuin	2012	Impact of gas industry on sustainable economy in nigeria: Further estimations through eview	The scholars identified the need to utilize the Regulatory Impact Analysis (RIA) to assess its approach in the long run.
55.	European Parliament	2011	The effects of oil companies' activities on the environment, health and development in Sub-Saharan Africa	The report analysed the non-oil segment creation for the income for manageable development and advancement of Nigeria and identified World Development Indicators for Nigeria and contrasted them and those of some African nations to see the subjects for variation.
56.	US Department of State	2014	Investment climate statement	The report studied the administrative requirements, different vulnerabilities, and security dangers in Nigerian oil industry that have restricted a new interest in this area

57.	Gamerschlag, Möller, and Verbeeten	2011	Determinants of voluntary disclosures: empirical evidence from Germany	The size and industry membership are factors that affect the amount of Social environmental disclosure. Moreover, higher profitability leads to more environmental disclosures
-----	--	------	--	--

2.7.6 Discussions for the SLR Table

Odera et al. (2016) observed the impact of Nigeria's oil companies' social and environmental policy disclosures. The analysis was conducted to foresee the quality and the quantity of the conclusion provided by the disclosure agreements. These activities, known as the SEDs, are collected by studying the annual reports of all the companies existing in the Nigerian oil industry. In this context, a detailed analysis occurs by measuring the reports in two significant units, i.e., the number of sentences and the number of pages. Connection investigation is performed among the diverse SED classes to recognise their connections. Most organisations

conduct SED exercises, and representative data appears to be the most generally accepted type of disclosure based on the quantity of data collected in these activities. Despite significant public awareness about the degree of ecological corruption caused by oil industry charges, SED quantity and quality in nature classification were disproportionately low.

Yusuf & Rahman (2016) investigated and provided a theoretical background on Corporate Environmental Reporting (CER), which assumes an imperative role because of the attention given to ecological issues. Subsequently, to be helpful, corporate administrators should not just highlight CER data but stress the nature of the data revealed. There are various advantages to releasing significant amounts of CER, and the nature of CER may be seen as an essential motivator for organisations. The nature of CER can be viewed as a critical incentive for organisations, and numerous advantages could be given if organisations discharge high calibre ecological data. Earlier natural revelation writing has not concentrated much on exposure quality; instead, it focused on the amount of divulgence. Likewise, most of the few examinations that concentrated on the nature of natural disclosure have uncovered the low level of nature of such exposure. Along these lines, the main attempt intends to examine the nature of environmental revelation in various announcing mediums by oil and gas organisations in creating nations. The results of this investigation uncover that the nature of the example organisations' ecological revelation is high contrasted with past examinations. This examination has critical ramifications in upgrading the comprehension of natural divulgence practices of oil and gas organisations in creating nations.

Dibia and Onwuchekwa (2015) looked at the factors influencing natural declarations in Nigerian oil industries. The study's objectives were to examine the effects of company size, profit, and audit firm composition on natural exposures. The investigation was conducted using a cross-sectional study design. The investigation revealed a significant link between

organisational size and corporate social responsibility declaration. In terms of exposure, there is also no crucial link between profit and corporate social responsibility. Also, there is no critical connection between profit and corporate social responsibility regarding exposure. Finally, no essential connection was found between the power and corporate social responsibility declarations. There is no critical connection between review firms' composition and corporate social responsibility attributes. The investigation presumed that the deliberate position has frequently been utilised as an appeal for organisations to submit underestimated figures for their impact on the earth. This is a deliberate attempt from a few corporate substances' carelessnesses concerning corporate social and ecological detailing. The examination suggests that motivators be set up to force these ignorers to provide reasonable explanations.

According to Moussa et al. (2021), companies have done scant research in the field of public declaration of environmental targets. Therefore, the study aimed to investigate the extent of corporate environmental target disclosures and the influence of environmental governance. Results indicated that U.K. firms depict significant variations in variability and inconsistency in reporting. The study supports stakeholder, legitimacy, and management impression theories. The study leaves the gap of which actions to take to reduce a negative impact on the environment by creating a "win-win" situation. According to Sani (2018), corporate social and natural revelation is essential in forming nations and animating training; many developing countries establish restrictions. The Code of Corporate Governance for registered organisations in Nigeria demanded specific disclosure. The authenticity hypothesis is used to assist the investigation, while corporate characteristics are tested to see how they affect the number of revelations. The exposure volume is determined using adjusted word verified content analysis of yearly reports and records of test organisations. Two sample t-tests provide the factual mean of the disclosure at the same time. The Board Corrected Standard

Error regression analysis is used to determine corporate characteristics' influence on acknowledgement volume. The results of the board relapse investigation show that company size has a favourable and notable relationship with the revelation.

De Klerk et al. (2015) examined the association of company shares and SED levels among UK-based large firms. SED and CSR data from an independent firm was used in conjunction with a period coinciding with increased legislation and public awareness about corporate social and environmental issues. A modified model (Ohlson of 1995) was used in the study. The study helped the researchers discover that disclosure levels are associated with higher share prices. It was also identified that companies operating in environmentally sensitive sectors have a stronger relationship with share prices.

Otiotio (2018) analysed the effect of natural and social revelation on the monetary regulation of majorly cited oil and gas organisations in Nigeria. Information and data collection regarding time agreements for a long time were gathered and dissected. The factual investigation uncovered that the confession on worker well-being and security and network improvement does not essentially influence monetary execution. At the same time, divulgence in the waste administration had a positive and critical impact on its budgetary implementation. The examination prescribed that oil and gas organisations survey their waste administration technique and utilise waste administration innovation to relieve their effect on the earth. Moreover, oil and gas organisations should enhance the representative well-being and security as a significant aspect of their main goals and vision explanation for improved firm esteem. Organisations should likewise guarantee a managed improvement of their host networks to avoid hostile competitors, which will negatively impact their activities and, like this, influence the execution process.

Gamerschlag et al. (2011) argue that in the current times, companies are spending a lot of effort on corporate social responsibility disclosures. SED is associated with providing information regarding a company's environmental and social performance. The study was tested with an index grounded on GRI guidelines and used the content analysis approach. Using the technique, 130 German companies were analysed to determine the determinants of voluntary disclosure practices. The study showed that inconsistency with the political cost theory, visibility, the structure of shareholders, and their relationship with U.S. stakeholders affect companies' disclosures. Furthermore, higher profitability leads to more environmental disclosures. Moreover, the industry's size and membership affect the disclosure level.

Odera (2014) argues that SEDs do not have any significant bearing with other nations in different phases of monetary improvement and for organisations with contrasting levels of mindfulness and mentalities. SEDs are regularly seen as instruments for conveying an organisation's social and natural activities' social and biological impacts to its significant, intriguing gatherings to the public. Partners have become progressively competitive about how organisations connect with society and the condition. This way, the expanded enthusiasm for organisations' social and ecological effects has increased weight from partners for SEDs. This examination looks to distinguish Nigerian host networks' Host Communities (H.C.s) view of SEDs from other oil organisations. On the other hand, the organisations analyse SEDs' amount and nature in the Nigerian oil industry. The future aim of the paper is to recognise whether there are contrasts among nearby and outside oil organisations concerning their SEDs.

Effiong (2010) explains how the financial and political difficulties confronting Nigeria's oil-delivering system are filled with natural and social issues that emerge from oil slicks, gas flaring, and the land's corruption. This study's premise depends on a survey of government reports and materials delivered by global advancement offices. Both national and worldwide

nongovernmental associations have propelled crusades to address the issues; however, little has been accomplished because the oil organisations are hesitant to be mindful of corporate neighbours. The Nigerian government is reluctant to devise answers for the location of the issue. The scholars concluded that a new method for building up a powerful oil strategy system should be introduced, which will incorporate every one of the partners in oil assets administration.

Thorne et al. (2017) considered how corporate social responsibility in Canada differs from that in the United States. They identified differences in institutional social activities in the two countries, and the existing differences were related to variations in their CSR practices. The research further indicated the existence of an implicit-explicit conceptual framework where explicit CSR activities are viewed as more voluntary and strategic than implicit CSR practices. The study also investigated the correspondences of CSR strategic alliances, reporting, and performance to implicit versus explicit practices, and the results were linked to stakeholders and signalling perceptions. The Sustainalytics Global Platform (SGP) was the main point of reference in providing SED data and scores for the two countries concerning CSR activities. The findings were that U.S. firms had higher scores meaning more engagement in CSR activities. On the other hand, in Canada, there were no mediating effects. The study further suggests that U.S. companies engage in signalling activities described as more strategic and explicit than Canadian firms.

According to Sani (2016), corporate social revelation is a former medium utilised by enterprises to impart their effects and duties to the public. Accordingly, this examination's fundamental point is to depict and clarify social and ecological revelation rehearses by recorded Nigerian oil industries as analysed between the economies of Nigeria and that of the U.K. The investigations of the yearly reports, records, supportability reports, scoring, and nature of revelations are dependent on Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) exposure rules.

Authenticity discussion and weakness and exploitability were upheld to build a hypothetical structure to support the examination. The results show that Nigerian industries are exposed to less social and ecological perspectives than U.K. organisations.

The amount and nature of revelation by Nigerian industries are low contrasted with U.K. organisations. While the amount of exposure indicated expanding patterns, the spirit of disclosure portrayed diminishing marks. Corporate size, use, proficiency, and liquidity are noteworthy in clarifying exposures by inspected organisations. The low amount and nature of exposure by recorded Nigerian oil and gas firms demonstrate shared social responsibility. This outcome might help strategy creators in the business exchange with directors of the organisations on the significance of their social responsibility to national economic improvement endeavours.

Jike (2010) performed a quick hypothetical review of the struggle between oil industries and host networks in Nigeria's Niger Delta. It looks at the fighting issues around the substantive elements of oil industries and the dormant outcomes of natural corruption, which has remained a steady wellspring of erosion between oil industries and host networks. The paper embraces basic functionalism or comprehensive quality as a hypothetical model for comprehension and limits peace in the Niger Delta. The technique adopted for this paper is grave and ethnographic, including long-drawn meetings and non-member perceptions of both oil labourers and indigenes of the host network. Finally, the article encourages cooperative energy and prescribes a situation for complementary strengthening between oil industries and the host communities in the Niger Delta of Nigeria.

Cho et al. (2014) carried out a study to investigate factors leading to U.S. companies' urge to acquire assurance on their CSR and whether market participants value the security. Logistical regression is the method engaged by the author in the determination of the factors affecting

safety. It was discovered that industry membership the disclosure levels influence the choice of attaining the assurance, especially the third-party contract. Moreover, the research indicates that certainty is unrelated to market value for companies reporting disclosure.

Taiwo (2010) highlighted the workers' issues and the workplaces existing in the oil industries of the Nigerian economy. The kind of workplace in which workers work decides how such activities flourish. This paper aims to break down the effect of the workplace on future specialists' efficiency. Along these lines, the governments at the administrative and state levels investigate methods for enhancing and refreshing infrastructural offices with the end goal of making the workplace more helpful for an upgrade of work profitability. Correspondingly, the bosses must investigate work and authoritatively related components and business strategies for surveys to make them more productive and challenge labourers to be more beneficial.

Haufler (2010) contended that if extractive firms reveal their instalments freely to governments, nationals will have the capacity to consider governments responsible. This will enhance the administration of regular assets, decrease defilement, and relieve struggle. This article argues that converging transnational systems with common worldwide standards encouraged the development of straightforwardness to answer the administration of asset incomes. Thus, the advanced continuous developments of institutional engineering participate, despite noteworthy political boundaries. Moreover, Ebiringa, Yadirichukwu, Chigbu, and Ogochukwa (2013) analysed the impact of firm size and benefit on the degree of corporate social revelations by Oil industries in Nigeria. The result of the study demonstrates that an irrelevant negative relationship exists between CSR exposure and firm size. Gainfulness is identified with the CSR divulgence of the organisations.

Haladu & Salim (2017) argued that specialisation is required in individual classes of supportability data statements. An attempt has been made to examine the natural and social courses of maintainability disclosure. The results demonstrate that organisations performed better on social detailing than ecological announcing regarding higher maintainability exposure rates and critical connections. The current pattern of revealing manageability data revelation under social and environmental publicising is empowering, considering how divulgence of manageability issues in Nigeria is intentional.

According to Omenikolo and Amadi (2010), oil is Nigeria's most important industry and the most significant contributor to the nation's Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Despite the Nigerian government's excessive monetary speculations in the oil and gas business, it has not resulted in significant benefits for Nigerians. The business's neighbourhood content is modest, accounting for more than 60% of the basic workouts. Multinational oil companies, for example, continue to manage and monitor the investigation, generation, well mediation, and administration arrangements. Nearby contractors have only been awarded a modest contract. The problems with the everyday use of Nigerian content were highlighted in this study. This paper distinguished the difficulties of the low usage of the Nigeria content approach using questionnaires and built up a system that comprehensively addresses the variables expected to advance Nigerians' active interest in oil and gas drills without trading off norms with the end goal of invigorating the development of indigenous limit.

Ironkwe & Promise (2016) proclaimed many potentials to cause a few avoidable ecological troubles by unchecked oil and gas explorations and drills. However, extreme well-being hazards are typically connected with oil and gas explorations coming about because of contamination. Regarding the way of life, neighbourhood and the financial and social structure of the community and native networks are also generally influenced. To worsen the

issues, it is trusted that natural laws in developing economies, such as Nigeria's, are regularly inadequate, claiming they are substantively insufficient to regulate the economic process.

All it takes is attention to assess the need for implementing satisfactory Environmental Reporting, both budgetary and non-money related announcing, and its significance in the industry in connecting with partners. It is secured on the authenticity hypothesis of corporate social obligation announcing while evaluating the detailing necessities and what is generally revealed in oil industries' monetary proclamations with standard exposure necessities. It was found that the detailing group should be steady and followed to guarantee straightforwardness in announcing the organisation's task. It has been discovered that the business's best difficulties concerning supportability execution revealing are deciding how to gauge, characterise, and select fitting markers.

John (2011) analysed the hypothetical system for gas flaring and its suggestion for natural bookkeeping in the Nigerian Petroleum Industry. Information was sourced from the yearly reports of organisations associated with gas flaring in the oil industry. The outcome uncovers that the issue tormenting ecological bookkeeping revelations identifies with the absence of an institutionalised necessity for exposure, political will for enactment, authorisation, and natural expenses designation. Accordingly, the examination suggests improving an incorporated corporate natural approach and the legitimate sponsorship to streamline ecological data revelations in yearly accounts.

Ebimobowei (2011) analysed the act of social bookkeeping exposure in Nigerian organisations. The outcomes demonstrate that Nigerian organisations like to reveal social bookkeeping data in the Director's Report, Chairman's Statement, and Notes to the Accounts as short subjective data. Human Resources (H.R.), people group association, and the condition were recognised as the most prevalent topics. Henceforth, the paper prescribes,

among others, that organisations should accept social bookkeeping as an ethical obligation, i.e., to follow the policy of enactment for all organisations to reveal social bookkeeping data in Nigeria; social markers to be created at the national level in the region of business openings, natural control, vitality preservation, human services, and so forth and expert bookkeeping bodies in the nation should work together.

Asuquo (2012) conveyed the natural benevolent approaches and the impacts of monetary regulations on Nigeria's corporate execution of oil industries. Along these lines, it was inferred that the related expense of ecological assurance and administration positively impacts the company. The examination accordingly indicated that organisations should define and actualise environmental and satisfying strategies to upgrade their aggressiveness and steadiness, which would, in this manner, result in superiority.

Gabriel, Kareem, Kari, Alam, and Matuin (2012) argued that the goal of supportable monetary advancement, particularly in any struggling nation like Nigeria, is to build up strength and improve economic standards viability, which is both monetarily effective and manageable. The declining results and the co-incorporation examination demonstrate that usage of Nigerian flammable gas impacts, particularly on the economy, is also possible. Even though the burden of fine on flared gas can end or diminish flares, it has not fundamentally prompted any fundamental changes in the level of flares. The final verdict suggested by the authors is for the governments to depend on utilising the Regulatory Impact Analysis (RIA) to assess their approach in the long run.

Yusuf, Joseph & Ekundayo (2016) argued that modern organisations are confronting weights to exhibit nature's obligation. As a result, in reacting to these weights, organisations have revelations about their exercises' ecological effects. This investigation has utilised an exposure file custom-fitted to a survey that is uncovered, the shape in which it is unveiled,

where it is revealed in the yearly report, and whether the declaration is viewed as necessary data. The investigation is one of a kind as it evaluates environmental acknowledgement in Nigeria's oil industry utilising yearly reports alone. It is the central data archive of any organisation that can be used to impart to its partners. The discoveries from the examination focus on how oil and gas organisations working in Nigeria consider the exposure of data identifying the natural effect of their activities in their yearly reports. As the world is becoming environmentally viable, illuminated financial specialists feel ethically bound to put resources into organisations that connect with green, environmentally friendly activities.

Oscar & Juliet (2015) analysed the impact of corporate administration on natural detailing. This examination utilises board estimate, board autonomy, and advisory group freedom to the intermediary for corporate administration. The examination results demonstrate that board measure, board autonomy, review panel, space, and administrative possession focus positively and critically associated with natural revealing. Considering the discoveries, the suggestion is that organisations that need to enhance their realistic detailing quality should consider corporate administration systems and proprietorship focus inside the organisations.

Otu, Okon, Okafor & Nnanna (2018) studied the importance of the relationship between natural bookkeeping and oil industries in Nigeria. The optional information utilised has been taken from the reviewed monetary records of the oil industries. Ecological bookkeeping detailing was estimated by the expenses of air contamination, water contamination, corruption, staff welfare, network welfare, and prosecutions. Considering these discoveries, it is suggested that the administration make environmental divulgence obligatory, and force endorses the infringement by oil industries in Nigeria.

Odia & Imagbe (2015) analysed the outcomes of corporate social and ecological exposures in Nigeria. The results show a changing level of contrasts concerning partners and sex

concerning the social and monetary results of CSED. It was inferred that the corporate social and natural divulgences have more social than financial bestows and henceforth bolster the authenticity hypothesis. The outcomes have important ramifications for Nigerian organisations as they figure out their socio-ecological procedure and correspondence. In this manner, it is suggested that organisations should expand the revelations on social and condition issues to enhance their social and environmental exhibitions, which could, in the end, affect their monetary displays.

Pantamee (2014) evaluated corporate administration's impact on the corporate social duty declaration in the Nigerian oil advertising industry from 2008 to 2012. The investigation pointed out that board piece, chance administration advisory group creation, the hazard administration board of trustees meeting, and possession display a critical but positive association with the corporate social obligation about the Nigerian oil advertising industry. While executive gathering, the administration board of trustees measure and productivity uncover a significant negative association with corporate social duty exposure in the Nigerian oil promoting industry. Therefore, the examination prescribes, among others; that the governing body of these oil advertising organisations ought to incorporate corporate social obligation revelation programs as part of their plan to be talked about in the broad yearly gatherings and edify other partners on the idea and its advantages when to fit into the code of best rehearses. Discoveries of this investigation also bolster the significance of hazard the administration advisory group regarding the corporate social obligation in the oil promoting organisations.

Nwaiwu and Oluka (2018) offered the perspective of the world's most significant global network, the United Nations. The United Nations Organisation (UNO) has conducted extensive research on natural exercises from various perspectives, including preservation, manageability, administration, assurance, control, and the overall impact on the global

economy (Nwaiwu& Oluka, 2018). The influence of environmental cost disclosure and monetary execution fractions of mentioned oil industries in Nigeria is examined in this study (Nwaiwu& Oluka, 2018).

This examination examines the impact of ecological cost revelation and monetary execution proportions of cited oil industries in Nigeria. Time arrangement information was gathered from yearly monetary revealing and financial audits of the Central Bank of Nigeria. The econometric outcomes investigated satisfactory revelation on natural cost, consistency to corporate environmental directions have a meaningful positive impact on budgetary execution measures in this way. The examination prescribed the administrative requirement for genuine cost divulgence and legitimate announcing. The administration of oil industries in Nigeria ought to build up a well-articulated environmental costing framework to ensure a contention-free corporate environment for enhanced corporate execution.

Adinehzadeh, Jaffar, Shukor & Rahman (2018) proclaimed that the rising number of natural standards and directions had created a slightly alarming situation. There are hardly any examinations that consider the relationship between actual execution, corporate administration, and ecological revealing. In this way, the investigation aims to research the relationship between corporate administration and natural revelation qualities and the intervening job of actual execution in this relationship. The result of the study demonstrates that corporate administration is decidedly connected with realistic implementation and divulgence. The outcomes show that natural performance mainly intervenes in the connection between corporate administration and natural exposure quality. This position is a significant contribution to top administration regarding the significance of corporate administration systems towards the foundation of natural related approaches and methodologies that enhance realistic execution.

Haladu & Salim (2016) have directed this research paper's attention towards Paris' Atmosphere Deal'. The efficiencies of the government's natural offices in discovering ecological data by touchy firms in Nigeria are examined. Ecological offices were additionally tried for their job in supportability announcing. The examination suggests nonexecutive individuals from the Board of Directors be instructed on natural issues to balance their negative effect on acknowledging ecological data.

Yunusa, Mohamed, and Adam (2016) studied the connection between official and non-official evaluators connected with the ecological statements amongst recorded organisations' yearly reports in Nigeria. This examination aims to look at official and non-official inspectors' jobs on the natural revelations of ecologically registered organisations in Nigeria. The information provided by this examination is gathered from the yearly financial reports of some organisations. Utilising standard slightest square relapse to test the investigation's speculation, the analysis results appear that while official evaluators have no critical association with ecological divulgence, non-official examiners are observed to be hugely affected by the natural revelation in Nigerian earth's delicate recorded businesses.

Joseph (2016) analysed the impact of manageability, providing details regarding the firm's execution. The utilised data assembled from diaries, books, and web materials, along with survey findings, uncovered that observers had not achieved an accord on whether firms can intensify execution on the possibility that they actualise support. Oba and Fodio (2012) presented research in Nigeria Discoveries that examined the degree of environmental disclosures in mentioned oil and gas and development companies (Oba & Fodio, 2012). The oil industry gave an exposure level; however, this distinction was not huge. In this way, the two ventures displayed extremely insufficient ecological data in their yearly reports, which concur with the examination's contentions.

Esira, Ikechukwu, and Ikechukwu (2014) determined the natural cost administration impacts on oil division in Nigeria. The result uncovered a meaningful connection between the effects of genuine cost administration and the benefit of the oil segment in Nigeria. Likewise, it was found that Nigeria has norms controlling the environmental cost administration in oil and gas businesses. It was concluded that the degree of natural cost administration in the oil division is at its simple stage. This will encourage the worldwide battle for an ecologically upgraded society. The degree of realistic cost administration as underscored in this investigation should be considered.

Nosakhare, Ahmad & Adam (2016) conducted a detailed examination of Nigerian organisations' environmental data. The examination configuration received by this investigation is essentially unmistakable. The study found that the length of divulgence of ecological data is around three sentences for every low organisation, particularly in examining other created and creating nations. It was likewise discovered that following the occasions that prompted the correction of the code of corporate administration. There was an enduring increment in the amount revealed after some time. The exciting element of this paper is that it expands the writing on natural revelation by giving a distinctive portrayal of the amount of environmental data uncovered by organisations in Nigeria.

Adaeze (2017) utilised the longitudinal and overviewed outline to realise its destinations. Essential information was gathered using the survey regulated to organisations to translate the significance and execution of variables that decide maintainability detailing in Nigeria. The experimental outcomes depended on 2010 to 2014 information on manageability revealing, institutional field factors, and announcing process factors loan some help to the new institutional hypothesis and the authenticity hypothesis.

Cephas, Ukori & Ohalehi (2017) analysed the different determinants of corporate social and natural divulgements in oil and gas. The expansive target of the examination was to inspect the social and ecological revelation of oil and gas organisations in Nigeria and research the effect of firm size, productivity, monetary use, company age, and reviewed firm size on the social and natural divulgence of oil and gas organisations in Nigeria.

Tomlinson (2017) conducted this study to review the oil and gas industry's social and natural administration rehearses. It plots the advancement of global oil organisations' methodologies, audits what social and ecological administration among such organisations implies, and features a portion of the uncertain issues developing today. In contrast, most organisations presently display their way of dealing with social and natural administration on worldwide standards. They range from agreeing to worldwide estimation with the end goal to access back to following new host nation enactment and direction.

Environmental data releases hurt the market value of fifty companies in Nigeria, according to Olayinka and Oluwamayowa (2014). They found that both mean and middle characteristics were within their base values. The standard deviation was low, indicating that the original information's divergence from their mean esteem was minimal. The investigation suggests that businesses should take alert in territories where ecological exercises impact contrarily on the firm's Value and put resources into zones that upgrade an incentive for the firm.

Onyinyechi & Ihendinihu (2016) analysed the effect of ecological and corporate social obligation bookkeeping on firms' authoritative monetary execution in Nigeria. The investigation was additionally masterminded to decide the degree to which firms' Profit After Tax (PAT) influences the CSR, Environmental Maintenance Cost (EMC), and Personnel Benefit Cost (PBC). The examination configuration utilised was an exploratory research plan. The optional information was time arrangement information containing CSR, EMC, PBC,

and PAT of cited firms in the NSE. Factual devices of Multiple Linear Regression and understudy t-tests were utilised for the examination. The relapse demonstration was assessed using a substantial bundle for sociologies (SPSS). The three invalid theories utilised in this ponder were tried at a 5% level of criticalness. The outcome demonstrated no effect and an adverse effect on CSR.

Moreover, EMC on PAT individually, while the PBC positively affects PAT. The p-esteem for CSR and EMC isn't critical, while PBC is profoundly noteworthy. The F-test demonstrated a solid match for the model. The investigation along these lines reasons that firms use to natural and social issues are not proportionate to their money-related execution as spoken to by PAT. In this way, CSR and ecological upkeep should involve concern for the Government, NGOs, and firms on the loose.

Cui (2018) offered a profound record of the Nigerian legal structure identified with oil, with the end goal to feature the inconsistencies and lacunas that prompted the present circumstance; furthermore, to interface this investigation to the investigation of ethnicity, society, and condition in the nation; thirdly, to coordinate these highlights with Corporate Social Responsibility, looking to consolidate its ideas to the national collection of standards, in the perspective of the accomplishment of manageability in the advancement of such a dubious vitality asset.

According to Egbon (2014), modern multinational companies' monetary exercises in the extractive enterprises of creating nations deliver a heap of immediate adverse social, financial and natural effects on networks facilitating their tasks. As a result, the partners have progressively called for these organisations' responsibility for the impact of their functions on partners and the more extensive society. The degree to which these MNCs are responsible for their tasks' adverse ecological effects in the creating nations is underexplored as earlier

examinations have focused on corporate social duty instead of the responsibility of these enterprises. In any case, responsibility implies specific things to distinctive gatherings, particularly in a non-Western setting. Finally, the researchers investigated the idea of responsibility in creating a nation setting and comprehending and rehearsing inside the Nigerian oil industry.

According to Eze (2015), defilement was utilised as an independent variable because of its significant antagonistic impact on the Nigerian economy. Corruption has consumed a profound sector of the nation's economy, one of the actual emergencies that Nigeria is confronting today. This examination investigates the effect of unrefined petroleum sent out on Nigeria's economy and its level of humiliation. The study concentrated on the income produced from oil trade with the motivation behind surveying oil investigation and defilement to explore Nigeria's oil fare and its commitment to the development of the economy and see whether the level of humiliating influences the financial development in Nigeria. Considering the discoveries, the outcome representations that oil sends out have noteworthy affected the economy regardless of its impact by defilement, which seems to be adversely identified with other financial factors. This way, it was suggested by the author that the approach of oil and non-oil send-out advancement system ought to be taken genuine by the administration with the end goal to impact a positive change.

Musa, Yusuf, Mcardle & Banjoko (2013) presented this examination to contrast the past investigations by including a significant number of small and medium endeavours exchanging the business and both in the upstream and downstream segments of the industry. The company conveys CSR as a social permit to pick up and hold adequacy by its host networks. Past investigations of CSR in Nigeria's oil and gas industry have focused exclusively on multinational administrators and their exercises in Nigeria.

Lebura (2013) analysed the connections between partners in the business and comprehended the associations between these connections and CSR in the industry. This paper has brought about the decision of 'Social Contract and Resource Dependence' hypotheses to be utilised in agreement as a component of the theoretical base for this investigation, further developing the stakeholder hypothesis. The social contract hypothesis draws out understanding in support of these connections between partners, with the assets being vital in assuring the power balance.

James & Gbalam (2013) studies various variables influencing social bookkeeping divulgence in Nigerian oil prospecting organisations. There are mainly three organisations working in Nigeria where haphazard has been observed to have taken place. The paper uncovered that the tested organisations did not report a near-reality gauge of the externalities created by their generation exercises but said the little intercession cost brought about by the executives or the administrator's report. For example, cost of execution, the impact on benefit, the presence of a lawful casing work, the serene condition, and the best administration bolster the influence of social and environmental bookkeeping practices among the organisations considered.

Adedeji, Sidique, Rahman & Law (2016) discussed how receiving a substance approach benefits the financial development of creating oil-rich nations is not a new concept. The authors point out that the Local Content (L.C.) approach to nearby esteem creation has produced different hypotheses in Nigeria. However, this study tends to focus on this hole by evaluating the L.C. strategy's effect on nearby esteem creation with specific reference to indigenous oil firms' investment in reverse linkages and employment creation. In any case, we found that nearby esteem made in the Nigerian oil industry because of L.C. strategy is lower than the standard target. This suggests the usage of the arrangement should be nearly checked to guarantee its viability towards expanding monetary advancement.

Vita, Lagoke, and Adesola (2015) draw from arrangement reports and semi-organised meetings. At that point, an informal community investigation uncovers that a considerable number of connections between key players is unidirectional. Advanced education establishments inside the system play a minor role. Still, universal oil organisations, instead of indigenous administrators, display worldwide centrality inside the business organisation, with the previous partner significantly deciding industry exercises.

Aigboduwa & Oisamoje (2013) emphasised the connection between the small and medium scale companies (SMEs) in Nigeria. Theoretically, it has been found that these operating subsidiaries have been recognised as having the potential for conducting large business orders to help boost Nigeria's economy. In Nigeria, be that as it may, the division remains generally little as far as its commitment to GDP or profitable business (Sonibare et al. 2008) even though the Nigerian oil and gas industry has assumed a significant job in the nation's financial advancement. Be that as it may, the sanctioning of policies has provided Nigerians with various chances to partake in the oil area. This paper looks at the original pattern in SMEs' advancement in Nigeria and recognises the few options and upper hands presently only held for Nigerian organisations.

Okafor (2018) utilised the financial reports of oil industries cited in the Nigerian Stock Exchange Market for over a decade. This study revealed that better environmental execution affects the business estimation of an association or an established company. Besides, natural bookkeeping gives the association a chance to decrease environmental and social expenses and enhance its execution.

Uzonwanne, Yekini, Yekini, and Otobo (2014) explored directors' views associated with maintainability and management affairs in the Nigerian oil industry. The information assembled was categorised subjectively under different aspects. The general view rising

amongst most directors was that oil organisations working inside the district have social obligations to carry out while operating in the sector (Wopara, 2015). The fact remains that the Nigerian Federal Government's job is to support the institutional structure around which the local community's improvement is to be directed. Likewise, Hackett (2018) emphasised Nigeria's history, where the development of the state into a subordinate asset nation observes the barriers to existing human rights commitments as they identify with businesses. In propelling MNCs to outline and actualise successful CSR arrangements inward states like Nigeria, the challenge in coming years.

According to the material provided by the U.S. Department of State, Nigeria has been marked as the major oil producer in the African subcontinent. Nigeria's oil yield has contracted the administrative requirements, different vulnerabilities, and security dangers that have restricted a new interest in this area. A significant blockage has widened the monetary improvement in Nigeria's weaker power segment. A far-reaching change in Nigeria's capacity segment is a continuous form of regulation. At the same time, numerous difficulties lay before Nigeria in maintaining the social status of being the largest oil producer in the future.

A report presented by the European Parliament analysed the non-oil segment creation for the income for manageable development and advancement of Nigeria. This study identified World Development Indicators for Nigeria and contrasted them and those of some African nations and rising economies to see the subjects for variation. It additionally utilised the trial in the examination of the factors under investigation. The outcome appeared in interest in the non-oil economic development and improvement sectors due to its potential effect on producing different income groups.

Otomposoba & Dosunmu (2016) examined the state of negligible oil fields in the Nigerian economy. Given the vital significance of minimal field advancement, the utilisation of

neighbourhood content arrangement in minor field tasks is of crucial importance since it will, without delays, incur lower expenses to produce oil. The substance approach's obligation to little field tasks takes over many nations caught in the same frenzy. Finally, Yakuba (2017) argued that Nigeria is subject to its raw petroleum and gaseous petrol assets; thus, the economy is powerless against oil value variances. Elective energies to non-renewable energy sources debilitate Nigeria's economy and vitality security. This report examines the Nigerian Petroleum industry and its potential future concerning current patterns in the vitality business.

2.7.7 Finalisation of the SLR

The systematic literature review is considered very time-consuming when assessed against the other types of reviews (Xiao & Watson 2017). Therefore, the researcher followed strict timelines to ensure that the review did not adversely affect the completion deadline of the entire research project. The researcher finalised the systematic literature review article identification and selection process within two (2) months after the review began. The article screening for title pages, abstracts, and introduction phase took the most time (approximately five weeks) because of the need to analyse and review the contents related to each article that was subjected to screening. Specifically, the finalisation of the systematic literature review was expected to end after the inclusion of the peer-reviewed journal articles, which focus on the SED reporting practices within the Nigerian oil and gas sector. However, it took a few days to systematically select the additional published articles (European Parliament and the U.S. Department of State) identified through the reference lists of the included articles. Therefore, the entire systematic literature review ended by containing the two articles as part of the final list of review articles, fifty-seven (57) in total.

2.7.8 Systematic Review of the Existing Research Gaps in the study

Previously, studies have been carried out to reveal the impact of SED in the Nigerian oil industry but have left some gaps behind, calling for further studies. For instance, according to Sani (2018), corporate social and natural revelation is essential in forming nations and animating training; many developing countries establish restrictions. The Code of Corporate Governance for registered organisations in Nigeria demanded specific disclosure. Two sample t-tests provide the factual mean of the disclosure at the same time. The Board Corrected Standard Error regression analysis is used to determine corporate characteristics' influence on acknowledgement volume. The results of the board relapse investigation show that company size has a favourable and notable relationship with the revelation.

According to Sani (2016), corporate social revelation is a former medium utilised by enterprises to impart their effects and duties to the public. Accordingly, this examination's fundamental point is to depict and clarify social and ecological revelation rehearses by recorded Nigerian oil organisations as analysed between the economies of Nigeria. The investigations of the yearly reports, records, supportability reports, scoring, and nature of revelations are dependent on Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) exposure rules. Authenticity discussion and weakness and exploitability were upheld to build a hypothetical structure to support the examination. The results show Nigerian organisations being exposed to less social and environmental perspectives than U.K. organisations.

Odia & Imagbe (2015) analysed the outcomes of corporate social and environmental exposures in Nigeria. The outcomes show a changing level of contrasts concerning partners and sex about corporate social environmental disclosure's social and monetary results. It was inferred that the corporate social and natural divulgences have more social than financial bestows and henceforth bolster the authenticity hypothesis. The outcomes have important

ramifications for Nigerian organisations as they figure out their socio-ecological procedure and correspondence. In this manner, it is suggested that organisations should expand the revelations on social and condition issues to enhance their social and environmental exhibitions, which could ultimately affect their monetary displays.

Tomlinson (2017) conducted this study to review the social and natural administration rehearses petroleum industry. It plots the advancement of global oil organisations' methodologies, audits what social and environmental administration among such organisations implies and features a portion of the uncertain issues developing today. In contrast, most organisations presently display their way of dealing with social and natural administration on worldwide standards. The range from agreeing to worldwide estimation with the end goal to access back to following new host nation enactment and direction.

The existing gaps in previous research are identified, and this study intends to address them using regression analysis. The use of Board Corrected Standard Error regression analysis helps identify the level of social-environmental disclosure and the determination of corporate social responsibility authentication. Moreover, the study will involve discussions that will help determine the weaknesses and exploitability using a hypothetical structured analysis in support of the examination.

2.8 Conclusion

The literature review section has provided insight into past SED research by exploring SED theory and its related activities linked to the companies' responsibilities to the environment and larger society. Reviewing historical trends shows that firms have become increasingly responsible for the environment and society. The motivation to engage in SED was also studied, which has led to stakeholders' concerns for accountability, including a review of the

market responses explanatory for the momentum behind the growth of SED. SED evidence focusing on A.R. as a disclosure tool was also evaluated following the study's objectives. As mentioned earlier, most studies used content analysis through measuring, counting, and assessing the degree of disclosures. In the end, gaps in the existing literature were identified, focusing on the SED quality assessment, which remains controversial. Identifying the current gaps hence demands the implementation of a framework for SED analysis.

CHAPTER THREE: THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

3.1 Introduction

The theoretical framework is a vital structure or guideline that describes how research variables are associated with explaining the research problem (Briggs 2007). Generally, a theoretical framework describes the basis for the relationships and explains why the research problem of interest occurs, given the context of the study. This study guided two theoretical frameworks: stakeholder theory and legitimacy theory. The stakeholder theoretical framework posits that corporate organisations must meet the interests of all stakeholder groups, including employees, the community, suppliers, governments, customers, and environmental groups (Huang & Kung 2010). The implication is that inconsistent with the traditional view (shareholder theory), the stakeholder theory indicates that the firms' owners are not the only vital stakeholders due to the rise in consumerism and community empowerment. As part of the initiatives to enhance their overall strategic competitiveness, more firms now recognise the need to issue social and environmental disclosure (SED) reports and annual financial statements (Duff 2016; Sani 2018).

The stakeholder theoretical framework is considered relevant to the present research study, which investigates the SED reporting practices in the Nigerian oil industries. The publication of annual SED reports by the Nigerian oil industries to disclose their performance in community welfare development, environmental conservation, efficient energy conservation, and waste management provides evidence that corporate entities now recognise host communities as essential stakeholders (Yusuf, Samuel and Ekundayo 2016). This contrasts with the previous practice where oil companies gave annual financial report disclosure was given considerable priority.

The theoretical legitimacy framework is also a critical theory that guides the present research study. According to Duff (2016), the legitimacy theory is based on the idea that corporate entities disclose their community welfare contribution and environmental conservation initiatives to portray a socially responsible image desired by the external stakeholders, including the host communities. The social legitimacy theoretical framework is based on the inherent awareness/knowledge that an implicit social contract binds corporate organisations and society (Huang and Kung 2010). This means that even though expectations are not written, corporate entities acknowledge that they are responsible for behaving in a socially responsible manner. According to Duff (2016), social legitimacy gained when organisations are perceived as socially responsible corporate citizens is an important asset that allows the business entities to charge premium fees for their products and obtain a substantial market share. The social legitimacy theory is relevant to this study because it describes how the SED reporting practices by the Nigerian oil industries are motivated by their desire to gain social acceptance and attain substantial market share.

No developing society can run efficiently without oil and gas (Watts, 2005). This is the reason these items are essential today. The interest in oil and gas surpasses their generation. This additionally clarifies the motivation behind why nations with an immense store of raw petroleum are among the most extravagant countries in the world (Iwuagwu, 2009). Since the usefulness of an advanced society depends to a gigantic degree on raw petroleum, it is then vital to utilise innovative and bleeding edge mechanical procedures towards this imperative field with the end goal to guarantee adequacy simultaneously ("Oil industry's" 2010). Oil and gas are exceedingly requested in enterprises and for business and residential purposes. The items are utilised for many purposes, from the driving of hardware to the generation of plastics and manures.

Undoubtedly, the world would lose its taste if oil and gas were expelled from existence (Gabriel, 2018). Therefore, the expenses of different items increment at the expense of oil and gas. This makes it critical to control the expense of oil and gas to guarantee that the costs of different merchandise and enterprises are lessened or kept ideal (Bhardwaj, 2013).

3.2 Evaluation of How the Theoretical Framework Evolves from the Literature Review

The stakeholder and the theoretical legitimacy frameworks can be traced directly from the literature review. The implication is that the social theories that underline the SED reporting practices by the Nigerian oil industries evolve from the literature review, which incorporated 57 articles. The theoretical insight that the annual SED reports, which are published by the Nigerian oil industries, are mainly targeted to meet the needs of the external stakeholders, including the host communities supported by the findings from prior empirical studies such as Odera, Scott and Gow (2016) as well as Sani (2018). A considerable number of the literature articles reviewed highlighted the connection between the SED reporting practices and the desire to meet the informational needs of the other external stakeholders, such as the host communities.

The social legitimacy theoretical framework also seems to evolve from the literature review insight, primarily based on the study by Duff (2016). According to the stated article, contemporary corporate organisations are beginning to appreciate issuing regular SED reports to portray a socially responsible image to the public. The socially accountable image/reputation will likely enhance their market share and strengthen their market position. Therefore, the theoretical framework that guides the present study appears to evolve directly from the literature review insight.

3.3 Adapted Theories for This Study

For many years, many studies have focused on companies' interaction with society, especially regarding the nature and extent of their voluntary or involuntary disclosures (Uwuigbe and Jimoh 2012). Most of these studies have emphasised voluntary disclosure and have tried to investigate the nature and patterns of corporate social and environmental exposures (CSED). Other empirical studies have focused on examining the determinants of CSED in terms of company size, profits, and industry affiliation (Zeng et al., 2010). According to Oba et al. (2012), many businesses operate within a framework of social systems. Thus, despite the limited obligatory requirements for reporting, existing literature on corporate social disclosures suggests that many organisations in developed economies carry out corporate social responsibility disclosures of their activities differently. To explain the different nature of reporting, various theoretical frameworks have emerged mainly to clarify why most organisations may decide to provide voluntary disclosure.

In their article, Gamerschlag et al. (2011) categorised a lot of existing empirical research literature, particularly on corporate voluntary environmental reporting, into two overlapping theoretical frameworks: stakeholder theory and legitimacy theory. To Gamerschlag et al. (2011), the two theories often take a system perspective. They seek to recognise that business organisations constantly interact with their environments and affect entities far beyond their artificial boundaries. According to Uwuigbe et al. (2011), these theories should not be viewed merely as competitive explanations but as a way of understanding the varying organisational factors at the different resolution levels.

3.4 Legitimacy Theory

According to Legitimacy theory, the degree and different forms of corporate social disclosure in the annual report are directly related to the management's perception of the local community (Uwuigbe and Egbide 2012). To Uwuigbe and Ajibolade (2013), the theory helps analyse an organisation's corporate behaviour within the existing environment. In other words, legitimacy is fundamental to organisations and constraints that are often imposed by social norms and values, and reaction to such restrictions offers the focus of interest for analysing the firm's behaviours that have been taken concerning its environment.

According to legitimacy theory, Oba et al. (2012) observe that business organisations always seek to ensure that they strictly operate within the community's specified bonds and norms. Society expects business organisations to make necessary outlays that aim to prevent or repair any destruction to the environment and provide a measure to safeguard the overall health and security of their customers, workers, and those residing in communities where the company is located. In their seminal work, Uwuigbe and Jimoh (2012) argue that legitimacy is regarded as a generalised perception or even assumption that corporate actions remain desirable, proper and appropriate within the existing socially constructed beliefs, values, and norms and even definitions. Thus, organisations' responsibility is to establish congruence between their internal social values as portrayed in their daily operations and the patterns of good behaviour in the broader social system in which they operate.

This theory also defines a professional and social structure where organisations are bound by the social contract in which the organisation's consent to perform different socially wanted activities as a result of the endorsement of its targets and different prizes, and this at last ensures it proceeded with existence (Tilling, 2018). It features the degree to which corporate social and ecological divulgences are affected by the limits built up by the public with the end

goal to be valued and abstain from being punished by the network in which the organisation works. Despite over 50 years of oil creation in the Niger Delta which holds 95 per cent of its oil resources, Nigeria's key oil-delivering district has stayed subject to broad defilement and severe underinvestment. Because of endemic government defilement and monetary botch, oil incomes have not entirely added to the nation's open assets for framework or social arrangements. The Niger Delta remains one of the nation's poorest and most immature districts.

Similarly, numerous people need a fundamental framework, including running water, power and solid medicinal services (Hussin et al., 2013). As needs are, indigenes of Nigeria's key Niger Delta oil-creating area have long felt that they have been abused and shunned by the Abuja government and have not profited from the nearness of oil in the district ("Once Again" 2017). Besides, disdain towards remote oil organisations that have collected billions in benefits from oil generation in the Niger Delta and broad natural harm caused by oil spills has finally prompted the foundation of the infamous Niger Delta activist gatherings. Uncalled for dispersion of oil riches and wrecking ecological damage are the two fundamental reasons aggressor bunches give for waging war against the administration and oil organisations.

The requirement for vitality and the related financial advantages from the oil and gas stores mainly found in the Niger Delta district of Nigeria required the investigation and misuse exercises being conveyed by the oil industries. Be that as it may, these investigation and misuse exercises, due to their eccentric nature, have tremendous potential for ecological contamination that has been knowledgeable about the frame of oil slicks, gas flaring, flighty transfer of waste and a few different exercises that have brought about the ecological corruption of the Niger Delta area (Bayagbon, 2011). Notwithstanding, this examination work that is gone for assessing the effect of the natural insurance strategies in upstream oil

and gas exercises in the Niger Delta area included surveys and interviews. The meeting was completed to give pertinent criticism on evaluating the effect of natural assurance arrangements on the upstream oil and gas exercises in their operational zones/have networks.

3.5 Stakeholder Theory

The theory has been built around hierarchical administration and business morals that tend to ethics and qualities in dealing with an association ("What is Stakeholder Theory" 2018). The partner's procedure incorporates both an asset- and market-based view and includes a socio-political level. One regular adaptation of the partner hypothesis looks to characterise an organisation's partners and afterwards inspect the conditions under which administrators regard these gatherings as partners. According to the Oil and Gas Journal (OGJ), Nigeria positions among the best ten countries in demonstrated oil and flammable gas saves worldwide. The substitution proportion reflects the degree to which Nigeria has pushed the store's crunch to go back in time and the readiness to remain a practical player in the worldwide oil and gas industry for a considerable time to come (Iledare, 2007). The maintainability of oil business condition contrasts positively and the worldwide proportion over a similar period, indicating that the oil industry standpoint in Nigeria is extremely powerful. The primary marker with a massive dread is the high rate at which recoverable oil holds in Nigeria are being removed. Nigeria is separating its oil in abundance from many world stores (Ka, 2018). Although the essential concentration in this position paper is on monetary frameworks outline and Organisation of the Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPEC) enrolment issues, other industry issues and concerns are likewise quickly evaluated, including asset proprietorship, good indigenous investment, human and institutional improvement, and subsidising choices for the joint endeavour activities.

A critical problem to the advancement of the business is administrative vulnerability, the absence of access to data. In 2008 the Federal Government, as part of its motivation for change, set out on a complete lawful system. The purpose of the change was to rebuild the oil and gas industry, solidify laws' establishment, and increment government take and nearby substance necessity (Oilprice, 2017). This exertion was the Petroleum Industry Bill (PIB), sent to the National Assembly. The critical goals of the bill included, among others, the administration and assignment of oil assets and their derivatives in agreement with the standards of good administration, straightforwardness, and the sustainable improvement of Nigeria (Otiotio, 2018). Its entry has been slowed down as promising as it appeared because of resistance from the international oil companies (IOCs). The administration of the National Assembly had additionally guaranteed a fast bill entry.

The Niger Delta's rough treatment has networks against worldwide oil organisations (IOCs) that are wild and relentless. The viciousness that happens is hurtful to networks, people, and oil organisations that give a specific monetary security level to the locale. The Nigerian government faces a noteworthy test of settling network brutality in Nigeria (Vaughan, 2011). This contextual analysis utilised the social trade hypothesis to comprehend better the causes and results of the absence of network trust against the oil organisations in the area. Host group doubt and viciousness against oil organisations is an issue in Nigeria (Awogbade et al., 2017). The worldwide oil organisations (IOCs) are moving without end to the costlier profound water adventures. Oil organisation specialists express dread of host network doubt and viciousness against the oil organisations. The host networks endure under development and are not enabled (Amabipi, 2016). The Nigerian government couldn't give any arrangement, an enormous number of oil fields is still shutting down, and neither the administration nor the oil organisations could return to these fields because of dread of

network doubt and savagery against the oil organisations. The requirement for a deliberate report is to give an enduring arrangement.

On the other hand, stakeholder theory believes they require their stakeholders' support for organisations to operate constantly. Therefore, based on this, the organisation's management should seek their approval, and its activities must be adjusted to get that approval (Uwuigbe and Jimoh 2012). To this extent, the company must continuously improve and adapt to the stakeholders' will. To Russo and Perrini (2010), this theory assumes that corporations' social and environmental disclosure is always due to the pressure emanating from the stakeholders, including customers, society, workers, the physical environment, suppliers, and the shareholders. The theory is founded on the premise that organisational ability to attain its objectives is dependent entirely on the appropriate management of the relations with its stakeholders (Lyon and Maxwell 2011). Thus, corporate social responsibility (CSR) is the most suitable way to ensure that the organisation shows an excellent image to its stakeholders to strengthen the relationship and boost profits.

Even though legitimacy theory is most commonly used in providing explanations about business social and environmental disclosures based on empirical evidence that organisational management employs legitimising plans, the same is not valid for stakeholder theory, particularly in third world countries such as Nigeria (Deegan 2014; John 2011.; Uwuigbe and Jimoh 2012). The recent civil unrest incident witnessed around the Niger Delta in Nigeria, as cited by Uwuigbe et al. (2011), points to the contemporary organisational neglect that has continued to cripple industrial operations.

It is worth pointing out that the existing empirical evidence shows that CSED practices by organisations vary from one country to another. The difference is even significant between companies in developing countries and those in more developed nations (Oba et al., 2012;

Mahadeo et al., 2011). Besides, some differences exist in reporting relative to the specific industry or sector to which an organisation belongs. In a survey conducted by Roca and Searcy (2012) on CSED practices by companies in developed nations, much focus is given to human resource management issues. Arguably, there is considerably limited disclosure on sensitive topics such as trade union activities, redundancy schemes, costs and even pay awards.

In a report on global trends in CSED reporting, Burritt and Schaltegger (2010) observe that most companies usually provide separate annual reports showing their corporate responsibility and sustainability levels. Most of these reports published annually are stakeholder-linked, often depicting the organisation's plans, policies, and strategies for implementing corporate sustainability measures. According to Uwuigbe and Uadiale (2011), business organisations derive numerous benefits such as improved public perception, increased returns on investment, and increased shareholder value from such reports.

Besides, corporate social responsibility reporting may also enable the company to track its progress against the specified social and environmental targets through proper information relay. In a developing country such as Nigeria, corporate social responsibility reporting is vital for an organisation to sustain its operating license from the business community and society (Mahadeo et al. 2011). Uwuigbe and Jimoh (2012) observe that this is attributed to the tendency where business organisations with higher levels of CSED are associated with the view that they operate within the stipulated standards of honesty and transparency, especially in their management of environmental issues and information sharing.

Multiple studies conducted in the past have suggested that environmental disclosure is targeted at the pacification of different stakeholders (Osazuwa et al., 2016, p. 22). According to Freeman and Reed (1983), stakeholders are interested in the actions of a company (p.89).

He further refined his definition in a subsequent 1984 study where he defined stakeholders as any individual/group with interest in a company because they can affect the firm and affect them (Freeman, 1984, p. 17). Carroll (1999) defines stakeholders as persons or groups who may influence or be influenced by an organisation's activities, choices, policies, practices, or objectives (p.270). Stakeholder relationships can be recognised based on their claims' validity (Dibia & Onwuchekwa, 2015, p. 147). Shareholders, creditors, management, workers, customers, suppliers, local communities, and the public are stakeholders.

According to the theory, a firm responds to influential stakeholders' concerns and expectations and among these responses are strategic disclosures. The rationale for selecting this theory is to provide insight into the factors that motivate managers' behaviour tied to companies' SED practices and how the Host community perceived SED activities in the Nigerian oil industry. Therefore, the managers' motivations and other behaviours, including factors that affect these behaviours related to SED, were identified through the theory.

The stakeholder model is a paradigm that analyses how corporations include social and environmental problems into their business processes and stakeholder associations. The research demonstrates how this concept is employed as the primary framework for evaluating social and environmental disclosure in the oil business (Aminu, 2015). Analyzing organizational behaviour through the lens of Stakeholder Theory has proven to shed light on numerous SED complexities. For example, the function of the industry is to establish the bounds of abstract concepts such as corporate social responsibility and efficiency (Sujin, 2019). Furthermore, the model elucidates the relationship between managers' significance allotted to the demands of specific stakeholders and the behavioural norms of organizations that are both more environmentally conscious and better in terms of sustainable growth

(Office, 2016). Therefore, the stakeholder model analyses how corporations include problems into their operations and stakeholder relationships.

One of the essential theoretical foundations in the study's assessment is Stakeholder Theory. Evaluating social information disclosures by the oil companies through their relationships with their relevant parties has raised issues, such as the limited utility of environmental information freely disclosed by large companies in their annual report to stakeholders. However, it has also helped explain various other issues (Sujin, 2019). Moreover, there is still plenty of potential for developing a sufficiently rigorous theoretical framework to describe the firm's relationship with its stakeholders (Sujin, 2019). Therefore, stakeholder theory was essential in the framework's foundations.

Stakeholder theory is reinforced by legitimacy theory in the oil industry's SED framework. The intersection of these ideas emphasizes the industry's desire to be seen as acting within the restrictions and standards of the communities in which it operates (Esposito et al., 2021). Essentially, this increases the requirement for interaction regarding the oil company's social and environmental transparency. In addition, legitimacy theorists claim that a firm would go to any length to legitimize its actions to stay in business (Office, 2016). Consequently, legitimacy theory broadens the scope of stakeholder theory to include more than just public expectations of duty. It also invests in a legitimization procedure, ensuring that the firm's actions comply with social norms by different stakeholder groups (Sujin, 2019). Thus, legitimacy theory broadens the scope of stakeholder theory, emphasizing the industry's desire to be seen as acting within the restrictions and standards of the communities it operates.

3.6 The Justification for Adopting Stakeholder Theory

The primary justification or rationale for using the stakeholder theory as the primary theoretical framework in this study is its clarity in depicting the relationship between SED reporting practices and the desire to attain the host communities' social welfare needs or interests. The stakeholder theory is grounded on the idea that contemporary corporate entities recognise other external stakeholders, such as the host communities, as critical as business owners (Huang & Kung 2010). Therefore, the stakeholder theory was considered an essential theoretical framework that clearly describes the connection between the oil industries' social and environmental disclosure (SED) practices and the different needs of the host communities, customers, and governmental agencies.

The other rationale for using the stakeholder theory is a comprehensive theoretical framework that takes a multi-perspective view of firm value creation. The traditional shareholder theoretical framework is based on the idea that value creation by a company mainly targets maximising shareholder wealth at the expense of social welfare needs (Huang & Kung 2010). However, the contemporary stakeholder theory assumes that corporate entities create value for all key stakeholders, including the host communities, instead of considering the interests of only the stockholders. In this study, the stakeholder theory was deemed ideal for depicting how the issue of annual SED reports by Nigerian oil industries is expected to benefit all the key stakeholder groups, including the host communities, government agencies, suppliers, and customers.

Furthermore, the stakeholder theory is justified because it has become a key pillar for studying corporate citizenship and business ethics. The fact that the stakeholder theory emphasises the consideration of the needs/interests of all stakeholders rather than the business owners indicates that corporate entities are now becoming aware of the importance of being

socially responsible corporate citizens. Certain SED reporting aspects, such as the need to limit the oil explorations' negative environmental impacts and set aside substantial CSR budgets to support the community, are considered crucial pillars in business ethics, closely connected to the stakeholder theory.

3.7 Conclusion

Stakeholder Theory, in summary, is one of the essential theoretical underpinnings in the study's evaluation. Examining social information disclosures by oil industries through their interactions with relevant parties has highlighted concerns, such as the limited value of environmental data given by big corporations in their annual report to stakeholders. It has also aided in the explanation of several other situations. Furthermore, the relationship between legitimacy and stakeholder theory holds that for organisations to run continuously, they need the support of their stakeholders. To this end, the organisation must constantly improve and even adapt to the wishes of its stakeholders. As a result, corporate social responsibility (CSR) is the most effective strategy to ensure that the company presents a positive image to its stakeholders to develop relationships and increase revenues. As a result, the organisation's management should seek their approval, and its operations should be altered to obtain that acceptance.

CHAPTER FOUR: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

4.1 Introduction

The thesis investigates social and environmental disclosure (SED) practices among Nigerian oil Industries. This thesis relies on primary data analysis (Interview) and secondary data analysis (Content Analysis) from annual SED reports published by the Nigerian oil Industries. The three main objectives of the primary qualitative research are as follows. (1) To identify the motivations for social and environmental disclosure in the Nigerian oil industry. (2) To investigate the perceptions of host communities on the SED reporting practices of the Nigerian oil industries. (3) To discuss the challenges faced by the Nigerian oil industry in developing and promoting SED. The two objectives (Quantitative content analysis research) are restated as follows. (4) To examine the scope of SED among Nigerian oil industries. (5) To examine the differences in SED reporting practices between the Nigerian domestic and international oil industries.

Figure 4.1 Diagram Showing the Breakdown of Primary and Secondary Research Method Approaches.

Sources: Diagram created by Charles Atang 2018

The methodology chapter describes how the research study collects the primary and secondary data based on a mixed research design approach. In addition, this chapter also describes the thematic and content analysis to facilitate the attainment of the research

objectives/questions. This chapter discusses the research methods and procedures that the researcher used in the thesis. Precisely, this chapter is divided into sections and sub-section as follows: Section 4.2 comprises the Research Design with its Sub-Section, which includes: - Pragmatism Psychological stance, Research Philosophy, Different Types of Philosophy Position, Justification for the use of Pragmatic Research Philosophy, Study Zone of Thesis, Thesis Population and Sample, Judgmental Sampling and the Characteristics of Judgmental Sampling. Section 4.3 explains the Primary Data Collection Design that elaborates the research methodology for collecting the interview data. Section 4.4 discusses the Primary Research Data with its Sub-Section, which includes: Interviews, Interview Sample selection, Descriptive: Interviewees Sample Structure, Qualitative Data Analysis, Data coding for qualitative analysis, Unit of Analysis for Qualitative data, Quality of primary data (Interview) and the Reliability and Validity of Interview.

Section 4.5 explains the Secondary Research Objective, which examines the Scope of SED in the Nigeria Oil Industries. Section 4.6 explains Secondary Data Design with its Sub-Section, which includes: Data Collection Design, Sample Design, Content Analysis, Data Analysis, Data Coding for Quantitative Analysis, Data Analytical Tools, Component of Analysis for SED Quantity, Quantity of Annual SED Reports, The Quality of SED, Quality in Annual SED Reports, Social and Environmental Disclosure Categories, Validity and Reliability of Content Analysis. Section 4.7 described the Differences in SED Reporting between International and Domestic Oil Companies with Sub-Section, including Differences in SED Reporting, Relative Analysis of Differential Reporting on SED, Data Analysis Tools, and SED Index. Section 4.8 explains the Ethical Consideration with its Sub-Section Ethical Issues and Principles, and Section 4.9 describes the Conclusion of the chapter.

4.2 Research Design

The research design refers to the blueprint for conducting research and contains the methods and procedures employed in data collection and analysis. According to Aburaya (2012), discussing the thesis's theoretical framework is vital in determining the research methodology and selecting an appropriate research design. The thesis examines social and environmental disclosures in the Nigerian oil industry. The primary research question answered during this investigation is to describe the causes of social and environmental exposures in the Nigerian oil industry. Besides, five research objectives will be accomplished using qualitative and qualitative techniques. The identification of SED motivation in the Nigerian oil industries and the discussion of challenges the Nigerian oil industry faces in developing and promoting SED will be conducted using qualitative research. Likewise, the perceptions and the association of host community members on the disclosure of SED in the Nigerian oil industry will be investigated through qualitative analysis. Similarly, a quantitative approach will be performed to examine the scope of the social and environmental disclosure in the Nigerian oil industry and the difference between domestic and international oil companies concerning the disclosure of SED information to various stakeholders. A mixed research design that entails both the quantitative and qualitative approaches will be used.

According to Creswell & Creswell (2017), this technique includes gathering, evaluating, and combining quantitative and qualitative data in a single study to give a deeper understanding of the research topic under consideration. To this end, the rationale for using a mixed research design assumes that neither quantitative nor qualitative methods are enough to provide a thorough approach to comprehending a research problem's existing trends and details (Bryman 2015). However, when used in combination, the two research methods complement one another to provide for a more robust analysis of the situation, taking

advantage of the strength inherent in each approach. Thus, the technique was deemed fit since it would allow the researcher to gain a depth understanding as well as corroboration while at the same time offsetting the weaknesses inherent in adopting each method independently.

A mixed research design has been successfully used in previous different studies. In a similar study, Bayoud, Kavanagh, and Slaughter (2012) adopted mixed research methods to investigate factors influencing corporate social responsibility disclosure (CSR) in Libyan companies. From their study, the quantitative outcome showed that the company's age and industry type had a significant positive relationship with the levels of companies' CSR. On the other hand, the study's qualitative findings revealed a significant positive association between all factors that influence levels of CSR used in the research and the level of CSR commitment by the Libyan firms (Bayoud, Kavanagh, and Slaughter 2012). While the method's contextual application may vary depending on the nature of the study, mixed research design effectively delivers conclusive findings (Bryman 2015). Besides, it provides the possibility of triangulation, allowing the researcher to investigate aspects of the phenomenon under study more precisely by approaching it from different vantage points utilising various techniques and methods.

4.2.1 Pragmatism Stance

The thesis will also adopt a pragmatism stance to provide a vibrant fusion of the two approaches (Qualitative and Quantitative) as well as a basis for the adoption of the mixed research methods as a third alternative should the researcher establish that neither of the methods could offer enough findings to the subject matter under investigation (Bryman 2015). According to Bryman (2006), the pragmatic stance has been used in research to provide a common ground and some level of compatibility in cases where the adopted method sought to challenge the conventional sterile and unproductive aspect of dualism

inherent in some philosophies of research. Both primary and secondary data sources will be used in this investigation. Different secondary data sources will be reviewed for quantitative data collection, such as the annual reports of 18 oil companies sampled from the Nigeria oil industry and the Nigeria Stock Exchange.

According to Binh (2012), secondary data sources are defined as the sources previously gathered and studied by scholars during primary investigations. These sources provide authentic and valuable information for the given topic that can be used while organising results and drawing conclusions. Besides, yearly reports of the sampled organisations from the Nigerian oil sector will be reviewed. For this purpose, a comprehensive examination of annual reports for eight years published from 2011 to 2018 will be performed due to the recent rise of awareness and interest in CSR. These reports will be accessed from the official websites of selected companies, and their information on the increase in awareness and interest in CSR will be helpful in this study.

In addition to the quantitative approach, data for qualitative research will be collected from primary data sources such as field, raw data collected using semi-structured interviews of SED experts and professionals working in the Nigerian oil sector and host community's member within the Nigeria oil industries. The motivation behind choosing interviews as the preferred method for primary data collection is that they enable the researcher to elicit reliable and the latest information about the subject matter and closely analyse both subject and the situation to which the interviewees respond to the question (Creswell & Creswell, 2017).

The interview will be conducted mainly for the heads of departments of the sampled companies and leaders within the host communities to ensure the information's accuracy. Besides, an interview of the people responsible for the different departments in the organisation would provide a rich blend of views on the company's responsibility to both

social and environmental aspects of their existence and operation. The researcher will conduct a one-to-one interview using structured topic guide questions on two target groups: (1)—Oil Company, which consists of Company Management and their Employees. (2). Host Communities consist of: - Community Leader, Community Youth Leader, Community Resident, Church Leader and Academician within the target company area.

Four companies will be selected from the sampled eighteen oil firms for the interview. In contrast, each two of the oil companies will be international oil company, and the other two will be domestic (Local) oil companies; these Oil companies will include: Shell Petroleum Development Company (SPDC), located in Warri, Delta State, Nigeria (International); Exxon Mobil (Mobil Producing Nigeria Unlimited), Eket, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria (International); Nigeria LNG Limited (NLNG) in Bonny Island, River State, Nigeria (Domestic) and Bayelsa Oil Company, Yenagoa, Bayelsa State, Nigeria. (Domestic). The four companies were chosen based on their different geographical locations in various states, enabling the researcher to gather information from varied social and environmental settings.

4.2.2 Research Philosophy

Research philosophy is a dominant belief held by a researcher on how data for the research should be collected, analysed, interpreted and applied to address a specific research problem or issue (Creswell 2014). According to Zukauskas (2017), research philosophy in scientific and social research captures a system of researchers' thought processes, which leads to the generation of new knowledge related to the research topic. The implication is that the research philosophy is an important concept that guides or provides a framework for data collection, analysis, interpretation, and application of the findings (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill 2016). Zukauskas (2017) also contends that a research philosophy provides the

basis for selecting the best research strategy, research problem formulation, data collection, and analysis to answer a research question.

4.2.3 Different Types of Philosophical Position

Four (4) leading philosophical research positions in scientific and social research guide the formulation of research strategy, research problem, data collection, and analysis (Akaranga & Makau 2016). These four research philosophies include pragmatism, realism, positivism, and interpretivism philosophy. The research philosophy usually reflects critical assumptions held by the researcher, which serve as the basis for formulating the research strategy. The four research philosophies are briefly described in this subsection of the methodology chapter.

1. Pragmatism Research Philosophy

The pragmatism research philosophy is based on the facts and assumes that the most appropriate research strategy should be guided by the formulated research problem (Zukauskas 2017). The pragmatism philosophy grants researchers the freedom to adopt the most suitable research study framework, data collection and data analysis design that best facilitates the attainment of their needs or the research aims. The insight based on Creswell (2014) indicates that followers of the pragmatism philosophy do not view the world as an absolute unity. The implication based on the pragmatism research philosophy is that the researchers should use multiple research methods/designs to answer a specific research question (Zukauskas 2017). The pragmatism research philosophy was considered the most ideal and consistent for this study, given several aspects briefly described in the final subsection of the methodology chapter.

2. Positivist Research Philosophy

The positivist research philosophy assumes or underlying belief that can effectively objectively understand social phenomena (Zukauskas 2017). The insight also informs the positivist philosophy that a researcher is an objective data analyst and should dissociate from the personal subject views, which are not supported by scientific facts. This research philosophy contrasts with the interpretive view, which allows the researcher to incorporate personal or subjective ideas concerning a given research topic (Sekaran & Bourgie 2016). Generally, the positivist philosophy is highly structured, uses a large data sample, and primarily uses quantitative data analysis approaches.

3. Interpretivist Research Philosophy

The interpretive research philosophy assumes that one can effectively understand social research phenomena interpreted in a subjective approach (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill 2016). This means that, in contrast to the positivist research philosophy, the researcher is not restricted to facts or objective information but can apply personal views or insights to answer the research questions. The interpretivism research philosophy focuses on how people experience the social world (Zukauskas 2017). The interpretivism philosophy is ideal in research studies involving a small sample, which requires qualitative data analysis approaches (Creswell 2014).

4. Realist Research Philosophy

The realist research philosophy combines the principles of positivist and interpretive philosophies (Zukauskas 2017). This research philosophy assumes that it is the nature of human beings to incorporate both a subjective and objective view of a given social phenomenon. The implication is that the research method chosen to analyse the problem must

fit the subject matter. A researcher using the realism philosophy can incorporate their own subjective opinion or apply objective facts depending on the research aims.

4.2.4 Justification for the use of the Pragmatic Research Philosophy

The pragmatic research philosophy (stance) is considered most appropriate for this research study because the specific research objectives guided the mixed research design (using primary and secondary research). For instance, the primary research based on the interview was considered ideal for collecting qualitative data on the host communities' views and perceptions of the SED reporting practices undertaken by the Nigerian oil industries. On the other hand, content analysis of the SED reports was necessary to facilitate the assessment of the determinants of social and environmental disclosures among the Nigerian oil industries.

The pragmatic stance is appropriate because it can view social and environmental disclosures from multiple perspectives (Sani 2018). Therefore, analysis of the scope of SED and the hosts' perceptions of the social and environmental disclosures by the Nigerian oil and companies can be effectively undertaken using both an objective and subjective approach. The causes of SED were analysed using descriptive and inferential analytical tools (quantitative, objective facts). At the same time, the host communities' perceptions of the SED reporting practice among the Nigerian oil and gas firms were undertaken using thematic analysis of the interview transcripts (subjective). Creswell (2014) notes that researchers adopting the pragmatic stance do not view the world as a unity but as an integration of various facets of life.

4.3 Study Zone of Study (South-South Region of Nigeria)

Nigeria's south-south region was mainly formed because of the amalgamation of the Eastern and Western areas over five decades ago (Craggs & Neate 2018). The implication is that the

region was formed from the Niger-Delta states, making it six states within the area, including Akwa Ibom State, Bayelsa State, Cross River State, Delta State, Edo State, and Rivers State. Although, the Nigeria Government drew three states from the Eastern region to form part of the south-south states. Historically, the south-south in Nigeria, endowed with natural resources such as oil and gas reserves, is considered multi-ethnic (Udotong et al., 2017). The daily output of around 1,9 million barrels makes Nigeria Africa's top oil producer and the world's 13th largest.

Additionally, according to the International Energy Agency, Nigeria possesses the second-largest proven oil reserves in Africa and the tenth largest globally. Despite widespread corruption, insurgency, oil disasters, and oil theft, Nigeria's petroleum sector remains the country's most important export and source of foreign earnings. According to Sylvester Asenguah in 2017, the South-South area of Nigeria contains six states. It is strategically positioned where the Y tail of the Niger River meets the Atlantic Ocean through the Gulf of Guinea (Sylvester, 2017).

Nigeria's economy relies heavily on oil despite being a relatively small area. In addition to oil and gas, the region is rich in other essential resources, including tourism and agriculture, which provide considerable investment prospects.

Figure 4.2 South-South Region in the Nigeria Map

Sources: Charles T. Atang

4.4 Thesis Population and Sample

The thesis also targeted understanding the perception, motivation, and challenges the host community faced towards the oil Industries to explain the SED practices. Interviews were used to collect data to determine their perceptions and experiences of these companies' environmental performance and accountability. This interview will be conducted based on HC's perception and opinions of the oil companies' behaviour regarding selected social and environmental factors. These interviews will provide personal views of organisational heads and their employee regarding social and environmental existence and operation and their responsibilities in their respective corporations.

The secondary data gathered information from the eighteen Nigeria registered oil companies between 2011 and 2018. A comprehensive list of 281 oil companies' records was obtained from the Department of Petroleum Resources, Lagos State and the internet. Data on SED are unmatched between reports of different years or companies in the same sector (Jenkins &

Yakovleva, 2006, p. 275). The investigation of SED vigorously showed the development of the nature, content, and style of reports, whether there were reliabilities in development across companies and future reporting inferences. Secondary data were obtained through Nigeria Stock Exchange (NSE), Companies' Annual Reports, which include:- Annual Reports, Corporate Governance Section, Notes to the Account, CSR Report, Financial Statements Report, Director's Report, Abridged Report, Environmental Report, Social Report, Annual Report and Accounts, Climate Report, Sustainability Report, and Internet web pages. Thirteen oil companies were listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange as well as an additional five non-listed major oil companies (Shell, Exxon Mobil Chevron. Bayelsa Oil Company and Nigeria Liquefied Natural Gas (NLNG)) were preferred as samples because of the scale of their operations in the Niger Delta (Aaron, 2008). It was accessible and available to assess online through the oil company's annual reports, Nigerian Stock Exchange.

4.5 Judgmental Sampling

Sampling is essential to any research design because it allows for selecting and analysing a subset of the study population (Creswell 2014). In most research studies, the selection and analysis of data from the entire population are impossible due to time and cost constraints (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill 2016). However, even though sampling saves on time and cost, the most crucial aspect is that the sample selected should represent the population the researcher drawn in terms of its characteristic (Knapik 2006). In this thesis, the researcher employed a critical sampling approach when selecting the 28 interview respondents from the target population of stakeholders for the Nigerian oil industries.

Moreover, for the secondary data (content analysis), the research sampling entailed using a judgmental sampling design, which involves selecting research subjects (unit of analysis)

based on the researchers' prior knowledge and experience (Knapik 2004). According to the critical sampling approach, a sample of 18 Nigerian oil Industries was selected. After that, the researcher retrieved the annual SED reports for each of the 18 Nigerian oil Industries. The researcher collected the annual SED reports to cover eight years, from 2011 to 2018.

A judgmental sampling, sometimes called purposive sampling, is a non-probability-based approach where the researcher selects the interview participants based on their expert knowledge of the research subjects (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill 2016). The judgmental sampling approach was justified because the stakeholders selected must be knowledgeable in matters associated with the SED practices implemented by the Nigerian oil and gas firms. According to Creswell (2014), a critical sampling approach is ideal when only a limited number of respondents with the attributes desired by the researcher.

According to Jokovich (2013), judgmental sampling involves choosing the most favourite subjects to provide the required information relevant to the study. Thus, in the present context, the judgmental sampling method is preferred over other sampling methods because it would allow the researcher to base the sample for the study on the specific company attributes relevant to the subject matter under investigation. In this sense, therefore, the researcher only chooses those companies whose characteristics form the population's best representative. The preference of these companies is driven by their size, performances, and nature of their production processes, which directly influence social lives and the environment, the nature of their waste disposals, the extent of environmental pollution, and their market capitalisation.

4.5.1 Characteristics of Judgmental Sampling

In this thesis, the main characteristic of the subjects is that they must have knowledge and experience of the social and environmental disclosure (SED) policies/practices adopted by the Nigerian oil industries. The other justification for using judgmental sampling is also based on the need for accuracy regarding the research findings. Frey (2018) contends that the judgmental sampling approach is most suitable where the researcher needs to lower the margin of error associated with the research findings. Besides, the judgmental sampling approach was appropriate given the time and cost constraints faced by the researcher and the movement restrictions in some states due to the Covid-19 pandemic. The judgmental/purposive sampling approach is ideal when the research faces time-constraint issues, requiring reliance on the researchers' knowledge when selecting the study sample (Frey 2018).

As part of the judgmental sampling, the researcher was guided by his knowledge, experience and instincts when selecting the interview respondents. Specifically, the respondents' knowledge of the SED practices associated with the Nigerian oil and gas firms, leadership attributes, charisma, and personalities informed the study sample selection based on the judgmental sampling approach. For instance, senior managers and experienced employees working in the Nigerian oil and gas firms were given preference during the sample selection process. However, for the other stakeholders (community leaders, church leaders, youth leaders, residents, and academicians), the focus was mainly on recruiting experienced and older respondents. This sampling strategy explains why 64% of the respondents were aged 40 years and above, with only 36% less than 40 years old.

The other characteristic in selecting the judgmental sample is that the respondents must be Nigerians familiar with the social and environmental disclosure issues related to the local and international oil firms operating in the country. The knowledge of SED practices and policies, including the social welfare benefits and environmental damages associated with the Nigerian oil industries, was paramount in selecting participants. The implication is that one of the attributes of the participants is that they must have been affected in one way or the other by the oil extraction/production processes associated with the Nigerian oil Industries. The other characteristic considered when selecting the judgmental sample is that the respondents must be either internal or external stakeholders of the Nigerian oil Industries. These internal or external stakeholders must be managers and employees of the oil Industries or the host community members who can be categorised explicitly as community leaders, youth leaders, church leaders, community residents and academicians.

Finally, the other important attribute of the purposive sample participant is that a respondent must be physically accessible to be involved in the face-to-face interview. The semi-structured interview was organised as a face-to-face interview with the respondents required to be physically present. This sample attribute explains why it was impossible to collect the views/opinions of a manager and employee from the Shell Petroleum Development Company (SPDC) located in Delta state and a manager and employee from the Nigeria LNG Limited located in River state.

The researcher preferred the judgmental sampling approach due to its several benefits compared to other probability-based sample selection techniques. Firstly, as noted earlier, the judgmental sampling technique has substantial time and cost advantages because the researcher can select the sample and collect data within a short period (Creswell 2014). The judgmental sampling approach is also productive because it allows the researcher to directly

address subjects in the target population, improving the findings' accuracy and saving time. The purposive sample selection approach is ideal because the researcher can generate immediate or real-time results on the research topic of interest (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill 2016).

However, despite its numerous strengths, the judgmental sampling approach is susceptible to the risk of bias, which might adversely affect the reliability of findings. However, to address the risk of bias in the judgmental sample selection, the researcher selected an equal number of respondents from each of the four Nigerian states except Delta state and River state, where there were five stakeholders due to the inaccessible two managers and two employees because of the current Covid-19 pandemic.

SECTION 1: INTERVIEWS

4.6 Primary Research Design

4.6.1 Introduction

In SED, interviews are the most significant source of qualitative data. According to Easterby-Smith et al. (2002), interviews are one of the most effective ways to collect qualitative data. According to Deegan & Blomquist (2006), a better way to acquire data is to ask the connected persons directly, rather than relying on secondary data sources like interviews. To facilitate the selection of participants from the selected Nigerian oil industry, the researcher would depend on suggestions from firms, company management, company workers, community leader, community youth leader, church leaders, academicians, community residents, and community connections. To set up the interviews, the researcher will contact the participants.

At the beginning of the interview, participants will be introduced. The purpose of the research will be explained to them. Every participant will be asked to present themselves and their position afterward. When the respondents felt it was required, further explanation may be provided, allowing for better judgments regarding SED. In addition to conducting interviews, the interviewer might also do follow-up interviews. After conducting the interviews, the interviewer could unexpectedly observe nonverbal indications, such as facial expressions, tone of voice, and body language. Interviews showed used face-to-face for data collection as they permitted the probing of the respondents' perceptions of the interviewees' oil companies. The interviews were semi-structured, allowing standardisation and flexibility in responding and the development of unpredicted themes. The semi-structured interviews allowed examining the degree of understanding of the issues under discussion and further probing unclear responses. The indicators of the pressures on the locals were collected for disruptions of oil operations, hostage-taking, social unrest, and protests.

4.6.2 Primary Data Collection Design

The data for the primary research component of the study was collected using a semi-structured interview approach. A semi-structured interview is a direct data collection approach in which the interviewer does not rely solely on a formalised list of interview questions (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill 2016). Under the semi-structured interview approach, even though the interviewer follows a structured set of questions, there is considerable leeway for the interviewer to deviate from the list of questions and pose open-ended questions (Creswell 2014). One of the main strengths of the semi-structured interview approach is that it allows the interviewer or researcher to assess the respondents' feelings and beliefs related to a specific research topic of interest (Knapik 2006). Besides, the semi-structured interview approach allows the interviewer to delve into personal and sensitive issues that the respondent might not have divulged based on the structured interview approach (Creswell 2014).

The other justification for using the semi-structured interview approach is that the primary data collection technique allows the interviewer and the respondent to seek clarification if the formalised questions or the response from the interviewee is not straightforward. However, the risk with using a semi-structured interview approach is that if employed by a less experienced researcher, the interviewer might deviate substantially from the research topic (Knapik 2004). This research addressed the stated risk because the interviewer is an experienced researcher aware of the need to stick to the research topic during the interview.

The semi-structured interview comprised 24 respondents comprising Nigerian oil firms' managers and employees, community leaders, youth leaders, community residents, church leaders, and academicians. The initial expectation of 28 respondents was targeted, which

seven interviewees from each state of the four Nigerian states, including Akwa Ibom State, Bayelsa State, Delta State and Rivers State) would be subjected to a semi-structured interview to assess their views on the SED practices by Nigerian oil industries. However, because of the Covid-19 pandemic, which created movement restrictions in some states, the researcher was not able to schedule an interview audience with a manager and employee from the Shell Petroleum Development Company (SPDC) as well as a manager and employee from the Nigeria LNG Limited (NLNG). The face-to-face interview with the four stakeholders (two managers and two employees) from the Nigerian oil companies was impossible because most were working remotely from home. Therefore, the semi-structured interview was organised and conducted with only 24 out of the expected 28 stakeholders. The researcher showed the transcription of the semi-structured interview data related to the 24 respondents in the appendix section of this research thesis.

The interview guide included a list of vital structured questions and open-ended questions posed to the 24 respondents/stakeholders. The researcher organised the semi-structured interview into three main sections, which were generally the same for each interviewee. The researcher incorporated a preliminary/background section to collect respondents' demographic information regarding age, gender, educational level, marital status, position in the company, years of working experience, and the respondent state.

- The first section of the semi-structured interview consisted of questions that sought to assess the respondents' views on what motivates them to be interested in the SED information published by the Nigerian oil industries. When evaluated from the company management and employee perspective, the questions in this section evaluated review sought to ascertain what inspires the Nigerian oil industries to publish regular SED reports. However, from the other stakeholders' perspective, questions in this section evaluate what motivates respondents (i.e., community

leaders, youth leaders, residents, church leaders, and academicians) to read the annual SED reports published by the Nigerian oil industries.

- The second section of the semi-structured interview asked respondents questions about their perceptions of the SED practices undertaken by the Nigerian oil industries. This section focused on how the stakeholders viewed Nigerian oil and gas firms' social and environmental disclosure practices.
- The final section of the semi-structured interview consisted of a set of questions that asked respondents their views on the challenges that have adversely the ability of the Nigerian oil industries to publish annual SED reports consistently.

The researcher considered the specific set of interview protocols when conducting the face-to-face interview with the 24 respondents. First, the researcher was required to greet the interviewee and introduce himself to the respondent. The interviewee was also briefed on the details related to the research topic and subsequently provided with the participant information sheet and a proper consent form to append their signature as evidence of approval to partake in the interview. Furthermore, as part of the interview protocol, each interview was supposed to take a maximum of 1 hour, depending on the interviewees' willingness to divulge additional information. At the end of the interview, the researcher must debrief the respondent on the next course of action and whether they would access the study findings. Finally, the interviewer makes thank-you remarks to the interviewee for taking the time to participate in the interview.

4.6.3 Interview Sample Selections

Interviewees were selected for interviews in their host communities (HCs) due to their convenience and readiness. Firstly, in Akwa Ibom State, the researcher conducted interviews

in Eket Local Government Area (LGA) for one Community leader and one Academician, Ibeno LGA for one Community Youth Leader, Esit-Eket LGA for one Community Resident and Onna LGA for one Church Leader. However, in Bayelsa State, the researcher conducted interviews in Sagbama Local Government Area (LGA) for one Community leader, Ekperi-Ama, Nembe LGA for one Community Youth Leader, Okutukutu, Yenagoa LGA for one Community Resident, Opolo, Yenagoa LGA for one Church Leader and Otuoke, Ogbia for one Academician.

Moreover, in Delta State, the researcher also conducted interviews in Utagba-Uno, Ndokwa West Local Government Area (LGA) for one Community Leader, Ovade, Ogahara, Ethiope West LGA for one Community Youth Leader, Ughelli South LGA for one Community Resident, Warri North LGA for one Church Leader and Ododegho, Ughelli North LGA for one Academician. Finally, in Rivers State, the researcher conducted interviews in the Oropotoma Kingdom, Elemenwo and Rumuola in Port-Harcourt LGA for one Community Leader and one Academician, Akuku-Toru LGA for one Community Youth Leader, Ogoni Khana LGA for one Community Resident: and Obio/Akpo LGA for one Church Leader.

All the Interviewees above were invited to answer questions concerning their perceptions and their association with SED disclosure by the Nigerian oil industry. All the interviewees, as mentioned earlier, were asked about their perceptions of SED disclosure by the Nigerian oil sector and their associations. On the other hand, Community Leaders were expected to have a basic understanding of their communities' well-being, issues, and objectives and be able to reply to the interview questions in general. Community residents were interviewed to examine their leaders' perceptions and whether they are at the same level as their community leaders towards their challenges and goals. The researcher also conducted interviews at Exxon Mobil (Mobil Producing Nigeria Unlimited), Eket, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, for one

Company Management and one Company Employee. In Bayelsa Oil Company, Yenagoa, Bayelsa State, Nigeria, the researcher interviewed one Company Management and one Company Employee.

The outcome of the thematic analysis, which was performed in NVivo version 12 qualitative data analysis software, relies on the interview transcripts from seven (7) stakeholders drawn from each of the four Nigerian states of Akwa Ibom State, Bayelsa State, Delta State and Rivers state. The seven stakeholders include company management, company employees, community leaders, youth leaders, church leaders, community residents, and academicians. The initial plan was to have 28 participants (N = 28), with seven interviewees drawn from each of the stated four Nigerian states.

However, due to current Covid-19 restrictions and the 'work at home' orders, the researcher couldn't gain access/ audience from the remaining stakeholders: company management and employees. Therefore, only two company management and two company employees could participate in the interview. Specifically, one Company Management and one Company Employee from Exxon Mobil Company and one Company Management and one Company Employee from Bayelsa Oil Company were able to participate in the study. Therefore, given that the researcher did not find the required employees and managers from Delta State and Rivers State, the implication is that only five participants each were drawn from the states. Seven participants were sourced from the Bayelsa and the Akwa Ibom states. The affected companies that the researcher could not get an audience for interviews due to pandemics were Shell Petroleum Development Company (SPDC) located in Warri, Delta State, Nigeria (International Oil Company) for one Company Management and one Employee then Nigeria LNG Limited (NLNG) in Bonny Island, River State, Nigeria (Domestic Oil Company) for one Company Management and Company Employee.

Table 4.1 Evidence of interviews Conducted

S/N	Codes	Date	City/Town	Duration
AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA				
1	Company Management 1	07/05/2019	Exxon Mobil, Eket	29.19Mins
2	Company Employee 1	07/05/2019	Exxon Mobil, Eket	27.33Mins
3	Community Leader 1	26/04/2019	Eket LGA	15.14Mins
4	Community Youth Leader 1	24/04/2019	Ibena LGA	24.48 Mins
5	Community Resident 1	09/05/2019	Esit-Eket LGA	28.27 Mins
6	Church Leader 1	26/04/2019	Eket LGA	35.14 Mins
7	Academician 1	25/04/2019	Eket Academician	23.18 Mins
BAYELSA STATE, NIGERIA				
1	Company Management 2	03/05/2019	Bayelsa Oil Company, Otiotio	28.42Mins
2	Company Employee 2	03/05/2019	Bayelsa Oil Company, Otiotio	38.39Mins
3	Community Leader 2	03/05/2019	Sagbama LGA	35.56 Mins

4	Community Youth Leader 2	03/05/2019	Ekperi-Ama, Nembe LGA	46.08 Mins
5	Community Resident 2	02/05/2019	Okutukutu, Yenagoa LGA	43.31 Mins
6	Church Leader 2	03/05/2019	Opolo, Yenagoa LGA	27.50 Mins
7	Academician 2	03/05/2019	Otuoke- Ogbia LGA	28.08 Mins
DELTA STATE, NIGERIA				
1	Community Leader 3	04/05/2019	Ndokwa West LGA	25.03 Mins
2	Community Youth Leader 3	08/05/2019	Ethiope West LGA	21.12 Mins
3	Community Youth Leader 3	08/05/2019	Ughelli South LGA	28.25 Mins
4	Church Leader 3	03/05/2019	Warri North LGA	20.16 Mins
5	Academician 3	04/05/2019	Ughelli North LGA	29.10 Mins
RIVERS STATE, NIGERIA				
1	Community Leader 4	01/05/2019	Eelenwo LGA	21.28 Mins
2	Community Youth Leader	01/05/2019	Akuku-Toru LGA	28.18 Mins

	4			
3	Community Youth Leader 4	01/05/2019	Ogoni Khana LGA	16.49 Mins
4	Church Leader 4	01/05/2019	Obi -Akpor LGA	25.04 Mins
5	Academician 4	01/05/2019	Port-Harcourt LGA	23.09 Mins

4.6.4 Descriptive: Interviewees Sample Structure

The descriptive insight related to the sample constituent (profile) is essential in providing the participants' demographic information, which can facilitate data analysis (Rourke & Anderson, 2004). Information on sample composition is necessary to assess the extent to which the sample represents the broad subject population of interest (Creswell, 2014). Besides, the descriptive statistical information on the sample composition can also highlight whether the model is biased. This subsection presents the participants' sample profile outcome based on their educational profile, marital status, age, and gender orientation.

- Gender and Marital Status

The insight from the review of the participant's characteristics based on gender indicates that the sample was biased in gender orientation. The justification for the stated conclusion is that all the 24 stakeholder participants were male, with no female included in the sample. The central reliability and risk issue associated with the stated sample design is that the participants' perceptions of social and environmental disclosures are likely to be biased towards the views most associated with males (Saunders, Lewis & Thornton, 2016).

However, to address the stated sample design limitation, Table 4.2 and Figure 4.4 indicate that majority of the interviewees were married. Specifically, 75% of the participants reported being married, while only 25% were single. This means that the participants' perceptions, views, attitudes, and experiences incorporated in the study are likely to capture the consideration of family issues such as children's education, health, and environmental conservation to maintain resources for the future generation.

Table 4.2 Sample Structure Based on Interviewees Gender Profile and Marital Status

Gender	Number	Percentage
Male	24	100%
Marital Status:	Number	Percentage
Single	6	25%
Married	18	75%

Figure 4.3 Sample Structure Based on Interviewees Marital Status

- **Age**

The sample constituent information based on the participants' age profile is presented in Table 4.3 and Figure 4.5 below. The sample characteristic in terms of age shows that most of the subjects selected to partake in the interview were aged 41-50 years (33%), followed by those 31-40 years (29%). This means that approximately 62% of the sample was composed of individuals between the age of 31-50. The implication is that the sample was collected from experienced stakeholders likely to have considerable exposure to social and environmental issues. Sekaran and Bourgie's (2016) insight indicates that older participants in any research study tend to possess considerable experience articulating the various problems about the research topic. The sample composition in terms of the age profile also shows that 13% of the interviewees were aged between 71-80 years, while individuals aged 51-to 60 also constituted 13% of the sample. The sample composition descriptive based on age indicates that 61-70 years (4%) and 20-30 years (8%) were the least represented in the age profile.

Table 4.3 Sample Structure Based on Interviewees Age

Age	Number	Percentage
20-30 Years	2	8%
31-40 Years	7	29%
41-50 Years	8	33%
51-60 Years	3	13%
61-70 Years	1	4%
71-80 Years	3	13%

Figure 4.4 Sample Structure Based on Interviewees Age

- **Educational Status**

The interviewees' educational level also plays an efficacious role in highlighting the extent of knowledge, experience, and views on various research topics of interest (Creswell, 2014). The sample configuration based on their educational status is presented in Table 4.4 and Figure 4.6. The results show that 42% of the interviewees who participated in the study reported having a master's education level. In comparison, 38% of the participants had a bachelor's degree level of education.

Therefore, considering the single participant who had a PhD degree, the implication is that our sample was composed of highly educated individuals. The expectation is that the participants' insightful views will capture a considerably higher level of knowledge and expertise concerning social and environmental disclosure practices among the Nigerian oil industries. According to Kelley, Clark, Brown and Sitzia

(2003), one of the good practices in selecting a highly informative sample is to consider the participants' educational levels. The descriptive show's insight shows that only 8% of the sample participants reported having a certificate level of education. A similar 8% (N = 2) reported holding a higher national diploma educational level.

Table 4.4 Sample Composition Based on Participants Educational Status

Degree	Number	Percentage
Certificate	2	8%
Higher National Diploma	2	8%
Bachelor's Degree	9	38%
Master's Degree	10	42%
PhD Degree	1	4%

Figure 4.5 Sample Structure Based on Participants Educational Level

The descriptive information on sample attributes is expected to be efficacious in analysing the implication of the participants' views, attitudes and perceptions, which tend to vary depending on demographic characteristics. Therefore, the thematic analysis outcome's synthesis is expected to draw insightful references to the dominant participants' attributes to understand their views on SED practices among Nigerian oil industries.

4.6.5 Qualitative Data Analysis

Qualitative data analysis challenges because the information or interview responses are available in non-numerical formats (Frey 2018). The stated attribute of qualitative data implies that the risk of inaccurate and biased data analysis due to the subjectivity attribute of qualitative data is likely to be high. Therefore, as part of qualitative data analysis, thematic analysis was selected to analyse the transcribed interview responses of the 24 respondents. Thematic data analysis is the most objective method of analysing qualitative research data, available in texts (i.e., interview transcripts) and visuals (Nowell, Norris & White, 2017). Using the thematic data analysis, the researcher identifies common themes and broad subject matters from texts and visuals. The implication is that using either inductive or deductive reasoning, the researcher identifies a standard set of themes from the ideas and patterns displayed in the interview transcripts (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill 2016).

The thematic data analysis approach is conducted based on six (6) steps: familiarisation, coding, theme generation, theme review, theme definitions, and presentation of the broad thematic subjects associated with the research topic (Nowell et al., 2017). The thematic coding and theme generation are the two most important and equally challenging steps in the 6-step thematic analysis process. The thematic coding and theme generation steps create a challenge because of the risk that two researchers might develop different sets of research

themes from the same interview transcripts, thereby creating subjectivity and bias in the qualitative data analysis (Sekaran & Bourgie 2016).

There are several advantages and justifications for using thematic analysis as a qualitative data analysis approach. Firstly, thematic analysis is considered appropriate in analysing qualitative data, available in textual or visual formats that cannot be reliably analysed using statistical tools (Nowell et al., 2017). The second justification and advantage of using thematic data analysis is its flexibility in exploring a vast amount of qualitative data. The implication is that the researcher is not restricted by any factors when identifying and generating broad themes from the interview transcripts (Creswell 2014). Thirdly, thematic data analysis is considered an evidence-based approach because primary data supports the broad research themes. However, despite its suitability for analysing qualitative data, thematic analysis is considered very subjective, primarily when conducted by a less experienced researcher (Nowell et al., 2017).

The subjectivity aspect of thematic analysis clarified that two researchers could develop different research themes using the same interview transcripts (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill 2016). Besides, thematic analysis can take some time to analyse data, primarily where the transcribed interview responses are not organised well. In this research, thematic data analysis was possible because the researcher managed the research interview transcript data file regarding the 24 interviewees who participated in the interview. The researcher used the NVivo statistical software to analyse, identify and generate broad themes and sub-themes from the interview transcripts.

As a qualitative statistical data analysis tool, NVivo is ideal for generating broad themes and sub-themes which effectively answer the research questions or facilitate the attainment of the research aim. These broad themes and sub-themes captured the main idea, insight, and views

of the interview respondents. The thematic data analysis approach was carried out using the grounded theory approach, which means that the key themes and sub-themes consistently aligned with the study's three research objectives/questions. The implication is that the researcher generated several broad themes and sub-themes to capture the host community's perception of the SED practices, motivations for SED and challenges faced by the Nigerian oil industries in providing social and environmental disclosure (SED) annual reports.

For instance, eleven (11) sub-themes were consolidated to capture this study's three research objectives/questions. The broad themes and sub-themes included 'alignment to community development projects', 'community welfare', 'SED benefits and damages' (motivations for SED), 'responsible corporate citizens', 'community involvement', 'social and environmental issues', and 'communication on SED policy' (perceptions on SED), 'SED policies', 'interaction with communities', 'community support', and 'funding' (SED challenges). The findings from the thematic data analysis approach were prepared using tabular and visual formats. For instance, based on the word frequency cloud (minimum length = 4 letters), the results of thematic coding were presented using tables and figures, prepared in MS Word and MS Excel spreadsheet tools. The researcher also presented visuals consisting of screenshot pictures of the NVivo qualitative data analysis results because of the structure in which the themes and sub-themes were performed as part of the thematic data analysis.

4.6.6 Data Coding for Qualitative Analysis

The data coding for the qualitative analysis was conducted in NVivo version 12 statistical software. Specifically, each of the 24 interview transcripts was imported into NVivo software for data coding and analysis. The data coding for the qualitative research was designed. The researcher assigned each of the three (3) broad themes (i.e., perception of SEDs, motivation

for SEDs and challenges for SED implementation) to a unique node in NVivo. After that, using the interview transcript texts, 3-4 sub-themes (sub-codes) were derived based on the frequency of appearance of the sub-themes from the analysis of the readers. As shown in Exhibit 2, the researcher recorded the number of reference sources associated with each coded theme and sub-theme to indicate the themes' significance. For instance, the 'Perception on SED' broad theme was coded. It had four (4) sub-themes related to 'community involvement', 'communication on SED policy', 'responsible corporate citizens, and 'social and environmental issues". The researcher traced all the themes and sub-themes derived from the data coding in NVivo statistical software to the interview transcript texts. Relationships in the coded theme are presented using the word frequency maps and tables.

4.6.7 Unit of Analysis of Qualitative Data

The integral unit of analysis in this qualitative research design consisted of the Nigerian oil industries. The focus was on the SED practices undertaken by the Nigerian oil and gas firms. The unit of analysis for the qualitative interview data consisted of the human subjects/interviewees who were critical internal and external stakeholders of the Nigerian oil industries. In primary or secondary research design, a unit of analysis is an entity, including individuals, groups, or organisations that form a significant research study subject (Frey 2018). The data was collected based on the interview, which included 24 interviewees classified into seven major groups with managers and employees of the Nigerian oil industries from the four Nigerian states, including - Akwa Ibom State, Bayelsa State, Delta State and Rivers State. In addition, as part of the unit of analysis for the qualitative interview data, the interviewees were also classified into external stakeholders: community leaders, church leaders, community youth leaders, community residents, and academicians. These

interviewees formed a fundamental unit of analysis for the qualitative interview data that guided findings related to the qualitative research design.

4.6.8 Quality of Primary Data (Interview)

The researcher consistently maintained the quality of the primary interview data throughout the interview and transcription of the interviewees/ responses. Firstly, to guarantee the quality of the interview data, the researcher was required to be knowledgeable and experienced in analysing and synthesising the primary interview responses. Secondly, the researcher consistently maintained the quality of the interview data because the semi-structured interview questions were pilot tested before being applied for the interview (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill 2016). The researcher's sensitivity to the social relations with the subjects was also considered part of the strategy to enhance the interview quality. Furthermore, the researcher was made aware of the need to minimise exposure to research bias and consider the ethical considerations in the research.

4.6.9 The Reliability and Validity of Interviews Data

The reliability and validity of the primary research design were guaranteed by ensuring that only accurate interview responses were captured and recorded by the researcher. For instance, applying the semi-structured interview approach was expected to clarify those interview responses, which were either unclear or ambiguous. The researcher also maintained the reliability of the qualitative interview data through the critical sample selection approach, which mainly recruited interview participants who were highly knowledgeable in the research topic of interest (Kelly, Clark, Brown & Sitzia 2003). In addition, the researcher also maintained the validity and reliability of the interview data by ensuring that the data

transcription process was as accurate as possible. Specifically, the researcher used automated data transcription tools to minimise errors during the transcription process.

The validity of the semi-structured interview questions was also guaranteed by testing the formal set of interview questions to ensure no leading questions or ambiguous questions that do not align with the research topic of interest. In the primary research, the questionnaire and interview instrument's design are vital for maintaining the validity/reliability of the responses (Creswell 2014). There is considerable evidence that a poorly designed primary data collection instrument is likely to create partial and inaccurate responses that might affect the validity and reliability of the research data (Knapik 2004; Knapik 2006).

SECTION 2- CONTENT ANALYSIS

4.7 Secondary Research Design

4.7.1 Data Collection Design

The data for the secondary research was mainly collected using information presented in the SED annual reports related to a sample of 18 Nigerian oil Industries. The secondary data collection design incorporated a strategy to attain data triangulation given the multitude of information on the Nigerian oil Industries' social and environmental disclosure practices. Triangulation is an approach to data collection which relies on multiple data sources to analyse a research phenomenon or problem (Creswell 2014). The other justification/basis for using published secondary data (SED annual reports) to investigate the research problem is justified by its low cost and time convenience when assessed against the analysis of primary research data (Knapik 2006). The insight based on Saunders et al. (2016) indicates that compared to the preliminary data collection design, the secondary data collection approach is less expensive because the researcher relies on existing data which has already been collected.

This publicly available published data implies that the researcher does not need to spend considerable time searching for the information. However, the main challenge with the published secondary data is that its reliability might be adversely affected when the source or publisher modifies the information to suit their objective (Creswell 2014). The researcher mainly collected annual SED reports from the websites of the 18 Nigerian oil Industries and the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE) and the oil companies' annual reports. In some oil Industries that operate in Nigeria, the SED reports are included as part of the annual reports. In contrast, in other oil Industries, the SED reports were included as part of the annual sustainability reports. The SED reports present information on the Nigerian oil Industries'

social welfare, environmental and energy conservation practices over a given period, mostly one year (12-month).

4.7.2 Sampling Design

Eighteen Oil companies were chosen, and out of the 18 sampled oil industries, thirteen (13) were listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE). At the same time, the remaining five were Nigeria's domestic and international oil companies that operate in the country but are not listed on the Nigeria Stock Exchange. Exhibit 14 in the appendix presents a list of the sampled 18 oil Industries that serve in Nigeria. The thirteen listed Nigerian oil industries include Anino International Plc., Capital Oil & Gas Plc., Conoil Plc., and 11 Plc. Total Nigeria, Caverton, Eterna, Ardova Plc, Japaul Oil & Maritime Services, MRS Oil Nigeria, Oando, RAK Unity Petroleum, and SEPLAT Petroleum Development.

On the other hand, the five (5) remaining oil companies include SPDC, Exxon Mobil, Chevron and Bayelsa Oil Company and NLNG (Domestic Oil Companies); these five oil companies are not listed on the Nigeria Stock Exchange. The primary justification for using a judgmental sample to select the 18 oil and gas firms is that these firms are the best performing in the country. Furthermore, the Judgmental sampling of the 18 chosen Nigerian oil firms is justified because these firms have publicly available SED annual reports, annual reports and yearly sustainability reports etc. The implication is that it was much easier to access the annual reports, which contain the selected sample's social and environmental performance information. The reports were also acquired from the Nigeria Stock Exchange (NSE), the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) and the Oil Companies. The selected companies are shown in the table below.

Table 4.5 Sampled Companies in The Nigerian Oil Industry

S/No	Company Name	Representation	Status in Nigeria Stock Exchange (NSE)	Operational Status	Incorporation Date	Company Location Site for study in Nigeria
1	Shell Petroleum Development Company (SPDC).	International	Non- Listed	Operational	1937	Warri, Delta State, Nigeria
2	Exxon Mobil	International	Non- Listed	Operational	1955	Eket, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria
3	Chevron Nig.	International	Non- Listed	Operational	1913	Lekki, Lagos State, Nigeria/
4	Total Nigeria PLC	International	Listed	Operational	1956	Lagos State, Nigeria
5	Bayelsa Oil Company	Domestic	Non- Listed	Operational	2000	Yenagoa, Bayelsa State, Nigeria
6	Nigeria Liquefied	Domestic	Non- Listed	Operational	1989	Nigeria LNG Plant Complex,

	Natural Gas (NLNG)					Bonny Island, Rivers State, Nigeria www.nlng.com
7	Oando PLC. Lagos State, Nigeria.	Domestic	Listed	Operational	1956	Lagos State, Nigeria
8	Caverton Offshore Support Group, Lagos State, Nigeria.	Domestic	Listed	Operational	2008	Lagos State, Nigeria
9	Ardova PLC formally called Forte Oil PLC. Lagos State, Nigeria.	Domestic	Listed	Operational	1964 by the British Petroleum Nigeria Limited	Victoria Island, Lagos State, Nigeria
10	11 PLC	International	Listed	Operational	1907- Socony Vacuum Oil 1951- Mobil Oil Ltd 1971- Mobil Oil Ltd	Apapa, Lagos State, Nigeria

					2017-11 Plc	
11	Conoil PLC	Domestic	Listed	Operational	Founded in 1927 and was incorporated in 1984	Lagos State, Nigeria
12	RAK Unity Petroleum Company PLC.	Domestic	Listed	Operational	1982	Lagos State, Nigeria
13	Capital Oil & Gas LTD.	Domestic	Listed	Operational	1985	Lagos State, Nigeria
14	Mrs Oil Nigeria LTD	Domestic	Listed	Operational	1969- Texaco 2019- Mrs Oil Nig.	Lagos State, Nigeria
15	Eterna PLC, Lagos state, Nigeria	Domestic	Listed	Operational	1989 and commence business in 1991 then re-registered as a public limited	Lagos Nigeria

					company in 1997	
16	Anino International PLC.	Domestic	Listed	Operational	1981	Victoria Island, Lagos State, Nigeria
17	Japaul Oil & Maritime Services plc	Domestic	Listed	Operational	1994	Ikeja, Lagos State, Nigeria
18	Seplat Petroleum Development	Domestic	Listed	Operational	2009	Ikoyi, Lagos State, Nigeria

Source: Researchers sample selected from NSE/Annual Report. Company-profile and google search

Table 4.5.1 Thirteen Companies Listed on The Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE)

S/N	INDUSTRY	NSE LISTED
1	Anino International Plc.	LISTED
2	Capital Oil & Gas Ltd.	LISTED
3	Conoil Plc	LISTED
4	11 Plc	LISTED
5	Total Nigeria	LISTED
6	Caverton Offshore Support	LISTED
7	Eterna	LISTED
8	Ardova Plc	LISTED
9	Japaul Oil & Maritime Services	LISTED
10	MRS Oil Nigeria	LISTED
11	Oando	LISTED
12	Rak Unity Petroleum	LISTED
13	Seplat Petroleum Development	LISTED

The selected sampled companies shown in the table above display the 18-oil industries used for this research, of which 13 of the said companies are listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE). At the same time, the other five, which include: - Bayelsa Oil Company, Chevron Nigeria Limited, Nigeria Liquefied Natural Gas (NLNG), Exxon Mobil, and Shell Petroleum Development Company of Nigeria, are non-listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange.

However, 13 companies in the sampled oil industry are primarily involved in Marine Logistics/transportation services and jet fuels, manufacturing & marketing of petrochemicals such as (gasoline, motor oils, lubricant), production, Offshore Vessels Owning & Chartering, Dredging & Reclamation Works, Pipeline/Flowline Constructions, Repairs, dealer-assisted/developed retail outlets Mining, Equipment Fabrication, Leasing and Repairs These companies include Capital Oil & Gas Ltd, 11 plc (Mobil Oil Nigeria Plc.), Ardova Plc, Total Nigeria Plc, Rak Unity Petroleum Company Plc, Eterna Oil & Gas Plc, Anino International Plc, Oando Plc., Seplat Petroleum Development, Japaul Oil & Maritime Services, Bayelsa Oil Company, Nigeria Liquefied Natural Gas (NLNG) and Caverton Offshore Support Group Additionally, MRS Oil Nigeria Plc, which happen to be an African multinational company and one of the largest downstream companies in Nigeria, includes four Africa countries which are: Benin, Cote D'Ivoire, Cameroon, and Togo and Conoil Plc involved in the downstream petroleum industry.

Furthermore, three companies in the sample oil industry, including SPDC, Exxon Mobil and Chevron Nigeria Ltd, are involved in oil and gas exploration. Production SPDC(Shell) is the country's first-born oil establishment in Nigeria, followed by Exxon Mobil (Mobil Producing Nigeria Unlimited MPN Operation) and Chevron, a subsidiary of Chevron Corporation which functions mainly in the onshore and near-offshore areas of the Niger Delta region.

4.7.3 Content Analysis

Content analysis is comprehensively used to examine disclosure practices It is a research technique that makes valid and replicable inferences from information depending on its context. Content analysis is the process of making conclusions according to objective coding of information It collects and organises data Either deductively or inductively, it can be

employed When the frame of analysis was operational based on previous knowledge and the study's rationale, which was connected to theory testing, deductive content analysis was practical (Kyngas & Vanhanen, 1999) The inductive data technique changes from a specific to a generic approach Specific examples are therefore studied and integrated into a generic statement (Chinn & Kramer, 1999) Due to a lack of preceding research, this study relied on inductive content analysis.

To critically explore the Social and Environmental Disclosures in the Nigerian Oil Industry, the research will use a sample of eighteen (18) out of 281 companies in the oil sector of the economy which thirteen (13) are listed the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE). Their annual report These firms will be chosen for the study because it was readily available to access their annual disclosure reports since this is a requirement for all companies listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange. Eighteen companies will be chosen from the population of 281 major oil companies using the judgmental sampling method. The preference of these companies is driven by their size, performances, and nature of their production processes, which directly influence social lives and the environment, the nature of their waste disposals, the extent of environmental pollution, and their market capitalisation.

Finally, annual reports were used as they included social and environmental information. The analysis was limited to company reports as these were the primary documents used by companies to present information. Communication studies conducted in the past also used such reports hence allowing the making of comparisons the general measurement of SED, and specifically in AR, is indefinite critics have shifted their attention to SED quality since companies insist on the news, which favours their image resides, these critics do not consider such companies prosecuted because of infringement (Deegan & Gordon, 1996).

4.7.4 Data Analysis

Data from annual corporate reports and the NSE within the eight years was cleaned and coded for interpretation and analysis. The researcher utilised the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23 to analyse the gathered information. Further, content analysis was adopted for analysing the data collected from corporate reports; the NSE The content analysis report is appropriate as it is orderly and impartial (Dong and Burritt 2010) Also, the method eases the systematic classification and comparison of SED in different companies, which is vital in establishing trends. The approach has been used in other multiple studies in the area (Zeng et al. 2010, Mahadeo, Oogarah-Hanuman and Soobaroyen 2011, Uwuigbe and Uadiale 2011) and has proven to be effective. For instance, Unerman (2000) examined the adoption of content analysis in the investigation of social and environmental accounting (SEA) and established that minimum attempts had been made towards integrating the methodology to understand the various aspects of the SEA.

The secondary data consisting of the SED annual reports for the 18 oil Industries that operate in Nigeria was analysed using content analysis. The content analysis is a qualitative data analysis approach which identifies certain words, themes, or concepts in a qualitative document containing texts (Elo et al., 2014). Using content analysis, the researchers can deduce meaningful inferences from the relationship between words and fundamental concepts as presented in the qualitative text document The content analysis provides a systematic and objective approach to describing a research phenomenon (Schreier 2012) A essential aspect of content analysis as a qualitative data analysis tool is that it can reduce texts into key concepts that describe a specific research phenomenon by identifying relevant conceptual frameworks (Elo et al., 2014) In content analysis, the most crucial stage in the deduction of meaning from the qualitative texts relates to the abstraction phase, which captures the process

that created the key concepts. The researcher can use both deduction and induction reasoning to undertake qualitative content analysis (Schreier 2012) effectively.

There are several advantages associated with qualitative content analysis. Firstly, content analysis can be applied to draw key concepts and meaning from a voluminous qualitative document, which might not be possible using quantitative statistical tools or the narratives approach (Elo et al., 2014). Secondly, as a qualitative data analysis tool, the content analysis provides the most appropriate method of analysing insights into complex models of human thought process. Besides, the researcher applied content analysis in this research because it is less complicated and inexpensive than other primary data analysis techniques (Schreier 2012). The qualitative content analysis research design is also appropriate in this study because of its greater relevance and efficacy when integrated with other research methods such as interviews and observation (Elo et al., 2014). However, like the thematic data analysis approach, qualitative content analysis can be subjective, time-consuming, and susceptible to errors, mainly when relational data analysis is used (Schreier 2012).

In analysing the secondary data from the SED annual reports of the 18 Nigerian oil industries, the content analysis was used to identify key themes and concepts from the voluminous documents that covered the eight years from 2011 to 2018. Specifically, content analysis guided by the two research objectives/questions sought to identify SED determinants among Nigerian oil industries and assess the extent to which the SED practices of the local and international oil firms in Nigeria are different. For the first research objectives, the researcher applied content analysis to assess the frequency of relevant words or terms related to the disclosures on 'environment', 'energy', 'customers', 'community', and 'employee' for each oil industry over the period from 2011 to 2018.

For instance, to identify the frequency of disclosures on pollution for SPDC, which represents an environmental disclosure, the researcher counted the number of times that the word pollution or its synonyms appeared in the company's annual SED reports over the period 2011-2018. The frequency of words' appearance was presented both as counts and percentages. After that, descriptive statistical analysis using mean SED by size and component for each of the 18 Nigerian oil industries was computed to ascertain the determinants of SED among the oil industries that operate in Nigeria. The percentage disclosure for each of the five SED components (environment, energy, customer, employee, and community) was computed for the 18 Nigerian oil industries.

The researcher reduced the raw data on SED for the five components based on the Hackston and Milne (1996) model of SED reporting (environment, energy, customer, employee, and community). The researcher decreased the 18 oil and gas sectors firms to inferential statistical analysis. The inferential statistical analysis based on ANOVA and paired samples t-test used to compare the extent and quality of SED disclosure among the Nigerian local oil firms and the international oil firms. The inferential statistical analysis on the raw data drawn from the content analysis was appropriate for evaluating how the difference in SED reporting practices between the local and international oil firms is significant. The researcher used a 5% significance level to ascertain whether the difference in social and environmental disclosure among the local and international oil firms is statistically significant or not based on the ANOVA or the paired samples t-test.

Qualitative content analysis was the ideal tool for analysing the SED annual reports and annual sustainability reports because of their large volume. For instance, some of the international oil industries, such as Exxon Mobil, had over 50 pages of annual SED reports, covering the period 2011 to 2018. In addition, the qualitative content analysis also justified

the fact that the analysis of secondary data guided by the five SED components that captured environmental disclosure, energy disclosure, customer disclosures, employee disclosures, and community disclosures. However, as noted by Elo et al. (2014), the main challenge that encountered with the qualitative content analysis is that the data analysis approach is time-consuming given the need to count the frequency of words from the sizeable voluminous SED annual reports of the 18 Nigerian oil firms over the period from 2011 to 2018.

Descriptive statistical analysis was the primary data analysis approach applied to analyse SEDs' scope among companies that operate in the Nigerian oil industry. Specifically, means, standard deviations and percentage frequencies were computed to establish the composition of 'community', 'environmental', 'customer', 'employee', and 'energy' SEDs based on the review of the SED annual reports for the 18 Nigerian oil industries. Percentage frequencies were also used to report the composition of the five SED components among the top five oil industries within the sample and the remaining 13 oil industries. Linear regression analysis was also employed to analyse the scope of SED reporting among the oil companies that operate in Nigeria, and they are Shell, Exxon Mobil, Chevron Total and NNPC. The top five (5) oil industries which consist of international oil companies and the other 13 Nigerian domestic oil companies, will be analysed to give a better insight into the extent of SED in the Nigerian oil industries.

Therefore, using content analysis contributed to the corpus knowledge on using the method in understanding SEDs. The level of disclosure was determined regarding the number of disclosing sentences. This was preferred over the proportion of pages as it factored in the documents' print sizes (Zeng et al. 2010). Instead, the SED was determined based on four specific themes and founded on the operational definitions postulated by Hackston, and

Milnes (1996) as cited by Bìn (2012). The measurement instrument contained sixteen contents with four evaluable areas.

- Disclosure Themes: physical environment, firms' products, customers, societal involvement, and workers' welfare (Binh 2012).
- Disclosure Proof: monetary or non-monetary evidence and those declared by management (Bìn 2012).
- Type of Information: A positive, negative, and unbiased
- Source area of the report: Manager's declaration and processes, the perception, among others (Binh 2012).

To comprehend SED, the differences between domestic and international companies were investigated. The disclosure was classified based on whether it related to the environment, energy, customer, community, and employee disclosure. Descriptive analysis was used to compare their proportions. Following the content analysis. The Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) test was used to establish a significant difference in the levels of corporate social and environmental disclosures among the sampled firms.

4.7.5 Data Coding for Quantitative Analysis and Analytical Tools

Data Coding for Quantitative Analysis The data coding for the quantitative analysis is guided by the five SED factors associated with Hackston and Milne (1996). The implication is that using the qualitative content analysis, the focus was on establishing the frequency counts for each of the five SED components (i.e., community, environmental, energy, customer, and employee). Key sub-themes related to the five (5) coded themes on social and environmental disclosures were also derived from the coding process for quantitative analysis. For instance, the "environment" SED assigned the following sub-codes; 'pollution', 'ant-litter',

'wastes', 'awards', and 'waste recycling'. These sub-codes, which represented each of the five SED components, were searched and counted using the qualitative content analysis. In addition, 'quantified monetary', 'quantified non-monetary', 'narratives', and 'pictures' were derived to capture SED disclosures. Frequency counts on the number of these SED disclosures were recorded for each of the four (4) types of SED reporting.

This objective/question sought to evaluate the social and environmental disclosure scope among Nigerian oil companies. In attaining the first objective, the narratives (discursive) provided the primary data source of information analysed using content analysis. Specifically, using qualitative content analysis, the researcher generated key codes and themes through skimming the SED annual report documents of the 18 Nigerian oil companies. The narratives consist of texts, phrases, and keywords included in a SED annual report to convey the social and environmental disclosure (SED) performance the scope of SEDs in the Nigerian oil industry.

4.7.6 Component of Analysis for SED Quantity

A single unit of analysis is used in many contents analysis studies, usually the context unit for indices and the recording unit for volumetric studies. In particular, the context unit required the most care (Pattern & Crapton, 2004). The largest body of content that may be analysed establishes the nature of a recording unit in the context unit (Berelson, 1952). According to sentences, the justification of measurement relates to the fact that, first, sentences were perceived to be more accurate than words. Secondly, sentences conveyed meaning while the meaning of words was a problem. Thirdly, sentences overcame allocating portions of pages, thus removing the urge to give an account of the number of words.

Finally, counting sentences was more straightforward than relying on words (Hackston & Milne, 1996). As a result, sentences were picked because they were identifiable as a refined disclosure assessment. Milne and Adler (1999) found the same findings when calculating volume according to the page's percentage when measured in sentences. According to those who argued against using pages to measure, there would be differences across ARs when it came to page sizes as well as column and print sizes. According to Milne & Adler (1999), using pages to measure SED contributes to unneeded reliability. As a result, the number of pages and the number of sentences were used to estimate SED quantity in AR in two different units. Because of using these two distinct units, it was determined that their findings were identical.

4.7.7 Quantity of Annual SED Reports

The SED annual reports of the 18 oil and gas firms in Nigeria were analysed for the years 2011 to 2018. The implication is that for most of the sampled 18 oil industries, an average of 10 SED reports were subjected to content analysis to examine the fundamentals of social and environmental disclosures. Each annual SED report or annual sustainability report was also slightly voluminous with an average of 10-15 pages. This means that the SED annual reports were voluminous and extensive in size. The annual SED reports contained information on the oil firms' environmental conservation initiatives, social welfare and community development programs financed by the oil firms, customer disclosures, energy conservation, and employee welfare programs implemented by the Nigerian oil industries.

The information is presented in monetary quantified, non-monetary quantified, narratives format, and terms of visuals. A preliminary review of the content analysis indicates that 66%

of the SED annual report content consisted of the narratives or discursive, involving using texts to describe the organisations' social and environmental disclosures. The quantified monetary SEDs constituted 16.3% of the total SED contents of the 18 Nigerian oil industries. The quantified monetary SEDs included information on the dollar amount of the CSR budget or dollar expenditure on various social welfare and development projects financed by the Nigerian oil and gas firms. The quantified non-monetary (12.2%) and visuals (5.6%) were the least adopted forms of presenting the SED information based on the content analysis of the SED annual reports of the 18 Nigerian oil industries.

4.7.8 The Quality of SED and Annual Reports

To fully grasp the phenomena of SED, it is also necessary to measure the quality. It may be challenging to evaluate the quality of SED, and the techniques may lack impartiality, but they should be channeled together with the quantity for better comprehension (Hassan, 2010). There is a great deal of controversy regarding the definition of SED quality. According to the business definition of quality, qualified services and products fulfil the user's expectations in terms of their perceived quality. Quality of SED in this context, on the other hand, determines whether disclosure meets stakeholder expectations (Hassan, 2010).

Regarding quality, all the SED annual reports for the 18 sampled oil industries were highly reliable. To fully grasp the phenomena of SED, it is also necessary to measure the quality. It may be challenging to evaluate the quality of SED, and the techniques may lack impartiality, but they should be channeled together with the quantity for better comprehension (Hassan, 2010). There is a great deal of controversy regarding the definition of SED quality. According to the business definition of quality, qualified services and products fulfil the

user's expectations in terms of their perceived quality. Quality of SED in this context, on the other hand, determines whether disclosure meets stakeholder expectations (Hassan, 2010).

The other justification that explains the quality of the annual SED reports is that each document at least captured one aspect of the social and environmental disclosure as proposed by Hackston and Milne's (1996) model of SED. A standard SED report must grab at least one of the five (5) components of social and environmental disclosure (SED), including environment, energy, customer, employee, and community disclosure (Tagesson et al., 2009). The quality of the SED annual reports, which were subjected to content analysis, is justified because all the reports included a combination of the four (4) disclosure formats/types (i.e., quantified monetary, quantified non-monetary, narrative/discursive and pictures). This guaranteed the understandability of the SED annual reports from multiple perspectives. The quality of the SED annual reports was also enhanced because the researcher retrieved the report from highly reputable/reliable online sites (company websites) and data repository sites such as the NSE website.

The standard method that measures the quality of SED is disclosure information. Different ranking systems have been implemented to measure the quality of SED. These systems depict various scales that assess quality. A point scale system ranges from a 3-point scale system to a 7-point scale system. The difference in these ranking systems depends on the information that SED reports. A ranking system that consists of many points reduces the reliability in the measurement. Moreover; a ranking system that has many points also causes a more significant opportunity for subjective judgement. Therefore, using a ranking system with the lowest number of issues could yield reliable results. Therefore, this study investigated Hassan's (2010) measurement. This 2-point scale system assesses SED quality in AR, as observed below.

1: if SED looked at quantity and reported a company's activities regarding its environmental and social responsibility.

0: otherwise

There were five main reasons for choosing this measuring metric: A quantitative SED in AR, the disclosure of environmental and social policies, externally monitored SED, the amount of information accessible in the reports, and non-quantified information.

4.7.9 Social and Environmental Disclosure Categories

To get the precise SED measurement, it is essential to get a good definition of the SED categories. The literature points out four main themes for CSR. These themes include employees, natural environment, customers, and community (Grey et al. 1995b). Research has shown that Hackston and Milne (1996) produced a comprehensive index in the literature that explains the determinants of SED. They produced themes like customers, community development, employee, product, energy, and environment. Based on different studies, the categories of SED are shown in the table below. The five SED categories, which consist of health & safety, environment, corporate governance, employee and community, are also regarded as a method of measurement (Hackston & Milne, 1996, Ernst & Ernst, 1978).

Table 4.6 SED Categories

SED Categories
1 Environment
1-1 Environmental pollution
1. Preventing wastes
2. Receiving awards
3. Supporting anti-litter campaigns
4. Using materials sources efficiently in the process of manufacturing
5. Using recycled materials
6. Conserving natural resources
7. Preventing or repairing environmental damages
8. Complying with pollution regulations and laws
9. Pollution control
1-2 Aesthetics
10. Restoring historical structures/buildings
11. Contributing to beautifying the environment
12. Designing facilities that are harmonious with the environment
1-3 Other
13. Wildlife conservation
14. Undertaking environmental studies
2- Energy
15. Conserving energy
16. Energy policies
17. Receiving awards

18. Voicing the concerns of the company on energy shortage
19. Improving energy efficiency of products through research
20. Disclosing the increment in energy efficiency in products
21. Utilising waste materials to produce energy
3- Employee
3-1 Employee health and safety
22. Giving employees low-cost care
23. Conducting research that improves work safety
24. Establishing a safety policy/committee/department
25. Receiving a safety award
26. Complying with both health and safety regulations and standards
27. Accident statistics
28. Decreasing hazards in work environments
3-2 Employment of women or minorities
29. Disclosing about internal advancement statistics
30. Employing other special interest groups
31. Advancing minorities in workplaces
32. Establishing goals that represent minorities in the workforce
33. Employing or recruiting women and/or racial minorities
3-3 Employee training
34. Establishing trainee centres
35. Financial assistance
36. Using in-house programmes to train employees
3-4 Employee benefits/assistance

37. Providing recreational facilities/activities
38. Providing staff accommodation
39. Providing guidance or assistance to employees.
3-5 Employee remuneration
40. Policies of remuneration
41. Providing percentage figure and/or amount for taxes pay superannuation, salaries, and Wages
3-6 Employee profiles
42. Providing information regarding the qualifications of the recruited employees
43. Providing statistics per employee
44. Providing data on the number of staffs
45. Giving information on the disposition of staff 's
46. Number of employees
3-7 Employee share purchase schemes
47. Providing profit sharing schemes
48. Pension programme
3-8 Employee morale
49. Communicating with employees
50. Giving awards for effective communication with the employee 's.
51. Stability of the employees' jobs
52. Improving employee motivation and job satisfaction
3-9 Industrial relations
53. Industrial action
54. The relationship of the company with trade unions

3-10 Other
55. Statistics on the turnover of employees
56. Re-organising the company
57. Improving working conditions
4-Products
4-1 Product development
58. Information by research projects by the company aimed at improving its product 's.
59. Development expenditure
60. Developments in the products of the company
4-2 Product safety
61. Safety research
62. Improving the procedures of preparing and processing products
63. Safety standards of the products
5- Community development
66. Supporting government sponsored/national pride campaigns
67. Funding scholarship activities or programmes
68. Sponsoring educational conferences
69. Supporting medical research
70. Funding public health projects
71. Part-time or summer employment of students
72. Donating cash, employee services or products to support communities
73. Other special activities that are related to the community
6- Customers
74. Value added statement

8-Others
75. Corporate policies/objectives
76. Other

Source: From Hackston & Milne (1996)

4.8 Validity and Reliability of Content Analysis

Validity in content analysis refers to the degree to which the categories accurately represent the concepts on which they are founded. These describe how they came to be and quantify a notion (Wood & Ross-Kerr, 2010). Establishing a coding scheme throughout the study was the first step in ensuring validity (Potter & Levine-Donnerstein, 1999). Several critical features in the material were identified and formed inferences about the patterns of various parts.

4.9 Scope of SEDs in the Nigerian Oil Industry

The data analysis outcome based on the content analyst provides helpful insight into SEDs' scope in the Nigerian oil industry. The content analysis and the findings from prior empirical research indicate that community SEDs constitute the most considerable proportion of the social and environmental disclosure in the Nigerian oil and gas industry (Ekundayo, Yusuf & Samuel 2016). A preview of the content analysis findings suggests that community SEDs constituted 42% and 50% of the total social and environmental disclosure for the thirteen local and five international oil industries. The content analysis findings imply that Nigerian oil industries have shifted their focus toward community SEDs on social and environmental disclosures. Analysis of the SED reports indicates that most Nigerian oil industries had set aside substantial financial budgets to support the social welfare and community development

programs in their active regions. Therefore, community SEDs are considered the critical scope of social and environmental disclosures in the Nigerian oil industry.

Employee SEDs also constitute the second most important determinant of the social and environmental disclosures in the Nigerian oil and gas industry. For instance, employee SEDs constituted 30% of the local oil industries' total social and environmental disclosures. In contrast, 27% of the total SEDs captured among the international firms had implemented information on employee welfare programs. The insight from the content analysis reveals that most firms have focused on staff motivation across the Nigerian oil industry by adopting efficacious employee training, development, and compensation programs. The focus on employee SEDs expounded on the fact that in any organisation, personnel are vital strategic resources that are likely to enhance the organisation's strategic competitiveness (Campbell 2007).

The review of the SED contents also indicates that environmental sustainability is another important determinant of the social and environmental disclosure in the Nigerian oil industry. On average, 11% of the SED contents analysed from the annual sustainability reports of the 18 Nigerian oil industries focused on environmental sustainability performance. The implication is that despite the considerable focus on community and employee SEDs, Nigerian oil industries also concentrated on environmental conservation, including reducing pollution and other forms of environmental damage.

Therefore, community, employee and environmental SEDs were the most critical determinants of the social and environmental disclosure across the Nigerian oil industries. The three (3) components of SEDs accounted for more than 85% of the social and environmental disclosure associated with the eighteen oil industries in Nigeria. The stated

insight confirms the relevance of the stakeholder theoretical framework and the social legitimacy theory, as noted by Duff (2016). The considerable focus on attaining the interest of communities and employees highlights the recognition of both internal and external stakeholders as crucial participants in the overall corporate governance performance of the Nigerian oil industries. However, the researcher did not give energy conservation issues considerable focus among the 18 Nigerian oil industries. A preliminary review of the SED reports indicates that less than 2% of the total SEDs constitute energy conservation disclosures. The top five (5) oil industries, consisting of international oil companies and the other 13 Nigerian oil companies (Domestic Oil Companies), will be analysed to understand better the extent of SED in the Nigerian oil industries.

4.10 Differences in SED Reporting between Domestic and International Oil Industries

A preliminary review of the content analysis from the SED annual reports reveals a substantial difference in the quality and quantity of SED reporting between the local and international oil industries that operate in Nigeria. Generally, Nigeria's five international oil industries recorded substantially higher mean SED values than Nigeria's domestic oil industries. Specifically, the international oil industries reported a greater focus on environmental conservation, employee welfare and community welfare disclosures. The review of some of the annual reports indicates that the global oil industries allocated substantial CSR budgets to build social amenities, hospitals, and schools compared to the local oil industries. For example, Exxon Mobil, an international oil industry, reported that in 2016, it allocated \$242 million to fund social development projects across the globe. The global oil industry that operates in Nigeria also reported significantly higher quantified monetary and visual disclosures than the local oil companies used in the country.

The differences in the quality and quantity of SED reporting between the domestic and international oil industries are explained by variations in the financial resource endowment (Ekundayo et al., 2016). The implication is that the international oil industries can support significant community development projects because of their excellent financial capability. The entrenched philanthropic (human) organisational culture among the international oil industries also accounts for their better SED reporting practices and willingness to invest in mega social development projects and environmental conservation initiatives (Olayiwola 2010). Finally, top management commitment and corporate solid governance frameworks associated with the international oil industries also explain their best SED reporting practices compared to the local oil industries. Essentially, organisations with robust corporate governance frameworks are likely to be better positioned to support social and community welfare projects in their areas of operations (Ekundayo et al., 2016).

4.10.1 Differences in SED Reporting Practices and Relative Analysis

The secondary research design for the differences in SED reporting between domestic and international oil industries had the same data collection and sampling design as the secondary research design approach for the scope of SEDs in the Nigerian oil industry. The annual SED reports for the 18 Nigerian oil companies were utilised as the primary source of secondary public data in constructing the data collecting method. On the other hand, the 18 local and foreign oil industries that operate in Nigeria were selected using a judgmental sample technique. However, the primary difference is in the data analysis and statistical analytical tools.

An analysis of AR identified significant differences in the length of sentences within the companies. Some words were used as a measurement unit to avoid difficulties while accounting for the differences, and Sentences were used as the analysis unit. A comparative

analysis was carried out between International and Domestic Oil companies regarding the SED quantity in AR to maintain a good corporation. This analysis was achieved through subdividing SED into five categories related to the environment, energy, customer, community, and employee disclosures. The stated SED categorisation is based on Hackston and Milne's (1996) five social and environmental disclosure components.

4.11 Data Analysis Approach and Analytical Tool

The raw data on SED for the five components based on the Hackston and Milne (1996) model of SED reporting (environment, energy, customer, employee, and community) and for each of the 18 oil industries was subjected to inferential statistical analysis. The inferential statistical analysis based on ANOVA, paired-samples t-test and non-parametric tests (Kruskal-Wallis test) was used to compare the extent and quality of SED disclosure among the Nigerian local oil industries and the international oil industries. The inferential statistical analysis of the raw data drawn from the content analysis was appropriate for evaluating how the difference in SED reporting practices between the local and international oil industries is significant. The researcher used the 5% significance level to ascertain whether the difference in social and environmental disclosure among the local and international oil industries is statistically significant or not based on the ANOVA or the paired samples t-test. Correlation analysis was also employed to examine the extent of association in the five SED components among the local and international oil industries in Nigeria.

This objective/question sought to evaluate the variation in SED reporting practices among the local and international oil firms that operate in Nigeria. The quantified monetary and non-monetary information are used as the data source for analysis. For instance, based on the

quantified financial disclosures (i.e., dollar budget for CSR and social welfare projects) reported by the oil companies, inferential statistical analysis was used to ascertain the difference in the SED reporting practices between the local and foreign oil companies. Similarly, based on the quantified non-monetary disclosures (i.e., percentage allocations or the number of scholarships awarded), inferential analysis, including parametric (ANOVA, paired-samples t-test) and non-parametric (Kruskal-Wallis test), was employed to compare the difference in SED reporting practices between the local and foreign oil companies in Nigeria.

4.11.1 Social and Environmental Disclosure (SED) Index

The social and environmental disclosure (SED) index is an important metric that measures the extent of social and environmental disclosure commitment for a given company or group of firms (Singhania & Gandhi, 2015). The SED Index is a composite metric measuring a company's social and environmental disclosure (SED) reporting performance. For the second objective in the secondary research design, the SED index was applied to compare the SED reporting practices between the Nigerian local and international oil firms. The insight based on the study by Sani, Hassan and Bala (2020) indicates that corporate size and profitability are essential factors that influence the Nigerian oil industry's social and environmental disclosure (SED) index. Therefore, given that international oil and gas firms have historically been the most profitable and significant asset size compared to the local firms, the implication is that these foreign oil industries are likely to report substantially higher SED index (Sani, Hassan & Bala 2020). Based on the preliminary empirical evidence, the expectation is that the international oil and gas firms that operate in Nigeria are likely to report a relatively higher SED index than the local oil industries.

Different approaches were used to come up with the disclosure of AR by using a scoring scheme. An equivalent weighted index refers to the ratio of the company's items to disclose. Under such an index, the user should consider all the information. According to this index, the consideration was determining if a company announced environmental or social information in AR.

4.12 Ethical Considerations

Miller (2012) argues that researchers' responsibility is to observe moral and ethical standards while conducting their research, especially in studies involving people. Adherence to stipulated standards is vital in ensuring that the study participants are not placed in harm's way during the research process. Therefore, the researcher worked within the 18 frameworks of organisations' ethics when obtaining the annual reports to ensure adherence to the ethical standards. Before the interviews were administered, this thesis was reviewed and approved by the University of the West of Scotland Ethics Committee. Interviewees were enlightened about the purpose of the study and established their participation. Consent was required from the Interviewees by confirming that they had access to the participant information sheet before participating in the research. Furthermore, the respondents were also requested to sign a permission form outlining the purpose of the thesis.

It was made clear to interviewees that they could ask questions at any moment throughout the interview. In addition, it was made clear to them that they may opt out of the process whenever they wanted, with no explanation. The researchers informed participants that the research was for academic purposes and that their replies would be treated confidentially by the researcher. Each participant was promised that they would remain anonymous during the study and would not disclose their names. However, the researcher also emphasises that all information the Interviewees give will be audio-recorded and stored securely on the study

designated computer, which the research team can only access through a password. At the end of every interview, the written notes were taken good care of and kept with the highest degree of privacy. Moreover, the information was stored in a data storage device with a password-protected memory; after some years, these files will be entirely erased from the storage device.

The secondary data research design did not entail retrieving information or insight from human subjects. The quantitative secondary research design relied on the social and environmental disclosures presented in annual SED reports. The researcher retrieved these published SED reports from the website of the respective Nigerian oil industries and the NSE website. Therefore, there were minimal ethical issues for consideration concerning the secondary research design. However, the primary research, which entailed analysis of the interview transcripts based on the responses of the 24 participants (human subjects), meant that ethical issues had to be given more significant consideration to maintain the dignity and confidentiality of the respondents.

According to Akaranga and Makau (2016), research studies that involve human subjects as participants must consider the need to mitigate the ethical violations that might interfere with the privacy of the respondents. In general, the primary research component in this study placed due diligence on various ethical issues that might adversely affect the privacy and confidentiality of the participants' information. First, participants' details, including names and personal identification numbers, were anonymous to mitigate the likelihood of disclosing the subjects' identities. All the 24 stakeholders participating in the interview were only required to state their demographic profiles, such as age, gender, marital status, and occupation. This information was unlikely to reveal the exact identity of the individuals who participated in the face-to-face interview.

4.12.1 Ethical Issues and Principles

The primary research component of this thesis was guided by the five (5) principles of ethics in research. These include beneficence, non-maleficence, fairness/justice, anonymity, confidentiality, and respect. This subsection of the methodology chapter describes how the researcher considered each of the six ethical principles when interviewing the 24 participants.

1. Beneficence

The ethical concept of beneficence captures doing good deeds such as being merciful, charitable, and kind to the interview respondents (Akaranga & Makau 2016). The idea of beneficence implies that the researcher is responsible for explaining the purpose of the research and any direct benefits that would accrue to the respondent due to participation in the interview (Creswell 2014). One of the essential benefits of ethics in research is the avoidance of deception and promotion of the welfare of the study participants.

The researcher maintained the ethical principle of beneficence in this study by providing a participant information sheet to all 24 respondents. The participant information sheet allowed the researcher to explain the study's primary purpose, significance, and what it entails to the interviewees. The beneficence ethical principle was also maintained when the researcher made it clear to the participants that no direct financial benefits would accrue to them due to their participation in the interview. Akaranga and Makau (2016) indicate that a researcher guided by the beneficence ethical principle should neither exaggerate nor understate the potential benefits of participation in the study. However, inconsistent with the beneficence moral principle, the participants were informed during the debrief session that they could access the study's findings after completing the final thesis.

2. Non-Maleficence

The ethical principle of non-maleficence states that a researcher must promote the safety of the participants during the interview session (Barrow et al., 2020). Therefore, as part of familiarisation with the research project, the researcher is expected to explain the potential risk of participation in the study to the human subjects (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill 2016). This concept emphasises the need for the researcher to minimise research subjects' exposure to physical, psychological and emotional harm that the respondents might experience during the interview (Akaranga & Makau 2016). Essentially, based on the non-maleficence ethical principle, the researcher should attempt to minimise intentional and potential harm to the researcher (Sekaran & Bourgie 2016).

The researcher widely applied the non-maleficence ethical principle in this study to promote the participants' physical and psychological safety. For instance, to ensure that the interviewees did not experience any possible psychological or emotional distress from the semi-structured interview, the researcher avoided asking sensitive questions that touched on the participants' personal life. In addition, due to the current Covid-19 pandemic, the researcher maintained social distance with the interviewees to avoid possible contamination. The interviewees were also informed that there are minimal risks of physical injury while partaking in the face-to-face interview. However, the researcher took the utmost care to mitigate any risk of physical harm to the participants during the interview.

3. Fairness and Justice

The ethical research principle of fairness/justice states that the researcher must ensure fair treatment and privacy of information to participants (Barrow et al., 2020). The ethical principle of fairness/justice also dictates that the researcher must provide appropriate treatment to not only those selected respondents but equally to those who declined to partake in the interview without any prejudice (Creswell 2014). In this study, the researcher

guaranteed fairness and justice to the participants in several ways. First, selecting the 28 participants (seven from each of the four (4) Nigerian states), a representative sample of stakeholders, including community leaders, community youth leaders, community residents, church leaders, academicians, company managers, and company employees of the oil companies, was selected. The implication is that there was no discrimination in choosing the 28 participants who were chosen relatively and equally from the four (4) Nigeria states of Akwa Ibom, Niger Delta, River state and Bayelsa.

The other important aspect of fairness/justice that the researcher considered is that all the potential respondents were given a participant information sheet to familiarise themselves with the research study. Additionally, as part of ethical consideration in the administration of informed consent, potential participants, including those who declined to partake in the study, were not prejudiced. The researcher understood the predicament of the two managers and two employees from SPDC and the Nigeria NLNG Limited; the researcher could not access it due to the movement restrictions occasioned by the current Covid-19 pandemic. These four participants were not as planned, which meant that the researcher interviewed only 24 out of the 28 participants who were initially scheduled to partake in the interview.

4. Anonymity and Confidentiality

Anonymity is an essential ethical principle, which refers to maintaining the secrecy of participants' details, including age, cultural orientation, names, and other sensitive information (Akaranga & Makau 2016). Confidentiality, also related to anonymity, refers to not disclosing the participants' details, including names and other personal identifiers. According to Barrow et al. (2020), anonymity and confidentiality are essential ethical principles that create a trusting and honest relationship between the interviewer and the interviewee.

The researcher guaranteed the principle of anonymity in the primary research study by making all the interview transcripts anonymous. This means that no unauthorised person could deduce the respondent's identity using names not disclosed as part of the ethical consideration. In addition, based on the structure and design of the semi-structured interview, no person could trace the identity of the interviewees using demographic details such as age, gender, marital status, and occupation or position in society. Furthermore, as part of the need to safeguard participants' privacy included in the study, no individual was required to state their information number or bank details, which would have compromised the security of their financial information.

5. Respect

The ethical principle of respect is a human dignity aspect that requires researchers to safeguard the respondents' autonomy while at the same time ensuring that the participants are aware of all the relevant factors surrounding the study (Barrow et al., 2020). As a show of respect to the study participants, autonomy is guaranteed by allowing each stakeholder to decide whether to participate or decline to partake in the interview. Autonomy is evidenced by the fact that each of the 24 participants was given an informed consent form to decide whether to participate in the face-to-face interview.

In addition, respect for the participants is also evidenced by the fact that each stakeholder had a right to seek clarification of any question during the interview which is unclear or asked questions to comprehend a research point. The respect and autonomy of the primary researcher are also evidenced by the fact that the respondents were at liberty to withdraw their participation (formal consent) without offering reasons to justify their decision. Furthermore, as part of the need to enhance respect of the participants in the primary research, no individual participant was victimised or prejudiced for declining to accept the interview or withdrawing from the face-to-face interview. The implication is that the

researcher used no coercion or incentives to recruit the 28 participants who were initially scheduled to participate in the discussion. According to Barrow et al. (2020), the provision of extreme rewards can sometimes be construed as a form of coercion to influence the decision of the subjects to participate in the study. Finally, the researcher also guaranteed respect for participants in the primary research by providing a participant information sheet to each of the 24 respondents that partook in the face-to-face interview.

4.13 Conclusions

The three main ingredients of research include: constructing the theory, collecting data, and designing methods for collecting data. The methodology chapter served as a bridge between the analysis of the study and the theoretical perspective. Thus, this whole chapter has investigated the data collection procedures and research design while at the same time incorporating a theoretical framework. The outcome of the thematic analysis, which the researcher performed in NVivo qualitative data analysis software, relies on the interview transcripts from seven (7) stakeholders drawn from each of the four Nigerian states of Akwa Ibom State and Bayelsa State, Delta State and Rivers state. The seven stakeholders include company management, company employees, community leaders, youth leaders, church leaders, community residents, and academicians. The initial plan was to have 28 participants (N = 28), with seven interviewees drawn from each of the stated four Nigerian states. However, due to current Covid-19 restrictions and the 'work at home' orders, it was impossible to access all the company employees and managers.

Therefore, only two company managers and two company employees could participate in the interview. Specifically, one manager and one employee from Exxon Mobil Company and one

manager and one employee from Bayelsa Oil Company participated in the study. Therefore, given that the researcher did not find the required employees and managers from Delta State and Rivers State, the implication is that only five participants each drawn from the states. Seven participants were sourced from the Bayelsa and the Akwa Ibom states. This section presents the outcome of thematic coding and analysis performed in the NVivo statistical data analysis software. The thematic analysis seeks to derive the central themes regarding the interviewees' perception of the Nigerian oil companies' SED practices. However, before presenting the thematic analysis results and findings, this section describes the sample composition based on gender, marital status, and educational level.

Furthermore, the research aims at evaluating the level of social and environmental disclosures among the companies that operate in the Nigerian oil industry. The study analysis anticipated that the social and environmental disclosure in the Nigerian oil industry varies significantly based on the differences in their annual reports. The average disclosure scores are further expected to vary considerably between the sampled firms in the oil industries. The researcher will use the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) to ascertain whether the variance in the sampled companies' social and environmental disclosure is significant.

CHAPTER FIVE: FINDING 1: INTERVIEWS

5.1 Introduction

This chapter aims to answer the three research objectives. It is also guided by the stakeholder theoretical framework that seeks to ascertain the host community's perceptions, motivations, and challenges of social and environmental disclosures (SED) among Nigerian oil companies. However, conferring to Greenwood 2001 defined a community as a group of people with diverse attributes who share standard social norms, perspectives, and cultural affiliations. Due to the prominence of the stakeholder theory, the community has become an essential organisational stakeholder, given its role as a customer and host to corporate organisations. According to Maddaloni and Davis (2017), the community has become a vital stakeholder for social and environmental reporting for corporate organisations. The consideration of community social and environmental reporting needs has forced contemporary organisations to issue non-financial reports such as annual sustainability reports in addition to the traditional financial statements. The community's expectation as a key stakeholder is that corporate organisations would be responsible for how their activities and, or operations influence the social and environmental aspects.

The qualitative study's focus is presented by the following three primary research objectives, which are specified as follows; 1. Identify the motivations for social and environmental disclosure in the Nigerian oil industries. 2. To investigate the host community's perceptions of the SED by Nigerian oil industries. 3. Discuss the challenges the Nigerian oil industries face in developing and promoting social and environmental disclosures (SED). Therefore, based on the stated three primary objectives, the following three research objectives/questions are also expected to guide the study's overall focus.

- What motivational aspects influence stakeholders' view of the Nigerian oil industries' social and environmental disclosure (SED) practices?
- What are the host communities' perceptions of the social and environmental disclosures (SED) practices by the Nigerian oil industries?
- What are the stakeholders' perceptions of the Nigerian oil industry's challenges in developing and promoting social and environmental disclosures?

Nevertheless, the chapter is organised as follows; Section 5.1 Describes the introduction with their Sub-Section 5.1.1 data coding and analysis and Sub-Section 5.1.2 present the Overview of the thematic Analysis Results, Section 5.2 Discusses thematic codes on SED motivations, Section 5.3 Deliberate thematic codes on SED perceptions, Section 5.4 Argues thematic codes on social, environmental challenges and Section 5.5 summary of the chapter.

5.1.1 Data Coding and Analysis

This section presents the outcome of thematic coding and analysis performed in the NVivo statistical data analysis software. The thematic data coding entailed analysing and identifying texts (interview transcripts) linked by a common theme or idea. The data files were first organised for interviewees (N = 24). After that, NVivo statistical software indexed the interview transcripts into broad themes and sub-themes to capture the interviewees' main ideas (view). The thematic data coding was mainly undertaken using grounded theory and template analysis guided by the three research objectives or research questions. The tabular and graphical form presented the derived thematic codes from each node based on the NVivo output. The thematic analysis seeks to derive the central themes regarding the interviewees' perception of the Nigerian oil companies' SED practices.

5.1.2 Overview of the Thematic Analysis Results

A summary of the broad themes derived when the interview transcripts were subjected to NVivo coding is presented in Table 5.1 below. The qualitative data analysis using NVivo statistical software generates three general thematic insights. These include- Motivations for social and environmental disclosure (SED), Host community perceptions of SED practices and the Challenges related to SED reporting. The stated three broad thematic subjects mainly guided the focus of the interview.

Table 5.1: Summary of the Thematic Coding

Motivations on SED	References	Percentage Frequency
Alignment to Community Development	24	38%
Community Welfare	20	31%
SED Benefit or Damage	20	31%
Perceptions on SED	References	Percentage Frequency
Responsible Corporate Citizens	20	31%
Community Involvement	20	31%
Social and Environmental Issues	20	31%
Communication on SED Policy	4	6%
Social Environmental Challenges	References	Percentage Frequency
SED Policies	24	34%
Interactions with Community	23	32%
Community Support	20	28%
Funding	2	6%

The broad theme on SED motivations was incorporated to assess the perceived driving factors that influence the consideration of social and environmental disclosure reporting across the Nigerian oil and gas industry. Similarly, as a broad thematic subject, motivation on SED also sought to ascertain the factors that motivate the host communities to be interested in issues about SED reporting. A considerable number of the interviewees who participated in the study were mainly motivated by the desire to ascertain how the Nigerian oil industries care about environmental conservation. For instance, an Exxon Mobil Company Employee acknowledged that,

"So driven by that, the company cares about the environment, it cares about the people, and I know that, so because that adds into corporate social responsibility and the company prides itself in having goodwill, so if the company is trying to keep the goodwill and a decent corporate image, then it wants to do everything that will not put it in a bad light, so that's the key motivation."
(Company Employee 2).

The interview transcript based on the Company Management from Exxon Mobil suggests that the perceived confidence and belief from the community motivates them to issue the SED reports regularly,

"Well, it's just, you know if you have the confidence that people believe in you, they can only believe if they know, if they hear from you" (Company Management 1).

The other motivational aspect based on the interviewees' perceived impetus on SED reporting relates to their desire to know about the Nigerian oil industries' corporate social responsibility (CSR) practices. In this respect, an Academician in Bayelsa State observed that his primary motivation for the SED reporting is based on the need to compare the corporate profits and the percentage allocations towards CSR activities. The insight based on the interview with the Academicians in Bayelsa State is that even though some Nigerian oil firms allocate annual CSR budgets from their profits, most of their actions have a destructive impact on environmental sustainability. For instance, Academician 2 is quoted as follows,

"What they keep out of the community at times when the oil companies say they are giving Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) and all that, no doubt is good but compared to what the oil companies are doing to the community, they are destroying the community"
(Academician 2).

Furthermore, the interviews revealed a lot about the industry's general viewpoint. To strengthen the industry's SED disclosure, the link between the audience and the form must be addressed, resulting in a stable working environment (Odera et al., 2018). In general, public engagement is essential since the industry's audience has a significant impact on its development and survival. This collaboration promotes sustainability and corporate social responsibility are critical drivers of industry value generation (Odera et al., 2016). Because of society's standards, most firms are being pressured to create a SED policy these days. Audience engagement is at the heart of social expectations, and it has been proven that good concentration increases people's trust in a company's aims and trends. Successful engagement

enhances involvement, learning, and preference; hence it must be used in SEDs. Committed audiences are more likely to share information on social media, which helps others believe in the organisation. SED policies are essential in a business since they describe the industry's vision and goal regarding the environment, community, and benefits to long-term growth (Esposito et al., 2021). As a result, such regulations are a laudable trend that encourages various types of adaptation since social and environmental trends are constantly evolving.

Depending on the structure, a company's SED policies should be linked with worldwide needs. As a result of this context, sustainable development and work respect the rule of law and human rights, allowing business activities to match public goals. As a result, without a suitable structure, business efforts, policies, and sustainable growth will be impossible to coexist (Odera et al., 2016). A corporation with a clear framework makes it easier to implement policies, and the existing structure allows employees more clarity in expectation management, which in this instance focus on social and environmental disclosure to improve trust between sectors and the public (Odera et al., 2018). The interview transcript based on Community Leader in Bayelsa State suggests that the lack of good SED practice of the oil companies and their false CSR reports is mainly driven by the fact that the Nigerian oil companies do not have adequate information on what is happening at the community level in terms of the damages they have caused.

"The damage is environmental pollution, their spillage; we suffer it. If you go to the river-round area, you see, in the meantime, you understand—the pollution of the gas flare and the heat in the community. The gas is full of the black smoke you wake up in the morning to see, you

inhale it, and it affects your health and the life span, the life stock, plantation, both life water stocks and plantations. It's affecting it. And we don't have this coordinated system. It's a big problem; imagine if they give it to a local contractor, they won't ensure that national standard is practised. Atomic chemicals will be buried and kept on the land, and when they see it, they cover it up, not understanding that those things have long adverse effects on the habitation of that land''.

Nevertheless, another interviewee (community leader) also acknowledges the importance of SED bad practices of oil companies to the host communities, which create significant damage to the community, stating that,

"Earlier on, in the 80s, Mobil contributed to the development of the community. I can talk about the electric power generating station here, in Eket, and Mobil got involved with it. They also undertook some road projects and water, but since they have become political partners with the state government, all that has stopped. So, everything we now grant from Mobil can be said to be the negative aspect of oil production and gas flaring because oil spills happen every other day. The fish no longer comes close to the shore, they now go

right to where the water is warm along the pipelines, and no fisherman gets anything here".

The oil industry's Social Environmental Reporting practices adhere to society's standards to maintain local support. For example, Mobil, its employees, and other firm entities should work together to ensure that whatever impacts the company also impact the population (Odera et al., 2018). The business's authorisation of operation was obtained from the town rather than the federal government, making Mobil more dependable to follow the community's set rules, requiring the corporation to meet the public's aspirations (Odera et al., 2016). However, numerous community leaders have observed various problems regarding the oil business's failing support of the community, resulting in the necessity for a SED disclosure filing of the corporation as a method of regulating the oil industry's operations toward social and environmental progress. Therefore, a firm's SED policies should be linked to share goals, and a corporation with a clear framework ease the process of implementing policies.

Moreover, the perceived reliability of the SED reports was also noted to be an essential aspect that motivates the Nigerian oil companies and the host community to review the annual corporate sustainability reports and or yearly reports of the oil industries. There has been a perception that due to poor monitoring, most of these reports do not reflect the actual social and environmental sustainability practices across the Nigerian oil industry. The interview transcript based on Academician in Rivers State suggests that the lack of accuracy in the SED reports is mainly driven by the fact that the Nigerian oil industries do not have adequate information on what is happening at the community level,

"The report about the activities, social activities and of course the environmental effects may not be so correct, because sometimes the experience we have is different from the actual effects we have seen." (Academician 4).

The broad theme of perceived social and environmental disclosure (SED) practices mainly captures the host community and stakeholders' perceptions and attitudes on the Nigerian oil industries' social and environmental performance. Based on the interview transcripts' review, most Interviewees appear to concur that the SED practices across the country's oil and gas industry are disgraceful.

Specifically, several of them, including Academicians in Bayelsa State, appears to acknowledge that the multinational oil companies tend to rip the societies while claiming to provide CSR initiatives, which in most cases, comes at a cost. The stated finding is based on the following extract statement from Bayelsa state academician,

"My perception on SED is poor because the oil companies are ripping our communities, and what I mean ripping in terms of what they produce and what they keep out of the community at times when oil firms say they are giving Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) and all that, no doubt is good but compared to what the oil companies are doing to the community, they are destroying the community, so I think the oil companies are taking more than what they are giving

back and they will never report the correct thing, never."

(Academician 2).

Community Residents in Bayelsa State further strengthened this by stating that,

"My perception is that the people in the area tend to suffer a lot from the activities of these oil companies as they do not carry along the interests of the people."

(Community Resident 2).

Furthermore, the insight based on the interview with the church leader in Akwa Ibom state also tends to concur with the perceptions of poor SED practices among the Nigerian oil industries. According to the church leader, most of the annual and corporate sustainability reports are doctored to suit their need for an excellent public image and reputation.

"I would like to use what is commonly used in Nigeria. I may say it is a kind of doctored report, it is not real because they know what is real." (Church Leader 1).

Based on the stated interview insight, the insinuation is that the host community does not trust the authenticity of the annual corporate sustainability reports issued by the Nigerian oil firms as part of their SED reporting practices. However, some interviewees seem to have a fair perception of the SED practices adopted by the Nigerian oil industries. The community leader from Bayelsa states opines that the host community, the government, and the Nigerian corporate entities have played their expected role. In this case, the community leader observes that,

"I look at it from three quarters, most likely the government, the host community and the company itself. Everybody has a role to play. And what I have seen so far is that all three parties are playing their role effectively. It has always been on personal and selfish interests from the three tiers I mentioned: the government, the company itself, and the host community. It has always been a personal interest, what is my gain, not all about the well-being of society." (Community Leader 2).

The interview transcript's primary position is that most of the host community members and other stakeholders negatively perceive the SED practices undertaken by the Nigerian oil and gas firms.

The third broad thematic subject matter drawn from the interview transcripts with the 24 interviewees pertains to the stakeholders' perceived challenges that hinder the adoption of effective SED reporting. Based on the NVivo output, 13% of the interviewees acknowledged that most local Nigerian oil industries cannot curtail environmental damage and prevent pollution. In this regard, the academician in Bayelsa State observes that,

"The main problem with the oil firms is that they have found it difficult to mitigate the environmental damage from their activities" (Academician 2).

The second reason given by Community Youth Leader in Rivers State was that oil companies are causing environmental hazards, especially oil spillages, and it is affecting the community aquatic life as several residents depend on fishing as a way of their income,

"So, while you are crying to the gallery, they are smiling to the banks. Secondly, like the oil spillage kills our aquatic life, so that makes life miserable and unbearable for us." (Youth Leader 3).

The other challenge associated with the SED reporting is the poor Nigerian governance and political system, which has restricted the oil industries' ability to undertake adequate social and environmental disclosure. The implication is that the Nigerian oil industries face numerous bureaucratic obstacles that impede their ability to engage in socially beneficial CSR practices. For instance, Delta state Academician emphasises this aspect as follows,

"The oil companies are trying to see how they could help alleviate some of these impacts socially by giving out things that would benefit all. But our system, you know, we also have our Nigerian factor, people try to corner things" (Academician 3).

Furthermore, financial challenges were also noted to be among the main factors that restrict the Nigerian oil industries' ability to engage in effective SED reporting practices. For instance, the Company Employee IN Bayelsa Oil Company acknowledged that limited funds had restricted Nigerian oil industries' ability to implement their MOU with the host community concerning investment in various CSR initiatives.

"The current challenge, if I may put it this way, is the lack of funds to implement the Memorandum of Understanding (MOU). We are supposed to develop the

items we have signed with them from the first to the last. Where the company make less return or make little revenue, we find it difficult to implement the MOU and, in a way, it becomes a challenge because the communities expect us to do it to the fullest." (Company Employee 2).

The Company Management of the Bayelsa Oil Company acknowledged the issue of limited funding. However, from the host community's perspective, most interviewees appear to recognise that the SED challenge mainly emanates from the Nigerian oil industries' failure to prevent environmental damage. For example, the Community Resident in Akwa Ibom state observes that,

"The main challenge with the oil industries is environmental damage "(Community Resident 1).

Moreover, based on the interview insight by the youth leader from Bayelsa, there is a general perception that the challenge associated with SED disclosure emanates from the fact that the Nigerian oil industries do not operate an open-door policy. This is because the MOUs with the host communities are signed by the community leaders and the local administrators, who might not disclose the agreement's actual terms. Specifically, the youth leader in Bayelsa state is quoted as follows,

"The problem with the Nigerian oil industries is that most do not operate an open-door policy, but they operate in a divide and rule system" (Community Youth Leader 2).

5.2 Thematic Codes on SED Motivations

The NVivo output in Exhibit 10 (Appendix) shows that three specific themes mainly defined the interviewee's or host communities' perception of the Nigerian oil industries' social and environmental disclosure (SED) practices. The NVivo data analysis software findings, summarised in Table 5.1 and Figure 5.1, indicate that there are three specific thematic codes with their sub-section, which capture and describe their motivational insight on SED reporting. These include Alignment to community development, the production that considers the community welfare, and the benefit and damages from the social and environmental disclosures.

The interviewees' SED motivation was primarily defined or captured by aligning the SED reporting and practices to community development initiatives. This is because 38% of the thematic codes on SED motivations (N = 24 references) captured the host communities' perception of how the social and environmental disclosure practices are consistent with the community development initiatives. On the other hand, 31% of the thematic codes about SED motivation also related to community welfare (N = 20 references) and SED benefits or damage (N = 20 references).

Figure 5.1 Thematic Codes on SED Motivation

5.2.1 Alignment to Community Development

The host community's interest in SED disclosure and reporting was mainly guided by the need to know how the country's oil and gas firms' social and environmental disclosure (SED) practices are aligned to the community development initiatives. The word frequency cloud in Figure 5.2 illustrates the importance of "Community", given that the stated word was cited 1091 times by the 24 interviewees based on the interview transcripts. The implication is that the host community's primary motivation is their desire for the SED practices and reporting framework to align with the community development plans.

Furthermore, the Company Employee from Bayelsa Oil Company also observes that their primary motivation in issuing SED reports is community development. In this respect, the employee from Bayelsa state observes that,

"As a corporate organisation, we believe that if we are developing the communities by implementing the MOU, we are also developing the state, so the state could not reach out to develop communities we have identified in operation. It is our motivation that we must develop those communities; we cannot leave everything in the hands of the government, you know. So, our presence should be our motivation to develop the community, so we are passionate about developing the communities as long as we operate within the state" (Company Employee, 2).

The Company Management from Bayelsa Oil Company also agrees that their primary motivations in issuing the SED reports are based on their perception of the community as an important stakeholder. The stated view is based on the following statement,

"Yes, we, the company are part of the project, that's the motivation, they are stakeholders, so the same way profit is shared to shareholders, they too are part of the project, so, that motivates us to disclose the report" (Company Management 2).

The insightful review of the interview transcript indicates that the host communities do not feel that the SED reporting undertaken by the Nigerian oil industries is aligned with their respective community development plan. For instance, the academician in Bayelsa State observed that the nature of SED reporting by the Nigerian oil industries is primarily inconsistent with the community development needs. Moreover, the academician observes that some of the community development projects initiated by the Nigerian oil industries are duplicated and, therefore, do not add value. In this respect, he states that,

"I have witnessed a case where Shell does a small road project, and before you know it, the road has already been commissioned... there was a case where the community decried that this road had already been commissioned; why is it being commissioned again. So, most times, they don't report proper issues. If you go to them, they will tell you something different. But I have to go to communities to find out from them what is the real thing the company has done" (Academician 2).

The insinuation is that the Nigerian oil industries tend to undertake some community development projects with less regard to the existing plan.

The insinuation is that the Nigerian oil industries tend to undertake some community development projects with less regard to the existing plan.

Poor monitoring and follow-up have also been noted as issues that have restricted SED practices by Nigerian oil companies to align with community development needs. There is

substantial evidence that the CSR and scholarship allocations offered by the Nigerian oil companies do not benefit the vulnerable poor communities. As observed by the Church Leader in Akwa Ibom state, most oil and gas firms in Nigeria do not have effective machinery for monitoring and evaluation.

"The companies might allocate a specific budget for the investment project, but the funds are not used for their intended purposes because these companies lack machinery for monitoring and evaluation. I learned some years ago that Exxon Mobil is still awarding the scholarship. But who is the beneficiary? The people that can afford their children's school fees are the people that are still benefiting from this scholarship. Rather, the scholarship was meant for the bright and less privileged"
(Church Leader 1).

Therefore, based on the stated interview transcript, poor monitoring, evaluation, and follow-up appear to have limited Nigerian oil firms' SED reporting ability to be aligned to the community development plan.

Furthermore, there is also a perception that most of the CSR projects that are implemented by the oil industries in Nigeria are not aligned to the long-term community needs. The stated problem, which the employee from Bayelsa Oil Cooperation also noted, is that not all Nigerian oil industries' CSR projects are aligned to community development projects. The employee from Bayelsa Oil Company articulated the stated concern as follows,

"I think alignment of our policy with the host community is like 90% because, as I said, there is no activity that is carried out without incorporating the host community; however, we feel we can do more"
(Company Employee 2)

Based on the stated insight from the interview with the Company Employee, the insinuation is that some Nigerian oil industries have not yet fully integrated their CSR initiatives and planned community development projects.

5.2.2 Community Welfare

The host community's motivations for SED disclosure were also captured by their desire to know the extent to which the Nigerian oil industries undertake their activities. At the same time, maintain community welfare. Due to the negative externalities of oil production, the oil industries are responsible for minimising the adverse environmental impact of their production activities on society (Oyadonghan & Balam, 2013). The academician from Akwa Ibom state observed that the host community's motivation concerning the SED practices related to the Nigerian oil firms is mainly defined by the level of community welfare support initiatives financed by the oil firms.

"Motivation itself is a drive. If oil companies have done all that we have been trying to interact with them, that would have been the sort of motivation. Like maybe paying subsidising school fees etc., these would have been motivated by the community" (Academician 1).

Similarly, the Community Resident in Bayelsa State also adds that motivations for the need to know about SED practices mainly appear in the budget allocations for educational scholarships, casual employment and training.

"Motivation, well, occasionally, they employ some casual staff. Some persons, you know, are employed on that casual basis—very few anyway" (Community Resident 2).

However, in their endeavour to meet the community's social welfare needs, there is a concern, especially among the youths stating that the allocated funds for community development are not used for the community development as the oil company has claimed. The Community Youth Leader from Rivers State alleged that,

"The community heads, the leaders of the various communities, the kings and the traditional rulers will receive incentives. This money is supposed to be from oil derivation, which is supposed to be for community development. Now this money is being paid to the community leaders, and the money eventually ends up being embezzled" (Community Youth Leader 4).

As observed earlier, this concern is attributed mainly to the inadequate monitoring and evaluation by the Nigerian oil industries, which trust the community leaders to initiate the community development projects.

The other insight based on the community welfare theme is that there is a feeling among the host communities that the funds allocated towards community development initiatives do not match the extent of environmental damage to society. The Community Youth Leader in Delta

State acknowledges that host communities receive social welfare benefits, including free medical care, scholarships, and youth training programs. The environmental damage is so severe that the stated benefits cannot match it.

"We receive some benefits from them, but the benefit is not commensurate with the damages. Sometimes, they come to an open school field within the community, send doctors and give free medical care to the community; people will go there to receive, sometimes they say they award the scholarship. They train some of our youth in some skill acquisition programs. Still, it is not commensurate with the damages done to the community" (Community Youth Leader 3).

5.2.3 SED Benefits or Damages

The final thematic code that captured the host community's motivation on SED reporting and disclosure practices by the Nigerian oil industries pertained to the perceived social and environmental benefits and damages. Based on the stated theme, the insinuation is that a considerable majority of the host communities desire to know the extent of the social and environmental benefits and, or damages based on their annual sustainability reports. In this respect, the Academician in Akwa Ibom state acknowledges that providing information on employment opportunities would have been a vital SED benefit given the current unemployment among youth in the country.

"Employment would have been one of the SED benefits"

(Academicians 1).

Regarding damages, the Church Leader in Akwa Ibom State acknowledges that the environmental pollution evident within the host communities is attributed to the Nigerian oil industries' inefficient oil production practices. There is a feeling among the host communities that new oil industries do not consider community initiatives as it was in the 1990s.

"The benefit from the oil company in the early 90s was transparent, where almost every road in communities was marked for expansion or repairs. Similarly, the projects include water projects, electricity transformer for good power supply, but for some time now, we have not seen this impact from the oil company" (Church Leader 1).

Community Leader in Delta State give different reasons stating that

"Bad roads, no electricity and so on, we haven't seen the direct benefits from oil companies" (Community Leader 3).

Due to cost optimisation and the dynamic external environment, few oil companies allocate a considerable budget to support community development projects.

The adverse environmental effects of oil pollution contribute to sub-optimal crop yields due to soil erosion. The interview transcript analysis by the Community Resident in Bayelsa State

indicates that the host communities in Nigeria are primarily concerned that even though the oil companies provide infrastructural assistance, their activities contribute to soil erosion.

"It has affected agriculture in our various communities, you know, because of the oil exploration in the community and the damages done to our soil by this oil companies. It does not help the host community, but it reduces the soil's fertility. It kills our crops directly and then indirectly too" (Community Resident 2).

However, the Church Leader in Bayelsa state revealed that oil spillage had been one of the biggest problems to our farmers within the community as it's damaging their crops and aquatic life; the Church Leader stated that,

"We used to have good yield (Harvest), but ever since the oil company came in, when we plant our crops, our crops are no more yielding" (Church Leader 2).

The church Leader in Akwa Ibom State further strengthened this by stating that:

"Like now if you go to Ibeno local government area where they are drilling the oil, you will see that they are still burning the gas, which is disturbing, and in Ibeno here, you will observe that so many plants and trees couldn't survive because of the heat of the gas flare burning. Now it is transmitted to the surrounding

environment, and it is also affecting the output in terms of crop productivity, even in human life because of the intense heat" (Church Leader 1).

Furthermore, the Community Leader in Akwa Ibom State also observed that the Nigerian oil industries, specifically Exxon Mobil, used to undertake community development initiatives such as constructing electricity and road projects to benefit the local community. However, these oil companies have been lately associated with environmental and marine pollution due to oil spills, which affect marine life's sustainability.

"Earlier on, in the 80s, Exxon Mobil contributed to the development of the community. I can talk about electricity power generating station. Exxon Mobil got involved with it. They also undertook some road projects and water, but since they have now become a political partner with the state government, all that had stopped" (Community Leader 1)

5.3 Thematic Codes on SED Perceptions

The outcome based on the NVivo data analysis indicates four specific thematic codes, which capture the SED perceptions among the Nigerian oil industries. Figure 5.3 depicts those three principal thematic codes that capture the interviewee's SED perception include "Responsible Corporate Citizen" (N= 20 references), "Community Involvement" (N = 20 references) as well as "Social and Environmental Disclosure" (N = 20 references).

The implication in the interview transcripts, which includes the host community and other stakeholder perceptions, influenced the extent to which the Nigerian oil firms were perceived as responsible corporate citizens and their ability to involve communities in social development projects and the view on the social and environmental disclosures. The researcher captured three thematic codes as the main factors influencing interviewees' perception of SED reporting and practices among the Nigerian oil industries.

Figure 5.3 Thematic Codes on SED Perception

5.3.1 Responsible Corporate Citizens

The host community's perception of the Nigerian oil companies' reputation as responsible corporate citizens is qualified by how the oil company can control environmental waste and pollution. The academician from Akwa Ibom acknowledged observed that,

"I wish them to control waste and pollution" (Academician 1).

However, some interviewees, such as the Academician in Rivers State, were sceptic about the authenticity of the country's oil companies' social and environmental disclosures. Moreover,

the Academician in Rivers state believes that the Nigerian oil companies' reputation as responsible corporate citizens can question if their SED performance is based on the annual sustainability reports that are not interactive and authentic.

"Well, I am talking about being realistic; if the oil company claimed to have undertaken CSR initiatives, it has to be truly physically or seen that they have done it and not done on paper or their publication. Sometimes the communities don't even have contact with those papers or publications from the oil company to know whether what they have said is true or not. My perspective is that let the truth reports be true and not doctored reports." (Academician 4).

The Akwa Ibom state Church Leader reinforced these perceptions by affirming that,

"I may say it is a doctored report; it is not real because they know what is real. The oil company knew when they were related to the community directly; they could see the community change. Now that they indirectly relate to the community, things are not the way they were. However, during the 90s, the impact of Exxon Mobil oil company, hosted by this community, was better, but now, its impact on society has changed. Since the invention of this political system, the government has taken over the

benefit directly accrued to the host community by the oil company as a state government responsibility project. So, what they usually report in their annual journal is not exactly what is happening in the host community."
(Church Leader 1).

According to the church leader's insightful view in Eket, Akwa Ibom stated that oil firms' reputation as responsible corporate citizens could enhance the oil company's actions to promote social welfare. For instance,

"If you try to enter the other village around here now, you will see that it's not motorable because the road is terrible. And this is the community hosting the oil company, and they are supposed to see to the well-being of the communities, not that they would be able to employ everybody in this society. But at least there should be a provision of social amenities, water, electricity, and good road networks are good social welfare activities" (Church Leader 1).

The interview transcripts related to the church leader in Akwa Ibom State also highlight youth employment and provision of skilled labour are essential aspects that can enhance the overall reputation of the oil industries responsible for corporate citizens. The Community Youth Leader in Akwa Ibom state indication that,

"The major problems affecting our community is employment, the employment of people into skillful areas would naturally be considered a good practice"
(Community Youth Leader 1).

Similarly, the Akwa Ibom state's community youth leader also argues that creating educational scholarships, generating youth employment, and providing social infrastructural amenities, including roads and electricity, are equally important in raising the reputation of the Nigerian oil industries as responsible corporate citizens.

5.3.2 Community Involvement

The analysis of the interview extracts also raised critical issues regarding how the host community and other stakeholders perceive the social and environmental practices undertaken by the oil and gas firms. Several interviewees seem to acknowledge that Nigerian oil firms do not engage the community when launching community development projects. For instance, the Academicians in Bayelsa State suggest that most of the decisions to undertake development projects financed by the oil firms are usually from top to down. The ideal strategy is for the community development project decisions to be implemented based on a bottom-up approach, which integrates local participation. In this regard, Bayelsa academician stated that,

"The development of what I know is not just from bottom to top, but from top to bottom people should be involved in any development issues. Like you are giving people water, is that what they need? No. Because in a community, they are stakeholders." (Academician, 2).

In terms of the extent of community involvement, there is also a suggestion that the Nigerian oil industries tend to use inappropriate approaches to reach the community when deciding on the type of community development projects they intend to set up. Some interviewees acknowledged that the Nigerian oil firms usually engage the community through their elected leaders.

However, some selfish community leaders do not get back to their communities to inform the nature of the oil development projects company. Therefore, given the leaders' self-interest, the host communities usually feel left out of such important decisions. The stated concern by the researcher articulated based on the interview extracts with the community leader from Akwa Ibom state,

"Mostly, the community is not involved with the oil company because of the selfish acclaimed groups who claimed they represent the community. Sometimes elected members claim to represent their community while representing their selfish interests. Still, the communities do not feel the impact of the oil companies, so the community is not directly involved" (Church Leader 1).

Therefore, based on the host communities' views, most community members prefer the oil industries to engage them directly rather than through their representatives, who are likely to place their self-interest above the community's needs.

The interview extract analysis by the church leader from Delta state also provided significant insight into why the Nigerian oil industries do not consistently engage the host communities. According to the church leader, one of the factors is related to the fact that some of the Nigerian oil firms, especially the multinationals, tend to employ foreign expatriates who have a different cultural background compared to the local culture. These foreign expatriates do not touch with the local community's needs and preferences regarding environmental and preservation of the social and cultural conditions. In this case, the church leader from Delta state observed that,

"Serious negative impact because no single senior officer is involved in my community that this oil company employs. They bring foreigners and other people from outside, from other tribes here, so we are put at bay and are not allowed to participate in the community development projects. It is very challenging to have their full engagement with the community, so we watch them doing what they want. People will often revolt and talk and talk until no end, and so to the government, there is no end to it." (Church Leader 3)

The insinuation based on the evaluation of the interview extract from the church leader is that locals' employment is likely to increase the likelihood of community engagement. In extreme situations, the lack of community involvement resulted in the duplication of community development projects. For instance, an Academician in Bayelsa State noted that there was a

situation in which a project had been commissioned twice due to limited involvement of the local communities.

"I don't think they are reporting the right thing. The oil company have been bad if you go through ethical standards; I don't think they haven't been following the standard, but as I say, most times, I've seen where Shell will do small road, and before you know, you see the picture of that small road commissioned. There was a case where the community say this project has already been commissioned before, so why is it being commissioned again like a new project" (Academician 2).

These incidences are likely to occur when there is insufficient community involvement.

5.3.3 Social and Environmental Issues

The other thematic aspect based on the NVivo qualitative data analysis pertains to the host community's perception of social and environmental issues. Most interviewees seem to acknowledge that the Nigerian oil industries' focus on social and ecological issues has diminished to a greater extent in recent years. There is a perception among the locals that the oil firms used to engage in substantial social welfare development projects during the 1990s. Still, recently, such corporate social responsibility initiatives have diminished considerably. For instance, the academician from Akwa Ibom observed that,

"Let us go back to the electricity issue. Exxon Mobil was then used to support this community in terms of provision of electricity, and even water, which is one of the social amenities. But now these social amenities are not forthcoming" (Academician 1).

The insight based on the paper by Mgbame and Mgbame (2018) indicates that challenges with finance and bureaucratic issues have limited the Nigerian oil firms' ability to engage in good social and environmental (SED) practices. There is also a concern among the host communities that the Nigerian oil industries do not consider their actions' adverse social and ecological effects. The shell oil company's extraction and production of oil from the community were noted to cause a significant adverse negative impact on human and marine life due to air pollution and marine pollution resulting from oil spills. The academician from Rivers State put in plainly by observing that,

"Air pollution and airborne diseases are the effects of oil operations and black soot all over the place. The effect of the oil operation here is very glaring, and you don't even need to ask somebody; it is glaring." (Academician 4).

Community Leader in Akwa Ibom State made similar assertions that pollution of gas flaring is affecting the health of the community,

"The pollution of gas flaring caused by oil operations, generally everywhere in the world, cannot be overemphasised" (Community Leader 1).

Similarly, the Academician in Delta State made a similar claim about oil production's adverse social and environmental effects on human and aquatic life resulting from oil spills and gas flaring.

"Greatly, I think the biggest issue we have in this area is this issue of the operations affecting the livelihood of the community. When I say operations, you know, sometimes operations have some incidents. We have things like oil spills, such as gas flaring, which are all operational, and these things have adverse effects on the community's livelihood." (Academician 3)

Likewise, the Church Leader in Bayelsa state also concurs that the oil spills and pollution have contributed to adverse health outcomes among the host communities. In certain situations, the host community appears to complain of low crop yields, as was noted by the church leader from Bayelsa state,

"Our land before now, I came to hear from my father that when we plant, we used to have good yield (Harvests) but ever since the oil company came in, when we plant our crops, our crops are no more yielding." (Church Leader 2).

The implication is that the Nigerian oil industries have not considered the social and environmental issues when making their oil extraction operational decisions. For instance, onshore and offshore drilling practices have resulted in oil spillage, affecting marine life in most cases. The stated views by the Church Leader in Bayelsa state articulated that,

"You know the oil companies are doing both onshore and offshore drilling, and at times, we have oil spillage, which affects our aquatic life" (Church Leader 2).

The Delta and Rivers State is a fishing community, so oil spillage affects most residents' economic livelihoods. Therefore, the primary SED perception is that while undertaking their oil extraction through onshore and offshore drilling, the Nigerian oil industries do not consider the social and environmental issues that might occur due to their oil operations.

5.3.4 Communication on SED Policy

The final core thematic insight that captures the host community's perceptions of the oil firms' SED practices relates to their SED policy's perceived communication. The communication of the oil firms' social and environmental policy is a crucial practice that enhances transparency regarding how the organisations consider social and ecological issues (Uwuike & Jimoh, 2012).

The Company Employee in Bayelsa Oil Company confirmed that the organisation he works for has a policy of reporting its annual SED practices through the Environmental Impact Assessment report (EIA). The EIA's publication, either as a standalone report or integrated within the yearly reports, allows the firms functioning in the Nigerian oil industry to communicate their SED policies to the relevant regulatory authorities such as the Department

of Petroleum Resources (DPR) and the public. For instance, the Company Employee from Bayelsa observed that,

"Normally, like this CSR, we mentioned. We produced an annual report to DPR (Department of Petroleum Resources) through NNPC (Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation). These are called Environmental Impact Assessments (EIA). On that report, all the environmental issues within the community in Bayelsa state will be identified by the Bayelsa oil company, and DPR makes sure that we don't violate those environmental laws." (Company Employee, 2).

The analysis of the interview extract based on the Company Management from Exxon Mobil also indicates that besides the EIA reports, the oil firms also utilised the local bulletins to inform the public and other internal stakeholders' commitment towards social and environmental issues. However, in relaying the local publications, Exxon Mobil Company relies on digital platforms (social media) and the mainstream media (newspapers and television). In this respect, the company management from Exxon Mobil acknowledged that,

"We use all the national dailies, but within the company, there wasn't at the time we had our local information bulleting that we publish activities that have to do with the community and also, it is for internal consumption" (Company Management 1).

The Company Management for Bayelsa Oil Company also confirmed that in most cases, they choose to go on air using the stated mainstream media platforms to convey their organisation's social and environmental performance practices.

"Most times, the traditional way is to go on air and media to tell the people what the company is doing for the host community, but a modern standard is also required that they disclose their financial statements, which we have not done yet." (Company Management 2).

However, when assessed from the host community's perspective, there is a different perception of the oil firms' practice of communicating their SED policies. The general feeling is that Nigerian oil firms tend to share their SED practices and procedures on paper without presenting evidence on how they have implemented their actions. During the interview, the Delta State academician acknowledged that the public tends to view their annual EIA and corporate sustainability reports with greater cynicism. In most cases, such statements are rarely scrutinised.

The limited scrutinisation or review of the annual sustainability reports has meant that some oil companies tend to doctor their reports to enhance their reputation (Mgbame & Mgbame, 2012). The scepticism in the analysis of the annual EIA and corporate sustainability reports articulated by the academician from Rivers State, who argues that,

"If you claim to have done this, it has to be true physically and not on mere paper" (Academician 4).

Moreover, the Community Youth Leader in Akwa Ibom State also concur that,

"There's nothing they have done. The oil company only come when they want to start spreading news; sometimes, many people don't benefit from it because they don't have upper hands" (Community Youth Leader 1).

Another concern, articulated by the Company Employee in Bayelsa State, Company Management in Akwa Ibom State and Academician in Delta state, pertains to the fact that few host communities have access to mainstream such as newspapers and television, and the social media platforms. Its means that even though the oil firms might issue regular EIA and corporate sustainability reports, their SED policy might not be available to many host communities' residents.

5.4 Thematic Codes on Social Environmental Challenges

The results based on the detailed analysis of the broad theme related to social and environmental challenges suggest that four principal specific thematic codes captured the difficulties the Nigerian oil and gas firms encountered in developing a robust SED policy framework. Figure 5.4 shows that these three thematic codes, which explain the challenges faced by the Nigerian oil firms in developing and promoting SED, include ineffective SED

policies, inadequate community support, limited interactions with the community, and funding issues.

Figure 5.4 Thematic Codes on Social and Environmental Issues

5.4.1 SED Policies

The detailed analysis of the thematic codes representing the Nigerian oil industries' social and environmental challenges indicates that low SED policies have mainly contributed to the current challenge in developing and implementing the SED policies. However, as noted by the Academician in Rivers State, the Nigerian oil firms seem to have disjointed social and environmental disclosure policies.

As a result of low SED policies, most of the social amenities and infrastructural projects funded by the oil firms are either short-term or low quality and, therefore, less sustainable for the communities' long-term benefits. The Academician in Rivers State raised his concern by arguing that,

"I have not seen any steps policy from the oil company.

If not, why are the communities complaining? Even this

electricity, before you know it, it's gone. So, there's nothing one can lay hands-on; this is what the companies are doing to promote the social, environmental impact on the people." (Academician 4).

Furthermore, the issue of low SED policies has also created a challenge in implementing the community development projects promised by some of the Nigerian oil industries. According to the host communities, especially the Church Leader in Delta State, their lack of commitment to implementing SED policies has resulted in empty promises, which sometimes take a long to implement. During the interview, the Church Leader in Delta State articulated this concern by stating that,

"Well, for the past year, there has always been promises, it has always been on the air, we are coming to do this, we are coming to do that, that is just what we hear, like the Ogoni cleansing that we heard, for how many years till now nothing has happened? They even made us understand that employment will take place and all the rest of them, but till today, nothing is happening."
(Church Leader, 4).

The stated challenge implies that the Nigerian oil firms' low SED policies do not allow them to set aside an appropriate financial budget and other resource commitments to fulfil the planned community development projects.

5.4.2 Interaction with Communities

The interviewees also noted the limited interaction with communities as one of the significant factor aspects contributing to the challenges of implementing and promoting SED practices among the Nigerian oil industries. As noted in the word frequency map presented in Table 5.5, the words "community" and "involve" were cited frequently based on the interview transcripts' analysis. An important issue raised by the Academician in Delta State is that most of the host communities in Nigeria are not aware of the social development initiatives funded by the oil industries. The stated concern primarily expounded because the Nigerian oil industries do not regularly interact with the host communities. In this respect, the Academician in Delta State suggests that an important strategy to address SED implementation challenges is for the oil industries to interact with the communities.

"There should be good interactions between the Oil Company and the Host Community. However, the community should be in the know of whatever they are doing. And once they are in the know, whatever information goes out, whether, in the newspaper or radio, the community will not be apprehensive; they will be okay with it because they are in the know. And they know that what the oil company are saying is true. And then I think some of these publications too should trickle down to the community, even if it is in their magazines, these community should also see it and acknowledge that it is true." (Academician 3).

Community Leader in Delta State further strengthened this by stating that:

"As I said before, I think they should come closer to the community. Let them communicate and interact with people more and better, okay." (Community Leader 3).

These sentiments were also concurred and shared by the church leader from the Akwa Ibom State, who contends that the oil company can address SED implementation's challenge when they bridge the gap between themselves and the community. The Church Leader argues that,

"The oil company can address these issues if they decide to bridge the gap between the people in the society and the oil company" (Church Leader 1).

When there are such interactions, informal platforms such as meetings organised by the oil firms, the host community is likely to raise several issues about how their oil operations affect the communities' social and environmental aspects. Interacting with communities is expected to address some of the SED implementation challenges and help restore the harmony and cohesiveness between the oil companies and the host community. The Church Leader in Rivers State observed that,

"If the Oil company can come down like we used to have before, say okay, they ring the jingles through the social media, radio stations, television, that so-so XYZ company will be coming to the so-so community tomorrow or next week or by so-so time. We want to see the community leaders; we want to see the youth leaders, church leader,

residents, market women, we want to have one on one talk by so doing it can create cohesion" (Church Leader 4).

Community Youth Leader in Delta State made comparable statements on the oil company towards communication with the host communities:

"Well, they can do things to improve their social, environmental disclosure. Many things can create harmony, but first and foremost, there should be constant town hall meetings between the oil company Shell and the host communities." (Community Youth Leader, 3).

As observed by the Academician from Delta State, the insinuation is that dialogue can be essential in mitigating some of the challenges between the oil firms and the communities.

5.4.3 Community Support

The insight from the interview transcripts' review indicates that lack of community support is one of the primary factors that have created challenges in effectively implementing the Nigerian oil industry's social and environmental disclosure practices. According to Uwuigbe and Jimoh (2012), there needs to be a significant reciprocal and supportive relationship between the oil firms and the host communities to address social and environmental issues, which might be unknown to most multinational oil firms. The stated aspect articulated by the Academician in Akwa Ibom State, who argues that,

"Sometimes, the oil companies are unaware that they have created these negative effects in the community"
(Academician 1).

This means that if there is mutual support from the communities, the two parties can effectively address some of the adverse social and negative effects arising from oil explorations, including onshore and offshore drilling. The implication based on the evaluation of the Academician's view is that strategies to minimise the oil firms' adverse social and environmental impact require concerted efforts from both the companies and the oil firms.

There is also a perception, especially among the Church Leaders, that the local oil companies, rather than the multinational firms, have considerable awareness of the local conditions. This means that it would not be fair for the local oil companies to claim that they don't have any knowledge of the possible adverse effects on social-cultural heritage because of their actions,

"The community is well known to the oil firms, and the companies have a better knowledge of the communities. So, they should devise a possible solution and carry the community along." *(Church Leader 1*

However, the same interviewees (church leaders) also acknowledged the importance of cooperation between the oil firms and the communities, which is likely to create considerable benefits to the community, stating that,

"Okay, if we cooperate to do this or that, we are likely to benefit in terms of support from the oil companies"
(Church Leader 1).

Therefore, the critical insight based on the interview extracts' analysis is that community support should be reciprocal if the oil firms succeed in effectively implementing their SED practices.

5.4.4 Funding

The final thematic code generated based on the detailed analysis of the social and environmental challenge node relates to limited funding. However, a limited budget, likely to restrict SED practices' effective implementation, was noted by the Company Management and Company Employees from Exxon Mobil and Bayelsa Oil Company. This sentiment was evident based on the interview with the Company Employee from Bayelsa Oil Company. According to him, the main challenge that has restricted the ability of the oil firms to implement their SED programs effectively is due to limited funding,

"The biggest challenge, if I can put it that way, is the funds to implement the Memorandum of Understanding. (MOU) with the host communities (Company Employee 2).

Basically, according to the insight from the interview with the Company Employee, Bayelsa Oil Company, financial challenges are exacerbated during the period when there are significant drops in the global price of oil,

"And I must be sincere to you; the host community expects us to implement every item on that MOU to the latter. For instance, in 2015-2016, we had a drop in oil prices that led us to shut down even the oil wells; we found out that what we spend is more than what we can produce, so that we couldn't shut it again down. And the community do not understand that. It took us time to bring them into the discussion and let them know our challenges, the reasons why we are shutting down"
(Company Employee 2)

Similar sentiments, based on the analysis of the interview extracts related to the Company Management, Bayelsa Oil Company indicate that limited funding has restricted the Nigerian oil firms' ability to fund various community development projects. In this respect, he admits that given the rise in the number of oil wells shutting, the funds set aside for undertaking corporate social responsibility appear to hit adversely during such challenging economic times. However, the company management states that,

"Right now, when our oil well is shutting, we don't have funding for supporting community development projects...so all this affected our relationship with the host community" *(Company Management 2).*

Therefore, the insightful critical finding from the analysis of the interview extracts is that limited funding, especially during challenging economic times, appears to have affected Nigerian oil and gas firms' ability to implement their SED practices effectively.

5.5 Summary of Findings

The central insight from the data analysis is the importance of the community as a critical stakeholder for the oil industries that operate in the Nigerian oil industry. The thematic codes from the NVivo data analysis software depict how the interview focused on the 'community' given that the word had a total frequency count of 1,091. The main themes about SED motivations based on the analysis of the interview transcripts, especially from the employee's and managers' perspectives, focused on the need to align social and environmental initiatives to community development plans and the attainment of community welfare needs. Besides, employees, company management and other stakeholders, especially the community residents, were mainly motivated to analyse the SED reports to assess how the oil industries' operations resulted in various social and environmental benefits and, or damages.

Concerning the community perception of SED, most external stakeholders, such as Community Leaders, Community Youth Leaders, Community Residents, Church Leaders, and the Academician, feel that the Nigerian oil firms do not directly involve them in determining the social and environmental projects they initiated. Furthermore, given the environmental pollution, which has resulted in low crop yields and fewer CSR activities, the external stakeholders generally perceive the Nigerian oil industries as less responsible corporate citizens. The other thematic aspect based on the SED perceptions is that most external stakeholders view the communication on SED policies as insufficient, especially given the inaccessible nature of the platforms used by the Nigerian oil firms to present their social and environmental disclosures.

Finally, the thematic coding of the Company Management and Company Employees' insight indicates that funding issues and lack of community support are some of the main challenges

that have affected the Nigerian oil firms' ability to engage in social and environmental disclosures. The other stakeholders' insight also indicates that inconsistent SED policies have contributed to the Nigerian oil firms' failure to undertake CSR activities regularly. The internal stakeholders (Management and Employees) and other external stakeholders acknowledge that some of the challenges in SED implementations are attributed to limited interaction between the Nigerian oil companies and the community. These will help to address the stated gaps in the systematic literature reviews.

CHAPTER SIX: RESULT FINDINGS 2: CONTENT ANALYSIS

6.1 Introduction

The thesis explores the extent of social and environmental disclosures in the Nigerian oil Industries: the results' data analysis and presentation are guided by the two research questions for this thesis. The two research questions for this thesis are specified as follows; What is the scope of social and environmental disclosures (SED) among the oil Industries that operate in Nigeria? And are there considerable differences in the social and environmental exposures (SEDs) among Nigeria's domestic and international oil industries?

The content analysis results are presented using two quantitative statistical approaches to explore SEDs' nature in the respective firms' annual reports (AR) and yearly sustainability reports. The content analysis outcome is presented using descriptive statistics in terms of the mean frequencies and the study of variance (ANOVA). The descriptive highlight the frequency of disclosures (i.e., quantified monetary, quantified non-monetary, narratives, and pictures) across the top five and the other top thirteen oil companies in Nigeria. The ANOVA statistical analysis presents data that facilitates evaluating whether the variation in the extent of SED is significant when assessed at the 5% threshold.

CONTENT ANALYSIS 1

6.2 Descriptive Analysis Results: The Extent of SED in the Nigerian Oil Industries

This section examines the scope of SED among the Nigeria oil Industries using the top 5 oil industries (International) and the other 13 Nigeria oil industries (Domestic) for analysis. The content analysis research design has evolved considerably in recent years to enhance understanding, consistency, and comparability of the subject materials, including the annual reviews and the yearly CSR reports (Duff 2016). Specifically, content analysis has improved markedly to capture variation in disclosures such as monetary, non-monetary, narrative and

visual information. Visual information materials such as photographs and pictures are considered valuable and play an essential role in enhancing the annual reviews and sustainability reports (Ekundayo, Yusuf & Samuel, 2016). This section highlights the descriptive statistics concerning the mean number of SEDs per firm and the frequency distribution in terms of SEDs' composition by types of disclosures among the top five and the thirteen other oil companies in Nigeria.

The insight based on the analysis of Table 6.2, Figure 6.1 and Figure 6.2 indicates the mean number of social and environmental disclosures (SEDs) by exposure as monetary, non-monetary, narratives pictures. The annual and CSR reports review shows that the narratives (discursive) are the dominant form of disclosures for the leading five and the other 13 oil industries in Nigeria. The description accounts for 69% and 62% of the primary forms of social and environmental disclosures across the top 5 oil industries and the other 13 Nigerian oil industries, respectively.

Table 6.1: Top Five and The Other Thirteen Oil Industries

S/N	NAME OF TOP 5 OIL INDUSTRIES	REPRESENTATION	S/N	NAME OF OTHER 13 OIL INDUSTRIES	REPRESENTATION
1	Chevron Nigeria. Lagos State, Nigeria	International	1	Ardova PLC. Lagos State, Nigeria. formally called Forte Oil PLC. Lagos State, Nigeria.	Domestic
2	Mobil Producing Nigeria Unlimited. Eket, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria	International	2	Anino International PLC.	Domestic
3	Shell Petroleum Development Company (SPDC). Delta State, Nigeria	International	3	Bayelsa Oil Company in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State, Nigeria	Domestic
4	Total Nigeria PLC	International	4	Capital Oil & Gas LTD.	Domestic

5	11 PLC	International	5	Caverton Offshore Support Group, Lagos State, Nigeria.	Domestic
			6	Conoil PLC	Domestic
			7	Eterna PLC, Lagos state, Nigeria	Domestic
			8	Japaul Oil & Maritime Services	Domestic
			9	Mrs. Oil Nigeria LTD	Domestic
			10	Nigeria LNG Limited (NLNG). Bonny Island, River State, Nigeria	Domestic
			11	Oando PLC. Lagos State, Nigeria.	Domestic
			12	RAK Unity Petroleum Company PLC.	Domestic
			13	Seplat Petroleum Development	Domestic

This table revealed the top 5 Nigerian oil industries and the other 13 Nigerian oil industries used to analysis the scope of SED among the Nigeria oil Industries.

Table 6.2: Mean Number of SED per Firm

Type of Disclosure	Nigerian Top 5 Oil Firms	Other Top 13 Nigerian Oil Firms	Total
Quantified Monetary	74.2 (12.1%)	32.4 (23.3%)	44.0 (16.3%)
Quantified Non-Monetary	78.4 (12.8%)	15.5 (11.1%)	32.9 (12.2%)
Narrative, Discursive	418.4 (68.5%)	86.0 (61.8%)	178.3 (66.0%)
Pictures	40. 6 (6.6%)	5.4 (3.9%)	15.2 (5.6%)
Total Number of SED per Firm	611.0 (100.0%)	139.2 (100.0%)	270.3 (100.0%)

The narratives/discursive constitute the significant types of SED disclosures with an average of 66% composition in the annual reports of the top 5 and the other 13 oil firms. The quantified monetary and non-monetary are the second and third most dominant form of SED disclosures. The visuals which average 5.6% of the SED presentation are the least applied form of disclosures.

Figure 6.1: Composition of SEDs per Firm: Top Five Nigerian Oil Industries

The composition of social and environmental disclosure per firm of the top five (5) Nigerian oil and gas firms in figure 6.1 include: - Narrative, Discursive 68%, Quantified Monetary 13%, Quantified Non- Monetary 12% and pictures are 7% respectively.

Figure 6.2: Composition of SEDs per Firm: Other 13 Nigerian Oil Industries

Figure 6.2 shows the composition of social and environmental disclosure per firm of the other 13 Nigerian oil industries: -Narrative, Discursive 62%, Quantified Monetary 11%, Quantified Non-Monetary 23% and pictures 4%.

The stated insight is consistent with the findings based on the study by Ekundayo et al. (2016). They observed that among the listed oil industries in Nigeria, the generic narrative SEDs accounted for 87.5% of the types of social and environmental disclosures in the respective firms' annual reports. The popularity of the records in presenting the annual sustainability reports and the CSR reports is enhanced because the presentation approach has a greater detail level, which can be crucial in explaining various aspects of the words (Odera, Scott & Gow, 2016). However, discursive SEDs' popularity appears to have declined among the other top 13 Nigerian oil companies.

The descriptive statistics information presented in Table 6.2 also reveals that besides the narrative forms, the quantified monetary SEDs are the second most dominant form of social

and environmental disclosures among the Nigerian oil and gas sector companies. The quantified financial disclosures accounted for 12.1% and 23.3% of all the disclosure forms among the big five (5) and the other 13 Nigerian oil companies. As a specific form of disclosure, the attractiveness of the quantified monetary SEDs has increased because a growing audience that includes government agencies, NGOs and the public are interested in the financial and budgetary allocations towards the CSR as well as the social and environmental initiatives (Ekanayake & Perera, 2014).

For instance, many stakeholders, especially the public, are mainly interested in ascertaining what proportion of their annual net income the oil and gas sector companies set aside to support the CSR initiatives and other community projects. The quantified monetary SEDs mainly included the dollar amount of donations, CSR budgetary allocations and contributions towards supporting community initiatives. For example, Exxon Mobil reported that during 2016, the oil and gas company contributed \$242 million to support social development projects across the globe.

The quantified non-monetary was the other form of SEDs incorporated in the annual reviews, annual sustainability reports and other CSR reports among the Nigerian oil companies. The quantified non-monetary form of SEDs constituted 12.8% and 11.1% of the big five and the other 13 oil industries in Nigeria. Ekundayo et al., 2016, stated that the numerical non-monetary social and environmental disclosures are primarily presented as actual numbers and percentages. An example of quantified non-monetary information is the 2018 annual report related to Exxon Mobil. The insight based on the report's review illustrates that 40% of the company's executive management employees were female over the past decade. Compared to the quantified monetary, the numerical non-monetary data is efficacious in presenting information on the level of social and environmental development projects (initiatives) supported by a given organisation (Olayiwola, 2010).

The insight based on the review of the mean number of SEDs by type of disclosure also depicts the growing popularity (attractiveness) of the visuals such as graphics, pictures and photographs, primarily incorporated in the annual and CSR sustainability reports for gas companies. The results show that visuals (i.e., graphics and pictures) constituted 6.6% of the SEDs among Nigeria's big five oil industries. On the other hand, among the other 13 Nigerian oil sector firms, the visuals constituted only 3.9% of the SEDs. In contrast to the insight based on similar empirical research by Sani (2018), where the average composition of visuals was 3% among the Nigerian oil industries, visuals' importance (graphics and pictures) seems to have increased substantially over the past four years.

The justification for the stated assertion is that among the top five Nigerian oil industries, the average composition of visuals (6.6%) is substantially higher when assessed against the reported proportion of visuals among the UK professional accounting firms from 2008-to-2010. The rising popularity of visuals as a form of social and environmental disclosures is enhanced by its potential to increase the understandability of the information presented in the annual reviews and the CSR reports (Ekundayo, Yusuf & Samuel, 2016). Most stakeholders, especially the public, usually focus on the visuals when reviewing the corporate organisations' annual and sustainability reports (Odera, Scott & Gow, 2016).

The insightful information based on the SEDs reports by types of disclosure reveals that the narratives (discursive) constitute the most dominant disclosures among Nigeria's Oil industries. As a form of SEDs, the records are associated with considerable detail and clarity. However, the popularity of visuals as a form of social and environmental disclosures has been spurred by its potential to enhance the understandability of social and ecological disclosures. The visuals included graphics and pictures incorporated within the Nigerian oil industries annual and sustainability reports.

6.3 Content Analysis Findings

Content analytics was integrated into the research as a data analysis technique to establish the extent and determinants of social and environmental disclosures among the Nigerian oil companies. This section aims to present the outcome of content analysis in terms of the average number of social and environmental exposure by firm size and SED component and the mean number of SED by type of disclosure. The insight is based on the review of the annual and annual sustainability reports of the Nigerian oil companies expected to generate productive information on SEDs extent across the Nigerian oil companies and the determining factor of social and environmental disclosures.

6.3.1 The Scope of SED in the Nigerian Oil Industries

The information in Table 6.3 depicts the mean number of SEDs by firm size and the specific component of social and environmental disclosure (SED). The results are given based on the Hackston and Milne (1996) model of SEDs reporting, which incorporates information on ecological conservation, customer welfare, employee welfare, energy conservation and community welfare. The community SEDs account for the highest focus on social and environmental disclosures. These are because, among the big five oil companies in Nigeria, the community aspect of social and environmental disclosure constituted 42% of the total SEDs. On the other hand, among the other 13 oil industries, the SEDs community aspect included 50% of the entire social and environmental disclosure during analysis, 2011-2018. The stated insight illustrates the importance of community social and environmental disclosure among the oil companies in Nigeria.

The significance of the community SEDs among the Nigerian oil industries is also expounded by the stakeholder theory, which emphasises the organisation's responsibility to disclose financial-related information for the owners and the owner's non-financial information for the

society (Davison, 2010). The insinuation is that the Nigerian oil industries' focus has slightly shifted towards meeting the public social welfare needs (Ekundayo, Yusuf & Samuel, 2016). Furthermore, as Sani (2018) noted, providing information on social benefits can be accounted for by the organisation's desire to earn legitimate public recognition. The companies would see the information that has a considerable advantage in social welfare as socially responsible.

The outcome of the mean number of disclosures by firm size and SED category also illustrates that employee disclosures are the second most crucial aspect of social and environmental exposure. The data in Table 6.3 shows that among the top 5 Nigerian oil companies, 27% of the total disclosures focused on providing employee-related information. On the other hand, among the remaining 13 Nigerian oil industries, 30% of the SED disclosures related to information on employee social welfare aspects. This means that among the Nigerian oil industries, the employees are considered critical strategic human resources to the extent of effectiveness of the organisations' employee welfare programs assessed and reported regularly. Reporting employee welfare information is an essential aspect, given its effect on staff motivation and morale (Campbell, 2007).

However, the most striking insight based on the analysis of the information presented in Table 6.3 is that energy resource conservation issues have not been given more significant consideration among the big 18 Nigerian oil companies. Only 5% of the total SED focused on energy conservation disclosures among the top five Nigerian oil industries. Furthermore, among the other top 13 Nigerian oil firms, the energy composition related to the SED disclosures is only 1%. The statistics show that among the Nigerian oil industries, the information on energy conservation is less priority when assessed against the other aspects of social and environmental disclosures. The big five oil industries in the country appear to have

placed slightly greater emphasis on disclosing their energy conservation initiatives or actions when assessed against the other top 13 Nigerian oil industries.

Similarly, Nigeria's top five oil industries also seem to have a slightly higher focus on environmental aspects than the other big 13 oil industries. The stated revelation informed that environmental disclosures account for 16% of the total SED among the big five oil industries in the country compared to the 10% constituent related to the other big 13 oil industries in Nigeria. The insinuation based on the analysis is that due to their reputation, the big five oil and industries in Nigeria appreciate the importance of environmental conservation, which is likely to raise their overall image of environmentally sustainably corporate entities. Finally, the two categories of Nigerian oil industries seem to emphasize the importance of the customers. The reason is that the customer welfare disclosure composition of the total SED was 10% among the top five Nigerian oil industries. The other big 13 oil industries had 9% of their total SED, capturing the customer welfare disclosures.

Therefore, in terms of the SED scope among the Nigerian oil industry companies, the main factors influencing the nature of social and environmental disclosures are the community welfare, employee welfare and environmental responsibility disclosures. These three SED components account for 85% and 90% of the total SED among the top five and the other big 13 Nigerian oil industries. The community welfare disclosures account for the largest SED's constituent in the top five and other big 13 oil industries in the country. The key insightful conclusion from the analysis is that based on their financial power and resource strength, the Nigerian oil industries appreciate the importance of supporting the communities in line with the theoretical legitimacy framework.

Deegan (2002) explains that the stated strategic social initiatives present such firms with a more significant competitive advantage that allows them to charge a premium price. The

analysis also found that despite the increased focus on the community (social), employees and environmental disclosures, the other factors determining the social and environmental exposures among the Nigerian oil industries pertain to the customer welfare and the energy disclosures. The two SED aspects accounted for slightly less than 20% of the Nigerian oil industries' total social and environmental exposures.

Table 6.3: Mean Number of Disclosure by Firm Size and SED Component

Component of SED Disclosure	Top 5 Nigerian Oil Firms	Other Top 13 Nigerian Oil Firms	Total
Environment:			
Pollution	8.8	1.6	3.6
Wastes	27.8	1.4	8.7
Awards	7.2	0.7	2.5
Anti-litter	0.0	0.0	0.0
Waste Recycling	2.4	0.1	0.7
Natural Resource Conservation	10.4	1.4	3.9
Compliance with Anti-Pollution Laws	3.6	2.5	2.8
Total Environmental Disclosures	60.2	7.6	22.2
Total Environmental Disclosure (%)	16%	10%	11%
Energy:			
Energy Conservation	14.0	1.0	4.6
Energy Policies	1.6	0.1	0.5
Awards	3.8	0.2	1.2
Total Energy Disclosures	19.4	1.2	6.3

Total Energy Disclosure (%)	5%	1%	2%
Customers:			
Customer Safety	27.2	7.9	13.3
Customer Complaints	0.6	0.4	0.4
Customer Relations	8.0	2.2	3.8
Provision for Disabled	0.0	0.1	0.1
Total Client Disclosures	35.8	10.5	17.6
Total Client Disclosure (%)	10%	9%	9%
Community:			
Involvement in Community Initiatives	7.8	5.5	6.2
Charitable Donations	43.6	5.4	16.0
Educational Sponsorship	29.0	3.8	10.8
Public Health Initiatives	52.0	12.0	23.1
Sports Sponsorships	1.4	1.3	1.3
Pro-bono	0.0	0.0	0.0
Total Community Disclosures	133.8	28.1	57.4
Total Community Disclosure (%)	42%	50%	48%
Employee:			
Health and Safety	23.8	4.9	10.2
Diversity: Women and minorities	23.8	2.2	8.2
Training	42.8	11.6	20.3
Benefits	6.2	3.2	4.0
Welfare	0.6	3.8	2.9
Awards	3.0	0.0	0.8

Total Employee Disclosures	100.2	25.7	46.4
Total Employee Disclosure (%)	27%	30%	29%
Total SEDs	349.4	73.2	149.9

The mean SED disclosures on community and employee welfare sustainability comprise social, environmental disclosures in the top 5 and the remaining 13 oil industries in Nigeria. The top 5 Nigerian oil industries report the higher mean level of SED than the other remaining 13 oil industries.

Figure 6.3: Mean Number of SED by Firm Size and Component

6.3.2 The Extent and Variation in SED Among Nigerian Oil Industries

The analysis of variance (ANOVA) is an effective statistical tool that facilitates evaluating whether the observed deviations in values about two or more variables are significant or caused by randomness (Odera et al., 2016). The ANOVA statistical results presented in table 6.4 includes a presentation of the paired sample tests concerning the mean difference in the extent of SED among the Nigerian top five and the remaining 13 oil industries in the country.

The results show that the mean difference in the SED scores ($MD = 10.62$; $\rho < 0.05$) is positive and statistically significant when assessed at the $\alpha 0.05$ level. The implication based on analysis of the mean SED differentials among the Nigerian top 18 oil industries is that there is an apparent variation in their focus and reporting on social and environmental sustainability issues.

Specifically, given the positive mean difference, the big five oil industries in the country have a considerably higher focus on social and environmental sustainability issues when assessed against the remaining 13 Nigerian oil industries. The ANOVA outcome confirms that the mean difference in SED is statistically significant, given that the ‘between groups’ sum of squares ($SS = 1467.54$) has a statistically substantial F-statistic ($F = 11.92$; $\rho < 0.05$). The key inferential conclusion based on the ANOVA outcome is that the difference in the mean SED among the top five and the remaining 13 Nigerian oil industries is substantial when analysed and assessed at the 5% statistical threshold level.

Table 6.4 Summary of the ANOVA Results

	Mean Difference	t-statistics	ρ -value
SED (Top 5 Oil Firms) – SED (Other Top 13 Oil Firms)	10.62	4.25**	0.000

$\rho^{**} < 0.05$

ANOVA	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	F-statistic	ρ -value
Between Groups	1467.54	1467.54	11.92**	0.001
Within Groups	6156.30	123.13		
Total	7623.83			

$\rho^{**} < 0.05$

The outcome of the one-way ANOVA depicts that there is no significant variation in the Nigerian domestic oil industries' focus on different aspects of social and environmental disclosures. The mean difference of the SEDs variations for all possible alternative combinations in SEDs is not significant given that $p > 0.05$. However, the mean disparity when assessed in terms of the community SEDs appears to be substantially large despite the non-significance.

Table 6.5 One-Way ANOVA Test Results: Variation in SED among Domestic Oil Industries

(I) SED	(J) SED	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Environmental SED	Energy SED	1.0476	2.6685	0.995
	Client SED	-.7232	2.4238	0.998
	Community SED	-3.9107	2.1514	0.390
	Employee SED	-2.1468	2.1514	0.853
Energy SED	Environmental SED	-1.0476	2.6685	0.995
	Client SED	-1.7708	2.9535	0.974
	Community SED	-4.9583	2.7344	0.393
	Employee SED	-3.1944	2.7344	0.769
Client SED	Environmental SED	.7232	2.4238	0.998
	Energy SED	1.7708	2.9535	0.974
	Community SED	-3.1875	2.4962	0.708
	Employee SED	-1.4236	2.4962	0.978

Community SED	Environmental SED	3.9107	2.1514	0.390
	Energy SED	4.9583	2.7344	0.393
	Client SED	3.1875	2.4962	0.708
	Employee SED	1.7639	2.2326	0.931
Employee SED	Environmental SED	2.1468	2.1514	0.853
	Energy SED	3.1944	2.7344	0.769
	Client SED	1.4236	2.4962	0.978
	Community SED	-1.7639	2.2326	0.931

- **Environmental SED Component:**

The detailed analysis of the mean SED disclosures by firm size and the SED category illustrates the critical role of the five (5) components of social and environmental exposures formulated by Hackston Milne (1996). The detailed insight into the analysis information is presented in Table 6.4. The ANOVA results in Table 6.4 reveal that the top five Nigerian oil industries, including Shell, Exxon Mobil, Chevron, Total and NLNG, appear to have emphasised reporting environmental sustainability aspects such as pollution, waste management and natural resources resource conservation. The mean number of SED for corrosion, waste management and natural resource conservation related to the big five Nigerian oil industries is significantly higher than the corresponding SED disclosures associated with the stated three sub-components. For instance, in its 2012 annual report, Shell Petroleum Development Company (SPDC) emphasises its commitment to reducing pollution by noting that the oil company has pledged to support the Hydrocarbon Pollution Restoration Project (SPDC Annual Report 2012).

Furthermore, in its annual report for the year 2011, NLNG also confirms its no pollution commitment by reporting that the organisation set aside \$10 million for funding the Hydrocarbon Pollution and Remediation Project (NLNG Annual Report 2011). Also, Exxon Mobil said in its 2017 Annual Report that the organisation had placed a reliable, comprehensive mechanism to mitigate the adverse air and marine pollution effect in an oil spill directly attributed to its operations. The stated disclosures and financial commitments by the big five oil companies in the country highlight that environmental sustainability issues, including pollution, waste management, and natural resource conservation, are given greater priority by the big five oil industries in the country.

Besides the focus on environmental pollution, waste management, and natural resource conservation, the issues about compliance with the relevant anti-pollution legislation have also formed a considerable part of the Nigerian oil industries' reported disclosures. The big five oil industries in the country had a significant extent of environmental exposure to their overall compliance with the anti-pollution legislation compared to the other top 13 oil industries. Compliance with environmental conservation and anti-pollution legislation has become an essential aspect that new organisations evaluate regarding their overall commitment to environmental sustainability (Ekanayake & Perera, 2014). The big five oil industries had a considerably higher level of disclosures about the extent of adherence to the anti-pollution laws than the remaining 13 oil industries in the country. For instance, in its 2014 Annual Report, Exxon Mobil acknowledges that the company's reliable and helpful information management system appears to have enhanced its reputation in complying with anti-pollution legislation across more than 150 countries where it operates.

On the other hand, regarding the Sagbama LGA project, SPDC reported in its year 2018 Annual Report that the organisation had been concerned with its overall non-compliance with the Environmental Impact Assessment policy. Similarly, on issues about compliance with the

anti-pollution legislation, Total Nigeria Plc. Acknowledges the critical role of the company's risk and legal compliance department in ensuring that the organisation adheres to all the anti-pollution legislation in key markets (Total Annual Report 2018). The non-compliance with environmental legislation has a considerable adverse effect on the organisation's reputation as socially and environmentally responsible corporate citizens (Picard, Durocher & Gendron, 2014).

In terms of the environmental sustainability disclosures, the insight based on the analysis of Table 6.3 reveals that both the big five oil industries and the other remaining top 13 oil industries rarely reported the issues of anti-litter and waste recycling in the annual reports for the period, 2011-2018. These are because the mean number of anti-litter SED (0.0) and waste recycling (0.7) is considered very low to meet the required environmental sustainability disclosure threshold. The environmental pollution and common natural resource conservation issues have been attributed to the lack of corporate responsibility in supporting anti-litter and waste management (recycling) policies (Ekundayo, Yusuf & Samuel, 2016). The limited environmental sustainability disclosures on anti-litter and waste recycling are pretty alarming. Only a few companies have reported such Information among the big 18 Nigerian oil industries. Specifically, Oando, Total and Exxon Mobil reported on their overall responsibility and commitment to waste recycling.

- **Energy SED Component:**

The detailed review of the Information depicted in Table 6.3 also shows that despite the limited disclosures on energy conservation matters, the Nigerian big five oil industries appeared to offer a more significant commitment to energy sustainability. Virtually, the big five oil industries in the country outperformed their counterparts in terms of investment in

energy conservation initiatives, formulation of energy policies and recognition in the form of energy conservation awards. Specifically, the difference in energy SED disclosures was quite significant when assessed in energy conservation initiatives. For instance, in their respective annual reports for 2011-2018, both Total and SPDC seem to focus on disclosing their commitments to energy efficiency, energy optimisation, and the integration of solar energy solutions. Specifically, in its year 2015 Annual Report, Total Nigeria Plc. Reports that as part of the company's 15-year agreement for Solar Hybrid Solution, the oil firm has installed solar energy in 50 stations across the state of Ogun, Nigeria. The energy-efficient T-air stations and refrigerators also enabled Total to lower its energy consumption by 80% (Total Annual Report 2013).

The most exciting aspect based on the review of the energy sustainability disclosures is that among the Nigerian 18 oil industries, the majority of them appear to lack formal energy policies. Standard energy policies are essential because such plans and rules guide strategic and operational decisions. The lack of standard energy policies evidenced by the mean number of energy sustainability SED was only 1.6 among the big five oil companies and 0.1 across the remaining 13 Nigerian oil industries. The detailed review of the annual report for Ardova Plc (formally Fort Oil) reveals that it's one of the few oil companies with a formal energy policy that applies across the energy value chain.

Similarly, among the big five oil industries in Nigeria, SPDC also reports that the company has formulated various energy sustainability policies that guide its operations. Finally, the big five Nigerian oil industries had more significant energy conservation and energy policy awards when assessed against their competitors, constituting the other 13 oil industries. The implication is that the top five oil industries receive greater recognition in their efforts to promote energy sustainability than their counterparts. The central factor that explains the exceptional energy sustainability performance and disclosures among the big five oil

industries is their more significant financial, technical, and human resource potential than the limited resources associated with the remaining 13 oil industries.

- **Customers SED Component:**

The extent to which corporate entities meet the customer welfare needs in terms of quality, pricing, safety, and meeting the needs of the disabled is also considered an essential aspect of social and environmental disclosure (Terlaak, 2007). The comprehensive insight based on the detailed analysis of the mean number of SED across the Nigerian oil industry depicted in Table 6.3 illustrates significant variations in overall customer welfare disclosures. The big five Nigerian oil industries compared favour when assessed against the remaining 13 oil industries concerning customer safety issues. The mean number of customer safety disclosures among the big five industries (27.2) was considerably higher than the corresponding exposures associated with the other remaining top 13 oil industries (7.9). In this regard, Exxon Mobil reports that the oil industry has been operating a safety leadership forum for its clients and contractors since 2000 (Exxon Mobil Annual Report 2018). The company has also been coordinating its road safety initiatives with the Federal Road Safety Corps to minimise the number of accidents. Similarly, Eterna Oil, among the other 13 oil industries in Nigeria, appears to acknowledge its overall commitment to promoting customer safety by stating in its 2018 Annual Report that the organisation's operations are executed safely to protect human lives and prevent accidents".

The big five oil industries in the country have also reported exceptional customer relations disclosures compared to the remaining 13 oil industries. Customer relations is an important marketing strategy that enables corporate entities to interact with customers and clarify any

issues about product offerings (Odera et al., 2016). However, based on the review of the annual report, there are limited customer complaints disclosures among the 18 Nigerian oil industries. For instance, only SPDC and Total Nigeria report in their respective annual reports that they have a robust customer complaints management system that allows the clients and the general community to log in various complaints. In terms of the other remaining 13 oil industries, only Ardova Plc. It appears to acknowledge that it has invested in a customer complaints log system where the community can raise various issues about its social and environmental initiatives (Ardova Annual Report 2017).

The disclosures related to the provisions for the disabled are minimal based on the comprehensive analysis of the mean SED across the big 18 oil industries in Nigeria. The investment in initiatives that cater to the needs of disabled customers is a critical social sustainability aspect that can enhance a company's overall public image, legitimacy, and reputation (Olayiwola, 2010). The mean number of social and environmental disclosures that captured aspects related to provisions for the disabled was only 0.1 across all the 18 Nigerian oil industries. These show that across the top five oil companies and the remaining 13 oil industries, only a few companies reported on matters about the provisions for the disabled. For instance, among the 18 oil industries incorporated in this study, only 11 Plc. said that it had allocated N200,000 in donations to support its Disabled Sports Development Services (DSDS) program. The implication is that the focus on disclosures about the disabled is very limited to the extent that less than 5% of the sampled oil industries have disclosures that focus on the provisions for the disabled.

- **Community SED Component:**

The primary category of the overall social and environmental disclosures (SED) noted the community SED component. The need to support community initiatives and the consistent desire to attain social welfare objectives has been considered an essential aspect of social and

environmental sustainability, especially among the Nigerian oil industries, which generate substantial revenues (Ekundayo et al., 2016). The importance of aligning the community initiatives to the social and environmental sustainability plans expounded by the fact that there is a renewed level of expectation among the public that the multi-billion-dollar industries such as the Nigerian oil industry have a considerable moral obligation to support the communities (Odera et al., 2016).

The insight based on the review of the detailed mean social and environmental disclosure by the firm and SED category depicts that the three main aspects of the community disclosures include charitable donations, educational sponsorships, and investment in public health initiatives. Regarding philanthropic contributions, there is an apparent variation among the two groups of Nigerian oil industries regarding the disclosure of financial and non-monetary donations that are channelled towards the support of the community initiatives. For instance, as part of its CSR initiatives, Chevron Oil Company reported in the 2018 Annual Report that the company contributed \$2.5 million to support the anti-retroviral therapy program, which benefits close to 20,000 people and helps reduce the chances of mother-to-child HIV transmissions.

Moreover, as one of the big five oil industries in the country, Exxon Mobil also reported \$269 million in contributions channel towards assisting community-based organisations worldwide in 2013 (Exxon Mobil Annual Report 2014). The remaining 13 oil industries also made reasonably significant strides in charitable donations. For instance, in its 2018 Annual Report, Eterna reported that the oil company contributed N4.85 million to philanthropic institutions and organisations across the country. The trends highlight charitable donations' critical role as a crucial aspect of the oil companies' community welfare sustainability initiatives.

The other aspect of community welfare sustainability disclosures that has received considerable attention pertains to educational scholarships and public health initiatives. The

big five oil industries had higher reported SED disclosures on educational sponsorships and public health support initiatives when assessed against the other big 13 oil industries. Virtually, in its 2016 Annual Report, Exxon Mobil reports that the oil industries have contributed approximately \$1.2 billion to support the education programs across the globe. Chevron Nigeria also disclosed that in 2016, 5,424 scholarships were awarded to students from its education foundations program. Furthermore, as one of the other 13 remaining oil industries, Oando also reported that it offered 30 education scholarship programs to the less fortunate disabled students across the country. Based on the insightful review of the mean number of SED disclosures across the Nigerian oil industries, the implication is that an essential aspect of community support initiatives mainly pertains to education scholarships and other education sponsorship initiatives.

The Information presented in Table 6.3 also illustrates that there has been a substantial focus on public health initiatives, especially among the top five oil industries in the country. The emphasis on health evidenced the financial and non-monetary commitments associated with the big five oil industries and the remaining 13 oil industry entities. In this respect, the insight based on the Exxon Mobil Annual Report's review for the year 2016 reveals that the organisation has made substantial commitments to supporting public health initiatives. For instance, in 2016, Exxon Mobil allocated \$155 million to support the public health initiatives, which was set aside to train more than 589,000 health workers. Furthermore, during 2015, Total also donated N200,000 to support Koko Primary Health Centre in Nigeria. The other remaining 13 Nigerian oil industries also made substantial contributions to the investments in public health initiatives. In this respect, Oando reported that the oil company allocated N119.62 million that was set aside to support doctors' and nurses' training and aid the construction of various hospital facilities.

However, as part of the community support initiatives, the Nigerian oil industry's role in supporting sports initiatives has also increased considerably, given the numerous sports events and tournaments geared towards helping the youths. The two categories of Nigerian oil industries reported somewhat similar disclosures; the top 18 oil industries did not give the sport more significant consideration on sponsorships. For example, as part of the N3.84 million sponsorship program, Total Nigeria supported the St. Teresa Interhouse Sports program, which was considered an essential aspect of its overall commitment to sports sponsorship. The oil industry was also involved in several major football competition sponsorship programs, such as the Total Africa Cup of Nation tournaments. Among the other 13 Nigerian oil industries, Seplat Company also reported its sponsorship of the Omweri Sports Club, which only cost N2,946 in 2018.

Moreover, an essential aspect of concern regarding the community welfare sustainability disclosure is that none of the 18 Nigerian oil industries reports Information on pro-bono corporate social responsibility initiatives. The pro-bono initiatives, which are voluntary non-monetary staff initiatives undertaken by employees, can help raise the overall reputational image of corporate entities. However, across the Nigerian industries, it appears that there is limited appreciation of the role that pro-bono CSR initiatives can play in enhancing the public goodwill of the oil industries.

The final sub-component of the social and environmental disclosures also indicates evident variations in the employee welfare reporting among the big five oil industries and the other 13 oil industries. The main differences are attributed to the issues of employee health, safety, diversity, and employee training. The fact that employees are critical strategic resources implies that most organisations have invested in employee welfare programs to support their growth and development (Duff, 2016). The difference in employee health and safety disclosures among the big five and the remaining 13 Nigerian oil industries is attributed to

financial resources and leadership commitment. For instance, during the financial year 2018, Total Nigeria and SPDC indicated that they had set up effective employee safety regulations, which were supplemented by effective training programs to minimise accidents.

Similarly, Exxon Mobil also showed its employee health and safety program's effectiveness in 2017. According to the Year 2017 Annual Report for Exxon Mobil, the oil industries managed to reduce the number of employee-related accidents and incidences of lost time by up to 80% during 2016. Besides lowering the number of litigations associated with workplace injuries, the employee health and safety programs, which have a considerable positive effect on enhancing staff welfare, are also expected to raise the overall level of staff motivations (Parker, 2005).

The level of employee SED disclosures that capture the organisations' commitment to employee diversity in terms of responsibility towards recruiting women and other minorities shows apparent differences between the two oil companies in Nigeria. The big five oil industries in the country reported a higher mean average level of employee diversity when assessed against the related disclosures associated with the other 13 oil industries in Nigeria. In the company's 2018 annual report, Exxon Mobil demonstrated its commitment to women, minorities, and other indigenous people.

The company reported that the women and other minority groups among its senior management team comprised more than 30% of the entire management team. Furthermore, in 2017, Shell Petroleum Development Company (SPDC) also indicated its commitment to recruiting female employees and graduates as part of its workforce. In 2017, SPDC reported that 22% of its senior leadership comprised female managers, while over 50% of the graduate employees were females. Additionally, in 2016, Total said that as part of its staff welfare program targeted toward the female and other minority employees, the company organised a

female hygiene program. The stated insight illustrates the significance of attaining female and other minority staff's needs as part of the overall social and environmental responsibility.

Finally, employee training, benefits and awards were also somewhat noted as essential aspects of the employee welfare sustainability reporting, especially among the big five oil industries in the country. As a result of their substantial financial resources, the big five Nigerian oil industries have invested heavily in employee training and other initiatives seeking to raise staff motivation. In this regard, Exxon Mobil reported that as part of its employee development program, the company placed its staff in an employee training program focused on human rights education and awareness. On the other hand, Seplat also reported in the 2018 annual report that the company has spent over \$8 million since 2014 on employee education and training. The detailed analysis of all the 18 oil industries' annual accounts indicates a limited focus on employee benefits, awards, and other welfare program disclosures.

6.3.3 The Extent and Variation in SED by Types of Disclosures

The type of SED document also appears to be a significant fact that influences the understandability and clarity of the social and environmental disclosures (Sani, 2018). Due to its detail and clarity level, the narrative/discursive documents have been the primary conventional form of SED disclosures over the year. However, recently, due to the need for succinct information, which is highly understandable, the use of pictures, including graphics and other visual aids, has become evident in most annual financial reports and yearly sustainability documents that are presented by corporate entities across the globe (Ekundayo et al., 2016; Odera et al., 2016). Besides the popularity of pictures, the presentation of quantitative monetary and non-monetary information also seems to have become evident

when reviewing the new corporate entities' annual financial and sustainability reports (Duff, 2016).

The insight based on the mean SEDs review by type of disclosures in Table 6.4 and Figure 2 depicts that the narratives/discursive is the main form of exposure adopted by the Nigerian oil industries when presenting their social and environmental disclosures in their respective annual reports. The Information indicates that oil companies mainly use the narratives in presenting environmental, employee welfare, customer welfare, energy, and community welfare sustainability disclosures. Because, on average, the mean SED (504.4) for the narratives (discursive) was the highest form of disclosure compared to the quantified monetary (106.6), the quantified non-monetary (93.9), and the pictures (46.0).

An in-depth analysis shows that the narratives/discursive applied in presenting SED information about the community and employee welfare disclosures. The implication is that the narratives constitute the primary type of disclosure in giving community and employee welfare information. The stated outcome is consistent with Sani's (2018) findings, which also observed the narratives' dominant use in presenting social and environmental disclosures in the UK professional accounting firms' annual reports.

The Nigerian oil sector companies also consistently applied the quantified monetary and non-monetary types of disclosures. The outcome of the Information depicted in Table 6.6 and Figure 6.4 shows that the combined mean number of SED for the quantified financial and non-monetary Information is 200.5. The stated insight shows the growing popularity of the numerical (quantitative) disclosures among the Nigerian oil industries. Specifically, the increased popularity of quantitative monetary and non-monetary disclosures is accounted for by the public's growing expectation for corporate entities to report their social and environmental commitments in numerical terms.

For instance, an essential concern among customers and the public is the proportion of annual corporate income set aside to support community development initiatives. As opposed to narratives, Information can only disclose in the quantitative form (Sani, 2018). The inferential conclusion based on the analysis of the annual reports for the 18 Nigerian oil industries reveals that most of them reported their level of charitable donations and investment in community development initiatives in the form of dollars and percentage allocations. The popularity of the quantitative monetary and non-monetary Information expounded because it is easily understandable, objective, and comparable compared to the discursive, which can interpret qualitative techniques that are often less reliable (Campbell, 2007). The stated aspects have enhanced the quantified monetary and non-monetary reports in presenting social and environmental (SED) disclosures among new organisations, including the Nigerian oil industries.

The significance of visual-based Information such as pictures, graphics and charts has increased over the past two decades, spurred by technological innovation (Sani, 2018). For instance, the proliferation of 3-D technology has meant that most corporate annual reports integrate pictures and visuals that clearly illustrate the organisations' social and environmental sustainability commitments. The review detailed in Table 6.5 and Figure 6.4 shows that despite the reasonable restrictions on the integration of visuals, such as pictures and graphics in the annual reports of the Nigerian oil industries, the mean number of SEDs (46) related to the images, is slightly higher compared to the use among the Nigerian oil industries as reported by Ekundayo et al. (2016). The rise in popularity of the visuals as a form of social and environmental disclosure is also enhanced because the pictures, graphics and images have a considerable potential to improve the reports' understandability primarily from the users' perspectives (Ekundayo et al., 2016). There is growing optimism that the

composition of visuals, such as graphics and images in the annual reports of contemporary corporate organisations will increase in the future (Sani, 2018).

Table 6.6: Mean SEDs by Types of Disclosure

Types of Disclosure	Quantified Monetary	Quantified Non-Monetary	Narrative/ Discursive	Pictures	Average
Environment:					
Pollution	2.6	2.3	12.4	1.1	4.6
Wastes	7.4	6.5	34.9	3.2	13.0
Awards	2.0	1.8	9.4	0.9	3.5
Anti-litter	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Waste Recycling	0.6	0.6	3.0	0.3	1.1
Natural Resource Conservation	3.0	2.6	14.1	1.3	5.2
Compliance with Anti-Pollution Laws	1.5	1.4	7.3	0.7	2.7
Total Environmental Disclosures	17.1	15.1	81.0	7.4	30.2
Energy:					
Energy Conservation	3.8	3.3	17.9	1.6	6.7
Energy Policies	0.4	0.4	2.0	0.2	0.8
Awards	1.0	0.9	4.8	0.4	1.8
Total Energy Disclosures	5.2	4.6	24.7	2.3	9.2
Customers:					
Customer Safety	8.9	7.8	41.9	3.8	15.6

Customer Complaints	0.3	0.2	1.2	0.1	0.4
Customer Relations	2.6	2.3	12.2	1.1	4.5
Provision for Disabled	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0
Total Client Disclosures	11.7	10.3	55.4	5.1	20.6
Community:					
Involvement in Community Initiatives	3.4	3.0	15.9	1.4	5.9
Charitable Donations	12.4	10.9	58.5	5.3	21.8
Educational Sponsorship	8.3	7.3	39.1	3.6	14.6
Public Health Initiatives	16.1	14.2	76.4	7.0	28.4
Sports Sponsorships	0.7	0.6	3.2	0.3	1.2
Pro-bono	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Total Community Disclosures	40.8	36.0	193.1	17.6	71.9
Employee:					
Health and Safety	7.2	6.4	34.3	3.1	12.7
Diversity: Women and minorities	6.6	5.8	31.0	2.8	11.5
Training	13.7	12.1	64.9	5.9	24.2
Benefits	2.4	2.1	11.2	1.0	4.2
Welfare	1.1	1.0	5.3	0.5	2.0
Awards	0.8	0.7	3.6	0.3	1.3
Total Employee Disclosures	31.8	28.0	150.3	13.7	55.9
Total SEDs	106.6	93.9	504.4	46.0	187.7

The narratives/discursive constitute the main form of SED disclosure. The quantified monetary and the non-monetary SED information are equally applied by the Nigerian oil industries' visuals being the least applied form of SED reports.

Figure 6.4: Mean SEDs by Types of Disclosure

6.4 Normality Tests and Kruskal-Wallis Test for Extent of SED

This section aims to ascertain whether the SED score data meet the normality test assumption, which is essential for conducting most parametric tests and multiple regression analyses. This section also presents the outcome of variation in SED based on the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test. The study begins with the normality tests, followed by the Kruskal-Wallis test.

6.4.1 Normality Tests

The normality tests for the Shapiro-Wilk test reveal that the SED score data is usually distributed. The standard distribution assumption for the extent of SED in Nigerian domestic

and international companies was met. The Shapiro-Wilk statistics presented in Table 6.7 and Table 6.8 have a significance (ρ -value > 0.05) greater than the statistical threshold of 5%. Therefore, the inferential conclusion is that the SED score data for Nigerian international and domestic oil companies meet the normality assumption.

Table 6.7 Normality Tests for Extent of SED in Nigerian Domestic Oil Industries

	Shapiro-Wilk Statistic	ρ-value
Environmental SED	0.858	0.145
Energy SED	0.893	0.363
Client SED	0.892	0.391
Community SED	0.925	0.545
Employee SED	0.833	0.113

Table 6.8 Normality Tests for Extent of SED in International Oil Industries

	Shapiro-Wilk Statistic	ρ-value
Environmental SED	0.963	0.843
Energy SED	0.850	0.241
Client SED	0.734	0.027
Community SED	0.885	0.292
Employee SED	0.899	0.370

6.4.2 Non-Parametric Kruskal-Wallis Tests

The non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test for Nigerian domestic oil companies depicted in Table 6.18 indicates that domestic oil companies gave community SED reporting more significant consideration due to its higher mean rank (MR = 17.08) followed by the employee SED (MR = 15.83). However, the energy SED reporting (MR = 8.83) had a minor rank among the Nigerian domestic oil industries.

Table 6.9 Kruskal-Wallis Test: Differences in SED by Components for Nigerian Domestic Oil Industries

	Number of Observations	Mean Rank	Rank Position
Community SED	6	17.08	1
Employee SED	6	15.83	2
Client SED	4	12.25	3
Environmental SED	7	11.14	4
Energy SED	3	8.83	5
Chi-square (χ^2) Statistic	3.78		
Sig (ρ -value)	0.437		

The Kruskal-Wallis results in Table 6.10 reveal that among the Nigerian international oil industries, the employee SED reporting (MR = 16.83) ranked higher than the community SED reporting (MR = 15.92). The implication is that most Nigerian international oil industries tend to prioritise employee disclosures compared to community disclosures. However, as depicted by the chi-square statistic ($\chi^2 = 3.31$; $\rho = 0.508 > 0.05$), the mean rank variation is slightly less significant when assessed at the 5% statistical threshold level.

Table 6.10 Kruskal-Wallis Test: Differences in SED by Components for International Oil Firms

	Number of Observations	Mean Rank	Rank Position
Employee SED	6	16.83	1
Community SED	6	15.92	2
Environmental SED	7	11.71	3
Client SED	4	10.50	4
Energy SED	3	10.17	5
Chi-square (χ^2) Statistic	3.31		
Sig (p-value)	0.508		

6.5 The Effect of Firm Size and Age on Social and Environmental Disclosures (SED)

This section aims to present the outcome of multiple regression analysis to ascertain the effect of firm size, age, and profitability on SED scores for the Nigerian domestic and international oil industries. The regression outcome presented in Table 6.11 illustrates that only firm size ($\beta = 204.96$; $\rho = 0.044$) statistically affects SED reporting compared to the other factors (age and profitability). However, combined, the three factors explain 79% of the variation in SED reporting among the Nigerian domestic oil industries (Adjusted R2 = 0.79).

Table 6.11 Multiple Regression: Effect of Firm Size and Age on SED: Nigerian Domestic Industries

	Coefficient	ρ-value
Intercept	-15.53	0.789
Firm Size	204.96*	0.044
Age	0.56	0.502
Profitability	690.46	0.065
Adjusted R ²	0.79	
F-statistics	14.64*	0.001

ρ* < 0.05

The multiple regression analysis for the international oil firms (Table 6.12) depicts that none of the three-factor variables (firm size, age and profitability) significantly affect SED reporting among the multinational oil firms. The entire multivariate linear regression model is less significant ($F = 1.14$; $\rho > 0.05$) and explains only 7.5% of SED variation among the foreign oil industries. This means that the multivariate regression model for the international industries is less suitable for estimating the SED reporting, given its failure to meet the statistical significance threshold.

Table 6.12 Multiple Regression: Effect of Firm Size and Age on SED: International Oil Industries

	Coefficient	p-value
Intercept	492.66	0.305
Firm Size	386.37	0.206
Age	-4.74	0.439
Profitability	-1335.19	0.514
Adjusted R ²	0.075	
F-statistics	1.14	0.500

6.6 Social and Environmental Disclosure Index (SEDI)

The objective of this section is to compute the SEDI index for the Nigerian oil industries. The SEDI index is calculated using the actual and expected SED information for each of the 18 Nigerian oil industries over the eight years of analysis, 2011-2018. For each SED category, the actual disclosure is computed as the number of exposures reported in the annual reports (AR) of the 18 oil industries over the period 2011-to 2018. The expected disclosure for each SED category is the maximum number of exposures of the 18 oil industries over the analysis period, 2011-2018, which is 144 (18 x 8).

Table 6.13 summarises the SEDI index for the 18 Nigerian oil industries' annual reports classified based on the five SED categories. The SEDI index results indicate that community disclosures (84.7%) had the highest representation based on the content analysis of the respective companies' annual reports. The community disclosure was followed by the environment and customer disclosures, which recorded SEDI indices of 77.8% and 72.2%. The AR's content analysis reveals that the energy disclosures had the most miniature

representation in the annual reports of the Nigerian oil industries, with a SEDI index of 61.1%.

Table 6.13: SED Index for Disclosure of Nigerian Oil Industries' Annual Reports

SED Disclosure Category	Actual Disclosure	Expected Disclosure	SEDI Index (%)
Environment	112	144	77.8
Energy	88	144	61.1
Customer	104	144	72.2
Community	122	144	84.7
Employee	101	144	70.1
Total	527	720	73.2

The community SED disclosure with a SEDI index of 84.7% had the highest composition based on the respective firms' AR content analysis. The information on energy disclosures had the most miniature representation in the AR of the 18 oil industries, with a SEDI index of 61.1%.

CONTENT ANALYSIS 2

6.7 The Extent and Variation in SED between Domestic and International Oil Industries

This section depicted the differences in SED among domestic and international oil industries that operate in Nigeria, using the 18 oil industries for analysis. The results of the descriptive and ANOVA are expected to facilitate the attainment of the above research objective.

The primary research postulation that guided the overall direction of the research was that due to their financial resource commitment, the Nigerian international oil industries were expected to have a substantially higher mean level of SED when assessed against the Nigeria domestic oil industries. The stated hypothetical research premise was evaluated using descriptive, the ANOVA and the paired samples statistical t-test. These statistical tests sought to assess the extent of the difference (assertiveness) in SED between domestic and international oil industries.

The descriptive statistics presented in Table 6.14 reveal that the international oil industries that operate in Nigeria have a higher mean SEDs score ($M = 9.92$) when assessed against the average SEDs score for the Nigerian domestic oil industries ($M = 3.69$). However, the descriptive statistics show that the SED in Nigerian international oil industries has a considerably higher standard deviation ($SD = 11.83$) than the SED variability in the Nigerian domestic oil industries ($SD = 3.94$). The descriptive insights are consistent with the outcome of the ANOVA analysis.

Table 6.14 Descriptive Statistics: Extent of SEDs in Domestic and International Oil Industries

	Nigerian Oil Firms	International Oil Firms
Mean	3.69	9.92
Standard Deviation	3.94	11.83
Minimum	0.00	0.00
Maximum	14.7	40.0
Skewness	1.32	1.43
Kurtosis	1.33	1.02

The descriptive statistics in terms of the extent of SED by category (Table 6.15) also depict that the variation in SEDs between the Nigerian domestic and Nigerian international industries is substantially substantial when assessed in terms of the community and employee disclosures. The descriptive show that the mean of SEDs for all five components (categories) among international oil companies is higher when assessed against the average SEDs in Nigerian domestic oi industries. The results show that the Nigerian global oil industries have performed exceptionally better regarding their social and environmental disclosures than the domestic oil industries.

Table 6.15 Descriptive Statistics: Extent of SED Category in Domestic and International Oil Industries.

Environmental Disclosures:	Nigerian Oil Industries	International Oil Industries
Mean (<i>M</i>)	2.30	4.93
Standard Deviation (<i>SD</i>)	2.45	3.90
Energy Disclosures:	Nigerian Oil Industries	International Oil Industries
Mean (<i>M</i>)	1.25	3.78
Standard Deviation (<i>SD</i>)	1.32	3.98
Client Disclosures:	Nigerian Oil Industries	International Oil Industries
Mean (<i>M</i>)	3.02	7.13
Standard Deviation (<i>SD</i>)	3.64	11.47
Community Disclosures:	Nigerian Oil Industries	International Oil Industries
Mean (<i>M</i>)	6.21	16.31
Standard Deviation (<i>SD</i>)	5.38	16.72
Employee Disclosures:	Nigerian Oil Industries	International Oil Industries
Mean (<i>M</i>)	4.44	14.31
Standard Deviation (<i>SD</i>)	4.24	13.44

Tables 6.16 and 6.17 show that in terms of SED by category, the Nigerian international oil industries appear to have integrated a more significant proportion of narratives (M = 322.7) than the Nigerian domestic oil industries (M = 121.2). Similarly, based on the descriptive, the variation in SED by type of disclosures is also evident in Table 6.16. The average proportion of quantified monetary quantified non-monetary pictures is higher in Nigerian foreign oil industries than in domestic oil industries. The stated outcome is consistent because international companies present more social and environmental disclosures when assessed against domestic oil industries.

Table 6.16 Comparison of the Type of SED in Domestic and International Oil Industries

Type of SEDs	Nigerian Oil Industries	International Oil Industries
Quantified Monetary	28.6	72.3
Quantified Non-Monetary	28.8	65.5
Narratives (Discursive)	121.2	322.7
Pictures	11.3	29.7

Table 6.17 Descriptive Statistics: Type of SED by Domestic and International Oil

Industries

Quantified Monetary	Nigerian Domestic Oil Industries	International Oil Industries
Mean (<i>M</i>)	28.6	72.3
Standard Deviation (<i>SD</i>)	40.0	41.2
Quantified Non-Monetary	Nigerian Domestic Oil Industries	International Oil Industries
Mean (<i>M</i>)	28.8	65.5
Standard Deviation (<i>SD</i>)	50.2	60.5
Narratives (Discursive)	Nigerian Domestic Oil Industries	International Oil Industries
Mean (<i>M</i>)	121.2	322.7
Standard Deviation (<i>SD</i>)	145.1	149.5
Pictures	Nigerian Domestic Oil Industries	International Oil Industries
Mean (<i>M</i>)	11.3	29.7
Standard Deviation (<i>SD</i>)	17.8	16.8

The paired samples t-test depicts that the mean difference ($MD = -6.23$; $p < 0.05$) in the number of social and environmental disclosures about the Nigerian domestic and international oil industries is significant. The insinuation is that the observed variations in social and environmental exposures (SED) among the local and the global oil industries are substantial and not due to randomness (chance). The ANOVA outcome also confirms the stated statistical insight, revealing that the ‘between groups’ sum of squares ($SS = 1696.65$;

$\rho < 0.05$) is statistically significant when assessed at the 5% level. Therefore, considerable evidence supports the postulation that multinational oil firms have higher reported SED levels compared to the domestic oil industries. It is important to note that the leading international oil companies incorporated in the analysis include Exxon Mobil, Total Nigerian Plc., SPDC, MRS Oil International, 11 Plc. International and Chevron Oil Corporation.

Table 6.18 Summary of the ANOVA Results: SED in Domestic and International Oil Industries

	Mean Difference	t-statistic	ρ -value
SED (Nigerian Oil Firms) – SED (International Oil Firms)	-6.23	-3.74	0.001

$\rho^{**} < 0.000$

ANOVA	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	F-statistic	ρ -value
Between Groups	1696.65	1696.65	5.469	0.023
Within Groups	18612.77	310.21		
Total	20309.42			

$\rho^{**} < 0.000$

However, the one-way ANOVA for the international oil companies depicts no substantial variation in the mean difference in SEDs across the stated global industries. Like the domestic oil industries, the variation in SEDs appears to consider for the community SEDs despite their non-significance. The mean difference for the employee SEDs is also substantial based on the one-way ANOVA results in Table 6.19.

Table 6.19 One-Way ANOVA Test Results: Variation in SED among International Oil Industries

(I) SED	(J) SED	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Environmental SED	Energy SED	1.1508	7.9947	1.000
	Client SED	-2.1964	7.2615	0.998
	Community SED	-11.3770	6.4455	0.419
	Employee SED	-9.3770	6.4455	0.601
Energy SED	Environmental SED	-1.1508	7.9947	1.000
	Client SED	-3.3472	8.8485	0.995
	Community SED	-12.5278	8.1921	0.556
	Employee SED	-10.5278	8.1921	0.703
Client SED	Environmental SED	2.1964	7.2615	0.998
	Energy SED	3.3472	8.8485	0.995
	Community SED	-9.1806	7.4783	0.736
	Employee SED	-7.1806	7.4783	0.870
Community SED	Environmental SED	11.3770	6.4455	0.419
	Energy SED	12.5278	8.1921	0.556
	Client SED	9.1806	7.4783	0.736
	Employee SED	2.0000	6.6888	0.998
Employee SED	Environmental SED	9.3770	6.4455	0.601
	Energy SED	10.5278	8.1921	0.703
	Client SED	7.1806	7.4783	0.870

Community SED	-2.0000	6.6888	0.998
---------------	---------	--------	-------

The comprehensive review of the mean variation in SED by firm size and the social and environmental disclosure (SED) component indicates that the Nigerian domestic oil industries compared moderately worse in all five SED aspects. However, in terms of the focus on community welfare sustainability disclosures, the Nigerian-based domestic oil industries had a relatively higher percentage of exposures (51.1%) than the international oil industries, which had only 40.8% of the total disclosures related to community welfare sustainability reporting. The implication is that as domestic oil industries, the Nigerian-based oil firms consider the exposure of community welfare sustainability information as an essential strategy or tactic that is expected to enhance their legitimacy in the eyes of the public.

Regarding environmental disclosures, international oil Industries mostly noted variations in reporting pollution mitigation initiatives and waste management. The international oil and industries were transparent primarily about how they had invested in the waste recycling plants and water conservation initiatives. For instance, in 2012, Exxon Mobil reported that the company safely disposed of 2 million metric tons of hazardous material (Exxon Mobil Annual Report 2013).

The significant difference between the Nigerian domestic and international oil industries when assessed in terms of energy sustainability pertains to energy-efficient processes. The multinational oil firms showed greater transparency concerning energy conservation than domestic oil. As an illustration, Total Nigeria Plc. and SPDC mentioned on various occasions the reliance on energy optimisation and energy-efficient processes as part of their energy sustainability commitment.

The comprehensive review and analysis of the insightful information presented in Table 6.20 and Table 6.21 illustrate a significant variation in terms of customer welfare disclosures among the Nigerian-based oil industries and the international oil industries tied to the issues of client safety. The multinational oil entities appear to have made a substantial investment in customer safety compared to their domestic counterparts. Specifically, international oil industries such as Chevron Nigeria International have made important disclosures that capture the organisations' overall commitment to investing in road safety programs and minimising accidents that affect customers. The primary factor that explains the international oil firms' better transparency in customer welfare disclosures is that most of them feel that they can gain the public confidence and legitimacy by satisfying the various social needs of the customers (Picard et al., 2014).

Regarding the community welfare sustainability SED, the apparent variation between the Nigerian domestic oil industries and the multinational firms is mainly accounted for by charitable donations, education sponsorships and investment in public health initiatives. When assessed in terms of charitable contributions, the international oil industries reported higher monetary contributions mainly channelled to support community initiatives than the Nigerian- domestic oil industries. For instance, to illustrate the apparent differences in charitable donations, Exxon Mobil International reported that it set aside \$269 million in charitable contributions during 2013. Seplat made only \$255,000 in charitable contributions during the same period. The International Oil industries have been broadly involved in various education sponsorship programs and investments in public health initiatives, including supporting programs for health worker training, compared to the domestic oil industries.

Finally, the apparent variation in the employee welfare initiatives shows that the differences appear in the employee health and safety programs and the commitment to workforce

diversity and inclusion of women in management positions. Most international oil firms report substantial investments in employee health and safety programs compared to their domestic oil firms. Additionally, there is considerable diversity and inclusivity among the global oil industries, where the proportion of females in management and graduate trainee positions is higher than 20% for most organisations. There is also mention of the inclusion of the disabled and other minority groups such as the indigenous people in the international oil sector firms such as Exxon Mobil and Chevron International. The stated insight shows that the Nigerian domestic oil industries have worked to enhance their public reputational image concerning employee diversity and inclusion of minority workers.

Table 6.20: Mean SED by Firm Size and Component: Domestic and International Oil Industries

Component of SED Disclosure	Nigerian Oil and Gas Firms	International Oil and Gas Firms
Environment:		
Pollution	1.8	7.2
Wastes	7.2	11.8
Awards	1.3	5.0
Anti-litter	0.0	0.0
Waste Recycling	0.1	2.0
Natural Resource Conservation	2.9	5.8
Compliance with Anti-Pollution Laws	2.8	2.7
Total Environmental Disclosures	16.1	34.5
Energy:		

Energy Conservation	2.8	8.3
Energy Policies	0.3	1.0
Awards	0.8	2.0
Total Energy Disclosures	3.8	11.3
Customers:		
Customer Safety	7.8	24.2
Customer Complaints	0.4	0.5
Customer Relations	3.8	3.7
Provision for Disabled	0.0	0.2
Total Client Disclosures	12.1	28.5
Community:		
Involvement in Community Initiatives	6.3	6.0
Charitable Donations	7.6	32.8
Educational Sponsorship	8.0	16.5
Public Health Initiatives	14.7	40.0
Sports Sponsorships	0.8	2.5
Pro-bono	0.0	0.0
Total Community Disclosures	37.3	97.8
Employee:		
Health and Safety	5.9	18.7
Diversity: Women and minorities	2.0	20.7
Training	12.3	36.2
Benefits	2.9	6.2
Welfare	2.9	2.8

Awards	0.6	1.3
Total Employee Disclosures	26.7	85.8
Total SEDs	95.8	258.0

The international oil industries report a higher mean social and environmental disclosures compared to domestic oil industries. The variations are mostly evident in community welfare, employee welfare and ecological sustainability disclosures.

Table 6.21 SED Indicators (Frequency Scores) in Domestic and International Oil Industries

SED Indicators	Nigerian Oil Industries	International Oil Industries
Environmental Disclosure Indicators	12.0%	10.4%
Energy Disclosure Indicators	1.7%	3.2%
Client Disclosure Indicators	9.1%	9.9%
Community Disclosure Indicators	51.1%	40.8%
Employee Disclosure Indicators	26.0%	35.7%

Figure 6.5 SED Indicators (Frequency Scores) in Domestic and International Oil

Industries

Figure 6.6: Mean SED by Firm Size and Component: Domestic and International Oil

Industries

6.8 Relationship in Extent of SED among Domestic and International Oil Industries

This section highlights the extent of association between the various SED indicators among the Nigerian local and international oil industries. The stated information is presented in terms of the correlation analysis. Table 6.22 delivers the outcome of correlation analysis in terms of the association between the five SED components in the international oil Industries in Nigeria. The Pearson correlation analysis results show a significantly higher association between the SED categories for foreign oil companies.

Table 6.22 Correlation Analysis: Extent of SED in International Oil Industries

SED Indicators	Environmental SED	Energy SED	Client SED	Community SED	Employee SED
Environmental SED	1.000	0.922** (0.000)	0.696* (0.012)	0.881** (0.000)	0.796** (0.002)
Energy SED	0.922** (0.000)	1.000	0.498 (0.100)	0.922** (0.000)	0.656* (0.021)
Client SED	0.696** (0.012)	0.498 (0.100)	1.000	0.685** (0.014)	0.905** (0.000)
Community SED	0.881** (0.000)	0.922** (0.000)	0.685* (0.014)	1.000	0.751** (0.005)
Employee SED	0.796** (0.002)	0.656* (0.021)	0.905** (0.000)	0.751** (0.005)	1.000

$\rho^* < 0.05$; $\rho^{**} < 0.01$

The outcome of correlation analysis in Table 6.23 also illustrates that for the Nigerian domestic oil industries, the SED association's extent is significantly significant. The highest SED association was noted between environmental and community disclosures ($r = 0.947$). However, the least non-significant relationship was observed between employee and community disclosure ($r = 0.676$).

Table 6.23 Correlation Analysis: Extent of SED in Nigerian Domestic Oil Industries

SED Indicators	Environmental SED	Energy SED	Client SED	Community SED	Employee SED
Environmental SED	1.000	0.881* (0.020)	0.893* (0.017)	0.947** (0.004)	0.837* (0.038)
Energy SED	0.881** (0.000)	1.000	0.819* (0.046)	0.823* (0.044)	0.810* (0.051)
Client SED	0.893* (0.017)	0.819* (0.046)	1.000	0.784 (0.065)	0.970** (0.001)
Community SED	0.947** (0.004)	0.823* (0.044)	0.784 (0.065)	1.000	0.676 (0.141)
Employee SED	0.837* (0.038)	0.810 (0.051)	0.970** (0.001)	0.676 (0.141)	1.000

$\rho^* < 0.05$; $\rho^{**} < 0.01$

6.9 Validity and Reliability of Content Analysis

Content analysis has high environmental validity, given that it focuses on the detailed assessments of actual (real) events (Potter & Levine-Donnerstein, 2009). For instance, in this

case, content analysis is based on the actual ARs and, or existing sustainability reports for all the 18 Nigerian oil industries. Besides its high validity, content analysis is also associated with more excellent reliability because the secondary artefacts of ARs are mainly prepared to facilitate financial accounting disclosure rather than supporting the research (Rourke & Anderson, 2004). The implication is that there is less possibility of initial source bias, and the publisher is unaware that one can apply the information for content analysis. However, the reliability of content analysis is restricted by observer bias and culture bias (Potter & Levine-Donnerstein, 2009). The observer bias occurs when the research analysts interpret the categories, codes, and themes differently. The variation in culture among various research analysts can also influence the classes' performance and articles based on the published artefacts in an AR or annual sustainability reports (Rourke & Anderson, 2004).

6.10 Chapter Summary

This chapter presented the outcome of content analysis based on reviewing the annual reports for all the 18 oil and gas industries in Nigeria. The content analysis results were confirmed by the development of the paired samples and the ANOVA statistical analysis. The content analysis results indicated that the primary scope of the social and environmental disclosures (SED) across the Nigerian oil industries relate to the revelations on community welfare, employees, and environmental sustainability.

The outcome is drawn from the content analysis. The statistical ANOVA also indicated that Nigeria's big five oil industries reported higher mean SED levels than the other 13 Nigerian oil industries due to their financial resource competitive advantage. Furthermore, the international oil industries also appear to have a considerable SED reporting level when assessed against their domestic counterparts' related social and environmental disclosures. Finally, despite the dominance of narratives/discursive in the Nigerian oil industries' annual

reports, there is a growing proliferation and popularity of the use of quantified monetary and non-monetary disclosures. The visuals' attractiveness as a type of exposure has also been noted recently due to their ease of understandability.

CHAPTER SEVEN: DISCUSSIONS

7.1 Introduction

The stakeholder theoretical framework supported by the legitimacy theories guides the thesis with its five research objectives. Three out of the study objectives (Qualitative) are for the Interview analysis, while the other two study objectives (Quantitative) are for content analysis. The three objectives (Qualitative) which answered the interviewed questions investigate the perception of the effectiveness of the social and environmental disclosures (SED) in the Nigerian oil industry. In line with the stakeholder/legitimacy theory, the thematic analysis performed using NVivo data analysis software highlighted the importance of host communities as key stakeholders that influence Nigerian oil companies' SED practices. Based on the findings, the discussion is organised with a focus on the three research questions, which had been formulated in the previous chapter. The discussion will focus on the implication of the results in terms of the host communities' motivation for analysing SED Information, perception of SED, and the analysis of the challenges that have restricted the Nigerian oil firms from implementing SED practices effectively.

Similarly, the other two objectives (Quantitative) results were summarised and presented using content analysis. The statistical ANOVA analysis is mainly guided by the two research objectives formulated at the beginning of the research paper. One of the critical research questions sought to ascertain the scope of the social and environmental disclosures (SED) across the Nigerian oil industry. The other research aim was to examine the variation in the level of SED reporting across the country's oil sector and the differences in SED reporting between the Nigerian domestic and international oil Industries. Besides the stated two research objectives, the discussion is guided by stakeholder theory and another theory associated with social and environmental sustainability disclosures: legitimacy theory and the

outcome of similar empirical studies. Therefore, the implication of the findings for policy and current practice will be presented in this chapter.

7.2 Motivations for SED in the Nigerian Oil Industry

The rise in consumerism and increased acceptance of the insight from stakeholder theory and the social legitimacy theory have meant that most oil Industries in the Nigerian oil industry are cognizant of the need to issue annual environmental impact assessments and sustainability reports to the public (Uwuigbe & Jimoh, 2012; Odera, Scott & Gow, 2016). Specifically, Uwuigbe and Jimoh (2012) contend that Nigerian corporate entities' social and environmental disclosure reporting relies on the organisations' voluntary initiatives. According to Uwuigbe and Jimoh (2012), the implication is that, unlike in developed countries, there are no mandatory SED reporting requirements in Nigeria that would motivate organisations to issue annual SED reports. Similarly, Odera, Scott and Gow (2016) concur that the absence of SED reporting regulations has meant that most local and foreign Nigerian oil companies issue the reports voluntarily and mostly opt to disclose positive rather than non-negative information related to their social and environmental activities.

The stakeholders, especially the host communities, have raised the bar regarding their expectations of the SED practices and reports issued by the Nigerian oil Industries. For instance, from the thematic analysis and detailed review of the interview extracts, SED alignment to community development was captured. This means that most of the host communities are motivated or interested in reading the SED reports to determine the extent to which the oil Industry's social and environmental disclosure practices are aligned to community development.

Many respondents do not believe that the SED reports align with the community development plans from evaluating the interviews. An essential explanation by the Church Leader in Delta State states that the oil companies tend to undertake community development projects not out of their voluntary will but to appear generous or for publicity purposes. In this respect, the church leader stated, *"I would say they are forced to do what they would naturally not do, so the alignment is just negative"*. The alignment of social and environmental disclosure is a good practice because the strategy can ensure the adoption of those projects, which are likely to raise the communities' welfare without duplication of projects, as was noted by one of the interviewees.

The other SED motivation based on the insight from the thematic analysis and review of the SED reports is since the host communities, as critical stakeholders, desire to know about the social welfare and community development projects that the oil Industries have undertaken. The study by Juhmani and Duff (2016) depicts that contemporary society and customers are mainly interested in the SED reports to assess the extent of social welfare projects that corporate entities have funded. According to Juhmani (2014), 58% of the Bahrain companies are motivated to issue SED reports to enhance their social legitimacy and public reputation. Based on Juhmani's (2014) study, the stated insight is consistent with the stakeholder theory built on the foundation of organisations' need to align with social expectations. Duff (2016) also suggests that UK auditing firms' motivation to issue annual SED reports is mainly informed by the need to maintain their overall social legitimacy standing, which allows them to charge premium fees.

For instance, an academician from the Akwa Ibom region, his primary motivation to evaluate the annual SED reports published by the oil Industries is to assess whether the oil Industries

set aside some funds to support educational scholarships and infrastructure to place youths in employment. The Community Youth Leader in Delta State concurred with the Academician's sentiments in Akwa Ibom State by stating that the primary motivation in reviewing the SED reports is to examine the community development projects that the oil Industries fund. The Community Youth Leader in Delta State quoted, *"It is true as they put it in their SED reports, they send doctors and give free medical care, award scholarship and fund skill acquisition programs in the community"*. The curiosity to know the benefits or damages to the Nigerian oil Industries has also caused one of the thematic insights derived from the interview transcripts' analysis.

The study by Loate et al. (2017) also raised several aspects that concur with the findings of this thesis on the stakeholders' need to understand the social and environmental impact of the operations conducted by oil firms and other corporate entities. Loate et al. (2017) contend that to align with social expectations and gain social legitimacy, the South African coal mining companies started to issue regular SED reports, especially following media publications on the acid mine drainage. The implication based on the study by Loate et al. (2017) is that most South African mining companies sought to disclose the extent of their progress in limiting the negative effect of their activities on the environment through the annual SED reports.

From the review of the interview with the academicians from the Akwa Ibom and Bayelsa states, it is evident that most of the host communities are motivated to assess the benefits and, or damages that the oil drilling operations have caused. As noted by Akwa Ibom State and Bayelsa state academicians, some of the Nigerian oil industries' benefits pertain to "Offering employment opportunities, funding educational scholarship programs, and building

infrastructure' (Academician, Bayelsa state). Besides the direct benefits, the various stakeholders, including the host communities, are motivated to assess the extent to which the oil companies have minimised the negative environmental impact due to their oil operations. The investment in an environmentally friendly process, effective waste management and natural resource conservation is an essential consideration for the host community and the public. The importance of environmental conservation was also highlighted in the content analysis study. Most Nigerian oil Industries focus on environmental and waste management to appear responsible corporate citizens.

However, based on the interview transcripts review, there is a general understanding that some of the social and environmental performance figures included in the Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) might not be accurate. Lack of government monitoring and evaluation and the host communities' lack of knowledge are considered some of the main factors contributing to the practice of SED report doctoring. The church leader articulated the scepticism due to lack of authenticity in the SED reports issued by the Nigerian oil firms from the Akwa Ibom who argues that some of these reports are compromised, according to Church Leader, Akwa Ibom state which stated that *"I may say that the reports are not real because it is a kind of doctored report"*.

7.3 Perception of Disclosure of SED among Host Communities

The stakeholder theory posits that the host communities are equally important as the company's owners. Therefore, contemporary organisations should strive to provide both financial information (in annual financial reports) and non-financial reports such as the environmental impact assessments (EIA) for the benefit of the public (Campbell 2007). According to Campbell (2007), the stakeholder theoretical framework's relevance implies that

corporate entities increasingly acknowledge the need to issue non-financial information such as SED reports to the host communities and other external stakeholders. The general insight from the results is that the host communities negatively perceive the nature and quality of the SED disclosures by the Nigerian oil Industries.

The insightful review of one of the main thematic aspects of the host community's SED perception reveals that most Nigerian oil industries cannot be considered responsible for corporate citizens. Several interviewees, including the Community Leaders, Community Youths Leaders, Community Residents, Church Leaders and Academicians, observed that the oil companies' operations (both onshore and offshore drilling) contribute to soil erosion and marine pollution. For instance, the Community Youth Leader from Delta state was concerned that, *"Somebody used to make canoe or fishing net for fishermen, these people now are practically jobless. I want to talk to the farmer and fishermen. Where there is an oil spill, the whole farmland and sea are degraded, totally devastated"*.

According to Deegan (2002), firms' reputation as responsible corporate citizens is likely to be enhanced when organisations consider their production operations' adverse social and environmental impact. According to Deegan (2002), the issue of comprehensive SED reports highlighting the organisations' negative and positive aspects is likely to maintain the credibility of the Nigerian oil Industries' social and environmental disclosure reports. The implication noted in the content analysis study is that the Nigerian oil industries should give community welfare disclosure more significant consideration. From the review of the interviewees interviewed and the insight from the thematic analysis, it can be construed that the host communities' general perception is that the Nigerian oil Industries are not responsible for corporate citizens.

The other aspect that has influenced the host community's negative SED perception is that the Nigerian oil and gas firms do not engage or involve the host community when designing various community development projects. Community involvement is an essential strategy likely to influence cohesion and harmonious interaction between the company and the residents (Ekundayo, Yusuf & Samuel, 2016). The word frequency map illustrated that the word "Community" was cited 1,091 in the interview transcripts highlighting the importance of community as a key stakeholder in designing, formulation, and implementing the SED policies. The lack of community involvement was evident based on the Church Leader's insight in Akwa Ibom State, who put plainly, "Mostly, the community does not have any involvement with the oil companies because our representatives do it". Academicians in Delta State further strengthened this by articulating, *"I think the host community does not have a proper grasp of the oil companies' commitments as far as environmental issues are concerned."*

The implication is that although the oil companies involve community leaders, the representatives are rarely trusted in most cases. The insight based on the study by Ekanayake and Perera (2014) suggests that most communities in the developing countries where leaders have been blamed for being selfish prefer direct involvement in open forums (meetings) rather than through representatives who cannot be trusted.

This thesis's findings also highlight a concern among the host communities, contributing to their inherent negative perceptions of SED practices and reports on the oil companies' issue. From the thematic analysis and the detailed review of the interview extracts, there is a general understanding that the Nigerian oil industries' annual SED reports do not represent the actual social and environmental activities in place. For instance, several interviewees raised that

most SED reports that capture social and environmental programs implemented by the oil companies do not reflect the ground's actual situation. The Academician from Rivers State acknowledged, *"If you say you have done this, it has to be seen and not only on paper."*

The insight based on a similar study conducted by Oyadonghan and Ogbalam (2013) also noted the perceived lack of trust in the accuracy of the Nigerian oil firms' annual SED reports in the Niger Delta region. This problem is mainly attributed to the fact that the informal capital markets in developing countries do not perform their oversight function to check for these EIA and corporate sustainability reports (Dai, Du, Young & Tang, 2018).

The other related factor aspect that explains the host communities' negative and often low perception of the SED practices by the Nigerian oil Industries is associated with the poor communication on SED policies. Several participants claimed that most community members could not effectively articulate the SED policies due to the wrong media or platforms. It has been noted that most people, especially in the rural areas in developing countries, do not have access to social media and other mainstream media, such as television, that the oil Industries use to communicate their SED policies (Harrison & Smith, 2017; Iswaissi & Falahati, 2017). In this respect, Iswaissi and Falahati (2017) contend that open meetings with the rural communities or their representatives can be much more effective for organisations to communicate their social and environmental responsibilities/expectations.

Based on the interviews with the interviewees, it seems that the preferred platform for communicating the SED policies should be the open forums with the host communities rather than through the local bulletins and EIA reports, which in most cases are distributed through various digital and mainstream media as suggested by the Company Management and Employment from Bayelsa Oil Company. Furthermore, the focus on the quantified monetary

and non-financial disclosures (communications) can be equally important, as noted in the content analysis study.

Regarding the quantified monetary disclosures, most host community members would prefer to know the amount of CSR budget set aside for community development projects, including roads, sports facilities, electricity, water, and other social amenities. The stated issue was outlined as one of the SED factors influencing the host community's motivations. The integration of pictures as a form of SED disclosure is also likely to enhance SED communication quality from the community perspective instead of the narratives.

Furthermore, even as oil corporations operating in the area increase their corporate social responsibility (CSR) measures in community empowerment, poverty and violence persist in the Niger Delta. Despite this, there is almost no examination of transnational corporations' CSR initiatives prioritising data from host societies (Odera et al., 2018). Community residents perspectives of the SED provided by the Nigerian oil sector are more harmful than beneficial, as many believe the oil has been more of a burden than a gift to them due to human and ecological crises (Odera et al., 2018). Poverty and the influence of socio-environmental deterioration, among other things, have led to the host communities' unfavourable attitudes toward oil firms. Therefore, the community's perspective indicates the Nigerian oil sector has done more harm than good due to the socio-environmental deterioration.

Because communities witness their treasures, which carry social, economic, and psychological significance, being damaged, oil firms have been blamed for the detrimental effects of oil exploitation. Another reason for the wrong view of oil firms is a notion among

community people that the businesses are just doing their CSR programs to benefit themselves rather than safeguard their values (Odera et al., 2018). A firm that does not actively listen will not know the ramifications of perceptions and will be unable to build a solid foundation for top quality connections. As a result, any efforts to foster long-term harmonious relations must include measures to change public perception (Odera et al., 2018). As a result, to survive in the Niger Delta, oil corporations must work to change people's opinions and create lucrative partnerships with the locals.

7.4 SED Reporting Challenges in the Nigerian Oil Industry

The thematic analysis and review of the interview transcripts came up with four main challenges faced by the firms operating in the Nigerian oil industry, which appear to have restricted their ability to develop and promote SED practices. The most cited thematic insight based on SED challenges' broad theme pertains to poor SED policies that the Nigerian oil Industries use. Oyadonghan and Gbalam (2013) found that 79% of the Nigerian oil industry's social and environmental disclosure challenges can be attributed to ill-defined SED policies and a lack of top management support.

Similarly, Okpara (2011) also raised that poor SED policies can mainly be attributed to ineffective corporate governance and limited top management commitment. Weak SED policies tend to create a perception among the host communities that senior management is not committed to social and environmental conservation issues. Similarly, poor SED policies and lack of senior management commitment also confuse employees on how the organisation prioritises SED reporting. The point of poor SED policies was raised by the Church Leader in Rivers State, who argued that the challenge the Nigerian oil Industries' social and environmental disclosure (SED) is because these firms do not have a good policy on

undertaking community welfare development projects. In most cases, they tend to rely on community leadership, which tends to be selfish. The Church Leader also stated in that, *"Well, I want them to be kind of flexible in some of their policies towards the community, and I think, if the company is open to everybody and stop having hidden agenda and doing secret business with the community leadership, then we will have a better environment"*.

However, the poor SED policies of the Nigerian oil and gas firms are also evidenced by the fact that their social and environmental disclosure practices are mainly implemented over the short-term period. The stated concern is based on the insight from several participants who argue that the oil firms appear to have slowed down in their focus on community development projects. Specifically, the Church Leader in Akwa Ibom State observed that *"I told you in the 1990s, the oil firms were interested in social development, for instance, in some places, you'll see signposts such as NNPC/Mobil joint venture projects...but now, these projects have been abandoned"*.

The insinuation based on the stated sentiments is that due to poor and inconsistent SED policies, no framework guides the Nigerian oil Industries' social and environmental performance practice; this observation was also noted based on the study by Olayiwola (2010), who suggest that across the Nigerian banking industry, there is need to strengthen the enforcement mechanisms of the relevant regulatory institutions.

The thematic analytical insight from the NVivo coding also raised limited interaction with communities as an important challenge that has adversely affected the Nigerian oil Industries' ability to develop and promote their SED practices. Community interaction is an efficacious strategy likely to enhance social and environmental disclosure (Sani, 2018). In essence, the practice of interacting with the communities is expected to raise several cultural issues that

are affected by the oil operations, which might be unknown to some of the multinational oil corporations that operate in Nigeria (Oyadonghan & Gbalam, 2013).

The Academician from River state suggested that one of the strategies that the Nigerian oil Industries can adopt to address the challenges in SED disclosure is to interact with the communities through open forums on a regular occasion to ensure that they understand the problems currently affecting the communities. Besides, as noted by the academicians and church leaders in the interview transcript, there is a general understanding that the duplication of projects in the form of "recommissioning" is mainly attributed to the fact that the Nigerian oil Industries do not consult the host communities on the priority projects that need to be implemented.

The other challenge noted from the thematic coding and analysis of the interviewees' interviews relates that the oil Industries tend to receive minimal community support. According to the stakeholder theoretical framework, the importance of the public/host community as a critical stakeholder has enhanced their role to the extent that corporate organisations are relying on customers and the public to support the organisations in terms of comments and, or ideas that can create value (Terlaak, 2007; Shil, 2008; Uwuigbe & Jimoh, 2012). The implication is that customers and the public are expected to raise their profile by formulating insightful ideas on various platforms (Washington & Zajac, 2005).

Furthermore, based on the Academician's insight from Akwa Ibom state, some of these challenges in the SED reporting among the Nigerian oil Industries can be attributed to limited community support, which is rarely forthcoming to residents. According to him, several multinational oil corporations in Nigeria seem to be unaware that they have created adverse

effects on the society and the environment; he quoted, "***The companies are not even aware that they have created the negative effects... so they don't even ask for community support***". The insinuation is that the SED challenges facing the Nigerian oil Industries can be addressed when there is a sufficient community support level (Uwuigbe & Jimoh, 2012). This means that the host communities have an essential role in informing the Nigerian oil Industries, especially the international firms, on where priority for social and environmental initiatives should be.

Finally, the thematic analysis insight raised some issues about the limited funding as an essential aspect that has restricted the Nigerian oil Industries' ability to implement the SED practices effectively. The Company Management and employees in Bayelsa Oil Company acknowledged that when oil prices dropped, such as the year 2015-2016, their organisation was forced to dispose of some of the non-productive oil wells, which affected their revenues during the year. Nevertheless, the Company Management from Bayelsa Oil Company stated the company also acknowledged that despite the limited funding challenge, the society still expects them to continue implementing various community development projects, which might not be possible. Specifically, the company management from Bayelsa Oil Company also observed, "***Despite the funding issues, which does not mean that the community is not there. We ought to have been relating with them, but there is no relationship***". These sentiments were also noted based on a similar study by Oyadonghan and Gbalam (2013). According to the study's findings, which focused on the Nigerian oil Industries operating in the Niger Delta state, the high cost of implementation and the adverse effects of SED practices on profits ranked among the main factors that adversely affected 79% of SED implementation?

Additionally, Since the oil business consumes a significant amount of energy, it is vulnerable to overly restrictive social and environmental regulations. To get or retain their operating license, they must reconsider extraction, manufacturing, and distribution techniques (Mojarad et al., 2018). They must also give assurances and openness in handling their operations' environmental impacts. The oil sectors continue to be vital to the global economy. On the one hand, worldwide demand for fossil fuels continues to rise. At the same time, corporations confront complex investment constraints owing to the harsh operating environment of exploration and production operations. Labour rules ensure a safe and protected workplace (Mojarad et al., 2018). Exploration and development operations continue to pose local and global environmental dangers, such as groundwater pollution and global warming on a larger scale. Therefore, analysis and reporting procedures at oil firms are essential evaluation indicators of environmental sustainability (Mojarad et al., 2018). However, obtaining and analysing critical data appears to be a continuous difficulty, as does determine how these discoveries will influence oil and gas businesses' regular and strategic choices (Mojarad et al., 2018). Artificial intelligence technology in enhanced monitoring and overseeing Exploration and Production (E&P) activities are an effective preventative method for enabling oil firms to assess and manage activities and mitigate problems (Mojarad et al., 2018). Therefore, the Nigerian oil industry faces various challenges in developing and promoting SED.

7.5 The Scope of SED in the Nigerian Oil Industry

The content analysis, which was analysed in SPSS software version 23, found that community welfare disclosures accounted for 48% of the total social and environmental disclosures (SED) related to the Nigerian oil industries. The stated insight confirms the community's importance as a critical stakeholder in social and environmental disclosure reporting. Based on the review of the annual report, the implication is that the focus on

community initiatives, including CSR, investment in health projects, educational scholarships, electricity, and other social amenities, were given greater importance in the SED reports issued by the Nigerian oil Industries.

The significance of community welfare disclosures based on content analysis was also highlighted in the interview findings. Most of the host communities indicated that their primary motivation in analysing the SED reports issued by the Nigerian oil Industries is to examine how they have set aside a sufficient budget for community welfare development projects. According to the stakeholder and the theoretical legitimacy frameworks, attaining the host communities' needs is vital in ensuring that the organisations can receive the necessary support from the community, who also act as customers and potential employees (Oyadonghan & Gbalam, 2013).

The content analysis findings also highlighted that the focus on employee/personnel human resource and staff welfare practices had increased considerably in recent years. The average level of employee welfare disclosure (SED) based on the content analysis outcome in SPSS software was 29%. As a sustainability practice, a more significant number of Nigerian oil Industries are focusing on reporting employee welfare issues to attract the right calibre of employees and enhance the organisations' reputation as well as responsible employers. The interview findings' insight also confirms the importance of employee disclosure based on content analysis. The interview analysis shows that some stakeholders, including the academicians and the church leaders, cited employee diversity issues as a critical aspect that motivates their desire (interest) to analyse social and environmental disclosures.

The content analysis outcome in SPSS also showed that environmental disclosure is vital to SED reporting. On average, 11% of the Nigerian oil Industries focused on reporting their environmental conservation progress. The increased interest in environmental SED reporting is enhanced by the shift in consumerism, especially among millennials who are more inclined toward environmentally conscious organisations (Sani, 2018). The interview insight also confirmed the importance of environmental SED. Some of the interviewees acknowledged their desire for the Nigerian oil Industries to be conscious of the environmental impact of their oil production operations. The host communities recognised the importance of environmental conservation from the Nigerian oil Industries, given the adverse effects of the oil firms' operations, which had caused soil erosion and water pollution.

7.6 Difference in SED among the Domestic and International Oil Industries

The content analysis and statistical ANOVA tests performed in SPSS software indicated that the international oil Industries showed more significant SED reporting disclosures than Nigeria's domestic oil Industries. The SPSS findings indicated a significant difference in the average SED scores among the Nigerian domestic and international oil Industries. The international oil Industries in Nigeria, including Shell and Exxon Mobil, performed much better in their community welfare disclosures, employee related SEDs and environmental conservations.

The content and statistical ANOVA analysis results showed that the international oil Industries performed better in social and environmental disclosures, which supplements the insight from the thematic analysis of the interview concerning the SED reporting challenges. The SED challenges analysis based on the thematic understanding showed that lack of funding was an important aspect that adversely affected the Nigerian oil Industries' ability to implement community welfare development projects consistently. Therefore, the fact that the

international oil Industries performed better in SED reporting than the Nigerian oil industries shows their superior financial resources.

According to Ekundayo et al. (2016), the international oil Industries in Nigeria compare favourably to Nigeria's domestic oil Industries, given their substantially higher financial resources, which allows them to invest in multi-billion community development projects. The fact that the Nigerian domestic oil Industries rely on internally generated profits to fund such community welfare development projects implies that most local companies are unlikely to finance such projects when their earnings have declined consistently. The international oil Industries' unique financial resources in Nigeria have also meant that most of them can invest in environmentally sustainable processes compared to Nigeria's domestic oil Industries.

Variations in organisational culture can also explain the difference in the SED reporting performance among the Nigerian domestic and international oil industries. The philanthropic and benevolent cultural practices and values common among the international oil Industries explain why most of them perform exceptionally well in community welfare disclosures (Ekundayo et al., 2016). However, based on the interview, the thematic analysis highlighted that the foreign oil Industries did not have considerable awareness/knowledge of the vital community welfare issues. Some interviewees noted that due to their less familiarity with the local conditions, the international oil Industries needed to be supported by the host communities regarding their SED expectations. Therefore, despite their limited knowledge of the local conditions, the global oil Industries seem to perform considerably better in community welfare disclosures when assessed against the local firms.

Furthermore, the increased interest in environmental data from stakeholders and corporations' desire to keep their environmental commitment apparent has resulted in a growth in sustainability disclosure by firms, whether voluntary or mandatory, through yearly reports and other filings. Furthermore, as firms recognise that their activities have implications that impact stakeholders, social and environmental disclosures (SEDs) have gained traction. Consequently, some consideration has been devoted to analysing how firms report on specific concerns and the integrity of such reporting (Sujin, 2019). A substantial number of literatures have been dedicated to SED provision in yearly reports. Despite the growing interest in developing nations' corporate social responsibility (CSR) reporting, limited studies have evaluated the SED procedures of domestic and international corporations. Although several studies have looked at SED in Nigeria, there has been a minimal empirical study in the oil business (Odera et al., 2016).

Nonetheless, enterprises prioritise financially dominating shareholders and workers while disregarding the values of other stakeholders and the environment. A firm should function more responsibly and consider the effects of its activities on the ecosystem, individuals, and society. When undertaking critical business choices, a corporation should make different efforts to save the environment (Odera et al., 2016). This material should be publicly disclosed. Industries aim to improve their reputation by demonstrating excellent corporate engagement.

In terms of their positive SED, the level of significance of domestic and international enterprises implies a significant disparity between them. According to the research, environmental disclosures are primarily poor in quantity and quality (Odera et al., 2016). The data implies that if SED in yearly reports is left as an optional approach, information

integrity in Nigerian domestic and international oil corporations will not grow (Office, 2016). It is also doubtful that optional SED would result in more excellent rates of availability and value of disclosure; hence the Nigerian government should consider some regulatory action (Odera et al., 2018).

7.7 Implication for Policy and Practice

This thesis's findings have an efficaciously important implication for policy and SED practices among the Nigerian oil Industries. The stakeholder theoretical framework informs the first important implication of the thesis. The qualitative analysis of the findings supports the growing importance of the public and the host community as essential stakeholders. The insight from the thematic analysis noted that from the perspective of the internal stakeholders of the oil Industries (Company Management and Company Employees), their primary motivation in issuing the SED reports is to inform the public/host communities who are critical stakeholders in the various social and environmental projects that their organisations have sponsored. The growing importance of the host communities as critical stakeholders has meant that most corporate organisations tend to be obligated to publish annual EIA and corporate sustainability reports (Harrison & Smith, 2017). These corporate yearly sustainability reports disclose community welfare aspects, environmental management, and waste management.

The other helpful implication of the findings for practice pertains to the importance of the legal framework that needs to guide the issuing of annual SED reports by the Nigerian oil Industries. The insight based on the review of the thematic analysis and interviews illustrates how most interviewees were sceptic about the authenticity of the Nigerian oil Industries' annual social and environmental disclosures. Some observed that they don't trust the EIA and

sustainability reports that the Nigerian oil companies provide. According to Oyadonghan and Gbalam (2013), formulating and implementing a solid legal framework can enhance public confidence in the authenticity of the annual sustainability reports.

The findings based on the importance of community support in addressing some of the challenges faced by the Nigerian oil Industries also seem to have a considerable implication on the need to have a policy framework for raising public awareness regarding their duty to participate in community development projects. The outcome based on the review of the thematic analysis results illustrates how some interviewees, especially academicians, believe that a few multinational oil firms are unaware that their operations might affect specific social and cultural heritage within the host communities. The mutual support from the host communities through regular interactions with corporate organisations in open forums has been cited as one factor that has raised contemporary organisations' social and environmental performance (Mgbame & Mgbame, 2018). Therefore, an important implication of the results is that various government agencies, including the Department of Petroleum Resources and consumer organisations in Nigeria, need to raise awareness among the public on their responsibility to support the oil companies.

An additional implication of the findings for policy practice based on the results and discussion is the need for a robust legal mechanism that outlines various sanctions and obligations to oil firms that perpetuate environmental damage, including soil erosion and marine pollution. Some interviewees raised that the social development benefits in CSR (scholarships, infrastructure and social amenities) that the Nigerian oil Industries provide do not fully compensate for the adverse environmental damages caused by the onshore and offshore oil operations. Therefore, these findings have an important implication on legislative

enactments' role in mitigating environmental degradation's adverse effects. There is evidence that enacting strong environmental conservation laws can give the oil Industries an obligation to behave as responsible corporate citizens (Ioannou & Serafeim, 2014).

The thesis has several implications for the ideal corporate strategies and policies that the thesis can adopt. The Nigerian oil Industries can benefit from engaging the communities regularly. Most of the community residents, the youth leaders and the church leaders raised that the oil companies do not directly engage the communities. In fact, given that these companies tend to relate only with the community leaders, there is a perception that some of the community development projects, and social welfare benefits the oil companies offer do not get to the locals in the host communities. Therefore, an important implication of the findings for practice is for the oil Industries in Nigeria to engage the locals through open forums, transparent and articulate genuine issues from the host communities. The stated insight is also supported based on Lin, Yang and Arya (2009) and Oyadonghan and Gbalam (2012).

The other productive insightful implication of the study for practice based on the thematic analysis outcome pertains to the need to adopt consistent SED policies by the Nigerian oil Industries. A significant concern that the participants raised is that the SED practices that the Nigerian oil firms undertook during the 90s appear to have diminished significantly current period. One of the reasons for the Nigerian oil Industries' stated behaviour is that most of their social and environmental disclosure practices are not guided by a consistent policy framework (Oyadonghan & Gbalam, 2012). Therefore, formulating and implementing a consistent SED policy framework can go a long way in addressing SED practices and implementation among the Nigerian oil Industries.

Finally, to mitigate the issue of limited funding, which appears to have affected the ability of the Nigerian oil Industries to fulfil their social and environmental obligation, these organisations might find it helpful to establish a CSR fund that is less dependent on the annual corporate income. The company management and employees from Bayelsa Oil Company acknowledged that they usually face challenges in implementing various community development projects, especially during challenging economic times such as the 2015-2016 year when oil prices dropped substantially. Setting up an independent community development (CSR) fund can cushion the oil firms against unfortunate situations that affect their social and environmental responsibility adversely.

Furthermore, through the ministry of petroleum and natural resources, the Nigerian government can also support the local oil Industries by adopting favourable tax policies and subsidy programs. The savings from the low corporate taxes and subsidies would enhance the Nigerian oil Industries' financial ability to implement their CSR community projects consistently.

CHAPTER EIGHT: CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

8.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the conclusions structure of the thesis with a different section heading that address the key findings of the thesis. This chapter is divided into sections as follows: Section 8.2 discusses the key findings of the thesis with a critical thesis findings (interview & content analysis) summary table breakdown, in section 8.3, which describes the key findings that extend to existing literature. Section 8.4 presents thesis recommendations for the study. Section 8.4 elaborately discusses the original contribution to the research knowledge. Lastly, sections 8.5 and 8.6 explain the implications for future research and conclusion summary, respectively.

8.2 Key Findings

The five research objectives proposed in the introduction chapter guided the thesis for both qualitative and quantitative analysis. The qualitative analysis sought to investigate the host community's perceptions, motivations and challenges the Nigerian oil firms faced in implementing their SED disclosure practices. Similarly, the quantitative analysis analysed the determinants of SED in Nigerian oil industries and differences in SED between local and international oil industries. First, Table 8.1 presents a summary of the critical thesis findings, which sought to evaluate the social and environmental disclosure (SED) practices among corporate entities operating in the Nigerian oil and gas sectors. The three primary research objectives guide the summary of the key findings for the thesis below.

Table 8.1: Summary of The Key Thesis Findings (Interview)

S/N	Research Objectives (Interview)	Research Key Findings (Interview)
1	Motivations for SED practices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Host communities' motivations for SED are informed by the need to assess the number of social welfare projects (schools, hospitals, and social amenities) financed by the Nigerian oil industries. ▪ Host communities' motivation for SED is inspired by the need to ascertain how the social and environmental practices are aligned with the community development plans. ▪ Host communities are motivated to analyse SED to assess the social welfare benefits and environmental damages caused by the Nigerian oil industries.
2	Perceptions of SED practices by the host community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Host communities are important stakeholders in the Nigerian oil industry. ▪ Host communities tend to have negative SED perceptions due to limited involvement from the oil industries during the assessment phase. ▪ Host communities negatively perceive the SED practices adopted by Nigerian oil industries due to poor communication of policies and harmful environmental damages.
3	Challenges in promoting SED practices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Inconsistent SED policies, which are not aligned with their long-term goals, are the main challenge faced by Nigerian oil industries. ▪ Limited interaction with the host communities has also contributed to the challenge of poor implementation of SED policies and practices among Nigerian oil industries. ▪ Lack of mutual support from the host communities in terms of local cultural knowledge and awareness has hindered the effective promotion of SED practices, especially among the foreign oil industries. ▪ Nigerian oil and gas firms have faced funding challenges, especially during the challenging economic period when oil prices have declined. ▪ The funding challenge tends to restrict the number of social welfare projects implemented by the Nigerian oil industries.

Table 8.2: Summary of The Key Thesis Findings (Content Analysis)

S/N	Research Objectives (Content Analysis)	Research Key Findings (Content Analysis)
1	Determinants of SED among Nigerian oil industries.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Community SEDs were the main determinants of social and environmental disclosures among Nigerian oil industries. Community disclosure had the highest SEDI index of 84.7% based on the content analysis of the oil industries' SED reports. ▪ The SED reporting practices of the Nigerian oil industries are also influenced by disclosing information on employee welfare, customer, and environmental conservation issues. The SEDI index for the employee, customer and environmental disclosures were 70.1%, 72.2% and 77.8%, respectively. ▪ However, the disclosure of energy conservation is the minor determinant of SED practices among Nigerian oil industries, with a SEDI index of 61.1%. ▪ The narratives quantified monetary and non-monetary types of disclosures and determined the SED reporting practices of the Nigerian oil industries. Despite their growing popularity, pictures and visuals had a minor influence on the SED reporting practices of the oil industries.
2	Variation in SED between domestic and international oil industries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ There is a significant variation in Nigeria's SED reporting practices for the domestic and international oil industries. ▪ The international oil firms had more important SED reporting disclosures regarding quality and quantity than the domestic oil industries. ▪ The difference in SED practices is that the Nigerian oil industries have more significant financial budgets for supporting social and environmental conservation projects than the local oil industries. ▪ The variation in SED practices is also explained by the fact that the international oil industries have an entrenched philanthropic or benevolent culture, given their solid corporate governance system compared to the local oil industries.

Table 8.2 above summarises the critical thesis findings related to the content analysis findings on the determinants of SED in Nigerian oil industries and the differences of SED between local and international oil industries. Similarly, in this case, the summary of the key findings is guided by the two secondary research objectives of the content analysis study.

8.3 The Key Findings That Extent to Existing Literature

The findings from this thesis also extend the current insight concerning the stakeholder theoretical framework, as noted by Duff (2016) and Oyadonghan and Gbalam (2013). The main conclusion from the review of the qualitative insight is that the host communities and locals are the main stakeholders of the Nigerian oil industries. Implementing social welfare programs, adopting environmentally friendly oil extraction processes, and disclosing social and environmental practices by Nigerian oil firms are mainly targeted toward the local communities (Oyadonghan & Gbalam 2013). However, the findings from this thesis extend the stakeholder theory by suggesting adopting two strategies that will facilitate the attainment of the local community's needs.

- Firstly, as noted by Uwuigbe and Jimoh (2012), there is a need for the corporate entities involved in SED disclosure practices to actively involve the locals in the formulation of priority social welfare projects to prevent duplication of projects.
- Secondly, as suggested by Oyadonghan and Gbalam (2013), the locals need to reciprocate the good gesture from the Nigerian oil and gas firms, especially among the foreign firms, by creating awareness through their representatives of the existing cultural heritage, which need to be preserved.

The insightful findings from this thesis also extend the general knowledge of the social legitimacy theoretical framework based on the conclusion from the research study conducted by Duff (2016) using data from the UK professional accounting firms. The findings from this

thesis acknowledge that the Nigerian oil industries can only enhance their social legitimacy by providing regular SED performance reports that faithfully present the actual social and environmental projects implemented during the reporting period. There is a risk that some of the oil industries might take advantage of the host communities to provide inaccurate SED reports that do not portray their actual performance to gain positive publicity and social legitimacy (Sani 2018). Therefore, the findings from this thesis extend the insight into the social legitimacy theory by advocating for the formulation of mandatory solid SED reporting disclosure regulations with a requirement for an external review and audit to ascertain the authenticity of the SED reports (Oyadonghan & Gbalam 2013; Sani 2018).

The findings from this thesis also extend the previous theoretical literature insight on the appropriate format of SED disclosure reports that the Nigerian oil industries should adopt, inconsistent with the findings by Duff (2016). The thesis acknowledges that due to the challenge of SED communication, the Nigerian oil industries need to ensure that a considerable portion of the SED reports contains quantified financial disclosures and visuals (pictures, graphs and tables) to promote understandability of the SED reports. There is a consensus that many host communities lack knowledge of technical aspects of the SED reports (Oyadonghan & Gbalam 2013). Therefore, as a strategy to enhance effective communication of the SED practices, the thesis extends the insight by Duff (2016) that Nigerian oil industries need to minimise the narrative SED disclosures and instead incorporate visuals and quantified monetary disclosures in tabular format.

Finally, the thesis also extends the prior knowledge and theoretical evidence on the importance of having consistent SED policies, as suggested by Sani (2018). From the qualitative review findings, the thesis also highlights how the practice of integrating the SED

policies with the long-term goals of the oil industries might contribute to more outstanding top management support. The lack of consistent SED policies was noted by the respondents (Academicians and managers) as one of the significant challenges that hinder the implementation of adequate social and environmental disclosure among the Nigerian oil industries.

8.4 Policy Recommendations

The thesis recommends that reforms in the legislative enactments and SED management practices can enhance the effective implementation of SED practices among the Nigerian oil industries. Firstly, the design of a solid regulatory framework to monitor SED reports' authenticity and formulate strong environmental laws can equally be efficacious in discouraging ornamental pollution among the oil industries. From a policy perspective, the thesis acknowledges that the various government agencies, including the Department of Natural Resources, should consider raising awareness among the host communities concerning the duty to support the oil industries.

Secondly, this thesis also recommends that the Nigerian oil industries consider designing and adopting a consistent SED policy and interacting with the local's community regularly. The Nigerian oil industries should also consider using appropriate open forums to communicate with the locals. Finally, this study proposes can address the challenge of limited funding among the oil industries in Nigeria by setting up a CSR fund that is less dependent on their income-generating capacity. The strategy can be effective during challenging economic periods, such as when the oil prices decline. Through the ministry of petroleum and natural resource, the Nigerian government should consider reviewing the taxes on the Nigerian oil industries. Low corporate taxes to the Nigerian oil industries, coupled with effective subsidy

programs, can enhance the firms' financial ability to implement CSR community projects. The tax savings would allow the Nigerian oil industries to invest more in community development projects.

Thirdly, the other important recommendations to the Nigerian oil industries are that the organisations can improve the community's excitement by focusing on the disclosure of quantified monetary and non-financial disclosures. For instance, given the host community's desire to know about the CSR projects that the oil companies have implemented, the increased use of numbers and, or percentages (i.e., dollar amount set aside for roads, electricity, educational scholarships and health) is likely to be much more understandable from the community perspective as opposed to the narratives.

Finally, as noted in the content analysis study, the Nigerian oil industries can enhance their communication with the host communities by using more pictures and graphs in their SED reports. The incorporation of pictures as a form of SED disclosure is gaining popularity due to its ease of understandability, especially among the host communities. Most of them do not have the technical ability to analyse the SED narratives.

8.5 The Original Contribution to Knowledge

The thesis contributes to the theoretical literature in three ways. Firstly, the originality of the research regarding the stakeholder theory is that it stresses each stakeholder's mutual role in promoting effective SED reporting (Oyadonghan & Gbalam 2013). The qualitative interview findings generated new insightful knowledge that the host communities are equally responsible for determining the extent and effectiveness of the annual SED reports. Specifically, Academia Ibom state observed that some foreign Nigerian oil industries might

not be aware that their operations could adversely affect the cultural heritage within the host communities. Therefore, such companies need mutual support from the host communities to enhance their social and environmental disclosure (SED) performance (Sani 2018). The stated insight contributes positively to the existing knowledge on the stakeholder theory, which is based on the foundational premise that social and environmental performance is the sole responsibility of corporate organisations.

Furthermore, The SED belief in original contribution seems to carry the idea of originality. This is due to multiple pieces of research being used to clarify the study's proper trajectory, and the use of the community's interviews (Stakeholders) emphasises this contribution. From the given perceptions on SED, a broad theme helped assess the perceived driving factors that influence the consideration of social and environmental disclosure reporting across the Nigerian oil industries (Odera et al., 2016). As a form of original contribution to knowledge, SED reporting was employed in the form of interviews to shed light on the current state of the host communities (Stakeholders). It has been evidenced that the community residents' perspectives of the SED provided by the Nigerian oil industries are more harmful than beneficial, as many believe the oil has been more of a burden than a gift to them due to human and ecological crises (Odera et al., 2018). Poverty and the influence of socio-environmental deterioration, among other things, have led to the host communities' unfavourable attitudes toward oil industries.

Secondly, the originality of the research concerning the current practice of social and environmental (SED) disclosure is that it generates helpful insight into the most appropriate criteria for evaluating the social legitimacy of corporate organisations (Duff 2016; Mgbame & Mgbame 2018). From the interview, the thesis highlighted that some of the host

communities were sceptical about the reliability of the SED reports issued by Nigerian oil companies, with a few claiming that the SED reports are published for publicity purposes. Therefore, this thesis extends the social legitimacy theory by emphasising the integrating monitoring role to maintain the integrity of the annual SED reports issued by the Nigerian oil industries.

Finally, the third original contribution of the research to the existing literature based on the thematic analysis findings is that it extends knowledge on the practice of social and environmental disclosure. The findings indicate that the SED practices and policies need to be aligned to the community development priorities to be effective in enhancing welfare. Prior literature findings by Odera et al. (2016) and Mgbame and Mgbame (2018) highlighted how the SED policies need to support the organisations' long-term goals and objectives. However, the SED policies and practices for community development priorities were not explored based on previous theoretical insight. Therefore, this thesis extends the existing theoretical knowledge by emphasising SED policy's importance to community development goals, as noted by the academicians from Niger Delta state. The academician from Niger Delta state had decried that some of the community development projects initiated by Shell were duplicated given that they had already been commissioned.

8.6 Implications for Future Research

The thesis findings are restricted because the researcher assessed qualitative insight based on a small number of interviewees (N = 24). Challenges in logistics and availability of respondents, especially Company Management and Company Employees of oil firms in the Delta state and River's state who continues to work remotely due to the present Covid-19 restrictions, explained the use of the limited sample size. However, despite the small sample

of interviewees, the researcher incorporated a diverse set of interviewees (Company Management, Company Employees, Community Leaders, Community Youth Leaders, Community Residents, Church Leaders and Academicians) to enhance the validity of the thematic insight, the thesis relied on NVivo data analysis software to analyse the interview transcripts. The insightfulness of the interviewees' views was also enhanced by the fact that older interviewees (40-60 years) who are well educated dominated the sample. The findings have five significant implications for the direction of future research, which include?

Firstly, the suggestion for prospective future studies is to consider assessing the SED perceptions in the Nigerian oil industry using a reasonably large representative sample. This sample should include various segments of the host communities and employees and managers from multiple local and multinational oil firms. More managers and employees in the qualitative research will likely provide sufficient information on the SED perceptions and challenges from the oil and gas that operate in Nigeria. Additionally, for the quantitative component of the research, the suggestion is that future studies should incorporate more oil industries over the 18 oil firms whose SED reports were analysed based on the content analysis. Besides, future studies should consider including the insight from annual reports and the yearly sustainability reports of the Nigerian oil industries. The use of a considerably large sample size of interview respondents and the SED reports for Nigerian oil and gas firms is likely to enhance the representativeness of the findings.

Secondly, the suggestion for the future research study, which is worthy of further investigation, pertains to the concept of mutual community support. From the thematic findings, the researcher noted that community support is likely to be essential for the Nigerian international oil firms that are not familiar with the cultural heritage of the host

communities. Furthermore, the researcher highlighted that some of the international oil industries engaged in environmentally destructive activities or processes because they were not aware of the existing cultural heritage in the local community. As Oyadonghan and Gbalam (2013) noted, mutual community support from the locals can be crucial in facilitating the preservation of cultural heritage and environmental conservation. However, despite the stated insight, it is not clear the extent to which mutual community support and involvement by locals in planning social and environmental initiatives alongside the Nigerian oil industries would enhance the practice of SED reporting. Therefore, this aspect of how mutual community support would improve SED reporting by Nigerian oil industries is an important area that deserves further research investigation.

Thirdly, the proposed suggestion for future research study pertains to SED monitoring and regulations on the practice of SED reporting among the Nigerian oil industries. The insight from the qualitative component of the study also offers an important direction for future research to explore SED monitoring and regulations on the practice of social and environmental disclosure among Nigerian oil industries. Critical research gaps identified from the qualitative thematic analysis identified the role of SED monitoring and regulation on SED practices. Therefore, as an extension of the findings from this study, the suggestion is that prospective future studies need to evaluate the extent to which the SED reporting practices, and performance would change when there is consistent and mandatory regulatory monitoring. These compulsory regulatory monitoring of the annual SED reports published by the Nigerian oil industries would review the authenticity of the SED reports. The insight from the interview indicates that most of the local communities feel that most of the SED reports are issued for publicity purposes. The expectation is that if future studies assess the effectiveness of the mandatory SED monitoring by regulatory agencies such as the Securities

and Exchange Commission of Nigeria, the findings can be important in supporting the review of social and environmental reporting policies and laws.

Finally, another vital suggestion for prospective future studies to focus on includes examining the local community's perceptions of the different types of SEDs (narratives, quantified monetary, quantified non-monetary, and pictures). The central insight from the perspective of the Nigerian oil industries is that the growing importance of the quantified financial, quantified non-monetary, and picture SEDs is based on their ease of understandability. However, it is unclear how the locals perceive the efficacy of the stated types of SEDs in enhancing their comfort of understandability. Therefore, an urgent consideration for prospective future studies is to examine the locals' perceptions and views on the different types of SEDs (narratives, quantified monetary, quantified non-monetary, and pictures). The expected findings from the proposed future study will likely inform the review of the different types of SED report formats issued by the Nigerian oil industries.

8.7 Executive Summary

The key conclusion of the thesis is from the qualitative study, which analysed the interview extracts from 24 interviewees, is that the host communities are essential stakeholders who, according to the stakeholder theory, need to be the focus of attention when presenting the annual sustainability reports or the environmental impact assessment reports. The other critical insight derived from the thesis is that the host communities, who are essential firm stakeholders, tend to negatively perceive the SED practices pursued by the Nigerian oil industries. Limited community involvement, poor communication of their SED policies, and the harmful environmental damages (pollution and soil erosion from oil spills) are the main

factors that informed the interviewees' negative perception of the SED practices of the oil industries.

The thesis also concludes that the host communities are mainly motivated to assess the SED reports issued by the Nigerian oil firms to ascertain the number of community development projects that have been funded by the oil firms and the extent to which the stated projects align with the current community development plans. Besides, the host communities are also motivated to review the SED reports by the oil firms to assess the nature of the social welfare benefits and the social and environmental damages that the oil firms cause. The study's final insightful conclusion is that the SED implementation and, or option challenges faced by the Nigerian oil firms can be attributed to inconsistent SED policies, limited interaction with the locals, lack of mutual community support and limited funding, especially during challenging economic times.

The additional insight (quantitative analysis) based on the content analysis, which was in SPSS, also reveals that community welfare disclosure, employee related SEDs and environmental disclosures are the main determinants of the SED reporting. The substantial focus on community welfare disclosures, which was also apparent based on the thematic analysis, highlights the community's growing importance as a critical stakeholder. Besides also notes the similarity in terms of the employee diversity and environmental conservation issues based on the content analysis and the thematic analysis of the interviews.

The thesis also acknowledges that limited funding and organisational culture, which were noted as some of the SED challenges in the thematic analysis, explain the SED reporting performance differences among the domestic and international oil firms. The domestic oil

industries in Nigeria struggle to fund community welfare development projects when earnings decline. However, given their consistently higher financial capability, the international oil firms seem to be better positioned to fund the community development initiatives than the local firms. Furthermore, the study acknowledges that despite their limited knowledge of the local conditions, as was observed based on the thematic analysis, the solid organisational culture associated with the international oil and gas firms enables them to implement the social and environmental disclosures consistently.

REFERENCES

- Abbott, W. & Monsen, R., 1979. On the Measurement of Corporate Social Responsibility: Self-Reported Disclosures as a Method of Measuring Corporate Social Involvement. *Academy of Management Journal*, 22(3), pp. 501-515.
- Aburaya, R. K., 2012. *The Relationship between Corporate Governance and Environmental Disclosure*, Durham: Unpublished Doctoral Thesis.
- Adam, A. M. & Shavit, T., 2008. How Can a Ratings-based Method for Assessing Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) Provide an Incentive to Firms Excluded from Socially Responsible Investment Indices to Invest in CSR? *Journal of Business Ethics*, Volume 4, pp. 899-903.
- Adams, K. R., 2011. *Corporate Social Responsibility: Stakeholder Determination and Reporting*, Melbourne: Unpublished PhD Thesis.
- Adedejiab, A. k. N., Sidiquea, S. F., Rahman, A. A. & Law, S. H., 2016. The role of local content policy in local value creation in Nigeria's oil industry: A structural equation modeling (SEM) approach. *Resources Policy*, Volume 49, pp. 61-73.
- Adinehzadeh, R., Jaffar, R., Shukor, Z. A. & Rahman, M. R. C. A., 2018. The mediating role of environmental performance on the relationship between corporate governance mechanisms and environmental disclosure. *Asian Academy of Management Journal of Accounting and Finance*, pp. 153-183.
- Africa Check. 2018. *Nigeria's economy: services drive GDP, but oil still dominates exports*. [Online] Available at <https://africacheck.org/reports/nigerias-economy-services-drive-gdp-but-oil-still-dominates-exports/> [Accessed 22 Jun. 2019].
- African Markets. <http://www.african-markets.com/en/stock-markets/ngse/listed-companies/company?>
- Agudelo, M.A.L., Jóhannsdóttir, L. and Davídsdóttir, B., 2019. A literature review of the history and evolution of corporate social responsibility. *International Journal of Corporate Social Responsibility*, 4(1), pp.1-23.
- Ahmad, A. H., Murtala, I. & Bashiru, D., 2014. Exploring the Roles of Stakeholder Engagement and Stakeholder Management in CSR Practice. *Australian Journal of Business and Management Research*, 4(5), pp. 1-8.

Akaranga, SI & Makau, BK 2016, 'Ethical considerations and their applications to research: A case of University of Nairobi', *Journal of Educational Policy and Entrepreneurship Research*, vol. 3, no. 12, pp. 1-9.

Alawiye-Adams, A. & Busola, A. A., 2017. Environmental Disclosure Practices in Annual Reports of Listed Manufacturing Firms. *SSRN*, pp. 1-19.

Ali, W. & Muhammad, R., 2013. Factors Influencing Corporate Social and Environmental Disclosure (CSED) Practices in the Developing Countries: An Institutional Theoretical Perspective. *International Journal of Asian Social Science*, 3(3), pp. 590-609.

Ali, W., Wilson, J. and Husnain, M., 2022. Determinants/Motivations of Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure in Developing Economies: A Survey of the Extant Literature. *Sustainability*, 14(6), p.3474.

Alonso-Almeida, M., Llach, J. & Marimon, F., 2014. A Closer Look at the 'Global Reporting Initiative' Sustainability Reporting as a Tool to Implement Environmental and Social Policies: A Worldwide Sector Analysis. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 21(6), pp. 318-336.

Amabipi, A. K., 2016. Understanding Host Community Distrust and Violence Against Oil Companies in Nigeria. *Walden Dissertations and Doctoral Studies*.

Aminu, A., 2015. *Corporate Social Responsibility: A Review on definitions, core characteristics and theoretical perspectives*. [ebook] Available at: https://mpra.ub.uni-muenchen.de/75040/1/MPRA_paper_75040.pdf.

Amodu, L. O., 2006. Community relations strategies and conflict resolution in the Niger delta: A study of three major oil companies. *Covenant University*.

Asaolu , T. O., Agboola, A. A., Ayoola, T. J. & Salawu, M. K., 2011. *Sustainability Reporting in the Nigerian Oil and Gas Sector*. Abeokuta, Nigeria, Federal University of Agriculture.

Asuquo, A. I., 2012. Environmental friendly policies and their financial effects on corporate performance of selected oil and gas companies in Niger delta region of Nigeria. *American International Journal of Contemporary Research*, pp. 168-173.

Awogbade, S., Bamgbose, K. & Izekor, O., 2017. *Oil and gas regulation in Nigeria: overview*. [Online]

Available at: [https://uk.practicallaw.thomsonreuters.com/5-523-4794?transitionType=Default&contextData=\(sc.Default\)&firstPage=true&comp=pluk&bhcp=1](https://uk.practicallaw.thomsonreuters.com/5-523-4794?transitionType=Default&contextData=(sc.Default)&firstPage=true&comp=pluk&bhcp=1)

Ayoola, Olakunle Thomas, "Nigerian Oil and Gas Industry Content Development Act's Perceived Performance Impact" (2017). *Walden Dissertations and Doctoral Studies*. 3383. <https://scholarworks.waldenu.edu/dissertations/3383>

Barr, M. A., 2011. *Corporate Social Responsibility Reporting in Emerging Economies: A Case Study of the Petroleum Refining Industry*, Durham, North Carolina: Unpublished Master Thesis.

Ball, W.T., Alsing, J., Mortlock, D.J., Staehelin, J., Haigh, J.D., Peter, T., Tummon, F., Stübi, R., Stenke, A., Anderson, J. and Bourassa, A., 2018. "Evidence for a continuous decline in lower stratospheric ozone offsetting ozone layer recovery." *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 18(2), pp.1379-1394.

Barrow, JM, Brannan, GD, & Khandhar, PB 2020, *Research ethics*, StatPearls Publishing, New York.

Bayagbon, A., 2011. *Impact assessment of the environmental protection policies in the upstream oil industry in Nigeria*. [Online] Available at: https://repository.nwu.ac.za/bitstream/handle/10394/6276/Bayagbon_AM.pdf?sequence=1 [Accessed 26 10 2018].

Bayoud, N., Kavanagh, M. & Slaughter, G., 2012. Factors influencing levels of corporate social responsibility disclosure Libyan firms: a mixed study.. *International Journal of Economics and Finance*, 4(4), pp. 13-29.

Beattie, V 2005, 'Moving the financial accounting research front forward: the UK contribution', *British Accounting Review*, vol. 37, no. 1, pp. 85-114.

Beattie, V, & Thomson, SJ 2007, 'Lifting the lid on the use of content analysis to investigate intellectual capital disclosures', *Accounting Forum*, vol. 31, no. 1, pp. 129-163. Binh, T., 2012. Voluntary disclosure information in the annual report of non - financial listed company: the case of Vietnam. *Journal of applied economics and business research*, 2(2), pp. 69-90.

Brammer, S. J., Pavelin, S. & Porter, L. A., 2006. Corporate Social Performance and Geographical Diversification. *Journal of Business Research*, 59(9), p. 1025–1034.

Briggs, J 2007, Systematic review protocol example: Smoking cessations interventions and strategies for hospitalised patients, In *evidence-based clinical practice in nursing and healthcare*, Pearson Publishers.

Brown, T. J. & Dacin, P. A., 1997. The Company and the Product: Corporate Associations and Consumer Product Responses. *Journal of Marketing*, 61(1), pp. 68-84.

Bryman, A., 2006. Integrating quantitative and qualitative research: how is it done?. *Qualitative Research*, 6(1), pp. 97-113.

Bryman, A., 2015. *Social research methods*. s.l.:Oxford university press.

Bhardwaj, A., 2013. *Challenges and Solutions in an Upstream and Downstream Oil and Gas Operation*. [Online]

Available at: <https://globalenergy.pr.co/65678-challenges-and-solutions-in-an-upstream-and-downstream-oil-and-gas-operation>.

Campbell, JL 2007, ‘Why would corporations behave in socially responsible ways? an institutional theory of corporate social responsibility’, *Academy of Management Review*, vol. 32, no. 2, pp. 946-967.

Carroll, A. B., 1999. Corporate Social Responsibility: Evolution of a Definitional Construct. *Business and Society*, 38(3), pp. 268-295.

Chete, L. N., Adeoti, J. O., Adeyinka, F. M. & Ogundele, O., 2011. *Industrial development and growth in Nigeria: Lessons and challenges*, s.l.: Learning to Compete.

Clarkson, P., Fang, X., Li, Y. & Richardson, G., 2013. The Relevance of Environmental Disclosures: Are Such Disclosures Incrementally Informative? *Journal of Accounting and Public Policy*, 32(5), pp. 410-431.

Clarkson, P., Li, Y., Richardson, G. & Vasvari, F., 2008. Revisiting the Relation between Environmental Performance and Environmental Disclosure: An Empirical Analysis. *Accounting, Organisations and Society*, 33(4/5), pp. 303-327.

Cowen, S. S., Ferreri, L. B. & Parker, L. D., 1987. The Impact of Corporate Characteristics on Social Responsibility Disclosure: A Typology and Frequency-Based Analysis. *Accounting, Organisations and Society*, 12(2), pp. 111-122.

- Craggs, R & Neate, H 2019, 'What happens if we start from Nigeria? Diversifying histories of geography', *Annals of the American Association of Geographers*, vol. 110, no. 3, pp. 899-916.
- Crane, A., Matten, D. & Spence, L., 2008. *Corporate Social Responsibility: Readings and Cases in a Global Context*. 2nd ed. Abingdon, UK: Routledge.
- Creswell, JW 2014, *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative and mixed methods approach*, Sage Publications, New York.
- Creswell, J. & Creswell, J., 2017. *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approach*. s.l: Sage publications.
- Crowther, D. & Aras, G., 2008. *Corporate Social Responsibility*. Ventus Publishing: Telluride, CO.
- Cui, R., 2018. *Corporate Social Responsibility of Oil Multinationals in Nigeria. Human Rights, Sustainable Development and the Law*. s.l:Diplom.de.
- Dada, L. A., 2007. *The African export industry: What happened and how can it be revived?*, s.l.: Food and agriculture organization of the United Nations.
- Dai, NT, Du, F, Young, SM, & Tang, G 2018, 'Seeking legitimacy through CSR reporting: Evidence from China', *Journal of Management Accounting Research*, vol. 30, no. 1, pp. 1-29.
- Davison, J 2011, 'Barthesian perspectives on accounting communication and visual images of professional accountancy', *Accounting, Auditing and Accountability Journal*, vol. 24, no. 2, pp. 250-283.
- Deegan, C 2002, 'Introduction: The legitimizing effect of social and environmental disclosures as a theoretical foundation', *Accounting, Auditing and Accountability Journal*, vol. 15, no. 3, pp. 282-311.
- Deegan, C. & Blomquist, C., 2006. Stakeholder influence on corporate reporting: an exploration of the interaction between WWF-Australia and the Australian minerals industry. *Accounting, Organisations and Society*, 31(4-5), p. 343–372.
- Delmas, M. & Blass, V. D., 2010. Measuring Corporate Environmental Performance: The Trade-offs of Sustainability Ratings. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 19(4), pp. 245-260.

Dibia, N. O. & Onwuchekwa, J. C., 2015. Determinants of Environmental Disclosures in Nigeria: A Case Study of Oil and Gas Companies. *International Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 4(3), pp. 145-152.

Dickie, R.K 1966. Development of Crude Oil Production in Nigeria and the Federal Governments Control Measures. A paper presented to the institute of petroleum, London: January, at 1pp.

Duarte, F., 2010. Working with Corporate Social Responsibility in Brazilian Companies: The Role of Managers' Values in the Maintenance of CSR Cultures. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 96(3), pp. 355-368.

Duff, A 2016, 'Corporate social responsibility reporting in professional accounting firms', *The British Accounting Review*, vol. 48, no. 1, pp. 74-86.

Easterby-Smith, M., Thorpe, R. & Lowe, A., 2002. Management research: an introduction. London: Sage Publications.

Ebimobowei, A., 2011. A Study of Social Accounting Disclosures in the Annual Reports of Nigerian Companies. *Asian Journal of Business Management* , pp. 145-151.

Ebiringa, O. T., Yadirichukwu, E., Chigbu, E. E. & Ogochukwu, O. J., 2013. Effect of Firm Size and Profitability on Corporate Social Disclosures: The Nigerian Oil and Gas sector in Focus. *British Journal of Economics, Management & Trade*, pp. 563-574.

Effiong, J., 2010. Oil and Gas Industry in Nigeria: The Paradox of the black Gold. *Research in Social Problems and Public Policy* , Volume 18, pp. 323-349.

Egbon, O., 2014. *An exploration of accountability : evidence from the Nigerian oil and gas industry*, s.l.: University of St Andrews.

Eiti, 2015. *Nigeria*. [Online] Available at: <https://eiti.org/nigeria> [Accessed 26 10 2018].

Ekanayake, A & Perera, S 2014, 'The role of accounting in corporate governance in a developing country: institutional political economy perspective', *International Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Performance Evaluation*, vol. 10, no.2, pp. 109-132.

- Ekundayo, O, Yusuf, I & Samuel, J 2016, 'The extent of environmental disclosures in listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria', *Proceedings of Nigeria's Economic Development Conference*, pp. 400-413.
- Elijido-Ten, E., 2011. Media Coverage and Voluntary Environmental Disclosures: A Developing Country Exploratory Experiment. *Accounting Forum*, 35(3), pp. 139-157.
- Eljayash, K., 2015. Documentation of Environmental Disclosure Practices in the Oil Companies in the Countries of the Arab Spring – Some Evidence from Egypt, Libya and Tunisia. *Journal of Economics, Business and Management*, 3(10).
- Elo, S, Maria, K, Kanste, O, Polkki, T, Utriainen, K & Kyngas, H 2014, 'Qualitative content analysis: A focus on trustworthiness', *Sage Open Publishers*, pp. 1-10.
- Elum, Z.A., Mopipi, K., and Henri-Ukoha, A., 2016. "Oil exploitation and its socioeconomic effects on the Niger Delta region of Nigeria." *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 23(13), pp.12880-12889.
- Ernfjord , K. & Voigt , M., 2018. *Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) Disclosure and Earnings Management*, s.l.: Unpublished Master Thesis.
- Esira, A. F., Ikechukwu, E. C. & Ikechukwu, E. M., 2014. Environmental cost management and profitability of oil sector in Nigeria (2004-2013). *Journal of Good Governance and Sustainable Development in Africa*, pp. 181-192.
- Esposito, B., Sessa, M., Sica, D. and Malandrino, O., 2021. Corporate Social Responsibility Engagement through Social Media. Evidence from the University of Salerno. *Administrative Sciences*, 11(4), p.147.
- Eugster, F. & Wagner, A. F., 2011. *When and how is Voluntary Disclosure Quality Reflected in Equity Prices*, Zurich, Switzerland: National Centre of Competence in Research Financial Valuation and Risk Management.
- European Parliament: Directorate General for External Policies Policy Department, 2011. *The effects of oil companies' activities on the environment, health and development in Sub-Saharan Africa*, s.l.: Deve.
- Evbota, C. I. U. C. A. & Ohalehi, P., 2017. *Determinants of corporate social and environmental disclosure of Nigeria oil and gas companies*, s.l.: Michael and Cicilia Ibru University.

Eweje, G., 2006. Environmental Costs and Responsibilities Resulting from Oil Exploitation in Developing Countries: The Case of the Niger Delta of Nigeria. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 69(1), pp. 27-56.

Eweje, G., 2007. Multinational oil companies' CSR initiatives in Nigeria: The scepticism of stakeholders in host communities. *Managerial Law*, pp. 218-235.

Export, 2011. *Nigeria - Market Challenges*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.export.gov/article?id=Nigeria-Market-Challenges>

Eze, O. J., 2015. Analysis of oil export and corruption in Nigeria economy. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management*, 3(7), pp. 112-135.

Fajana, S., 2005. Industrial relations in the oil industry in Nigeria. *International Labour Office*, pp. 1-53.

Freeman, R. E., 1984. *Strategic Management: A Stakeholder Approach*. Boston: Pitman.

Freeman, R. E. & Reed, D. L., 1983. Stockholders and Stakeholders: A New Perspective on Corporate Governance. *California Management Review*, 25(3), pp. 88-106.

Frey, BB 2018, *Judgmental sampling*, Sage Publishers, New York.

Friedman, M.: 1962, Capitalism and Freedom, University of Chicago Press. *Corporate Moral Responsibility* 451.

Gabriel, 2018. *Overview of the Nigerian Oil and gas Industry*. [Online] Available at: <https://financialquest.com.ng/overview-of-the-nigerian-oil-and-gas-industry/>

Gabriel, O. M. K. S. D., Kari, F., Alam, G. M. & Matuin, O. D., 2012. Impact of Gas Industry on Sustainable Economy in Nigeria: Further Estimations Through Eview. *Journal of Applied Sciences*, Volume 12, pp. 1244-2251.

Gamerschlag, R., Moller, K. & Verbeeten, F., 2011. Determinants of Voluntary CSR Disclosure: Empirical Evidence from Germany. *Review of Managerial Science*, Volume 5, pp. 233-262.

Garcia, E., Carvalho, G., Boaventura, J. and Souza Filho, J., 2020. Determinants of corporate social performance disclosure: a literature review. *Social Responsibility Journal*, 17(4), pp.445-468.

Gbalam, O., James, K. & Peter, E., 2013. Social and Environmental Accounting: The Challenges of Implementation in Oil Prospecting Companies in the Niger Delta States of Nigeria. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 4(11), pp. 1-7.

G.Etikerantse 2004: Nigerian Petroleum Law(2nd ed)(Nigera,Dredew Publishers,p.53

Giwara, U., 2011. *History of the Nigeria Petroleum Industry*. [Online] Available at: https://giwaraufolatunde.files.wordpress.com/2011/03/ptdf_revision1.pdf [Accessed 9 January 2019].

Glaum, M., Baetge, J., Grothe, A. & Oberdörster, T., 2013. Introduction of International Accounting Standards, Disclosure Quality and Accuracy of Analysts' Earnings Forecasts. *European Accounting Review*, 22(1), pp. 79-116.

Gray, R., 2010. Is Accounting for Sustainability Actually Accounting for Sustainability...and How Would We Know? An Exploration of Narratives of Organisations and the Planet. *Accounting, Organisations and Society*, 35(1), pp. 47-62.

Greenwood, M. (2001). The importance of stakeholders according to business leaders. *Business and Society Review*, vol. 106, no. 1, p. 29-49.

Guthrie, J, Petty, R, & Ricceri, F 2007, *Intellectual capital reporting in Hong Kong and Australia, research Monograph*. Edinburgh: The Institute of Chartered Accountants of Scotland.

Hackett, C., 2016. The challenge of MNCs and development: oil extraction, CSR, Nigeria and corruption. *Journal of Human Rights in the Commonwealth*, 2(2).

Haladu, A. & Salim, B. B., 2016. Board Characteristics and Sustainability Reporting: Environmental Agencies' Moderating Effects. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Issues*, pp. 1525-1533.

Haladu, A. & Salim, B. B., 2017. Sustainability Reporting by Firms in the Nigerian Economy: Social versus Environmental Disclosure. *Journal of Accounting and Finance in Emerging Economies*.

Hamidu, A. A., Haron, H. M. & Amran, A., 2015. Corporate Social Responsibility: A Review on Definitions, Core Characteristics and Theoretical Perspectives. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 6(4), pp. 83-95.

- Harrison, JS & Smith, JL 2017, 'Responsible accounting for stakeholders', *Journal of Management Studies*, vol. 52, no. 7, pp. 935-960.
- Hassan, N. T., 2010. *Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure: An Examination of Framework of Determinants and Consequences*, Durham, England: Unpublished PhD Thesis.
- Haufler, V., 2010. Disclosure as Governance: The Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative and Resource Management in the Developing World. *Global Environmental Politics*, pp. 53-73.
- Henderson, J. C., 2006. Corporate Social Responsibility and Tourism: Hotel Companies in Phuket, Thailand, after the Indian Ocean Tsunami. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, , 26(1), pp. 228-239.
- Heise, S. S. a. K., 2014. *Re-evaluating the "Culture of Poverty"*. [Online] Available at: <https://thesocietypages.org/roundtables/culture-of-poverty/> [Accessed 26 10 2018].
- Herrera, J. and de las Heras-Rosas, C., 2020. Corporate social responsibility and human resource management: Towards sustainable business organisations. *Sustainability*, 12(3), p.841.
- H.L Schatzl 1969: *Petroleum in Nigeria(Ibadan, Oxford University Press)*P.1
- Huang, C & Kung, F 2010, 'Drivers of environmental disclosure and stakeholder expectation: Evidence from Taiwan', *Journal of Business Ethics*, vol. 96, no. 3, pp. 435-451.
- Hussin, W., Alazzani, A. & Nordin, W., 2013. Global Reporting Initiative's environmental reporting: A study of oil and gas companies. *Ecological Indicators*, Volume 32, pp. 19-24.
- Idowu, S. & Towler, B., 2004. A Comparative Study of the Contents of Corporate Social Responsibility Reports of UK Companies. *Management of Environmental Quality: An International Journal*, 15(4), pp. 420-437.
- Ifunanya, A. S., 2010. *The impact of oil spillage on agricultural production: a case study of Ibeno local government area, Akwa-Ibom state, Nigeria*, s.l.: University Of The Free State.
- Ifurueze, A., Etale, L. M. & Frank, B. P., 2013. The Impact of Environmental Cost on Corporate Performance: A Study of Oil Companies in Niger Delta States of Nigeria. *Journal of Business & Management*, 2(2), pp. 1-10.

Iledare, W., 2007. *Oil and the Future of Nigeria: Perspectives on Challenges and Strategic Actions for Sustainable Economic Growth and Development*, s.l.: International Association for Energy Economics.

Ioannou, I & Serafeim, G 2014, 'The consequences of mandatory corporate sustainability reporting: evidence from four countries', *Harvard Business School Research Working Paper*, pp. 11-100.

IPIECA, 2018. *Mapping the Oil and Gas industry to the Sustainable Development Goals: An Atlas*, s.l.: IPIECA.

Ironkwe, M & Promise, O 2016, 'Environmental reporting in the oil and gas industry in Nigeria', *International Journal of Research in Business Studies and Management*, vol. 3, no. 11, pp. 1-21.

Ironkwe, U. & Ordu, P. A., 2016. Environmental Reporting in the Oil and Gas Industry in Nigeria. *International Journal of Research in Business Studies and Management*, pp. 1-21.

Iswaissi, H & Falahati, K 2017, 'Challenges to corporate governance practices: case study of Libyan commercial banks', *Corporate Governance and Sustainability Review*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 33-41.

Ite, U. I. & U. E., 2006. Corporate–community relations in Nigeria's oil industry: challenges and imperatives. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management* .

Iwuagwu, O., 2009. Nigeria and the challenge of industrial development: the new cluster strategy. *African Economic History*, Volume 37, pp. 151-180.

Jenkins, H. & Yakovleva, N., 2006. Corporate Social Responsibility in the Mining Industry: Exploring Trends in Social and Environmental Disclosure. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 14(3/4), pp. 271-284.

Jike, V. T., 2010. Oil Companies and Host Community: A Probable Scenario for Reciprocal Empowerment. *Journal of Human Ecology*, 30(2), pp. 131-142.

John, A. T., 2011. Gas Flaring and its Implication for Environmental Accounting in Nigeria. *Journal of sustainable development* , pp. 244-250.

J.Oke 2006: " Oil Discovery ata Oloibiri" *The Guardian, Sunday, July 30*. P26.

Jokovich, G., 2013. Statistical Sampling in Auditing. *International Journal of Accounting and Financial Management*, pp. 892-898.

Joseph, U. B., 2016. Effect of Sustainability Reporting on Firm's Performance: A Review of Literature. *The International Journal Of Business & Management*, pp. 203-208.

Juhmani, O 2014, 'Determinants of Corporate Social and Environmental Disclosure on Websites: The Case of Bahrain', *Universal Journal of Accounting and Finance*, vol. 2, no. 4, pp.77-87.

Ka, C., 2018. *History of Oil and Gas in Nigeria*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.scribd.com/document/49781298/History-of-Oil-and-Gas-in-Nigeria>

Katsoulakos, P. & Katsoulakos, Y., 2006. *A Multi-Dimensional View of Corporate Responsibility*, s.l.: s.n.

Kelley, K, Clark, B, Brown, V & Sitzia, J 2003, 'Good practice in the conduct and reporting of survey research', *International Journal of Quality in Health Care*, vol. 15, no. 3, 261-266.

Kitchin , T., 2002. Corporate social responsibility: a brand explanation. *Brand Management*, 10(4-5), pp. 312-326.

Knapik, M 2004, *Engaging persons in narrative-based research: Taking a closer look at the word participant*. Paper presented at the Fifth Qualitative Health Research Conference, Banff, Alberta, Canada.

Knapik, M 2006, 'The qualitative research interview: Participants' responsive participation in knowledge making', *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 77-93.

Kolk, A., 2004. A Decade of Sustainability Reporting, Development and Significance. *International Journal of Environment and Sustainable Development*, 3(1), pp. 51-64.

Kolk, A., 2006. Sustainability Reporting. *VBA Journal*, 21(3), pp. 34-42.

KPMG, 2017. *The KPMG Survey of Corporate Responsibility*, The Netherlands: KPMG.

KPMG, 2005. *KPMG International Survey of Corporate Responsibility Reporting 2005*, Amsterdam: University of Amsterdam and KPMG Global Sustainability Services.

KPMG Professional Services, 2011. *Nigeria's Oil and Gas Industry Brief*, s.l.: KPMG NIGERIA.

KPMG Professional Services, 2014. *Nigeria's Oil and Gas Industry Brief*, s.l.: KPMG NIGERIA.

- Langer, W. L., 1926. *Oil Imperialism*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.foreignaffairs.com/reviews/capsule-review/1926-07-01/oil-imperialism> [Accessed 26 10 2018].
- Lebura, S., 2013. Stakeholder relationships in the Nigerian oil industry. *De Montfort University*, pp. 1-434.
- Lei, W., 2011. *Factors Affecting Perceptions of Corporate Social Responsibility Implementation: An emphasis on Values*, Helsinki: Unpublished PhD Thesis.
- Lewis, I., 2018. *Nigeria's new oil industry bill ready to launch*. [Online] Available at: <http://www.petroleum-economist.com/articles/upstream/exploration-production/2018/nigerias-new-oil-industry-bill-ready-to-launch>
- Lin, ZJ, Yang, H, & Arya, B 2009, 'Alliance partners and firm performance: resource complementarity and status association', *Strategic Management Journal*, vol. 30, no. 9, pp. 921-940.
- Liu, Z. G., Liu, T. T., McConkey, B. G. & Li, X., 2011. Empirical Analysis on Environmental Disclosure and Environmental Performance Level of Listed Steel Companies. *Energy Procedia*, Volume 5, pp. 2211-2218.
- Loate, et al. 2017, 'Acid Mine Drainage in South Africa: A Test of Legitimacy Theory', *Journal of Governance and Regulation*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 26-49.
- Lou, X. & Bhattacharya, C. B., 2006. Corporate Social Responsibility, Customer Satisfaction and Market Value. *Journal of Marketing*, 70(4), pp. 1-18.
- Maddaloni, FD, & Davis, K 2017, 'Project managers' perception of the local communities' stakeholders in megaprojects: An empirical investigation in the UK', *International Journal of Project Management*, vol. 1, no. 2, p. 1-24.
- Magness, V. & Bewley, K., 2011. *Environmental Disclosure in the Canadian Resource Industry – The Impact of Reporting Regulation*, Toronto, Canada: s.n.
- Margolis, J. D. & Walsh, J. K., 2003. Social Issues and Management: Our Lost Cause Found. *Journal of Management*, Volume 29, pp. 859-881.
- Matten, D. & Moon, J., n.d. *Implicit and Explicit CSR: A Conceptual Framework for Understanding CSR in Europe*, s.l.: University of Nottingham.

- Mgbame, AM & Mgbame, CO 2018, 'Discretionary environmental disclosures of corporations in Nigeria', *International Journal of Disclosure and Governance*, vol. 15, pp. 252-261.
- Mojarad, A., Tantau, A. and Atashabri, V., 2018. *Challenges for Sustainable Development Strategies in Oil and Gas Industries*. [ebook] Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/324388641_Challenges_for_Sustainable_Development_Strategies_in_Oil_and_Gas_Industries.
- Murthy, V. & Abeysekera, I., 2008. Corporate Social Reporting Practices of Top Indian Software Firms. *Australasian Accounting Business and Finance Journal*, 2(1), pp. 36-59.
- Musa, A., Yusuf, Y. Y., Mcardle, L. & Banjoko, G., 2013. Corporate social responsibility in Nigeria's oil and gas industry: The perspective of the industry. *International Journal of Process Management and Benchmarking*, pp. 101-135.
- Ngex, 2018. *Overview of the Nigerian Oil & Gas Sector*. [Online] Available at: <http://ngex.com/business/oil-gas/overview-of-the-nigerian-oil-gas-sector> [Accessed 2018].
- Nofsinger, J.R., Sulaeman, J. and Varma, A., 2019. Institutional investors and corporate social responsibility. *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 58, pp.700-725
- Nosakhare, O., Ahmad, A. C. & Adam, N. C., 2016. Environmental Disclosure in Nigerian Quoted Companies: The Longitudinal Study. *International Postgraduate Business Journal*, 8(2), pp. 19-33.
- Nowell, LS, Norris, JM & White, DE 2017, 'Thematic analysis: Striving to meet the trustworthiness criteria', *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, vol. 16, no.1, pp. 1-13.
- Nwaiwu, N. J. & Oluka, N. O., 2018. Environmental cost disclosure and financial performance of oil and gas in Nigeria. *International Journal of Advanced Academic Research*, pp. 2-23.
- Nwobu, O., 2017. *Adaeze Determinants of corporate sustainability reporting in selected companies in Nigeria*, s.l.: College of Business and Social Sciences.
- Oba, V. C. & Fodio, M. I., 2012. Comparative analysis of environmental disclosures in oil and gas and construction industries in Nigeria. *Journal of Sustainable Development in Africa*, pp. 19-28.

Oben-Torkornoo, E., 2018. *Overview of the Oil and Gas Industry in Nigeria*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.scribd.com/doc/24321432/Overview-of-the-Oil-and-Gas-Industry-in-Nigeria>

Odera, O., 2014. *An examination of social and environmental disclosures in Nigerian oil companies*, s.l.: University of Southern Queensland.

Odera, O., Scott, A. & Gow, J., 2016. An examination of the quality of social and environmental disclosures by Nigerian oil companies. *Corporate Governance: The International Journal of Business in Society*, pp. 400-419.

Odera, O, Scott, A & Gow, J 2016, 'Differential reporting of social and environmental disclosures between local and foreign oil companies in Nigeria', *Social Responsibility Journal*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 415-438.

Odera, O., Scott, A.H., and Gow, J., 2016. "Factors influencing corporate social and environmental disclosures: a systematic review." *International Journal of Business Governance and Ethics*, 11(2), pp.116-134.

Odera, O., Scott, A. and Gow, J., 2018. Community perceptions of Nigerian oil companies' commitment to social and environmental concerns. *Journal of Global Responsibility*, 9(1), pp.73-95.

Odia, J. & Imagbe, V. U., 2015. Social and Economic Consequences of Corporate Social and Environmental Disclosures in Nigeria. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, pp. 177-186.

Odoemelam, N. and Okafor, R.G., 2018. The influence of corporate governance on environmental disclosure of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria. *Indonesian Journal Sustainability Accounting and Management*, 2(1), pp.25-49.

Office, I., 2016. *Policies and regulatory frameworks to better align business and finance with global goals*. [ebook] Available at: https://www.un.org/esa/ffd/wpcontent/uploads/2016/01/Policies-to-better-align-business-with-global-goals_ILO_IATF-Issue-brief.pdf.

Ofoegbu, GN & Asogwa, C 2020, 'The effect of sustainability reporting on profitability of quoted consumer goods manufacturing firms in Nigeria', *International Journal of Innovative Research and Development*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 271-282.

Oilgasng, 2016. *Overview of Nigerian Petroleum Industry*. [Online] Available at: <http://www.oilgasng.com/overview-of-nigerian-petroleum-industry/>

Oilprice, 2017. *Nigeria's Oil Industry Overhaul*. [Online] Available at: <https://oilprice.com/Energy/Energy-General/Nigerias-Oil-Industry-Overhaul.html>

Oilprice, 2017. *Once Again, Tensions Are Rising In Nigeria's Oil Sector*. [Online] Available at: <https://oilprice.com/Energy/Crude-Oil/Once-Again-Tensions-Are-Rising-In-Nigerias-Oil-Sector.html>

Oisamoje, J. E. & Aigboduwa, M. D., 2013. Promoting small and medium enterprises in the Nigerian oil and gas industry. *European Scientific Journal*, 9(1).

Okafor, T. G., 2018. Environmental Costs Accounting and Reporting on Firm Financial Performance: A Survey of Quoted Nigerian Oil Companies. *International Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 7(1), pp. 1-6.

Okpara, JO 2011, 'Corporate governance in a developing economy: Barriers, issues, & implications for firms', *Corporate Governance: The International Journal of Business in Society*, 11(2), 184-199.

Okorie, A., 2005. *The Role of Multinational Oil Companies*, s.l.: s.n.

Okotie, S., Ogbarode, N. O. & Ikporo, B., 2018. The Oil and Gas Industry and the Nigerian Environment. *The Political Ecology of Oil and Gas Activities in the Nigerian Aquatic Ecosystem*, pp. 47-96.

Olayiwola, WK 2010, 'Practice and standard of corporate governance in the Nigerian banking industry', *International Journal of Economics and Finance*, vol. 2, no. 4, pp.178.

Olayinka, A. O. & Oluwamayowa, I., 2014. Corporate environmental disclosures and market value of quoted companies in Nigeria. *The Business & Management Review*, 5(3), pp. 171-184.

Omenikolo, I. & Amadi, R., 2010. Challenges facing Nigerian local content in oil and gas industry. *Continental Journal of Renewable Energy*, pp. 15-20.

Omofwonmwan, SI & Osa-Edoh, GI 2017, 'The challenges of environmental problems in Nigeria', *Journal of Human Ecology*, vol. 23, no. 1, pp. 53-57.

Omorede, C. K., 2014. Assessment of the Impact of Oil and Gas Resource Exploration on the Environment of Selected Communities in Delta State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Management, Economics and Social Sciences*, 3(2), pp. 79-99.

Onyinyechi, O. C. & Ihendinihu, J., 2016. Impact of Environmental and Corporate Social Responsibility Accounting on Organizational Financial Performance: Evidence from Selected Listed Firms in Nigeria Stock Exchange. *Journal of Emerging Trends in Economics and Management Sciences*, 7(5), pp. 291-306.

Osazuwa, N. P., Ahmad, A. C. & Adam, N. C., 2016. Environmental Disclosure in Nigerian Quoted Companies: The Longitudinal Study. *IPBJ*, 8(2), pp. 19-33.

Oscar, M. C. & Juliet, O. O., 2015. The Effect of Corporate Governance on the Extent of Environmental Reporting In the Nigerian Oil Industry. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*.

Otiotio, D., 2018. *An overview of the oil and gas industry in Nigeria by Dennis Otiotio*.

[Online]

Available

at:

[http://www.academia.edu/2654835/AN OVERVIEW OF THE OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY IN NIGERIA BY DENNIS OTIOTIO](http://www.academia.edu/2654835/AN_OVERVIEW_OF_THE_OIL_AND_GAS_INDUSTRY_IN_NIGERIA_BY_DENNIS_OTIOTIO)

Oti, PA & Geraldine, M -O. B., 2018, 'Analysis of environmental and social disclosure and financial performance of selected quoted oil and gas companies in Nigeria (2012-2016)', *Journal of Accounting and Financial Management*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 1-12.

Otomposoba, O. H. & Dosunmu, A., 2016. Local Content Policy and Its Implications on Marginal Oil Fields Operations and the Nigerian Economy. *International Journal of Innovative Research and Development*, 5(6), pp. 354-360.

Otu, U. A., Okon, A. M. & Nnanna, O. L., 2018. Oil Companies Performance and Environmental Accounting Reporting in Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting*, pp. 1-8.

Owolabi, A., 2009. Environmental Disclosures in Annual Reports: the Nigerian Perspective. *Economia Aziendale Online* .

Oyadonghan, KJ & Gbalam, EP 2013, 'Social and environmental accounting: The challenges of implementation in oil prospecting companies in the Niger Delta state of Nigeria', *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, vol. 4, no. 11, pp. 1-10.

Pantamee, A. A., 2014. *The effect of corporate governance on corporate social responsibility disclosure in the Nigerian petroleum marketing industry*, s.l.: Universiti Utara Malaysia.

Petroleum Economist, 2010. *Oil industry's increasing focus on CSR*. [Online] Available at: <http://www.petroleum-economist.com/articles/corporate/company-profiles/2010/oil-industrys-increasing-focus-on-csr>

Picard, CF, Durocher, S, & Gendron, Y 2014, 'From meticulous professionals to superheroes of the business world: A historical portrait of a cultural change in the field of accountancy', *Accounting, Auditing & Accountability Journal*, vol. 27, no. 1, pp. 73-118.

Qureshi, M.I., Rasli, A.M., Awan, U., Ma, J., Ali, G., Alam, A., Sajjad, F. and Zaman, K., 2015. "Environment and air pollution: health services bequeath to grotesque menace." *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 22(5), pp.3467-3476.

Rahman, A. H. I. & A. A., 2016. The quality of environmental disclosure in various reporting media of oil and gas companies in developing countries. *Corporate Ownership & Control*.

Rizk , R., Dixon, R. & Woodhead, A., 2008. Corporate Social and Environmental Reporting: A Survey of Disclosure Practices in Egypt. *Social Responsibility Journal*, 4(3), pp. 306-323.

Roca, L. & Searcy, C., 2012. An Analysis of Indicators Disclosed in Corporate Sustainability Reports. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 20(1), pp. 103-118.

Rosamaria, C. M. & Robert, C. P., 2011. Historical Background of Corporate Social Responsibility. *Social Responsibility Journal*, 7(4), pp. 528-539.

Rourke, D. O. & Connolly, S., 2003. Just oil? The distribution of environmental and social impacts of oil production and consumption. *Annual Review of Environment and Resources*.

Rourke, L & Anderson, T 2004, 'Validity in quantitative content analysis', *Educational Technology Research and Development*, vol. 52, no. 1, pp. 5-18.

Sani, M., 2016. *Social and environmental disclosures : a comparative analysis of listed Nigerian and UK oil and gas companies*, s.l.: Alberta University.

Sani, M., 2018. Mandatory Social and Environmental Disclosure: A Performance Evaluation of Listed Nigerian Oil and Gas Companies Pre- and Post-Mandatory Disclosure Requirements. *Journal of Finance and Accounting*, pp. 56-68.

Sani, M. D., 2018. Mandatory Social and Environmental Disclosure: A Performance Evaluation of Listed Nigerian Oil and Gas Companies Pre- and Post-Mandatory Disclosure Requirements. *Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 6(2), pp. 56-68.

Saunders, M, Lewis, P, & Thornhill, A 2016, *Research methods for business students*, Pearson Education Publishers, New York.

Schreier, M 2012, *Qualitative content analysis in practice*, Sage Publishers, Thousand Oaks, CA.

Sekaran, A & Bourgie, S 2016, *Research Methods for Business: A Skill-Building Approach*, John Wiley & Sons, New York.

Shil, NC 2008, 'Accounting for good corporate governance', *JOAAG*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 22-31.

Siddique, S., Sciulli, N. & Faux, J., 2011. Towards a Theoretical Model for Analysing the Quality of Corporate Environmental Disclosure: Emphasising What and Why. *International Review of Business Research Papers*, 7(3), pp. 194-206.

Smith, J. L., Adhikari, A. & Tondkar, R. H., 2005. Exploring Differences in Social Disclosures Internationally: A Stakeholder Perspective. *Journal of Accounting and Public Policy*, 24(2), pp. 123-151.

Snyder, H 2019, 'Literature review as a research methodology: An overview and guidelines', *Journal of Business Research*, vol. 104, no. 1, pp. 333-339.

Sobhani, F. A., Arnran, A. & Zainuddin, Y., 2009. Revisiting the Practices of Corporate Social and Environmental Disclosure in Bangladesh. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 16(3), pp. 167-183.

Surroca, J., Tribo, J. A. & Waddock, S., 2009. Corporate Responsibility and Financial performance: The Role of Intangible Resource. *Strategic Management Journal*, 31(5), pp. 463-490.

Smartsheet, 2018. *What Is Stakeholder Theory and How Does It Impact an Organization?*.

[Online]

Available at: <https://www.smartsheet.com/what-stakeholder-theory-and-how-does-it-impact-organization>

Sonibare, O., Jarvie, H. A. D. & Ehinolac, O. A., 2008. Origin and occurrence of crude oil in the Niger delta, Nigeria. *Journal of Petroleum Science and Engineering*, 61(2-4), pp. 99-107.

Stroker, P., 2008. Local content development in the Nigerian oil and gas industry: Why it is not succeeding?. *Potchefstroom Campus of the North-West University* .

Suh, S. & Heise, K., 2014. *Re-evaluating the "Culture of Poverty"*. [Online]

Available at: <https://thesocietypages.org/roundtables/culture-of-poverty/>.

Sujin, M., 2019. Exploring the Corporate Social Responsibility Dimensions that Affect Customer Satisfaction and Loyalty. [ebook] Available at: <https://archives.kdischool.ac.kr/bitstream/11125/32848/1/Exploring%20the%20corporate%20social%20responsibility%20dimensions%20that%20customer%20satisfaction%20%and%20loyalty.pdf>.

Tagesson, T. et al. 2009, 'What Explains the Extent and Content of Social and Environmental Disclosures on Corporate Websites: A Study of Social and Environmental Reporting in Swedish Listed Corporations', *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, vol. 16, no. 6, pp. 352-364.

Taiwo, A. S., 2010. The influence of work environment on workers productivity: A case of selected oil and gas industry in Lagos, Nigeria. *African Journal of Business Management*, pp. 299-307.

Tan, C.L., San Ong, T., Wei, N.I. and Rahim, N.A., 2021. Sustainable Economic Development and Environmental Performance of Developing and Developed Countries. *Journal of Environmental Management & Tourism*, 12(2), pp.429-443.

Terlaak, A 2007, 'Order without law? The role of certified management standards in shaping socially desirable behaviours', *Academy of Management Review*, vol. 32, no. 1, pp. 968-985.

Washington, M, & Zajac, EJ 2005, 'Status evolution and competition: theory and evidence', *Academy of Management Journal*, vol. 48, no. 1, pp. 282-296.

Thien, G., Tregidga, H. & Kearins, K., 2010. *Corporate Social Responsibility Reporting by New Zealand Financial Services Institutions: Analysing Understandings and Motivations*. [Online]

Available at: apira2010.econ.usyd.edu.au/.../APIRA-2010-185-Thien-CSR-reporti... [Accessed 10 January 2019].

Tilling, M. V., 2018. *Refinements to Legitimacy Theory in Social and Environmental Accounting*. [Online]

Available at: <http://www.flinders.edu.au/sabs/business-files/research/papers/2004/04-6.pdf> [Accessed 26 10 2018].

Tomlinson, K., 2017. Oil and gas companies and the management of social and environmental impacts and issues. *United Nations University*.

Tran, H., 2018. Differences in Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure between Japan and the USA. *Journal of Asian Business and Economic Studies*, 25(1), pp. 67-85.

Trenberth, K.E., Dai, A., Van Der Schrier, G., Jones, P.D., Barichivich, J., Briffa, K.R., and Sheffield, J., 2014. "Global warming and changes in drought." *Nature Climate Change*, 4(1), p.17.

Trotman, K., 1979. Social Responsibility Disclosures by Australian Companies. *Chartered Accountant in Australia*, 49(8), pp. 24-28.

Udoma, U. & Osagie, B., 2018. *Oil & Gas in Nigeria*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.lexology.com/library/detail.aspx?g=38ab9ccc-2392-4cd6-b0dc-997695d924b6>

Udotong, JIR, Uduodo, UP & Udotong, I 2017, 'Effects of oil and gas exploration and production activities on production and management of seafood in Akwa Ibom state, Nigeria', *Journal of Environmental Chemistry and Ecotoxicology*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 20-42.

Ugbebor, J & Yorkor, B 2018, 'Assessment of ambient air quality and noise levels around selected oil and gas facilities in Nigeria', *Journal of Scientific Research and Reports*, vol. 18, no. 6, pp. 1-11.

US Department of State, 2014. *Investment Climate Statement*, s.l.: US Department of State.

Uwaoma, I. & Ordu, P. A., 2016. Environmental Reporting in the Oil and Gas Industry in Nigeria. *International Journal of Research in Business Studies and Management*, 3(11), pp. 1-21.

Uwuigbe, U. & Uadiale, O. M., 2011. Corporate Social and Environmental Disclosure in Nigeria: A Comparative Study of the Building Material and Brewery Industry. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 6(2), pp. 258-264.

Uwuigbe, U & Jimoh, J 2012, 'Corporate environmental disclosure in the Nigerian manufacturing industry: A study of selected firms', *African Research Review*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 1-5.

Uzonwanne, G., Yekini, K., Yekini, S. & Otobo, P., 2014. An Evaluation of Management Perspectives of Sustainability Reporting in the Nigerian Oil Industry. *Journal of Management and Sustainability*, 4(2), pp. 70-81.

Vaughan, A., 2011. *Oil in Nigeria: a history of spills, fines and fights for rights*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.theguardian.com/environment/2011/aug/04/oil-nigeria-spills-fines-fights>

- Vidal, J 2010, *Nigeria's agony dwarfs the gulf oil spills: The U.S. and Europe ignore it* [online]. Available from: <<https://www.theguardian.com>> [Accessed on 23rd June 2021].
- Vita, G. D., Lagoke, O. & Adesola, S., 2015. Nigerian oil and gas industry local content development: A stakeholder analysis. *Journal of Public Policy and Administration*, 31(1), pp. 51-79.
- Wahyuni, D., 2012. The Research Design Maze: Understanding Paradigms, Cases, Methods and Methodologies. *JAMAR*, 10(1), pp. 69-80.
- Wan-Jan, W. S., 2006. Defining corporate social responsibility. *Journal of Public Affairs*, Volume 6, pp. 176-184.
- Washington, M, & Zajac, EJ 2005, 'Status evolution and competition: theory and evidence', *Academy of Management Journal*, vol. 48, no. 1, pp. 282-296.
- Watts, M. J., 2005. Righteous oil? Human rights, the oil complex, and corporate social responsibility. *Annual Review of Environment and Resources*, Volume 30, pp. 373-407.
- Wirth, H., Kulczycka, J., Hausner, J., and Koński, M., 2016. "Corporate Social Responsibility: Communication about social and environmental disclosure by large and small copper mining companies." *Resources Policy*, 49, pp.53-60.
- World Bank 2020, *GDP and GDP per capita: Nigeria* [online]. Available from: <<https://data.worldbank.org>> [Accessed on 23rd June 2021].
- Wopara, G. R., 2015. A Study of the Nigeria Liquefied Natural Gas Limited's CSR for. *University of Agder*, pp. 1-118.
- Wu, A., 2020, March. Analysis on Opportunities and Challenges in Information Disclosure of Chinese Corporate Social Responsibility in the Era of Big Data. In *4th International Conference on Culture, Education and Economic Development of Modern Society (ICCESE 2020)* (pp. 472-475). Atlantis Press.
- Wuttichindanon, S., 2017. Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure - Choices of Report and its Determinants: Empirical Evidence from Firms listed on the Stock Exchange of Thailand. *Kasetsart Journal of Social Sciences*, 38(2), pp. 156-162.
- Xiao, Y & Watson, M 2017, 'Guidance on conducting a systematic literature review', *Journal of Planning Education and Research*, vol. 39, no. 1, pp. 93-112.
- Yagboyaju, DA & Akinola, AO 2019, 'Nigerian state and the crisis of governance: A critical exposition', *Sage Journal*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 1-5.

Yakubu, Y. F., 2017. Future of Nigeria's Petroleum Industry in View of Global Development in Energy Alternatives. *Research gate* .

Yuen, C. P. & Yip, D., 2002. Corporate Environmental Reporting – The CLP Power Experience. *Corporate Environmental Strategy*, 9(1), p. 95–100.

Yunusa, N., Mohamed, R. & Adam, N., 2016. Executive and non-executive auditors and environmental disclosure among listed firms in Nigeria. *Journal of Advanced Research in Business and Management Studies*, pp. 1-7.

Yusuf, I., Samuel, J. & Ekundayo, O., 2016. *The Extent of Environmental Disclosures in Listed Oil and Gas Companies in Nigeria*. s.l., Proceedings of Nigeria's Economic Development Conference.

Zamora, V., 2021. Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure Credibility. https://www.seattleu.edu/media/albers-school-of-business-and-economics/centers-and-programs/center-for-business-ethics/Zamora_Corporate-Social-Responsibility-Disclosure-Credibility_Final.pdf

Zhang, J., 2013. *Determinants of Corporate Environmental and Social Disclosure in Chinese Listed Mining, Electricity Supply and Chemical Companies Annual Reports*, Perth: Unpublished Master Thesis.

Zhang, Q., Oo, B.L. and Lim, B.T.H., 2019. Drivers, motivations, and barriers to the implementation of corporate social responsibility practices by construction enterprises: A review. *Journal of cleaner production*, 210, pp.563-584

Zukauskas, P 2017, *Philosophy and paradigm of scientific research*, IntechOpen Publishers, New York.

Appendix: Exhibit 1

Research Schedule Gantt Chart

TASKS/ACTIVITIES	Year 1			Year 2			Year 3			Year 4
	Feb- May 2018	Jun- Sep 2018	Oct- Jan 2019	Feb- May 2019	Jun- Sep 2019	Oct- Jan 2020	Feb- May 2020	Jun- Sep 2020	Oct- Jan 2021	Feb 2021- Feb 2022
Research Proposal										
Working with the research supervisor for research topic refinement.										
Designing research questions, objectives and writing introduction.										
Presenting the introductory chapter to the supervisor.										
Conducting research and writing literature review/ Theoretical Framework.										
Presenting the outcomes of the literature review/ Theoretical Framework of the research to supervisor.										
Doing corrections on the suggested areas to the Research literature review/ Theoretical Framework.										
Writing the research methodology chapter of the Research and designing the research instruments.										
Address ethical issues and prepare an ethical statement.										

Ethical approval.										
Data Collection for both primary and Secondary data										
Transfer Event/Report										
Data Transcribe/coding										
Analysis of Data. /Publication										
Write up Thesis.										
Finalizing the Research work.										
Preparing for VIVA.										
Presenting the Research work to supervisor and making presentations.										
VIVA.										
Implementing changes and recommendation/Final submission.										

Exhibit 2

**Nigeria Registered Oil Companies-As of 1st January 1992 and other two industries
Registered on 2nd June 2008 and in June 2009.**

S/N	OIL INDUSTRIES	S/N	OIL INDUSTRIES
1	ABACAN	37	BAYWOOD CONTINENTAL LTD.
2	ABB SOIMI NIGERIA LTD.	38	B+B GAS & OIL SERVICES NIGERIA LTD.
3	ADDAX OIL NIGERIA LTD.	39	BASELINE PETROL & CHEMICAL NIGERIA LTD.
4	ADM PETROLEUM.	40	BECO PETROLEUM PRODUCTS PLC.
5	ACORN PETROLEUM PLC.	41	BELL OIL & GAS LTD.
6	AFRICA OILFIELD SERVICE LTD.	42	BINT AND PRATHEL LTD.
7	AFRICAN PETROLEUM PLC. (AP).	43	BG EXPLORATION AND PRODUCTION NIGERIA LTD.
8	AFREN ENERGY RESOURCES.	44	BRASS EXPLORATION.
9	AFROIL PLC.	45	BOLTON NIGERIA LTD.
10	AGIGAF OIL VENTURES.	46	BONGUSTO NIGERIA LTD.
11	AGIP OIL COMPANY (NIGERIA) LTD.	47	BRIAN MUNRO LTD.
12	AKOJA OIL & GAS NIGERIA LTD.	48	BRENTFORD (NIG) LTD.
13	AJOLAD PETROLEUM.	49	BRITTANIA-U NIGERIA LTD.
14	ALFRED JAMES PETROLEUM.	50	BUA OIL MILL LTD.
15	ALLIED ENERGY RESOURCES (NIGERIA).	51	BULWARK SVCS LTD.
16	ALOZ OIL & GAS LTD.	52	BUREAU VERITASNIG LTD.
17	AMALGAMATED OIL.	53	BUSADOR & CO LTD.
18	AMEC OIL AND GAS LTD.	54	CAKASA NIGERIA COMPANY LTD.
19	AMNI INTERNATIONAL PETROLEUM DEV. CO. LTD.	55	CALIN SWEDEN NIGERIA INTERNATIONAL.
20	AMOCO CORPORATION.	56	CAMAC (ALLIED ENERGY RESOURCES) NIGERIA.
21	❖ ANINO INTERNATIONAL PLC. (NSE LISTED)	57	CANADIAN PETROLEUM LTD.
22	ASCON OIL COMPANY LTD.	58	❖ CAPITAL OIL & GAS LTD. (NSE LISTED)
23	ASH-BERT LIMITED.	59	CAVENDISH PETROLEUM NIGERIA LTD.
24	ATLANTIC MERIDEAN COMPANY LTD.	60	CENTRAL OIL ENGINEERING COMPANY LTD.
25	ATLANTIC MEDITERRANEAN OIL SERVICES LTD.	61	CGG VERITAS.

26	ATLAS ORANTO PETROLEUM OIL.	62	• CHEVRON NIGERIA LTD. Non- Listed
28	ATLAS PETROLEUM LIMITED.	63	CHROME OIL SERVICES LTD.
29	AQUITANE.	64	CILLAZA INTERNATIONAL NIGERIA LTD.
30	ARIBOIL COMPANY LIMITED.	65	CISCON.
31	ARKLEEN OIL & GAS LTD.	66	CLIO COMM LTD.
32	AUSTIN SHERIF LTD.	67	COMPAGNE GENERAL DE GEOPHSIQUE NIGERIA LTD.
33	AYT NIGERIA LTD.	68	COMPASS OIL & GAS SERVICES LTD.
34	A-Z PETROLEUM PRODUCTS LTD.	69	❖ CONOIL PLC. (NSE LISTED)
35	BAKER HUGHES NIGERIA LTD.	70	CONOCO ENERGY NIGERIA LTD.
36	BAMOD OIL NIGERIA LTD.	71	CONOCO PHILLIPS OIL COMPANY NIGERIA LTD.
72	CONZICU NIGERIA LTD.	107	ETUGO OIL INTERNATIONAL LTD.
73	COPLUS NIGERIA LTD.	108	EXTERRAN NIGERIA ENERGY SERVICES LTD.
74	COTSGAS H. A. P. NIGERIA LTD.	109	EXPRESS PETROLEUM PRODUCT.
75	CS TOTAL GASTROIL NIGERIA LTD.	110	EXPRESS PETROLUEM & GAS COMPANY LTD.
76	DAEWOO NIGERIA LTD.	111	EXPRO.
77	DAN OIL AND PETROCHEMICALS LTD.	112	➤ EXXONMOBIL. (MOBIL PRODUCTION A UNLIMITED)- (Interview 1) NIGERI
78	DAMAGIX NIGERIA LTD.	113	FABRICO OIL & GAS LTD.
79	DAMBUSEY NIGERIA LTD.	114	FF-40 PETROLEUM AND GAS COMPANY LTD.
80	DANSAKI PETROLEUM LTD.	115	FALCK PRIME ATLANTIC.
81	DARLIVAN VENTURES LTD.	116	FAMFA OIL.
82	DELSERVE NIGERIA LTD.	117	FELPET NIGERIA LTD.
83	DES PETROLEUM & ALLIED CHEMICALS LTD.	118	FLAME PETROLEUM & GAS COMPANY LTD.
84	DETFE NIGERIA LTD.	119	FOMON PETROLEUM & GAS NIGERIA LTD.
85	DEZERN NIGERIA LTD.	120	❖ FORTE OIL PLC. (NSE LISTED)
86	D & G PETROLEUM & GAS LTD.	121	FUGARD GROUP OF COMPANIES.
87	DOMADE VENTURES NIGERIA LTD.	122	FUGRO NIGERIA LTD.
88	DOMART GROUP OF COMPANIES.	123	GENERAL OIL (NIGERIA).

89	DON-WEI OIL AND GAS COMPANY LTD.	124	G. EURAFRIC LTD.
90	DOWEL NIGERIA LTD.	125	GLOBAL ENERGY GROUP LTD.
91	DOZZY OIL AND GAS LTD.	126	GLOBAL OFFSHORE DRILLING LTD.
92	DREDGING INTERNATIONAL SERVICES NIGERIA LTD.	127	GOLDEN OIL & EXTRACTION COMPANY LTD.
93	DRILLOG PETRO-DYNAMICS LTD.	128	GRAMMER PETROSERV NIGERIA LTD.
94	DUBRI OIL COMPANY LTD.	129	HALIBURTON ENERGY SERVICES NIGERIA LTD.
95	DUPOINT NIGERIA LTD.	130	HARDY OIL & GAS PLC.
96	ELEME PETROCHEMICAL (EPCL).	131	HENCHOKO VENTURES.
97	ELF PETROLEUM NIGERIA LTD.	132	HONEYWELL OIL & GAS.
98	EMERAUDE NIGERIA LTD.	133	HYDROCARBON SERVICES OF NIGERIA (HYSON).
99	ENERGO NIGERIA LTD.	134	KADUNA REFINERY & PETROCHEMICALS (KRPC).
100	ENERGY TRADING & TRANSPORT COMPANY LTD.	135	KASOLUTE NIGERIA LTD.
101	ENSCO DRILLING COMPANY (NIGERIA) LTD.	136	IBAFON OIL LTD.
102	EQUATOR EXPLORATION NIGERIA LTD.	137	IGPES LTD.
103	ESCO EXPLORATION & PRODUCTION NIGERIA LTD.	138	IKART INTERNATIONAL SERVICES.
104	ESKAY PETROLUEM LTD.	139	INDEX PETROLUBE AFRICA LTD.
105	ESSO EXPLORATION & PRODUCTION NIGERIA LTD.	140	INTERTEC NIGERIA LTD.
106	❖ ETERNA OIL & GAS PLC. (NSE LISTED)	141	INVENSYS.
142	❖ JAPPAUL OIL & MARITIME SERVICES PLC. (NSE LISTED)	176	NIGER OFFSHORE NIGERIA LTD.
143	JENEW NIGERIA LTD.	177	➤ NIGERIA LNG LTD (NLNG). (Interview 2)
144	KEEDAC NIGERIA LTD.	178	NIGERIA OIL RESOURCES COMPANY LTD.
145	KENGRIN NIGERIA LTD.	179	NIGERIAN AGIP OIL COMPANY LTD.
146	KNIGHTS BRIDGE LTD.	180	NIGERIAN AGIP EXPLORATION LTD.
147	LADOL.	181	NIGERIAN NATIONAL PETROLEUM CORPORATION.

148	LA-MOND LTD.	182	NIGERIAN PETROLEUM. DEVELOPMENT COMPANY LTD.
149	LAMONT OIL AND CHEMICAL NIGERIA LTD.	183	NIMADEK LTD.
150	LIFE GATE OIL & GAS LTD.	184	NIPCO PLC.
151	MAA OIL & GAS NIGERIA LTD.	185	NISSCO.
152	MABON LTD.	186	NITRO ATLASCO NIGERIA LTD.
153	MANATH OIL & GAS.	187	NOBLE DRILLING NIGERIA LTD.
154	MARCA INTERNATIONAL LTD.	188	NOREAST PETROLEUM.
155	MARINE AND OIL SERVICES (NIGERIA) LTD.	189	NORTH-EAST PETROLEUM.
156	MCDEMOTT NIGERIA LTD.	190	NOSSIEN PETROLEUM AND GAS NIGERIA LTD.
157	MELVON.	191	❖ OANDO NIGERIA PLC. (NSE LISTED)
158	MIDLANTIC INTERNATIONAL.	192	OCEAN & OIL HOLDINGS.
159	M-I DRILLING FLUIDS NIGERIA LTD.	193	OIL & SERVICES LTD.
160	MILLAN OIL AND GAS LTD.	194	OILSERV LTD.
161	MILLENIU OIL & GAS COMPAN M Y (MOGCL).	195	OILWORLD.
162	MI SWACO.	196	OPTIMUM PETROLEUM DEVELOPMENT COMPANY.
163	❖ MOBIL OIL NIGERIA LTD. CHANGE NAME & NOW CALLED NAME TO 11 PLC) (NSE LISTED)	197	ORACLE NIGERIA.
164	MONBEL OIL & GAS LTD.	198	ORIENTAL ENERGY RESOURCES.
165	MONI PULO.	199	OUTTURN OIL & GAS LTD.
166	MOVIDO EXPLORATION & PRODUCTION NIGERIA LTD.	200	O VIKA GROUUP LTD.
167	MRS OIL NIGERIA LTD. (NSE LISTED)	201	PABE OIL & GAS NIGERIA LTD.
168	NACOIL INTERNATIONAL LTD.	202	PAN OCEAN OIL CORPORATION NIGERIA LTD.
169	NATIONAL OIL AND GAS CHEMICAL MARKETING PLC.	203	PEAK PETROLEUM LIMITED.
170	NEGRIS LTD.	204	PERE ROBERTO NIGERIA LTD.
171	NESTOIL LTD.	205	PETROBRAS.
172	NETWORK PETROLEUM COMPANY LTD.	206	PETROLEO BRASILEIRO NIGERIA.
173	NEXEN PETROLEUM NIGERIA INC.	207	PETROLEUM TRAINING INVESTMENT.

174	NIGER DELTA DRILLING FUND PLC.	208	PETROLOG LIMITED
175	NIGEOCON INTERNATIONAL LTD.	209	PGS EXPLORATION NIGERIA LTD.
		210	PHILLIPS OIL COMPANY (NIGERIA.)
211	PIPELINES & PRODUCTS MARKETING (PPMC).	245	TECHNIP.
212	PLATFORM PETROLEUM LTD.	246	TECO LTD.
213	POLAR-ICE OIL AND GAS LTD.	247	TECON OIL SERVICES LTD.
214	PORT HARCOURT REFINING (PHRC).	248	TEGMIC NIGERIA LTD.
215	PROFLOAD (SVCS) LIMITED.	249	THE IBETO GROUP.
216	RAHAMANIYYA OIL & GAS.	250	TEXACO NIGERIA PLC.
217	❖ RAK UNITY PETROLUEM COMPANY PLC. (NSE LISTED)	251	TITANIUM OIL & ENERGY LTD.
218	ROXAR.	252	❖ TOTAL NIGERI PLC. (NSE LISTE A D)
219	SADIQ PETROLEUM NIGERIA (SPNL).	253	TOTAL E AND P NIGERIA LTD.
220	SAHARA GROUP.	254	TOTAL UPSTREAM NIGERIA LTD.
221	SAIPEM NIGERIA LTD.	255	TRICONTINENTAL OIL SERVICES LTD.
222	SBM MARINA SERVICES.	256	TROPICAL PETROLEUM PRODUCTS PLC.
223	SCHLUMBERGER OIL SERVICES GROUP.	257	TROPICAL SERVICES NIGERIA LTD.
224	SEA PET GAS COMPANY LTD.	258	TYPHA CENIA LTD.
225	SEALAND OILFIELD SERVICES LTD.	259	UDOKANMA OIL.
226	➤ SHELL PETROLEUM DEV. CO. OF NIGERIA LTD. (Interview 3)	260	UNION VENTURES AND PETROLEUM PLC. (CHANGED NAME TO NAVITUS ENERGY PLC. ON 17/1/14)
227	SHELL NIGERIA EXPLORATION & PRODUCTION COMPANY.	261	UTURU OIL NIGERIA LTD.
228	SHORA OIL AND GAS (DOWNSTREAM).	262	VERACITY VENTURE LTD.

229	SOCOTHERM GROUP.	263	VETCO AIBEL NIGERIA LTD.
230	SODEXHO NIGERIA LTD.	264	VIRGO288 NIGERIA LTD.
231	SOGENAL LTD.	265	VITA-ACT OIL AND CHEMICAL MARKETING CO. LTD.
232	SOLGAS PETROLEUM LTD.	266	VRMT INTERNATIONAL NIGERIA LTD.
233	SONO NIGERIA LTD.	267	WALLHOUSE (W.A) LTD.
234	SOUTH ATLANTIC PETROLEUM LTD (SAPETRO).	268	WARRI REFINING & PETROCHEMICALS (WRPC).
235	SOUTHWEST OIL & GAS LTD.	269	WASCAP PETROLEUM LTD.
236	SOWSCO.	270	WASCO OIL SERVICES COMPANY NIGERIA LTD.
237	STAR DEEP WATER PETROLEUM.	271	WEAFRI.
238	STAR OIL FIELD SERVICES.	272	WEST AFRICA OFFSHORE LTD.
239	STATOIL NIGERIA LTD.	273	WESTERN ATLAS LOGGING SERVICES.
240	SUDELETTRA NIGERIA LTD.	274	WESTERN GEOPHYSICAL (WESTERN ATLAS NIGERIA LTD).
241	SUMMIT OIL INTERNATIONAL LTD.	275	WILBROS NIGERIA LTD.
242	SUNLINK PETROLEUM LTD.	276	WILSON GEORGE LTD.
243	SURVICOM.	277	WOG ALLIED SERVICES NIGERIA LTD.
244	SYNTROLEUM NIGERIA	278	YINKA FOLAWIYO PETROLEUM LTD.
		279	ZENON PETROLEUM & GAS.
		279	ZUKUS INDUSTRIES LTD

Those with red are listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange. Those with **blue** are chosen sample companies. (Source: Archival records of the Department of Petroleum Resources, Lagos, 1992)

**THE TWO OIL COMPANYS BELOW WERE INCORPORATED DIFFERENTLY
FROM THE ABOVE LISTED WHICH INCLUDES: -**

280	❖ CAVERTON OFFSHORE SUPPORT GROUP PLC. (NSE LISTED)	INCORPORATED IN NIGERIA ON 2ND JUNE 2008.
281	❖ SEPLAT PETROLEUM DEVELOPMENT (NSE LISTED)	SEPLAT WAS FORMED IN JUNE 2009 THROUGH THE PARTNERSHIP OF SHEBAH PETROLEUM DEVELOPMENT COMPANY LIMITED AND PLATFORM PETROLEUM JOINT VENTURES LIMITED.

This oil company's lists were obtained from the Department of Petroleum Resources in Lagos State, Nigeria indicated that there were 279 oil companies registered as of 1st January 1992 including two (2) oil companies registered differently, making it 281 registered oil companies. Thirteen oil companies listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange as well as an additional two non-listed major multinational foreign oil companies which includes Shell, Mobil and one non-listed domestic oil companies **Bayelsa Oil Company LTD (Interview 4)** were also selected as sample, because of the scale of their operations in the Niger Delta (Aaron, 2008).

Exhibit 3: Reflection on Data Collection Trip to Nigeria

The purpose of my study could inform the public of the information contained in the SED and how the oil companies endeavour to disclose this information. Importantly, the public needs to know the attempts the organisations in the oil industry are taking regarding conservation measures made to sustain the environment. Moreover, my research work will show the current world what the corporations are obliged to demonstrate high level of awareness of their activities and address the impacts of their daily operations on the environment and general society at large. However, after the approval by ethical committee of the University of the West of Scotland, I proceeded to Nigeria for my data collection. The researcher visited four states in Nigeria which includes: - Akwa Ibom state, Bayelsa state, Delta state and lastly, River's state. Getting there, I found out that things are different from what I thought they would be and based on the experiences the researcher decided to make this documentation for the purpose of evidence and to share the experiences of my trips to Nigeria for data collection.

In Nigeria, the researcher had an assistant (Data Project Assistant) who helped me in the entire collection of the said primary data. He was with me throughout the process of the data collection with key experiences and challenges on our way to the host communities and the Oil Companies respectively. These personal experience highlights supporting information needed to help with my research work and has transformed my initial perception of the relationship between the host community and the oil companies at large. The researcher and his Data Project Assistant had key experiences altogether and will be discuss in detail below. In here, I will talk about our travel experiences, the city/town experiences, the reception by the host community and the oil companies, our hotel experiences, food and cuisine, security challenges, the awareness of the host community knowledge concerning social environmental disclosure and how the oil companies have been related with the host community. We will also talk about the technical challenges during the data collection process. But first, we will start with Akwa Ibom state, Nigeria.

1. Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Akwa Ibom State was the first state the researcher and his assistant visited after landing from Abuja the capital city of Nigeria and its was an eye-opening state for the researcher and his assistant due to the kind of challenges faced in Akwa Ibom State. It was one of the difficult State comparing to other States within the target area of my research data collection. In getting into Uyo, the state capital of Akwa Ibom state, we travelled to Eket Local Government Area (LGA) and then, Ibeno LGA, the city where Exxon Mobil is located at. Having gotten to Ibeno, we find help with a community resident who introduced us to the town crier in one of the communities and from there we were led to the community leader and the chiefs within Ibeno community. The researcher then consults the community leader and chiefs by stating why he is in their community and how to penetrate the community for data collection data of his research work. But before the researcher can see either the community leader or chiefs in any of the town, there are always traditional ways of appeasing them, which mean, one must go with a very strong

drinks, such as brandy, whisky or gin to appease them for the intention of one coming into their community before they can listen to you. Then the community leader or chief will then call his village stakeholders, including the youth leader asking them to support you during the process of your data collection.

The researcher got access into the community, getting into the community was a different ball game as the community youths still cornered us demanded their own share of the money or gifts through consultation. These made it difficult for the researcher and assistant to access the community for the data collection. But in the long run, the researcher finally got through it by at least trying to dialogue in form of educating them on our research project, explaining to them how important it is to them and the changed it can bring to their community if implemented also stating that it will create awareness and bring stability and transparency of social environmental reporting from the oil company through such research project like this. The Researcher then consults the youth with a strong drink and then get full access into the community. We interviewed the community youth leader in Mkpanak, Ibeno local government area and left the community due to the unsettledness of the youths for their demand. We then proceeded to Ikot Udotu in Eket local government area, where we interviewed the community leader and the academician at Heritage Polytechnic, Eket, this was kind peaceful as the community leader was supportive to the research work. Although as a tradition one must go in with a strong drink and cola.

The researcher then left to Etebi in Esit- Eket LGA, we interviewed the community resident and proceeded back to Quo Ibom church to interview the church leader, who his from Onna-Eket local government area in Akwa Ibom State. From Esit- Eket we then moved to Exxon Mobil. Getting to Exxon Mobil, we managed to get access to the Public Relationship Officer (PRO) after giving us appointment, Exxon Mobil kept postponing the appointment each time we there, saying 'oh, there is no time because of their company meetings and busy scheduled. So, we kept coming in and out of that Exxon Mobil for close to a week before we were granted an audience. However, before the researcher and his assistant could get access into the oil company (Exxon Mobil) building, the youths from the four local governments area which comprises of Eket LGA, Esit-Eket LGA, Ibeno LGA and Onna LGA, blocked us from accesses Exxon Mobil building as they have different perception of what we were coming to do, even after explaining to them what the research project is all about. These four local governments area listed above are the Oil producing local government area in Akwa Ibom State. Moreover, one of the youths stated that since I travel from Scotland, United Kingdom to get this data which they all know that there is Shell in Scotland, that am working for the oil company (Exxon Mobil), especially when holding a file to see the Public Relation Officers (PRO) or management, that mean I have been given a contract from Exxon Mobil. Their perception was that the Exxon Mobil had given me contract and I need to recruit them or carry them along or nothing will work for me.

The researcher tries to explain more to the youths about the research project again, even though that it was already explained to them that the work is just for academic purpose only and not contract from Exxon Mobil. They threatened to even seize our working equipment if we don't settle them as we did with the chiefs. They started fermenting trouble, but we manage to pacify them that no, this is not for contract or for job, and that we are not being send by any oil companies nor anybody, that the research is purely for academic purpose. It took the intervention of their youth leaders there to calm the other members of their team down. After all that, they were receptive to what the researcher says, they opened stating their experiences between them and the oil company. It was a very good rapport with the members of the community.

The Youth leader then stated that I can only go in for the interview on one condition, stating that two of their executives will escort me in to see the PRO and observed the interview to see whether am telling them the true or not. The researcher managed to interview the one company management and one of the company employees. On getting out from Exxon Mobil, they demanded for settlement for allowing me in, as tradition we were told that we should present a strong drink which is their tradition there. We did that and left with our equipment intact. Then, another aspect we had challenges with was the youth of the area. Overall, our stay in Akwa Ibom state was peaceful, our hotel accommodation was very okay, and the place was serene. Their cuisine and their food were very-very good, and we ate some home-made delicacies and wow, cuisine-wise it was a very mouth-watering experience, the researcher was so grateful that communities and the oil company gave us the audience to carry on with the interview and fulfil our data collection in Akwa Ibom state.

This security challenges were partially fair and awareness levels of the host community concerning social environmental disclosure were positive as most of the community were educated except few. However, in most cases, researchers felt coming to collect data here as it is very difficult for someone to come and acquire data for any research work in here, except you are ready to go through the problems of accessing and meeting the peoples of the communities including the oil company. We managed to secure our equipment, because without that we could not move on to other communities or states as all our interviews recorded were on the voice recorder and we had to distribute them into flash drives and SD cards in case we lose the voice recorder. The threat in this environment was so high that we didn't know what is going to happen next, but at the end of the day we managed to secure our equipment and bring it back to our hotel room.

My observation with most of the community leaders within some communities is that they are trying to be a little bit secretive; they are trying to withhold information about the activities of the oil companies, because some of them have dirty deals with the oil company and they don't want to expose it. So, they don't want to tell the truth about the oil company's activities in the community. They were just talking very slowly so that we will not hear the full content of what they are saying and when you asked them to be more audible, they would tell you, that is how we

speak. So, these were just difficult challenges for us to tell them ‘Please Sir, can you speak up a little bit so that we can hear so that we don’t miss any valuable contribution you are giving to us in terms of your opinion’. But they kept going on with their very quiet voice and as if they don’t want you to hear what they are talking about. So, apart from that, we got the interview done anyway and these were our experiences Akwa Ibom state, Nigeria.

2. Rivers State, Nigeria

First and foremost, the travels through River were like wow, we got into a vehicle, heading towards River state and in the vehicle, we heard from one of the co-travelers that along the road we are travelling on now, there was a serious armed robbery incident the day before and that some people were even killed, the driver was shot in the head, the passengers were kidnapped and taken into the bushes or forests. We were like ‘oh, we are on this road today’. So, we prayed that we would get a safe passage. Along the road, every two poles you meet police checkpoints, different kinds of checkpoints, stop and search. We travelled down but the road was relatively calm that day, thank God for that. Along the road, the major road was newly done I think it was a collaboration with Petroleum Trust Fund (PTF), I think it was one of these government agencies, NDDC (Niger Delta Development Commission) that did the road, the East-West Road, so it was very smooth to drive on. Then, on arriving at Rivers, we got to the park where we were relieved. The place was ok, generally travel-wise Rivers was okay on the road.

Due to our experience, we had in Akwa Ibom state, we decided not to move into the deep-deep River state communities because of safety issues. We only went to the nearby accessible community area that we could access through road transport, but we chose not to go into deep communities for which we would have had to use canoe or boat to access them. Basically, it is just because of the security threat that we had to avoid areas that are more dangerous and more violent, as we wanted to come and get our data for my research work and not to end up losing our lives in the process. So, we moved into a fewer threatening community within River state, where most of the oil companies are operating and we got to meet stakeholders from those different communities. We went to Obio-Akpor local government area, where we interviewed the community leader, academician, and church leader. From there, we moved into another town called Ogoni in Khana local government area, where we interviewed community residents separately.

We moved into Abonnema in Akuku-Toru local government area to interview the youth leader of that community. At the end of the day, we conducted those interviews safely. Our experience in River state was a little bit calmer than what we expected because right before we came here, we heard about some cult groups and militants fighting each other. Some community residents were beheaded, and the area was so tense that we had to be careful about what we were doing in that environment. But we did not give up; we still proceeded to collect the data collected. Experience of accommodation, food was all very okay although we walked such a long journey before we could get the food, but it was quite okay. The security challenges in Rivers were not as much as we had in Akwa Ibom state, although we heard about a lot of violent things that have

happened before we came in, but we did our best not to fall into the hands of those mentioned above, (i.e., the occultists and militancy's) and we avoid those communities for safety reason.

Apart from the security challenges in River state was better off than the one in Akwa Ibom state. The awareness level of the host community concerning SED was satisfactory. Although we couldn't access the, NLNG in Bonny at that time, as appointments to meet up with their PRO was cancelled due to their daily busy operation and was reschedule but we never made it inside the oil company as appointment was shifted to the day I was meant to travelled back to the United Kingdom. So, we left and continued with other states due to the limited time I had to stay in Nigeria, as an international student I could not stay outside the United Kingdom for more than 4 weeks. So, we then proceeded to Bayelsa State

3. Bayelsa State, Nigeria

Travelling to Bayelsa state, was my first time. So, we boarded a bus from River state heading to Bayelsa and stop in Bayelsa capital city Yenagoa, when the driver asked us about where we are dropping off and we looked at each other, we said Well, we just wanted to go to Yenagoa, as we don't know any bus stop here, so the lady beside us said she was stopping at Opollo one of the communities in Yenagoa. So, we said 'okay, we will stop at Opollo' too. So, we all got off the bus at Opollo, she was very helpful, she helped us because she is a native of that same town. She helped us seek for our hotel accommodation and checked us in, she gave us a little tour around the environment and generally the reception at the town, the town experience in Bayelsa was good. Our only problem was that there was no electricity throughout our stay in Bayelsa; we had to rely on the generator, which was put on mostly in the evenings and taken even before we woke up. Mosquito bites, I am not sure if we can call them mosquitoes, but they were stinging us, making us to scratch our body. I am not from Bayelsa, but I discovered in Bayelsa their youths were mostly in the creek, they were not even in the town, as most menial jobs and things done there were done by people from other states. I discovered lots of my own kinsmen in Bayelsa. I was even shocked that it was like an extension of my own state. Bayelsa was good and a nice town, but the hotel we lodged on in Bayelsa was nothing to write home about. It was too poor, most especially because of the darkness. The place is so hot.

We get appointment in the Bayelsa Oil Company. As we got in there, we noticed that there was no billboard or sign that indicate the Oil Company. Because sometimes the community youths force the oil company to stop their production due to agitation and demands which sometimes leads to violent, so they moved their office to different location where they don't showcase their signpost to keep the community youths away. We managed to get through to the oil company, and audience was given to us by one of the managers who confirmed our appointment from the protocol officer. We then interviewed one company management and one employee who spoke with us by sharing their views of how they deal with the community youths and their own perception of how they are managing the whole situation. We later finished and moved into Otio community, where we interviewed one church leader at Assemblies of God Church. Afterwards we interviewed one community resident at the community leader palace.

From there, we left Yenogoa to Ogbia local government; in Ogbia local government area we visited Federal University, Otuoke where we interviewed one academician. But before then we visited the community leader, consulted the town chief, and stated our intention of visiting the community which he then supported us by giving one of the residents to show us around. Otuoke was very nice as we strolled around the town. It was very peaceful and calm, and they were security challenge within the town. This happened to be the town where the formal president of Nigeria (Goodluck Jonathan) comes from. It was a deep-deep town of Ogbia local government, and we went in and come back safely. Moreover, we proceeded to Agbere in Sagbama local government area, where we visited the community leader and chiefs, and appeased them as tradition demands.

The community leader granted us audience for an interview. We then leave for Ekperi-ama in Nembe local government area, consulted the host community leader and the youth leader for audience, which the youth leader then accepted, after the normal traditional right was given, the youth leader then granted us interview. The youth's leader and his executives were ready to speak; most of them even spoke off record. On reception by the host community, they received us very well, they conducted us around, they showed us many places, and even the transporters were helpful. They took us to different places; went to see different host communities around. They were like yeah that what we are doing is good and they need this kind of exposure, that even the people of Ogoni Kingdom in Rivers state stood their ground and had a voice, that is why there is no oil exploration in Ogoni-land as the people never give up to the government and the oil company to explore oil in their community. So, they need that same voice too here in Bayelsa state.

I think Bayelsa was one of the states that I am sure I would love to visit again because of how the place is and how we were received. We didn't have much challenge security-wise in there, it was relatively peaceful. Travelling within Bayelsa state was safe, the security level was good. On technical challenges, we don't have much issue, just the issue of electricity to charge our equipment; the people were friendly towards us with everything. The level of awareness of SEDs in Bayelsa state was relatively higher amongst states we visited as they were ready to speak, the youths were eager to get things out and they really showed appreciation for our cause and our project, the people there were ready and very helpful to us.

4. Delta State, Nigeria

Travelling into Delta State from Bayelsa State, we had our first port of call to Ughelli. Ughelli was wow; I don't know how to put it. Everything was busy. The town was not busy in the right sense of the word, but scary busy. Even at the park where we were waiting for the taxi, a motorcycle hit a little girl who was selling snacks. So, I was wondering what was going on, and the place, no compassion, nothing; everybody was like all busy and trying to rip people off. Despite this, we visited Ughelli South, met with one of the community leaders, explained to him

our purposed then present cola as tradition demand, he then asked one of the community residents to speak to us as he was about going out for a meeting before we got there. We interview one community resident in Ughelli South. People around were gathering, trying to eavesdrop, and finding out what was going on, and what are they signing after the interview, what documents are they bringing? So, after we finished, we moved to Warri North local government area.

At Warri, it was another episode. As we about to check into the hotel we initially booked, the taxi driver who was carrying us around stated that he is native of that same town we are in and he advised us not to leave that hotel, as the community there is full of dangerous people with crimes. He said to us to be honest with us that these criminal people literally know everyone in the environment, so when they observe that you are new, they will come to rob you. He also stated that at night, it is not as safe as we think it will be. Like the environments around those hotels are terrible, it is filled with all these cult activities and fights, anything can happen, there is militancy within those areas. So, he now took us to a hotel and that hotel was used as a police base, so it has some relative security. That is where we could drop our equipment; drop our things before we could move around the state.

We proceeded to Petroleum Training Institute, Effurun, Warri, where we met an academician who happened to come from Ododegho, Ughelli North LGA, we seek for his audience which he granted us and we interviewed him and move to Ovade, Ogahara in Ethiope West local government area. Nevertheless, getting to Ovade, Ogahara in Ethiope West local government area, which we met one of the community youth leaders. We appeased him and his executives as traditional demand and he gave us audience, we conducted the interview and left for Koko where we conducted interview with one church leader at the Deeper Life Bible Church. So, we proceeded to Utagba-Uno in Ndokwa West local government area where we met the town crier in one the community, who lead us to the community leader, we appeased the community leader as traditional demands, who spoke to us about the community and later granted us audience for the interview. We noticed that the chief wasn't speaking out much, so we prompted him to be a little more audible. At the end of the day, we did the interview and left.

The next day we went to Shell Company. It was difficult to get interview done as appointment given to us was postponed many times without a new date offered. So, due to the limited time that I was meant to spend in Nigeria, I had to go to the Shell liaison office in Abuja which I was told that once I return to Nigeria, I should call back to them for audience. Generally, our stay was very tense in there; we were always on our toes, but I am glad we got the interview done in Delta state except Shell that wasn't done. The reception in Delta state generally was the poorest among all the states that we have been to, but the hotel experience at Warri was okay due to the adequate security level and police presence that was in the hotel. But after our stay there we couldn't really go around as much as we wanted to because of the nature of security challenges we found there. The level of awareness of the host community on SED, I would say they are much aware; they were very much enlightened about the level of SED among firms there.

The chiefs initially tried to put up stumbling block, not to grant interview, but after much explanation and pacifying by the normal cultural way of doing things, giving them their drinks and whatever, they demanded by tradition and light refreshment, they opened, although we had technical challenges, especially among the chiefs. They were liked not vocal, too low, we had to put the recorder so close to them to get what they were saying. Apart from that, Delta is not what I would advise somebody who is a novice to go into that field. You must really know what you are doing, and you must be on top of your game security-wise to go into Delta state. The kidnapping business is becoming more rampant in there, so we were just so very-very careful about how we went about our ways in that town.

For me, this was a nice experience because without this, I would not have known what is really going on within the Niger-Delta states in Nigeria but through the community leaders, community youths, community resident, church leaders, academicians, and companies at large. This is an eye-opener for me as the way the communities perceived SED by the oil company and the way the oil companies think about the communities at large within the Niger-delta regions. I used this opportunity to highlight reflection of what I and my data collection assistant have seen in these four states from the beginning to the end.

It has been a pleasant experience; an experience that I would like to have all over again. We really went all out to get this data and from what we gathered I pray, and I believe it will be sustainable in helping and making companies more responsive to their social environmental disclosures to host communities and how the communities can work with the oil companies in betterment of the Niger-delta region. The Data Collection Assistant used this medium to thank the researcher for opportunity giving him in embarking this journey of wisdom and appreciated all what he learns during this course as he stated that, there is no knowledge lost, and that he has been more improved.

He also stated that he has been able to travel around to other parts of Nigeria, other communities within Nigeria to see and to get first-hand information about what goes on there which he thinks it is a pleasant experience to have. The researcher also uses this medium to thank his Data Collection Assistant for accompanying him through all the dangerous trips, without him, it would have been difficult to complete this project. Looking at the problems that we were faced, all round the challenges we have met, I would have been scared and would have just walked away from it by coming back to the United Kingdom to see whether to change my research topic to something else.

He kept pushing me saying, we can do it, we are part of Niger Delta, we are part of South-South, Nigeria and this is our homeland, this is our town, even though we are not living here, but we can still do it. This gives me a fresh determination and I say 'ok, let's forge ahead, whatever we see during our journey, we are going to stand together. And we did it, we went through this risk and dangerous area, and we got the data, and we came back. I will thank him for accompanying me

into those states and staying with me for about a month, making sure the project is completed.
Thank you very much for helping me out through this project.

EXHIBIT 4: INTERVIEW QUESTION GUIDE

Dear Respondent,

I am a doctoral student working on my research project entitled “An Investigation of Social and Environmental Disclosure in Nigeria Oil Industry. Therefore, I am required to establish the perceptions and opinions of different stakeholders on the SED among firms in the Nigerian oil industry.

Your participation in this interview is entirely voluntarily. If you decide to complete the interview and later change your mind, you can stop and withdraw your responses at any time. This study is being undertaken in fulfilment of the requirement for the award of a PhD. Degree. Your response will be kept confidential, used strictly for my academic work, and will be a valuable contribution to my research. Therefore, please complete the questionnaire as honest as you can.

Yours sincerely,

Charles T. Atang

PART ONE: Personal Data

- Gender
- Marital Status
- Age
- Education Level
- How long have lived in this community?
- Community position: Company Management, Company Employee, Community Leader, Community Youth Leader, Community Resident, Church Leader and Academician.
- Residence: Akwa Ibom, Delta , Rivers and Bayelsa State.
- Oil Company- Exxon Mobil, Shell, NLNG and Bayelsa Oil Company

PART TWO:

FOR NIGERIAN OIL INDUSTRIES

SECTION 1: INTRODUCTION

	<p>Research aim; importance of interviewees' participation.</p> <p>Assurance of confidentiality; permission of audio recording</p>
SECTION 2: SED AND THE FIRM (PERCEPTION AND ACTIVITIES)	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ As company management what are the host community perspective on social and environmental disclosure of your company? ➤ As company management how does the company publicise its SED policy and performance? ➤ As company management how does the SED disclosure get through to the clients and other stakeholders? ➤ As company management to what extent is your company committed to develop SED? And why? ➤ From company management perspective what do you think will be done to further improve SED disclosure in this company? ➤ As company management how long has the company operated its SED policy?
SECTION 3: MOTIVATIONS	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ As company management what motivates your company to develop a SED policy? Any objections? ➤ From company management perspective what are your views on the current SED policies of this company? ➤ From company management perspective how do you see SED policies of this company aligned with global requirements? ➤ From company management perspective what motivates the company to engage in SED activities? Examples? ➤ As company management what level of involvement do host communities have in the oil company before initiating their social and environment projects/activities? Any negative impacts? How about other stakeholders? (e.g., competitors, policy makers) ➤ From company management perspective how well do you think your company's policies are aligned with home community in aspects of SED disclosure?
SECTION 4: CHALLENGES	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ As company management what are the current challenges faced by the company from SED disclosure? ➤ From company management perspective what are the strengths

	<p>and weaknesses of the current SED framework of this company?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ From company management perspective what steps has your company taken to promote SED disclosure? Any challenges and new initiatives? ➤ As company management how have government policies affected internal SED policy and practice in the company? ➤ From company management perspective how has the economic recession affected SED in your company?
SECTION 5: CONCLUSION	
	<p>Return to any incomplete or unclear points in the interview.</p> <p>Encourage suggestions for future research.</p>
Thanks very much for your time and cooperation.	

FOR HOST COMMUNITY

Section 1: Introduction	
	<p>Research aim; importance of interviewees' participation.</p> <p>Assurance of confidentiality; permission of audio recording</p>
Section 2: SED and the firm (Perception and Activities)	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ As community leader can you tell me what you understand about SED disclosure? ➤ As community leader what are your perceptions on the disclosure of SER by this oil company? ➤ As community leader what level of involvement do your community have in the oil company before they initial their social and environment projects/activities? Any negative impacts? ➤ From community leader perspective, what will you say are the most important social and environmental issues or problem affecting your community?
Section 3: Motivations	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ As community leader what sort of motivation does the community received from the oil company to solve your social and environmental problem? ➤ From community leader perspective, how do you see SED

	<p>reporting of this company aligned with community development?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ As community leader can you please mention some of the benefit or damages that the oil company has contributed to your community? ➤ As community leader what sort of SER practices do you expect the oil company to adapt for the community to continue to support them?
Section 4: Challenges	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ From community leader perspective, what are the impacts of social and environmental challenges posed by this company? ➤ As community leader what nature of support does the community receive from the oil company to tackle these challenges? ➤ As community leader what steps has the oil company taken to promote SED disclosure within the community? ➤ From community leader perspective, what do you think will be done to further improve SED reporting by this oil company?
Section 5: Conclusion	
	<p>Return to any incomplete or unclear points in the interview.</p> <p>Encourage suggestions for future research</p>
Thanks very much for your time and cooperation.	

EXHIBIT 5: PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET

UNIVERSITY OF THE WEST OF SCOTLAND

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET

To: Participants

This information sheet tells you the purpose of this study and what will happen to you if you take part. Talk to others about the study if you wish. Ask me if there is anything that is not clear.

Project Title: An investigation of social and environmental disclosures in Nigerian oil industry

Student Researcher: Charles Thompson Atang

I am Charles Thompson Atang, a PhD student in the School of Business Enterprise, University of the West of Scotland. My research project is an investigation of social and environmental disclosure in the Nigerian oil industry. I would like to invite you to take part in this research project.

The Research aim: The research aims to examine social and environmental disclosures in the Nigerian oil industry.

What will happen? I would like to invite you to take part in our research study. Before you decide, we would like you to understand why the research is being done and what it would involve for you. We will go through the information sheet with you and answer any questions you have. We'd suggest this should take about 60-90minutes.

What is the study about? In the current business world, corporations are obligated to demonstrate a high level of awareness of their activities and address the impacts that their daily operations have on the environment and general society. The purpose of this research is to examine social and environmental disclosures in the Nigerian oil industry. The researcher will explore the scope of the social and environmental disclosure in the Nigerian oil industry and seeks to examine difference between domestic and international oil company concerning the disclosure of social and environmental information to various stakeholders. The study will also establish the differences between local and foreign companies regarding their reporting of social and environmental information. The study will also investigate the perceptions and the association of host community members on the disclosure of SED by the Nigerian oil industry. Furthermore, the study will identify the motivations for social and environmental disclosure in the Nigerian oil industry and finally, it will discuss the challenges faced by the Nigerian oil industry in developing and promoting SED. The researcher of this study is expected to receive a PhD degree as a part of this research.

OUTCOMES: The possible outcomes of this study are to evaluate the level of social and environmental disclosures between the companies that operate in the Nigerian oil industry and assist in creating awareness of the communities' opinions of the oil companies. From the study analysis, it is anticipated that the social and environmental disclosure in Nigerian oil industry vary significantly based on the differences in their annual reports. The average disclosure scores are further expected to vary considerably between the sampled firms in the oil industries.

The Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) will be used to ascertain whether the variance in the social, environmental disclosure of the sampled companies is significant or not. It also has the possibility of improving social and environmental reporting of the oil companies and as a result improves the quality of life for the wider community of the Niger Delta.

Why have I been invited? You are invited to participate in this research project because your region has experienced the environmental degradation/pollution and neglect by the oil companies. You have been specifically selected to state your opinions on the social and environmental reporting of the oil companies operating within your community. You must be at least 18 years old to participate in this research.

Do I have to take part? Participation in this study is entirely voluntary. It is up to you to decide whether to take part. We will describe the study and go through this information sheet. If you agree to take part, we will then ask you to sign a consent form. However, you are still free to withdraw at any time and without giving a reason for your withdrawal.

What will happen if I take part? If you consent to take part in the study, the researcher will contact you to make an appointment to meet and speak with at your convenient time and venue. The researcher would like about 60 - 90minutes of your time, to ask you some questions about your knowledge, perceptions, motivation, challenges, and experiences regarding social and environmental disclosures in the Nigerian oil industry. The researcher will audio record your

interview if this is acceptable, to help make accurate record of your conversations and thereby not missing out any valuable information that you give.

What will I have to do? All you will be required to do is agree on a convenient time and venue where you can speak freely about your experiences with the researcher. It will be a one-off interview and you will not have to worry about meeting up again except you have some concerns and would want to meet up again. Procedures for participation in this project will involve:

- Face-to-face interview: participants will be interviewed only once and the expected time for the completion of each interview is between 60 to 90 minutes.
- The researcher will record the responses in audio and handwriting method.
- A questionnaire with both open and close-ended questions will be used for the interviews.
- The participants in this research will include, Company Management, Company Employee, Community Leaders, Youth Leaders, Church Leaders, community residents and Academician within the chosen state

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part? No disadvantages and risks of taking part in this interview as much as harm is not anticipated during this study, should there be any form or cause of distress during this interview or afterwards, please feel free to contact the researcher on the details provided on the last paragraph of the last page of this information sheet.

Will my participation be kept confidential and what happens to the information? All information you give is entirely confidential. No one will be able to identify you from the study. Therefore, your real names will not be used rather pseudonyms or codes will be used for easy collection and analysis of data. All information you give will be audio recorded and will be stored securely on the study designated computer which can only be accessed by the research team through a password. Data collected for this research will be written up as a report for publication and made available for participants who will be interested to know the findings from the study; and, as a thesis will be produced in partial fulfilment for a postgraduate degree. All raw data collected on the audio recorder will be destroyed at the end of the study.

What will happen to the findings from the study? Findings from the study will be produced as a thesis for the fulfilment of a research degree, published on both national and international academic journals and presented in conferences. No one will be identified in any publication or report.

Who has reviewed the study? The study has been reviewed and given favourable opinion by the University of the West of Scotland Ethics Committee. Dr. Michael Xin Guo and Prof. Angus Duff of the University of the West of Scotland supervise it.

Contact for further information: Thank you for your interest. If you would like any further information about the study or need to ask any questions, please contact

Or Charles T. Atang, School of Business and Enterprise,

University of the West of Scotland, Dunlee Level 1, UWS Lanarkshire Campus, Hamilton International Technology Park, South Lanarkshire, G72 0LH, United Kingdom.

This study is being supervised by Dr. Michael Xin Guo, Senior Lecturer in Accounting and Finance, School of Business and Enterprise, University of the West of Scotland, Dunlee Level 1, UWS Lanarkshire Campus, Hamilton International Technology Park, South Lanarkshire, G72 0LH. United Kingdom. If you have any questions or concerns about this study, you should contact him on [REDACTED]

EXHIBIT 6: RESEARCH CONSENT FORM

UNIVERSITY OF THE WEST OF SCOTLAND

RESEARCH CONSENT FORM

Name of department: School of Business and Enterprise

Title of the study: An investigation of social and environmental disclosure in the Nigerian oil industry

I confirm that I have read and understood the information about the project as provided in the Participant Information Sheet. Date

I confirm that that I have had the opportunity to ask questions and the researcher has answered any questions about the study to my satisfaction.

I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw from the project at any time, without having to give a reason and without any consequences.

I understand that I can withdraw my data from the study at any time.

I understand that any information recorded in the investigation will remain confidential and no information that identifies me will be made publicly available.

I consent to use of the data in research, publications, sharing and archiving as explained in the Participant Information Sheet.

I consent to being audio/ video/ interviews being recorded as part of the project. Yes/ No

I agree / do not agree to take part in the above study.

.....
Name of Participant	Date	Signature
.....
Researcher	Date	Signature

Please retain one copy of the Consent Form for the Participant and one for the Researcher

EXHIBIT 7: ETHICS APPROVAL

25/03/2019

Dear Charles Atang,

Your application 8019: AN INVESTIGATION OF SOCIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL DISCLOSURE IN

THE NIGERIAN OIL INDUSTRY, submission 6503, has been approved by the Business and Enterprise SEC. You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study, you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Mr D McFadzean

Exhibit 8: Word Frequency Results: Minimum Length = 4

Word	Length	Count	Weighted Percentage (%)
Community	9	1091	3.54
Company	7	792	2.57
Know	4	457	1.48
People	6	410	1.33
Thank	5	285	0.92
Like	4	262	0.85
Even	4	259	0.84
Much	4	254	0.82
Things	6	252	0.82
Think	5	239	0.78
Just	4	218	0.71
Social	6	215	0.70
Environmental	13	208	0.68
Come	4	205	0.67
Government	10	202	0.66
Activities	10	200	0.65
Also	4	195	0.63
Leader	6	180	0.58
Well	4	168	0.55
Done	4	163	0.53
Challenges	10	162	0.53
Want	4	154	0.50
Communities	11	147	0.48
Disclosure	10	146	0.47
State	5	135	0.44
Youth	5	133	0.43
Host	4	130	0.42
Give	4	129	0.42
Motivation	10	128	0.42
Perspective	11	126	0.41
Good	4	119	0.39
Companies	9	117	0.38
Thing	5	115	0.37
Time	4	114	0.37
Environment	11	112	0.36
Really	6	112	0.36
Level	5	102	0.33
Problem	7	96	0.31
Sometimes	9	95	0.31
Anything	8	94	0.31
Impact	6	93	0.30
Questions	9	90	0.29
Tell	4	90	0.29
Need	4	88	0.29
Going	5	86	0.28
Shell	5	86	0.28

Make	4	84	0.27
Maybe	5	84	0.27
Continue	8	81	0.26
Water	5	81	0.26
Support	7	80	0.26
Understand	10	80	0.26
Actually	8	79	0.26
Reporting	9	79	0.26
Take	4	76	0.25
Area	4	75	0.24
Perception	10	74	0.24
Church	6	73	0.24
Place	5	73	0.24
Road	4	71	0.23
Years	5	71	0.23
Mobil	5	70	0.23
Money	5	69	0.22
Negative	8	69	0.22
Part	4	68	0.22
Information	11	65	0.21
Nigeria	7	65	0.21
Within	6	65	0.21
Kind	4	64	0.21
Long	4	64	0.21
Able	4	63	0.20
Benefit	7	63	0.20
Involved	8	62	0.20
Last	4	61	0.20
Projects	8	58	0.19
Development	11	57	0.18
Issues	6	57	0.18
Project	7	57	0.18

Exhibit 9: Word Frequency Results: Minimum Length = 8

Word	Length	Count	Weighted Percentage (%)
Community	9	1091	3.54
Environmental	13	208	0.68
Government	10	202	0.66
Activities	10	200	0.65
Challenges	10	162	0.53
Communities	11	147	0.48
Disclosure	10	146	0.47
Motivation	10	128	0.42
Perspective	11	126	0.41
Companies	9	117	0.38
Environment	11	112	0.36
Sometimes	9	95	0.31
Anything	8	94	0.31
Questions	9	90	0.29
Continue	8	81	0.26
Understand	10	80	0.26
Actually	8	79	0.26
Reporting	9	79	0.26
Perception	10	74	0.24
Negative	8	69	0.22
Information	11	65	0.21
Involved	8	62	0.20
Projects	8	58	0.19
Development	11	57	0.18
Affecting	9	56	0.18
Policies	8	56	0.18
Resident	8	56	0.18
Supposed	8	56	0.18
Whatever	8	56	0.18
Something	9	54	0.18
Electricity	11	53	0.17
Everybody	9	49	0.16
Question	8	49	0.16
Scholarship	11	48	0.16
Employment	10	44	0.14
Stakeholders	12	44	0.14
Management	10	42	0.14
Involvement	11	41	0.13
Affected	8	40	0.13
Employee	8	40	0.13
Everything	10	39	0.13
Academician	11	38	0.12
Somebody	8	37	0.12
Responsibility	14	34	0.11
Spillage	8	34	0.11
Directly	8	31	0.10

Multinationals	14	31	0.10
Particular	10	30	0.10
Position	8	30	0.10
Problems	8	30	0.10
Discussed	9	29	0.09
Important	9	29	0.09
Educational	11	28	0.09
Following	9	28	0.09
Pollution	9	28	0.09
Instance	8	27	0.09
Contributed	11	26	0.08
Operations	10	26	0.08
Business	8	25	0.08
Objectives	10	24	0.08
Building	8	23	0.07
Challenge	9	23	0.07
Children	8	23	0.07
Different	9	23	0.07
Relationship	12	23	0.07
Benefits	8	22	0.07
Especially	10	22	0.07
Happening	9	22	0.07
Implement	9	22	0.07
Operating	9	22	0.07
Contract	8	21	0.07
Definitely	10	21	0.07
Understanding	13	21	0.07
Perceptions	11	20	0.06
Corporate	9	19	0.06
Exploration	11	19	0.06
Positive	8	17	0.06
Practices	9	17	0.06
Remember	8	17	0.06

Exhibit 10: Research Themes

☐	●	Motivation on SED			4	4
		●	Alignment to Community Development		24	24
		●	Community Welfare		20	20
		●	SED Benefit or Damage		20	20
☐	●	Perceptions on SED			21	21
		●	Communication of SED Policy		4	4
		●	Community Involvement		20	20
		●	Responsible Corporate Citizens		20	20
		●	Social and Environmental Issues		20	20
☐	●	Social Environmental Challenges			24	24
		●	Community Support		20	20
		●	Funding		1	1
		●	Interactions with Community		23	23
		●	SED Policies		24	24

EXHIBIT 11: SUMMARY OF THE SOCIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL DISCLOSURE (SED) PER FIRM

Type of Disclosure	Shell SPDC	Exxon Mobil (Eke)	Total Nigeria	Bayels a Oil Co.	Chevron	Ardova Plc	NLNG	11 Plc.	Conoil Plc.	RAK Unity	Capital Oil & Gas	MRS Oil Nig.	Etern a Plc.	Anino Int.	Japau l Oil	Seplat Petroleum	Caverto n	Oando
Quantified Monetary	57	47	14	0	109	47	144	82	4	0	2	125	49	0	1	45	28	38
Quantified Non-Monetary	22	92	175	2	57	11	46	15	0	0	0	32	8	0	0	39	14	80
Narrative, Discursive	396	558	301	34	336	112	501	121	92	2	3	224	102	3	3	143	69	210
Pictures	29	44	52	0	31	8	47	13	4	0	0	9	5	0	0	13	2	16
Total per Firm	501	741	542	36	533	178	738	231	100	2	5	390	164	3	4	240	113	344

EXHIBIT 12: MEAN NUMBER OF DISCLOSURE BY FIRM SIZE AND SED COMPONENT

Component of SED Disclosure	Shell SPD C	Exxon Mobil (Eket)	Total Nigeria	Bayelsa Oil Co.	Chevron	For Oil	NLN G	11 Plc.	Conoil	RAK Unit	Capital Oil & Gas	Mrs. Oil	Etern a Plc.	Anin o Int.	Japau l Oil	Seplat Petroleum	Caverton	Oando
Environment:																		
Pollution	2	13	4	4	21	0	4	0	6	0	0	3	1	0	0	5	0	2
Wastes	4	45	21	0	1	0	68	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	9	0	4
Awards	2	3	1	0	23	1	7	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	6	1	0
Anti-litter	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Waste Recycling	1	5	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Natural Resource Conservation	6	15	7	2	7	0	17	0	3	0	0	0	1	0	0	6	1	5

Compliance with Anti-Pollution Laws	0	9	1	1	1	0	7	0	11	0	0	5	5	0	1	9	0	0
Total Environmental Disclosures	15	90	40	7	53	1	103	0	20	0	0	9	12	0	1	35	2	12
Total Environmental Disclosure (%)	9%	15%	15%	22%	18%	1%	25%	0%	18%	0%	0%	5%	9%	0%	33%	22%	2%	11%
Energy:																		
Energy Conservation	11	31	0	0	8	1	20	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	10
Energy Policies	0	6	0	0	0	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Awards	0	3	1	0	8	0	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0
Total Energy Disclosures	11	40	1	0	16	2	29	0	4	0	10							
Total Energy Disclosure (%)	7%	7%	0%	0%	6%	2%	7%	0%	3%	0%	9%							
Customers:																		
Customer Safety	15	63	32	1	14	10	12	0	23	0	0	21	10	0	0	15	18	5
Customer Complaints	1	0	1	0	1	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Customer Relations	1	12	3	1	5	1	19	1	0	0	0	0	10	0	0	14	1	0
Provision for Disabled	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total Client	17	75	36	2	20	15	31	2	23	0	0	21	20	0	0	29	19	6

Disclosures																		
Total Client Disclosure (%)	10%	12%	13%	6%	7%	17%	7%	4%	21%	0%	0%	13%	15%	0%	0%	18%	19%	5%
Community:																		
Involvement in Community Initiatives	3	14	7	13	7	4	8	4	2	0	0	1	0	0	0	10	6	32
Charitable Donations	47	65	23	6	45	12	38	1	1	1	1	16	15	1	1	8	5	2
Educational Sponsorship	5	33	10	0	37	1	60	10	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	15	5	15
Public Health Initiatives	34	58	65	0	55	21	48	3	11	0	0	25	35	0	0	22	13	26
Sports Sponsorships	1	1	4	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	0	6	6	0	0	1	1	1

Pro-bono	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	90	171	109	19	145	38	154	20	14	1	1	52	56	1	1	56	30	76
Community Disclosures																		
Total	54%	28%	40%	59%	50%	44	37%	42	13%	100	50%	31	43%	100	33%	35%	29%	69%
Community Disclosure (%)						%		%		%		%		%				
Employee:																		
Health and Safety	21	43	32	0	1	9	22	3	21	0	0	12	7	0	0	4	7	1
Diversity: Women and minorities	2	83	14	0	13	1	7	11	0	0	0	1	10	0	0	4	1	1
Training	5	84	37	2	35	7	53	9	16	0	0	47	8	0	0	24	35	3
Benefits	5	15	0	2	3	6	8	3	8	0	1	11	8	0	1	1	0	0

Welfare	0	0	2	0	1	7	0	0	8	0	0	14	10	0	0	1	8	1
Awards	2	3	0	0	3	0	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	35	228	85	4	56	30	97	26	53	0	1	85	43	0	1	34	51	6
Employee Disclosures																		
Total	21%	38%	31%	13%	19%	35	23%	54	48%	0%	50%	51	33%	0%	33%	22%	50%	5%
Employee Disclosure (%)						%		%				%						
Total SEDs	168	604	271	32	290	86	414	48	110	1	2	167	131	1	3	158	102	110

EXHIBIT 13: Mean Sed by Size and Component (International Oil Firms)

Component of SED Disclosure	Shell SPDC	Exxon Mobil	Chevron	Total Nigeria	11 Plc.	Mrs. Oil	Average
Environment:							
Pollution	2	13	21	4	0	3	7
Wastes	4	45	1	21	0	0	12
Awards	2	3	23	1	0	1	5
Anti-litter	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Waste Recycling	1	5	0	6	0	0	2
Natural Resource Conservation	6	15	7	7	0	0	6
Compliance with Anti-Pollution Laws	0	9	1	1	0	5	3
Total Environmental Disclosures	15	90	53	40	0	9	35
Total Environmental Disclosure (%)	9%	15%	18%	15%	0%	5%	10%
Energy:							
Energy Conservation	11	31	8	0	0	0	8
Energy Policies	0	6	0	0	0	0	1
Awards	0	3	8	1	0	0	2
Total Energy	11	40	16	1	0	0	11

Disclosures							
Total Energy Disclosure (%)	7%	7%	6%	0%	0%	0%	3%
Customers:							
Customer Safety	15	63	14	32	0	21	24
Customer Complaints	1	0	1	1	0	0	1
Customer Relations	1	12	5	3	1	0	4
Provision for Disabled	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
Total Client Disclosures	17	75	20	36	2	21	29
Total Client Disclosure (%)	10%	12%	7%	13%	4%	13%	10%
Community:							
Involvement in Community Initiatives	3	14	7	7	4	1	6
Charitable Donations	47	65	45	23	1	16	33
Educational Sponsorship	5	33	37	10	10	4	17
Public Health Initiatives	34	58	55	65	3	25	40
Sports Sponsorships	1	1	1	4	2	6	3
Pro-bono	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Total Community Disclosures	90	171	145	109	20	52	98
Total Community Disclosure (%)	54%	28%	50%	40%	42%	31%	41%
Employee:							
Health and Safety	21	43	1	32	3	12	19
Diversity: Women and minorities	2	83	13	14	11	1	21
Training	5	84	35	37	9	47	36
Benefits	5	15	3	0	3	11	6
Welfare	0	0	1	2	0	14	3
Awards	2	3	3	0	0	0	1
Total Employee Disclosures	35	228	56	85	26	85	86
Total Employee Disclosure (%)	21%	38%	19%	31%	54%	51%	36%
Total SEDs	168	604	290	271	48	167	258

EXHIBIT 14: Sampled Companies in The Nigerian Oil Industry

S/NO.	NAME OF LISTED COMPANY
1	Shell Petroleum Development Company (SPDC). Delta State, Nigeria
2	Mobil Producing Nigeria Unlimited. Eket, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria
3	Chevron Nigeria. Lagos State, Nigeria
4	Total Nigeria PLC
5	Bayelsa Oil Company in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State, Nigeria
6	Nigeria LNG Limited (NLNG). Bonny Island, River State, Nigeria
7	Oando PLC. Lagos State, Nigeria.
8	Caverton Offshore Support Group, Lagos State, Nigeria.
9	Forte Oil PLC. Lagos State, Nigeria.
10	11 PLC
11	Conoil PLC
12	RAK Unity Petroleum Company PLC.
13	Capital Oil & Gas LTD.
14	Mrs. Oil Nigeria LTD
15	Eterna PLC, Lagos state, Nigeria
16	Anino International PLC.
17	Japaul Oil & Maritime Services
18	Seplat Petroleum Development

Source: Researchers sample selected from NSE/Annual Report

EXHIBIT 15: Thirteen Companies Listed on The Nigerian Stock Exchange

S/N	INDUSTRY	NSE LISTED
1	ANINO INTERNATIONAL PLC.	LISTED
2	CAPITAL OIL & GAS LTD.	LISTED
3	CONOIL PLC. (NSE LISTED)	LISTED
4	11 PLC	LISTED
5	TOTAL NIGERIA	LISTED
6	CAVERTON OFFSHORE SUPPORT	LISTED
7	ETERNA	LISTED
8	FORTE OIL	LISTED
9	JAPPAUL OIL & MARITIME SERVICES	LISTED
10	MRS OIL NIGERIA	LISTED
11	OANDO	LISTED
12	RAK UNITY PETROLEUM	LISTED
13	SEPLAT PETROLEUM DEVELOPMENT	LISTED

EXHIBIT 16: ANOVA And Paired Samples T-Test Results: Nigerian Domestic Firms

Paired Samples Test

	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Pair 1 SED (Nigerian Top 5 Firms) - SED (Other Top 13 Nigerian Firms)	10.6249	12.7369	2.4979	5.4803	15.7694	4.253	25	.000

ANOVA

SED

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1467.537	1	1467.537	11.919	.001
Within Groups	6156.297	50	123.126		
Total	7623.834	51			

EXHIBIT 17: ANOVA & Paired T-Test: Domestic and International Oil Firms

ANOVA

SED

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1696.647	1	1696.647	5.469	.023
Within Groups	18612.769	60	310.213		
Total	20309.416	61			

0

Paired Samples Test

	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Pair 1 SED (Nigerian Oil Firms) - SED (International Oil Firms)	-10.4624	15.5622	2.7950	-16.1706	-4.7541	-3.743	30	.001

